

CALIPER
Gender Equality in STEM Research

Linking Research & Innovation for
Gender Equality

D2.2 Reporting results of multi-stakeholder dialogues

WP2- Design and development of
customized GEP

Version: 1.0

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Executive Summary

The present deliverable 'D2.2 Reporting results of multi-stakeholder dialogues' describes the main results of tasks T2.1 and T2.2 respectively. It is the first step in the design of the customized Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). First, it presents the institutional change scenarios developed by the RPOs/RFOS of the CALIPER consortium (T2.1). Drawing on the internal assessment carried out in WP1, each institution analyzed its key problems regarding gender equality in STEM and envisaged possible solutions. They also identified the main resistances and opportunities for those solutions, as well as strategies to overcome them. Second, the deliverable presents the results of the multi-stakeholders' dialogues (T2.2). Each RPO/RFO organized two workshops to discuss the institutional change scenarios with their respective the R&I Hubs. The aim of these dialogues was to identify common challenges, to develop a portfolio of strategic opportunities and to examine possible collaborative actions.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose & Scope

This deliverable is the result of the first two tasks of WP2 that aims at designing and developing customised Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) for each CALIPER RPO/RFO. The first task (T2.1) consisted of the development of strategic change scenarios for each partner. These scenarios were developed in a participatory way with internal members of each institution by examining the internal assessment realised in task T1.2¹. The objective of the scenarios' development was to identify possible resistances and opportunities for gender equality institutional change. Based on the developed scenarios for institutional change, the following task was to discuss the identified situations, resistances and opportunities with the external stakeholders involved in the CALIPER's R&I Hubs, thereby finalizing their setting. Two workshops were organized by each RPO/RFO to carry out the multi-stakeholder dialogues. As a result, common challenges with external stakeholders and a portfolio of strategic opportunities have been drafted for each partner. Several possible collaborative actions have been identified as well. In this deliverable D2.2, both the scenarios developed by each partner and the results of the multi-stakeholder dialogues are reported.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

After the introductory chapter, Chapter 2 focuses on the scenarios for institutional change. The scenarios are presented for each RPO/RFO and per area (human resources, research, teaching, students and student services, transfer to market, communication, intersectionality, sexism and harassment). Following the step, Chapter 3 describes the results of the multi-stakeholder dialogues with the R&I Hubs for each partner following the same areas described above. Chapter 3 starts with some aggregated data concerning the gender of the dialogues' participants, the types of stakeholders and the type of possible collaborative actions. The deliverable finishes with the conclusions of the two tasks.

1.3 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

This deliverable is related to WP1, concretely to T1.2 (internal assessment) since the results of the internal assessment carried out in the previous WP have fed the development of the scenarios. The results of T1.3 (external assessment) have also been used to finalize the setting of the R&I Hubs.

The deliverable is an essential step in WP2 since both the scenarios and the results of the multi-stakeholder dialogues (especially the portfolio of strategic opportunities and the possible collaborative actions identified) set the basis for the design of the customized GEPs in task T2.3.

¹ The scenarios have been built only upon the *internal* assessment previously carried out and not upon the *external* assessment as stated in D2.1 'Co-design Guidelines for the development and reporting of scenarios'. This was a mistake introduced in D2.1.

2 Strategic change scenarios

Based on the methodology provided (see D2.1 Co-design Guidelines for the development and reporting of scenarios), partners were asked to develop three scenarios focusing on the identification of the maximum resistances, the maximum opportunities, and a mix of both. The solutions proposed are based on this third scenario, which is the most realistic one and the one reported in the deliverable to avoid repetitions. Therefore, for most RPOs/RFOs the structure of the report follows the following structure (per area):

- Situation
- Main problems
- Objective(s)
- Possible solutions
- Resistances (including strategies to overcome them)
- Opportunities

Three RPOs (STU BA, IRB and ULB) adapted the suggested methodology to design three scenarios according to the degree or type of resistances that the possible solutions could trigger. For these partners, the structure of the report follows a slightly different structure (per area):

- Situation
- Main problems
- Objective(s)
- Scenario 1: Maximal resistance (including the possible solutions that would trigger high resistance and potential opportunities)
- Scenario 2: Low resistance (including the possible solutions that would trigger low resistance and potential opportunities)
- Scenario 3: Intermediate resistance (including the possible solutions that would trigger intermediate resistance and potential opportunities)

2.1 University of Zagreb – Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing (RPO)

Human resources

1. Recruitment procedures

Situation

UNIZG-FER follows the national regulations and its internal rules about gender sensitive protocols / policies for recruitment and hiring. UNIZG-FER implements its internal rules of operation based on Internal Labor Regulations of Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing, Internal Labor Regulations of the University of Zagreb, Collective Agreement for Science and Higher Education for Croatia and Labor Act of Croatia. The documents state that direct or indirect discrimination in the field of work and working conditions, including selection criteria and conditions in employment, promotion, in accordance with special laws, is prohibited.

Based on the answers given in the survey UNIZG-FER can conclude that most of the participants did not feel discriminated against when applying or being promoted for their last position in the UNIZG-FER. Proportion of shortlisted women and men is gender balanced and in accordance with the gender distribution of applicants for the job.

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Share of woman in recruitment or promotion boards/panels: 2015/2016 18,09%, 2016/2017 16,36%, 2017/2018 8,61%, 2018/2019 12,71%, 2019/2020 33,85%

The institution has a balanced gender success rate at academic (M-F 61% - 73%) and teaching or research assistant (M-F 74% - 71%), while more males have succeeded into postdoc positions (M-F 94% - 67%).

Main problems

The main problem is unbalanced gender success rate at postdoc positions (M-F 94% - 67%).

Hypotheses about the causes of the problem are the following:

- Fewer female candidates because the number of women in STEM is lower in all levels (high school, bachelor, master, doctoral students).
- The salary of a postdoc is lower than the salary for STEM experts in industry (same for men and women)
- Uncertainty whether after postdoc a person will get a permanent position in academia, so they choose more certain job with substantially higher salary (same for men and women).
- Many women in that period of life want to have children. For many, the uncertainty and expectations of a postdoc position brings is not compatible with starting a family.

Objective(s)

The goal is to obtain gender balanced success rate at postdoc positions and to have bigger number of the qualified candidates.

Possible solutions

- Explore which additional opportunities and advantages within the legal frame of the institution are possible for postdocs with additional care work so they can have better work-life balance. Inform doctoral students who are the future postdocs about these opportunities and advantages.
- Organize workshops for empowering doctoral students to choose career in academia, organized by Career Center or Doctoral Studies.
- Organize exit survey by the Office for human resources office for people who leave UNIZG-FER to better understand their reasons for leaving.
- Organize popularization events for high school students to increase number of female students.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first from internal stakeholders. Resistances are coming from the rules or structure of the organization like resistance to organization of events for women only. Next, some are coming from the administration such as resistance to additional work (survey, workshops). There are also resistances coming from high management related to the organization of events for women only. Finally, some resistances come also from researchers and still refer to the organization of events for women only, participation in popularization events and workshops. In addition, there are expected resistances from external stakeholders, in particular coming from the government/public sector, like resistances from high schools to participate in the popularization events for their students and resistances to the organization of events for women only.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative such as Postdoc positions that often remain vacant because they are not well paid and have uncertain future. This is bad for the research groups who are looking for postdocs. If UNIZG-FER implements these actions, hopefully the number of quality candidates for postdoc positions will increase and research group leaders will be able to fill vacant postdoc positions. Some strategies touch the rules of the organization: involve Career Centre and Doctoral Studies in organization of workshops. Other actions can be adding special events for girls in already existing

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popularization events of the UNIZG-FER.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are firstly from internal stakeholders. Opportunities are coming from the administration; UNIZG-FER can provide help to Human Resources office to create exit survey. It is also coming from middle management like the middle management will support measures that contribute to the increase number of qualified candidates for postdoc positions which often remain vacant because they are not attractive, Career Centre and Doctoral studies like to offer workshops for students. Other expected opportunities are coming from high management, since it will support measures that contribute to increase the number of qualified candidates for postdoc positions which often remain vacant because they are not attractive. Next, there are opportunities coming from researchers: the group of research group leaders will support measures that contribute to the increase number of qualified candidates for postdoc positions which often remain vacant because they are not attractive; there are enthusiastic professors who already participate in popularization events; researchers with European projects are obliged to add gender dimension in their research and collaborating with CALIPER project team can help some of them to obtain this. Finally, some are coming from students since there are students already engaged in popularization events. Secondly, there are opportunities expected from external stakeholders. In particular, opportunities come from the academia such as possible synergies in organizing popularization events with other STEM faculties of the University. Other opportunities are expected coming from the government/public sector, considering UNIZG-FER has a small network of schools who already participate in popularization events of UNIZG-FER. Finally, opportunities coming from industries/business stakeholders like business stakeholders who participated in the external assessment survey are expected, since they expressed willingness to participate in popularization events.

2. Work-life balance

Situation

Regarding the topic of work-life balance, all measures prescribed by the law are listed in The Labor Act of Croatia. At UNIZG-FER all these measures are available to employees. The institution does not implement any additional measures. The information about their rights is available to every employee, via intranet, but also can be provided by administrative services upon request.

Parental leaves in the last 3 years: less than 3 months (M-F 6-0), 3-6 months (M-F 0-1), 6-12 months (M-F 0-10), more than 1 year (M-F 0-2). Share of female career breaks and drop-outs in the last 5 years is 27,19%.

Main problems

The main problem is in the administrative offices where most of the employees are women, and parental leaves and sick leaves for female employees cause work-life imbalance.

In general, care work is mostly on women's shoulders. If the unit employees are mostly women, the unit is more strongly affected and more often employees face work-life imbalance.

Objective(s)

The goal is to help employees reach work-life balance.

Possible solutions

- Dialogue with managers of faculty units to enable more flexibility with deadlines for task given to employees in case of child illnesses.

Resistances

The expected resistances are from internal stakeholders. Resistances could be coming from the administration, resistance from unit managers to move deadlines because some work will be delayed, and clients will be disappointed. Others could be coming from middle management, resistance from unit managers to move deadlines because some work will be delayed, and clients will be disappointed. Some

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could be coming from high management: resistance from managers to introduce more flexible deadlines. Finally, resistances could come from researchers and students, because some work will be delayed. No resistance from external stakeholders have been identified.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative such as showing that employees who have better work-life balance are happier people, healthier, work better, atmosphere is better, burnout syndrome is avoided, stress reduced.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are from internal stakeholders. Opportunities are coming from the administration; employees will support measures which improve their work-life balance. Others are coming from high and middle management which being open minded managers will support measures which improve work-life balance of employees. No opportunities from external stakeholders have been identified.

3. Career breaks and job reintegration

Situation

The criteria are flexible when taking into consideration childbirth because this is prescribed by law. Other major life events are not taken into consideration because they are not prescribed by law.

Main problems

The main problem is, according to the responders, that maternity leave is causing delays in the career due to lower publication rates by female researchers. In addition, there are challenges with the procedure for getting substitutes for maternity leave of associates or project leaders working on projects financed by the Croatian Science Foundation. This problem could be addressed at the institutional level. The internal assessment did not provide enough information on the nature of the problem, this needs to be explored more before suggesting possible solution. This problem is a national problem, concerning also academic not employed at UNIZG – FER.

Hypotheses about the causes of the problem are the following:

- Women go on maternity leave, men do it in rare occasions so there is imbalance.
- There exist already informal solutions which work well and nobody is complaining.

Objective(s)

The goal is to improve working conditions of associates and project leaders working on projects financed by the Croatian Science Foundation concerning maternity leave.

Possible solutions

- Explore options for support measures for women scientists after returning from maternity leave (workshops, empowering?)
- Explore more about the details of the challenges of academics working on projects financed by the Croatian Science Foundation concerning maternity leave (in dialogue with employees of UNIZG – FER).
- Brainstorm about the possible solutions to solve issues.
- Start dialogue on institutional level between UNIZG – FER and the Croatian Science Foundation.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first from internal stakeholders. Resistance could be coming from high management such as resistance to start dialogue with the Croatian Science Foundation. It could also be coming from researchers like resistance to explore problems and participate in solution, resistance from male researchers if women will have extra opportunities Secondly, resistances are expected from external

stakeholders. It could be coming from the academia such as resistance from the Croatian Science Foundation to start a dialogue. Finally, resistances could come from the government/public sector such as resistance from male researchers employed at other institutions if women will have extra opportunities.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative. It would be good to explore and solve this issue in order to improve work conditions of associates and project leaders working on projects financed by the Croatian Science Foundation concerning maternity leave. Informal solutions that already exist should be formalized so that women have security. Men and women having children while working on these projects should have a fair opportunity to meet the project goals.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are firstly from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from high management, high management which will support measures that improve working conditions and increase the productivity of researchers. Opportunities could also be coming from researchers such as female researchers will support measures that improve working conditions and increase the productivity of researchers. Secondly, some opportunities are expected from external stakeholders. Opportunities could come from the academia such as improving working conditions of associates and project leaders working on projects financed by the Croatian Science Foundation concerning maternity leave; higher productivity of researchers.

Governance

1. Enhancing women leadership and access to top positions (academic and administrative levels)

Situation

UNIZG-FER implements its internal rules of operation based on Internal Labor Regulations of Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing, Internal Labor Regulations of the University of Zagreb, Collective Agreement for Science and Higher Education and Labor Act of Croatia. There is not much mention of the gender related topics in these documents except when prohibiting discrimination. The institutional governance of UNIZG-FER has foundations on the following documents: Internal Labor Regulations of Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing, Internal Labor Regulations of the University of Zagreb, as well as related national acts, such as Labor Law and Anti-Discrimination Law. These documents regulate gender equality very well.

In relation to the decision-making bodies those are the Dean's office and the Faculty Council. The Dean and the Council are advised in the decision-making process by various faculty committees. Women actively participate in the committees, and they can influence decision-making in this way. There are no official strategies/policies to foster gender balance in decision making. However, the institution has a long-term unofficial commitment to inclusion of women in management at all levels. There are no quotas or gender quotas applying to leadership positions, elections to decision making positions/governing bodies. Women are encouraged as much as men. Considering that there are much more eligible male candidates (there are academic requirements prescribed by constitutional documents), it is expected that mostly men occupy these positions. While, the UNIZG-FER has a long-term commitment to inclusion of women in management at all levels, there are no mentoring or coaching services/activities for leadership positions for women.

Gendered composition of governing bodies: dean M-F 1-0, vice deans M-F 2-1, committee's members M-F 83-23, faculty council M-F 189-49.

Number of women in leadership position: Head of department F-M 1-11, Head of (administrative) unit F-M 5-3, Head of committee F-M 3-8

Vertical segregation: proportion of women grade A/B/C staff : grade A (highest) 11,46%, grade B 12,00%, grade C 28,85%, grade D 28,26% (lowest after phd)

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Main problems

The main problem is that the institution faces a strong vertical segregation and managerial positions are male dominated. In addition, the participation of women in decision-making bodies is low.

Hypotheses about the causes of the problem are the following:

- The institution has a long-term unofficial commitment to inclusion of women in management at all levels.
- Considering that there are much more eligible male candidates (there are academic requirements prescribed by constitutional documents), it is expected that mostly men occupy these positions.

Objective(s)

The goal is to increase the participation of women in decision-making bodies and managerial positions.

Possible solutions

- Empowering women by organizing leadership workshops and mentoring programs via Research support center.
- Organize popularization events for high school students to increase number of female students (in the long run this will increase the number of eligible female professors).
- Organize empowering workshops that include role models for female students (start early with empowering women)

Resistances

Resistance is expected from first internal stakeholders. It could be coming from the administration like resistance from the Research support centre to participate in the organization of workshops. Resistance could also come from high and middle management, as well as from researchers about the participation in workshops and mentoring programs, resistance to special events for women. Finally, resistance could come from students such as resistance to participate in popularization and empowering events. No resistance has been identified from external stakeholders.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative and related to the pros of increasing the number of qualified academics for managerial positions; creating stronger network between women; promoting role models and diversity in managerial teams which can give strength to the institution (more different perspectives, different solutions); empowering women to lead projects (e.g., more projects and funding); increasing the number of female students.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first coming from internal stakeholders. They can come from the administration, like the research support centre can participate in the organization of empowering workshops for researchers; Doctoral Studies Program can participate in the organization of empowering workshops for doctoral students. They can also come from the high and middle management which can support diversity in managerial teams because they give strength to the institution (more different perspectives, different solutions). Opportunities are also expected from researchers such as female researchers will support increase of the number of qualified academics for managerial positions, stronger network between women, promotion of role models; empowering women to lead projects (= more projects and funding). Finally, opportunities could come from students participating in the popularization events. Secondly, opportunities are expected from external stakeholders coming from the government/public sector like high schools willing to participate in popularization events for female high school students and coming from industries/business stakeholders, which in the external assessment survey expressed willingness to participate in popularization events for high school students and to offer role models.

2. Gender disaggregated data collection at the institutional level

Situation

UNIZG-FER is not required to produce annual reports of any kind. Each 4 years UNIZG-FER produces a report for the Agency for Science and Higher Education of Croatia with the purpose of reaccreditation of the institution. This report contains a section concerning gender balance and this data is also used for the Self-assessment Report. With regards to gender segregated data, the institution collects data for all students about their gender when enrolling to studies. For all employees, the institution collects data about their gender when they are being employed.

When it comes to gender equality policies/bodies, a gender equality plan does not exist at UNIZG-FER. The institution plans to set it up via the CALIPER project. UNIZG-FER does not have any body whose work is focused on gender equality. There are no human or financial resources for gender equality, there is no intention of setting up a body dedicated to gender equality. Decision-making bodies of UNIZG-FER are available to influence the process of institutional change in order to improve gender equality.

Main problems

The main problems are that UNIZG – FER does not have a gender equality plan and it does not produce annual report on the progress of gender equality of the institution.

Hypotheses about the causes of the problem are the following:

- UZG-FER is in the process of setting up the Gender equality plan by the CALIPER project.
- UZG-FER was not required to produce annual report on the progress of gender equality.

Objective(s)

The goal is to set up sustainable GEP, execute it and follow the progress of gender equality at UNIZG – FER annually.

Possible solutions

- Set up and execute the gender equality plan of UNIZG – FER via CALIPER project.
- Set up a new body or entrust existing body to focus on and follow the state of gender equality at UNIZG – FER (Vice dean for research, Research Committee).
- Set up intersectional data collection processes and produce annual report on the current state of gender equality.

Resistances

The expected resistances are from internal stakeholders. Resistance to set up and participate in a new committee for gender equality can come from the administration, the middle and high management and researchers. No resistance from external stakeholders has been identified.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative. Gender equality plan is already being set up via CALIPER, committee on gender equality will follow the execution of GEP and ensure sustainability; having the GEP, gender equality committee and annual reports on gender equality will make UNIZG – FER eligible for application for funding from Horizon Europe.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are from internal stakeholders. It could be coming from the high management, the administration, researchers will support the GEP and annual reports on gender equality because they will make UNIZG – FER eligible for application for funding from Horizon Europe. No opportunities have been identified from external stakeholders.

Research

Situation

When it comes to integrating gender analysis into research, it is reported that there are no official guidelines on this issue. The institution provides practical support to researchers, without intervening in research content. The institution does not have direct influence on defining how research is conducted, it depends on the international scientific community. Research projects are financed by government institutions that determine the research policies, not UNIZG-FER. If the research includes people then research is conducted with highest ethical principles, which understand equal representation of both genders.

During the internal research statistics have been found about its active participation in Croatian Science Foundation Projects with a quite balanced gender ratio of 451,85 (100*M/F).

The gender ratio on patenting researchers is 4800. Share of women in patenting research outputs in the last 3 years: 4,35%. Moving to the scientific papers on STEM, females have been met as co-authors in a balanced percentage of 45%. Also, no female researchers have been identified in the teams of university spin offs. The share of women among P.I.s in the last 3 years: all institutional projects 11, 7%, European projects 10%.

Main problems

The main problems is that UNIZG-FER does not organize workshops on the topic of gender analysis and gender dimension into research.

Hypotheses about the causes of the problem are the following:

- The institution provides practical support to researchers, without intervening in research content.

Objective(s)

The goal is to familiarize researchers of UNIZG-FER with the application of gender analysis and gender dimension into research.

Possible solutions

- Organize workshops on the application of gender analysis and gender dimension into research (examples of good practice).

Resistances

The expected resistances are coming from internal stakeholders. First, it could be coming from the administration like resistance from the Research support center to organize workshops. Next, resistances could come from high management such as resistance from high management to organize workshops. Finally, resistances could come from researchers, resistance to topics of the application of gender analysis and gender dimension into research; resistance from researchers to participate in workshops. No expected resistance from external stakeholders has been identified.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative actions like organizing workshops topics of the application of gender analysis and gender dimension into research will make researchers stronger, and their research results better, open new innovative research problems.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are from internal stakeholders. It could be coming from high management; high management supports action that will help researchers have better research results. Opportunities could also be coming from researchers such as new innovative research ideas. No opportunities from external stakeholders have been identified.

Teaching

Situation

Currently there are no guidelines, checklists, policies or training of staff on how to integrate the gender dimension in the curricula. At the same time, there are no guidelines for gender sensitive teaching for professors.

Main problems

The main problem is that there is no mechanism in place regarding the gender dimension in the curricula and gender sensitive teaching at UNIZG-FER.

Hypotheses about the causes of the problem are the following:

- Faculty provides infrastructural and organizational support for the teaching programs, but professors are responsible for the content and the delivery of the courses.
- University professors have more training for scientific skills, than for teaching.
- All professors belong to STEM fields, so there is no awareness about gender sensitive teaching.
- The number of female students is very low.

Objective(s)

The goal is to integrate the gender dimension in the curricula and conduct gender sensitive teaching training for professors.

Possible solutions

- Set up guidelines on how to integrate the gender dimension in the curricula.
- Organize training / workshops for professors about gender sensitive teaching.

Resistances

The expected resistances are from internal stakeholders. It could be coming from high management like resistance to organize and implement trainings for professors. Resistance could also be coming from researchers such as resistance to participate in the training on gender sensitive teaching, course content and delivery is responsibility of professors, they are free and independent in their decisions. Finally, there could be resistance coming from students, male students could be against the change in content delivery of courses. No resistances from external stakeholders have been identified.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative. It would be good for the institution to offer training for professors that is currently missing, number of female students is slowly but constantly growing, and UNIZG-FER needs to adapt our teaching methods; integrating gender dimension into curricula will teach our best students, future researchers to integrate gender dimension into their research.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first from internal stakeholders. First it could come from high management; high management is interested in offering teaching training of any sort to professors. Next it could come from researchers such as professors, who are interested in training that will help them improve their teaching skills, and motivate students better, professors who are interested in the topic of including gender dimension in research. Finally, it could be coming from students like female students will be more comfortable, more motivated. Secondly, opportunities are expected from external stakeholders. It could come from the academia such as other faculties that would like to offer this type of training to their professors.

Students and services to students

Situation

The current situation regarding the student services and the presence of initiatives offering information/guidance to prospective students, since 2012 UNIZG-FER has an official program for popularization of science called “ŠUZA - from school to science and academia” which organizes various popularization events such as: Open doors, Day of women in IT, Day of UNIZG-FER in some schools, Lego league, Raddar and Summer robotics camps which are conducted for high school and elementary school students. Also, tours for students around the labs of the institution are organized on regular basis. UNIZG-FER also participates in STEM popularization organizations and events with more gender approach such as: IEEE Women in engineering section, Girls in ICT, Become IT girl and Gender 4 Stem. All programs have their own websites that can be accessed by the interested public and students. In relation to the presence of initiatives aimed at counselling enrolled students with a gender sensitive approach, such initiatives are typically aimed at preventing drop out from students of the under-represented sex. There is the Student Advisory Service at UNIZG-FER without any specific counseling with a gender sensitive approach. The figures below depict the current situation.

Number of female enrolled students:

Undergraduate level: 2016/2017 22%, 2017/2018 23,74%, 2018/2019 23,50%

Graduate level: 2016/2017 21,28%, 2017/2018 19,08%, 2018/2019 22,46%

Postgraduate level: 2016/2017 13,56%, 2017/2018 28,26%, 2018/2019 20,69%

Number of female students per level: Undergraduate level 23%, Graduate level 20%, Postgraduate level 21%.

Success rate of female STEM students in all levels: Undergraduate level 69,54%, Graduate level 73,17%, Postgraduate level 57,58%.

With regards to the student services, while there is the Student Advisory Service aimed at counselling enrolled students, the service does not have a website and the information about their work is short and insufficient without any additional material. Their main role is helping students with the motivation and learning difficulties and does not imply a gender sensitive approach.

Main problems

The main problems are the following. There are problems students are facing in case of pregnancy. Counseling services should be improved in this area. There is no formal approach to student-parent problems. Also, these problems should be addressed at the level of University of Zagreb. There is no counselling office for giving advice and support in the case of discrimination or harassment for students. These services should include a gender sensitive approach.

Hypotheses about the causes of the problem are the following:

- Challenges pregnant students and students-parents have are already addressed by the institution in an informal way. There is the strong dedication of the institution to help students resolve these challenges.
- Student Advisory Service helps students with the motivation and learning difficulties because counselors are professors of UNIZG-FER and they are not trained to provide counseling for other types of problems students have.
- There is no funding available to employ external expert to provide psychological counseling in the case of discrimination or harassment for students.

Objective(s)

The goal is to provide students with counseling services for young parents and pregnant students and to formalize procedures that solve their problems. Also, the goal is to provide students with counseling services in the case of discrimination or harassment.

Possible solutions

- Develop guidelines for a gender-sensitive approach to student counseling.
- More accessible information for students on available counseling opportunities and topics.
- To enable counseling and solving problems related to the studies of pregnant students and students-parents, this could be done in synergy with other faculties of the university.
- Provide psychological counseling and support in case of discrimination or sexual harassment, this could be done in synergy with other faculties of the university.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first from internal stakeholders. The administration can be reluctant on setting up guidelines. There could also be resistance coming from the high management: resistance to find funding for new external counselling services, resistance to establish dialogue with other faculties on this topic. Secondly, there are resistances expected from external stakeholders coming from the academia such as resistance from other faculties to jointly provide counselling service to students, and to jointly establish formal procedures that tackle challenges of pregnant students and parents-students.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative. We need to support our pregnant students and parents-students to finish their studies; this problem is not unique for our faculty so UNIZG-FER should solve it together with other faculties of the university.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first coming from internal stakeholders such as the administration like Student Service that is always supporting students, finding informal ways to help them; they would be interested to help students. Opportunities could also be coming from high management: high management is always supporting students, finding informal ways to help them; they would be interested to help students. Secondly, opportunities are expected from external stakeholders such as the academia: faculties are always supporting students, finding informal ways to help them; they would be interested to help students.

Transfer to Market

Situation

There are no gender sensitive/ gender specific measures /actions on enhancing transfer to the market of scientific research results. The process of technology transfer to the market is only in its beginnings at UNIZG-FER so it is impossible to expect gender sensitive specific measures. In regards to the presence of educational/science communication projects with a gender component three (3) research projects were given as examples: the CALIPER project; the European Network for Gender Balance in Informatics; and another scientific project financed by the Croatian Science Foundation that aims at transforming robots into educational assets.

Main problems

The main problem is that there are no gender sensitive/ gender specific measures /actions on enhancing transfer to the market of scientific research results. No female researchers have been identified in the teams of university spin offs.

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Objective(s)

The goal is to introduce to the researchers of UNIZG-FER gender sensitive/ gender specific measures /actions on enhancing transfer to the market of scientific research results.

Possible solutions

- Set up gender sensitive/ gender specific measures /actions on enhancing transfer to the market of scientific research results.
- Organize workshops to empower female researchers and students to participate in spin offs.

Resistances

The expected resistances are from internal stakeholders. First, they could be coming from the administration like resistance from the Research support centre to organize workshops, implement gender specific measures in transfer to market pipeline, resistance of SPOCK (spin-off centre) to organize workshops. Next it could be coming from high management like resistance from high management to set up guidelines for transfer to market. Finally, it could be coming from students and researchers: resistance from female students/researchers to participate in workshops about spin offs. No resistances are expected from external stakeholders. Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative actions such as empowering female students and researchers to participate in spin-offs will strengthen the potential of the institution.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are from internal stakeholders. It could be coming from the administration like SPOCK (Spin off centre of UNIZG-FER) that is always looking for new spin-off ideas. Next, opportunities could be coming from high management; high management supports action that will help researchers have better research results. Finally, opportunities could come from researchers and students like female students/researchers that have good ideas for spin-offs, but need to be encouraged and supported. No opportunities from external stakeholders have been identified.

Communication

1. External communication

Situation

Via desk research, the institutional website was reviewed to assess the external institutional communication. As a result, the front webpage of UNIZG-FER contains basic information about the study programs at UNIZG-FER. There is an effort to use gender neutral language on website. The Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing is perceived in public as a very successful male institution. There is a strong public perception that only men work and study at UNIZG-FER. There is no dedicated webpage for gender equality. UNIZG-FER promotes women researchers in the media.

On social media, UNIZG-FER is very actively represented on social networks especially on Facebook . Public relations office publishes daily news related to research and social life at the institution. The fact that the numerical ratio of male and female students is 75:25 is also reflected in the notices related to student achievement. Public relations service pays special attention to promote successful women on institutional social media. On Women's Day of 2020, a post dedicated to a prominent young scientist was published on the institution's Instagram profile, and it was pointed out that about 27% of assistant professorships at FER belong to young scientists.

In relation to the presence of dedicated communication activities promoting women, Career Center (CKF) is the organizational unit of UNIZG-FER, whose main tasks are systematic care of preparing students for a competitive domestic and global labor market after graduation. CKF combines different types of activities that complement the academic curricula regarding career development and works to improve better

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interaction of academia and economy. CKF educates students how to identify opportunities to achieve desired careers that match their values, interests, traits and skills. CKF pays special attention in attracting and promoting young successful women students.

Main problems

The main problem with regards to the external institutional communication is that the communication materials do not reflect diversity neither in gender nor in terms of ethnicity, disability etc., the desk research shows. Furthermore, additional communication material with content related to gender has not been identified on the webpage of UNIZG-FER. There are no awareness raising campaigns aimed at fighting stereotypes at UNIZG – FER.

Hypotheses about the causes of the problem are the following:

- It is clear the effort by the web team to put gender neutral graphics, on the website; but considering that UNIZG-FER is male dominated institution, tech images only enhance this perception.
- There were no requests so far to set up web page dedicated to gender equality.
- There were no suggestions to participate in awareness raising campaigns aimed at fighting stereotypes.

Objective(s)

The goal is to make external institutional communication compliant with guidelines on gender sensitive communication.

Possible solutions

- Set up guidelines or organize workshops for public relation officers and web officers about gender sensitive external communication.
- Set up dedicated webpage for gender equality.
- Organize awareness raising campaigns aimed at fighting stereotypes at UNIZG – FER.

Resistances

The expected resistances are from internal stakeholders. First, it could be coming from the administration like resistance from web team to participate in the training about gender sensitive external communication. Next, it could come from middle management such as resistance to participate in awareness raising campaigns. Resistances could also come from researchers and students: resistance to participate in awareness raising campaigns aimed at fighting stereotypes. Finally, it could be coming from high management: resistance to set up awareness raising campaigns aimed at fighting stereotypes, resistance to set up dedicated webpage for gender equality. No resistance has been identified from external stakeholders.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative actions, such as more inclusive webpage will make our institution more attractive for female students, having webpage dedicated to gender equality will enable us to publish in one place all related info, reports, news, projects making the content more available to the researchers and interested general public; making this data available to our researchers will help them write project applications eligible for application for funding from Horizon Europe (GEP requirement).

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are from internal stakeholders. It could come from the administration such as web team and public relations office that are already following unofficial guidelines for gender sensitive external communication which shows their good will to develop also official guidelines. Opportunities could

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also be coming from high management, high management is by the Rule of operations of UNIZ-FER obliged to build more inclusive environment; any initiative making UNIZ-FER more eligible for funding from Horizon Europe is welcome. Next, opportunities could be coming from researchers: researcher applying for funding from Horizon Europe will welcome having webpage dedicated to gender equality containing all related info, reports, news. Finally, it could come from students: our student population already is quite diverse, they will welcome showing this. No opportunities have been identified from external stakeholders.

2. Internal communication

Situation

There is an effort to use gender sensitive language on internal documents. There are no guidelines / protocols on gender sensitive nonbiased communication/language use.

Due to the specificity of the Croatian language, there is a legal problem in the scientific titles, as the law prescribes that scientific titles should be used in masculine gender in legal documents.

The complaint mechanism in cases of gender biased / sexist communication is available and effective. In cases of gender biased / sexist communication, one can submit a complaint to the Ethics Committee of UNIZG-FER.

Main problems

The main problem is that there is no institutional training or official guidelines on fighting stereotypes in communications. Due to the specificity of the Croatian language, there is a legal problem in the scientific titles, as the law prescribes that scientific titles should be used in masculine gender in legal documents.

Hypotheses about the causes of the problem are the following:

- There is an effort to use gender sensitive language on internal documents. Since no complaints have been raised, it was considered unnecessary to set up official guidelines for gender sensitive language.
- There was no effort to explore options for solving a legal problem in scientific titles, since nobody was complaining.

Objective(s)

The goal is to improve internal communication in view of gender sensitivity.

Possible solutions

- Organize training for employees on fighting stereotypes in communications.
- Set up guidelines for employees on fighting stereotypes in communications.
- Explore possible solutions that will enable writing scientific titles in the appropriate gender in official documents.

Resistances

The expected resistances are from internal stakeholders. There could be resistances coming from the administration like resistance to participate in the workshops and resistance to participate in the solution of the legal problems with scientific titles. Resistance could also come from middle level and high-level management, both having resistance to set up guidelines. Finally, resistances could be coming from researchers; they might have resistance to participate in the workshops. No resistances have been identified coming from external stakeholders.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative. Legal problems with scientific titles have been tackled by other institution, UNIZG-FER can follow their lead; unofficial guidelines for gender sensitive communication already exist, therefore it is not such a big step to make them official.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from internal stakeholders. Opportunities could come from the administration, general service is implementing gender equality policy and they will be interested in solving legal problems if possible. It could also come from high management, high management will support making unofficial good practices official. Finally, opportunities could be coming from researchers; female academic will welcome initiative to have their scientific title in proper gender.

Intersectionality

Situation

The institution implements Anti-discrimination Act and Ethics Code of the University of Zagreb. In the document Internal Labor Regulations of the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing it is stated that a worker who considers that he/she has been discriminated has the right to lodge a written complaint to the Person of Confidence elected by the Dean. All the procedures are defined in this document. UNIZG-FER implements a document Regulation on Internal Reporting of Irregularities of the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing.

UNIZG-FER has an Ethics Committee which implements the Code of Ethics of the University of Zagreb. This body deals with discrimination, harassment and plagiarism issues for all academic staff and students. Students can also report to the Student Ombudsperson at UNIZG-FER regarding issues of academic relations and student rights and freedoms. There is Person of Confidence elected by the Dean to whom employees can report any discrimination. His/her actions are prescribed by the law. There are legally defined procedures how to handle these situations, and UNIZG-FER is implementing them.

Finally, at UZG all types of discrimination are forbidden and taken seriously, but the topic of intersectionality is not well-known, thus raising awareness about the topic of intersectionality is highly recommended for the academic community.

Main problems

The main problem is that the topic of intersectionality is not well-known.

Hypotheses about the causes of the problem are the following:

- The topic of intersectionality is not well-known, so it was not possible to envisage measures.

Objective(s)

The goal is raising awareness about the topic of intersectionality.

Possible solutions

- Organize training / workshop for employees on the topic of intersectionality.
- Collect relevant data about students and employees and create reports.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first from internal stakeholders. Resistances could come from the administration like resistance to participate in the workshops and resistance to execute data collection process. It could also come from middle management such as resistance to participate in the workshops. Next, resistance could come from high management like resistance to organize workshops and resistance to set up data collection process. Finally, researchers could have resistance such as resistance to participate in the workshops. No resistances have been identified from external stakeholders.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative. This topic is not well known, and considering that next academic year UNIZG-FER will start new study program in English language and students coming from all over the world, this would be good for the institution

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are from internal stakeholders. It could come from high management that wants to prepare the institution for the new study program in English and new students coming from all over the world. No opportunities have been identified coming from external stakeholders.

Sexism and sexual harassment

Situation

In the document Internal Labor Regulations of the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing it is stated that a worker who considers that he/she has been harassed has the right to lodge a written complaint to the Person of Confidence elected by the Dean. All the procedures are defined in this document. UNIZG-FER implements the Regulation on Internal Reporting of Irregularities of the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing. UNIZG-FER has an Ethics Committee which implements the Code of Ethics of the University of Zagreb. This body deals with discrimination, harassment and plagiarism issues for all academic staff and students. Students can also report to the Student Ombudsperson at UNIZG-FER regarding issues of academic relations and student rights and freedoms. Students can report sexual harassment to Student Ombudsperson, respecting privacy is strongly implemented. Employees can report sexual harassment to Person of Confidence. There is the Ethical Committee at UNIZG-FER which implements Code of Ethics of the University of Zagreb.

At UZG, there are no publicly known cases of employees reporting sexual harassment. At the same time, there is no special counselling service for gender-based offenses and harassment for staff.

Main problems

The main problem is that there is no special counselling service for gender-based offenses and harassment for staff.

Hypotheses about the causes of the problem are the following:

- UNIZG-FER needs extra funding for employing external experts to do the counseling.

Objective(s)

The goal is to set up counselling service for gender-based offenses and harassment for staff.

Possible solutions

- Explore whether counseling services already exist on the university level to reduce costs.
- Explore possibility of synergies with other faculties of the university.
- Set up joint counseling service for gender-based offenses and harassment for staff.

Resistances

The expected resistances are from internal stakeholders. Resistances could come from high management such as resistance to provide financial support to set up counselling service at faculty level and resistance of high management to have dialogue with other faculties to search for joint opportunities. No resistance has been identified from external stakeholders. Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative. These serious problems in academia should be addressed and employees who need help should get it.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first coming from internal stakeholders. Opportunities could be coming from the administration; employees will support counselling opportunities for harassment and discrimination cases. It could also come from high and middle management both will support counselling opportunities for harassment and discrimination cases. Finally, opportunities could be coming from

researchers; they will support counselling opportunities for harassment and discrimination cases. Secondly, some opportunities are expected from external stakeholders. Opportunities could come from the academia; other faculties will support sharing the cost of counselling opportunities for harassment and discrimination cases.

Synthesis of stakeholders to involve

In order to overcome the described resistances and use afore-mentioned opportunities the following stakeholders need to be involved: the high-level management, the Career Centre and Office for Human Resources, scientific committee or UNIZG – FER and research support centre, Vice Dean for teaching, SPOCK (Spin off center of UNIZG-FER) to change the organizational rules and to accept and implement the proposed strategy; people who will be impacted by the strategy (research group leaders, doctoral students, employees of administrative offices and researchers and postdoc employees, high level and middle level manager). External stakeholders also need to be involved, especially stakeholders from the academia and other faculties from the ecosystem of UNIZG – FER, the Croatian Science Foundation, stakeholders from the CALIPER project, stakeholders from business/industry like companies, the government and public sector such as high school students.

Actions to be taken to ensure stakeholders' collaboration are argumentative action such as dialogues and brainstorming with internal and external stakeholders, such as High Management, Middle Management, research group leaders, researchers, female role models. There also are informative actions like using information websites of the involved organizational units of UNIZG-FER to publish news about the project. Finally, there are engagement actions like having dialogues with external stakeholders.

2.2 Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia (RFO)

Human resources

Situation

At the organization level of SRNSFG, there are no particular gender-sensitive recruitment protocols/policies. SRNSFG is only obliged to follow the regulations provided at a national level. The statistics show that in recruitment processes, more females apply for open positions across all departments, succeed and have both, permanent and temporary contracts. However, they get a middle or low management positions, while top management positions mostly are covered by males.

SRNSFG does not adopt any internal measures in order to improve work-life balance. Main measures at organization implemented in order to enhance work-life balance are only those which are defined by "Law of Georgia on Public Services". In addition, no parental leaves and no part-time/flexible hours arrangements were at the organization. During the last three years, there weren't any teleworking positions at the organization.

There are no particular appraisal systems for career evolution at SRNSFG and organization hasn't adopted any transparent and flexible promotion criteria for the promotion of staff yet, such as, for example, continuing education as well as individual performance measurement. Career development /promotion can be done only by application of employee to the position through a competition and takes place on the basis of the Head' recommendation. No flexible or fixed criteria exist for the promotion of staff.

Regarding the career breaks and job reintegration, according to statistics about work-life balance_ along the last three years, women used to drop out or break their careers in a shorter period than men. No parental leaves and no part-time/flexible hours arrangements took place at the organization. During the last three years, as well there weren't any teleworking positions at organization.

Main problems

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- Non-existence of gender-sensitive recruitment protocols/policies at organizational level;
- No internal measures for the improvement of work-life balance;
- No appraisal systems for career evolution;
- No internal policies/regulations for the career support and development;

Objective(s)

Five objectives have been identified. The first one is the implementation of gender-sensitive policies inside the organization. The second one is the improvement of working conditions and work-life balance. The third objective is the provision of flexible hours for students/employees which can give the opportunity for the improvement of knowledge and career development. The fourth one is the adoption of internal policies/regulations for the career support and development. The last and fifth one is the provision of different trainings and activities improving professional skills of staff.

Possible solutions

- Implementation of gender-sensitive recruitment protocols/policies oriented to prevent gender bias through the provision of particular guidelines ensuring gender equality in recruitment process (for example, guidelines for writing and publishing of recruitment advertisements; keeping records of recruitment decisions; trainings for people involved in recruitment process; guidelines for usage of gender neutral language).
- Adoption of measures oriented to enhance work-life balance: maternity/paternity leave, in house nurseries or agreements with local ones; telework, vacations policy, part-time employment options, career development plans, flexible working hours, career breaks, dual careers household support, gender sensitive healthcare plans, transparent and family friendly policies on overtime.
- Support and provision of career development of employees.

Resistances

The expected resistances are coming from internal stakeholders. Resistances are expected from staff of different levels, such as finding some goals impossible to achieve and critical or blocking positions. Some staff agreed with changes but still can be very passive and not supportive. Some staff considers gender equality topics not relevant and actual in case of the foundation and can be the source of implicit resistances. Mostly SRNSFG can say that resistances at SRNSFG represent individual/personal resistances rather than group resistances. No resistances come from external stakeholders yet.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are, to start, in the rules of the organization such as involving more women and men in the organization in gender equality work, keeping gender equality issues on the organizational agenda and making gender initiatives more visible and providing and making visible up-to-date quantitative data on gender equality indicators in the organization. Other strategies could also be communication and dissemination, in other words, effective communication of the intended changes of the GEP both in and outside the institution, enhancing the gender awareness (by organizing trainings/briefings by gender experts) and organizing enthusiastic kick-off meetings to engage the whole institution could also be organized. Other actions could be achieving consensus on different issues.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first that possible changes can be implemented based on internal decisions and do not require special permissions from Ministry/Government. Next, recruitment procedures are regulated by national law and goals mentioned above will not contradict the existing laws and since there is no internal regulations there will be also any opposition with internal policies of Foundation. Another opportunity is that some regulations and practices existed at Foundation in the past and it will be easier to implement them. Also, based on previous practices, the regulations will be more accepted by the top

management.

Governance

Situation

Gender equality matters are not adjusted/regulated with SRNSFG official documents and regulations and therefore there is no monitoring or evaluation process on gender equality.

SRNSFG provides annual statistics about SRNSFG gender composition to the National Statistics Office of Georgia, however statistical data are not analyzed.

In order to enhance women leadership and support their access to top positions, there are no strategies/policies at SRNSFG to foster gender balance in the decision making process which can provide gender quotas applying to appointment of leadership positions or elections to decision making positions/governing bodies.

For the maintenance of gender equality at SRNSFG, there are no special positions related to work regarding gender equality in the organization;

Main problems

- With no recent previous background in this regard, the organization does not have any policy regulating female career advancement;
- Although SRNSFG has an electronic system collecting data about gender statistics in the administered grant calls, funded grants and open vacancies, collection of this type of data is done upon request;
- A gender equality position/s does not exist, which focuses on the gender balance, monitors the gender situation in the organization, ensures the gender balance in organization's top positions and higher managerial level.
- gender imbalance in leadership positions;

Objective(s)

Several objectives have been identified. To start with the focus of enhancing women leadership and access to the top positions, related policies need to be elaborated, as well as regulatory documents, which sets gender equality in the organization's operational process and provides gender quotas for ensuring the gender balance in top management level. Another objective is defining special positions regarding gender equality in the organization, which could monitor gender balance at institutional level. Other objectives are doing regular monitoring process and setting the statistical data on administrative level and, achieving consensus on different issues.

Possible solutions

- To adopt a female career advancement policy, which ensures gender balance in organization's top positions;
- Collecting gender disaggregated data at the organization's institutional level;
- To modify existing job descriptions of SRNSFG Administration unit by adding targeted function to promote and monitor gender issues in the organization;

Resistances

The expected resistances are first coming from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from the top management and others coming from the department of law and administration. With no previous experience and elaborated evidence-based gender policy, the management may come across the difficulties in the setting process and may perceive the adoption policy as unnecessary to fulfill. Secondly,

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some resistances may come from external Stakeholders. It could be due to institutional changes, bringing modification within the organization, which needs consent from the Ministry.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first in the rules of the organization: engaging more women and men in the organization in work related to gender equality, keeping gender equality issues on the organizational agenda and enhance the focus on gender equality issues in administration and budgeting processes, by the means of involving them in the process of adoption of GEP and other related issues. Secondly, there could be argumentative actions like communication and dissemination. Effective communication to bring the necessity of gender equality issues, which supports raising awareness of activities, necessary for gender equality and disseminates information about intended changes.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are that some changes (e.g., positional) do not require permission from external stakeholder and can be decided on an internal level. Others are that SRNSFG is working in a gender friendly environment.

Research

Situation

SRNSFG does not administer gender specific funding programs. In the past few years more women than men took part to grant calls, but this situation may not be stable as SRNSFG grant call criteria do not include a paragraph on gender equality in research teams and gender dimension in research content. Also, at SRNSFG there are no special measures or policies for gender balance in funding decision-making and scientific evaluation panels and there are no specific protocols on gender sensitive recruitment of evaluators. In addition to this, SRNSFG does not collect data on the gender composition of evaluation panels.

At SRNSFG there are no guidelines on gender stereotypes and unconscious bias to evaluators. Project evaluators are not trained and, also, they are not provided with any kind of gender related evaluation practices. Finally, while SRNSFG supports the development of Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) system in Georgia, the mission and objectives of the foundation does not specifically aim at promoting implementation research projects with commercialization perspective, and technology transfer or transfer to market. Above mentioned activities is carried out by Georgia's Innovation and Technology Agency (GITA), which promotes commercialization of knowledge and innovations, to stimulate using them in all fields of economy. The Agency also promotes commercialization mechanisms according to Georgia's innovation and technology development priorities and facilitates the participation of researches and commercialization of innovation.

Main problems

- Limited annual budget of SRNSFG which is approved by the Government of Georgia;
- The most important problems are that, without a paragraph on gender equality in research teams, sex/gender balance is not taken into account during evaluation process and applicants are not required to provide information about the relevance of sex/gender in their research proposal or how the gender perspective will be integrated into the entire research or innovation cycle;
- Unconscious bias by evaluators in evaluation process;
- Without guidelines and trainings on gender stereotypes and unconscious bias there is a problem of “objective” evaluators, who are acting on rational arguments with cognitive gender bias.

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Objective(s)

Four objectives have been identified. The first one is promoting gender equality in research by allocating funds for specific programs on gender equality aimed at fostering the production of new knowledge for a better understanding of gender issues. The second objective is promoting the integration of a gender dimension in the content of scientific research by integrating gender dimension in current programs and calls for proposals. The third one is about creating gender balanced funding decision-making bodies, scientific evaluation panels and specific protocols on gender sensitive recruitment of evaluators, which will facilitate gender unbiased evaluation processes. The fourth one is providing evaluators with specific guidelines on gender stereotypes, unconscious bias and trainings ensuring successful evaluation processes without any kind of gender bias.

Possible solutions

- Convincing argumentation about the importance of creating and announcing new research funding program as well as integrating gender dimension in already existing grant calls. In addition to this, increasing SRNSFG annual budget or announcing new grant call at the expense of other grant calls;
- Require from applicants to indicate whether sex/gender are relevant to their research proposal and how the gender perspective will be integrated into the entire research or innovation cycle. Also, when sex/gender analysis is not relevant for the field of study, an explanation should be given by applicants. In addition to this raising awareness activities and trainings of the scientific community in Georgia regarding the importance of gender equality in research content and in research teams; encouraging and strengthening the research environment towards gender equality.
- Creating gender balanced funding decision making bodies or inviting gender experts for each evaluation procedure to make sure that potential unconscious bias towards female candidates are prevented and that gender is taken into account as a dimension in the content of scientific research.
- Hiring experienced gender experts who will help SRNSFG staff compile such materials and to disseminate guidelines for grant applicants and peer reviewers/evaluators on the integration of the gender analysis into research content, and to support their engagement with gender.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first coming from internal stakeholders. To start, resistances from researchers as additional evaluation criteria on gender equality may be perceived as unnecessary and problematic for them to fulfill. To continue, be resistances from administration, high management and researchers as creating funding decision-making bodies and scientific evaluation panels must be merit and experience based. In some scientific sub-fields there is a lack of experienced staff, therefore, the adoption of additional criteria may complicate the procedure for finding a proper evaluators. To finish, there could be resistances from high and middle management as at SRNSFG there are no experienced staff who will compile guidelines/ training materials on gender equality and provide them to evaluators. Secondly, some resistances are expected coming from external stakeholders. Resistances from the Government of Georgia as announcing new grant call require additional financial support. Current State budget related problems will possibly hinder the foundation from creating and announcing a new grant call. There could also be resistances and possible disapproval from the relevant bodies in the Parliament and the Ministry of Education and Science of Georgia about adopting a paragraph on gender equality in research teams and gender dimension in research content.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first in the rules of the organization such as involving

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more women and men in the organization in gender equality work, keeping gender equality issues on the organizational agenda and making gender initiatives more visible and providing and making visible up-to-date quantitative data on gender equality indicators in the organization. There could also be communication and dissemination actions like effective communication of the intended changes of the GEP both in and outside the institution; reasoned posing and explaining on the importance of gender equality in research to the relevant authorities and scientific community. Other actions could be achieving consensus on different issues.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from internal stakeholders. To start, the staff of the SRNSFG, including high and middle management, has a broad experience concerning creating and administering new grant calls as well as capacity to change already existing programs. To continue, SRNSFG high management and administration are capable of successful negotiations with the relevant bodies in the Parliament and the Ministry regarding the integration of a gender dimension in the content of scientific research as well as creation of gender balanced funding decision-making bodies.

Transfer to Market

While SRNSFG supports the development of Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) system in Georgia, the mission and objectives of the foundation does not specifically aim at promoting implementation research projects with commercialization perspective, and technology transfer or transfer to market. Above mentioned activities is carried out by Georgia's Innovation and Technology Agency (GITA), which promotes commercialization of knowledge and innovations, to stimulate using them in all fields of economy. The Agency also promotes commercialization mechanisms according to Georgia's innovation and technology development priorities and facilitates the participation of researches and commercialization of innovation.

Communication

Situation

At SRNSFG there are no specific raising awareness training activities on gender sensitive language use and/or gender sensitive communication.

Also, there is no gender related modules and no special policies/guidelines on internal and external gender sensitive communication exist. As Georgian language consists of no exclusionary forms such as he/she, there are no policies and training in place on this issue.

Main problems

- Gender equality is not presented/promoted through the SRNSFG website.
- There is no internal communication strategy in SRNSFG.
- There are no informal instructions/regulations and practices to make a gender mainstreaming a regular item in the activities of SRNSFG.

Objective(s)

Two objectives have been identified. To make society aware about sense and values of gender equality and to create an effective institutional communication.

Possible solutions

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- To elaborate a strategy encompassing all aspects related to institutional communication: special trainings, conferences, symposia.
- To create a special section on the website revealing successful Georgian women in STEM, to disseminate information revealing the need to support the transformation of research institutions to more gender-equal entities by increasing the number of women researchers in STEM, enhancing their career perspectives and adding a gender dimension in research.
- To develop a protocol for gender-sensitive communication - to make gender mainstreaming a regular item on the agenda of SRNSFG.
- To develop institutional communication with the aim to harmonize the STEM system- designing and then implementing a strategic communication plan that could motivate all internal stakeholders to become active participants, ensuring ongoing interest and progress.
- To establish gender equality priorities in public consciousness that women and men play an equal role in all areas of public life, including science. To collaborate with SRNSFG communication team or other relevant personnel with the aim to create a communications plan or campaign tailored to support gender equality initiatives in STEM.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first coming from internal stakeholders. Resistance might come from top managerial level to agree to introduce institutional changes. The use of gender sensitive language in the organization's documents as well as in the communication channels could also be a resistance. Some resistances are also expected coming from external stakeholder. They could be coming from the government/public sector.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first to create institutional websites and printed publications are sensitive to the issue of gender equality. Next, to create corporate media product, press releases, announcements, distribution of audio-video material, where inclusive language is used, the content is free of sexist language, discriminatory terminology and the content will be perceived by people of different sex. Another one is to disseminate information about the Foundation's activities aiming to the provision of better understanding of the role of women in the development of science in Georgia, as well as the contribution of women scientists from different countries to the development of Georgian sciences, popularization of Georgian history and culture is disseminated through the website. The stakeholders to involve in the strategies are first internal stakeholders such as high and middle management, head of respective units, middle management and employees of different units and female and male coworkers, researchers. External stakeholders should also be involved like the one from the academia (Universities, Research Centers), the one from civil society (NGOs, Women's organization) and the one from the government/public sector (the Government of Georgia and the Ministry of Education and Science of Georgia).

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first to involve internal stakeholders to design a gender sensitive strategy. Another opportunity is to create special policies/guidelines on internal and external gender sensitive communication. A protocol for on gender-sensitive communication could also be developed. Training / activities of Raising Awareness on gender sensitive language use and/or gender sensitive communication could be organized. A last opportunity could be to disseminate information about international activities, programs aimed at strengthening and promoting the role of women in the field of science and innovation.

Intersectionality

Situation

In a broader context, (on a national level), the Law of Georgia on the Elimination of all forms of discrimination (Parliament of Georgia, 2014), ensures to „eliminate every form of discrimination and ensure equal rights of every natural and legal persons under the legislation of Georgia, irrespective of race, skin color, language, sex, age, citizenship, origin, place of birth or residence, property or social status, religion or belief, national, ethnic or social origin, profession, marital status, health, disability, sexual orientation, gender identity and expression, political or other opinions, or other characteristics. (Parliament of Georgia, 2014). Considering this, SRNSFG at the organizational level operates in accordance with the law and ensures non-discrimination and equal treatment of its employees as well as its beneficiaries the researchers and scientists. However, currently, at institutional level, there are no specific policy and institutional mechanisms that consider gender in conjunction with other discriminations. Thus, interaction of gender and other variables has not been addressed through intersectional approach.

National policies on equality and discriminations are in place, however, this aspect has not been measured at an institutional level (SRNSFG). At the moment, the only available document that includes the idea of gender equality in conjunction with other discriminations and structural inequalities is an internal document, the N187 Order (14th article) of SRNSFG Director General, which envisages some exemption practices for women and parents regarding a working environment. There are no other specific institutional measures concerning this issue.

Legal and institutional mechanism on equality and discriminations are in place, such as the Law of Georgia on Gender Equality, adopted in 2010; number of national entities and agencies are responsible for the advancement of gender equality in the country: 1) the Gender Equality Council of the Parliament, 2) the Inter-Agency Commission on Gender Equality, Violence against Women and Domestic Violence Issues, and 3) the Gender Department of the Public Defender's Office). Presence of such legal and institutional mechanisms is a good starting point to integrate gender in the science and research field as well.

SRNSFG has a strong record of collaboration with external actors, mainly including joint calls and projects, multiple workshops, webinars and joint events, but no collaborations are in place with specific reference to gender equality.

Main problems

Intersectionality is a new concept and approach and is not understood properly, therefore it is not perceived as a component of equality policies within the institution. (SRNSFG). According to the interviews and focus groups data, there is a misunderstanding of a concept of an intersectional approach to gender equality as most of the participants confuse this term with gender equality.

Lack of specific measures and mechanisms that would foster promoting gender equality on a ground. For example, neither national legislation nor national action plans on gender equality contain any specific mechanisms to promote the under-represented gender in higher education or scientific research and innovation. Gender Equality Law does not require employers to develop internal gender equality plans. No national legislation/program is in place about the integration of the gender dimension in research.

Lack of sufficient measures towards gender equality necessary to maximize the workforce potential of women and stimulate deeper involvement of women in entrepreneurial and economic activities; women residing in the regions have less access to the programs; gender dimension in the services or products design has not been addressed .

At an institutional level, SRNSFG, no collaborations are in place with specific reference to gender equality.

Objective(s)

Several objectives have been identified. At first, there is the objective to increase understanding of Intersectionality as a component of equality policies within the institution with a goal of gradually introducing an intersectional approach at the institution. Next, there is the one of gradually introducing an intersectional approach at the institution (SRNSFG). Another objective is to introduce respective amendments to the law so that the existing laws are comprehensive and inclusive, as well as to envisage concrete institutional measures in the respective strategies and action plans of government and sectoral ministries. To continue, there is the objective to make involvement of women in entrepreneurial and economic activities more inclusive and effective. It is important to note that the foundation (SRNSFG), has established collaborations with its partner agencies with specific reference to gender equality.

Possible solutions

- Raising awareness about the definition and importance of intersectionality and on the importance of going beyond an existing understanding of gender equality issues and policies at the institutional level (SRNSFG) through specific trainings/ meetings or informative activities;
- promoting intersectional data collection measures at the organizational level, so that this enables disaggregated data by gender + ethnicity, gender identity, age, disability etc.

Resistances

As at this stage there is a low awareness on Intersectionality as a component of equality policies within the institution, thus the topic of intersectionality is not appropriately addressed at the institutional level; therefore, resistances might come from high and middle management staff over priority of the issue as well as on a low awareness of the topic. Some resistances are expected coming from administration on a limited human resource to incorporate this dimension in the respective legal documents and collect data. As to the broader dimension of the issue, resistances from external stakeholders are less likely to come.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first argumentative actions such as creating consensus between the staff members on the concepts of intersectionality used in the project and keeping this issue on the agenda. Next, some strategies touch the rules of the organization like establishing contacts with key persons and strategic units of the Foundation, (SRNSFG) to increase awareness of the issue, by organizing trainings/ find external partners such as UN Georgia or respective NGOs to enhance understanding of intersectional approach. Other actions could be organized like collaborating with other appropriate projects at institutional, national levels with an aim of sharing experience in this regard.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first coming from the rules or structure of the organization, the existing environment at the Foundation as well as broader national context about dealing the structural and other inequalities leaves a room for incorporating intersectional approach to gender inequalities at the institutional level. Other opportunities could be coming from the administration, since respective legal provisions might be required in order to incorporate intersectionality; it provides opportunity to the administration to make its structure and organization more compatible with legal obligations regarding gender equality and non-discrimination on a national level. Next, some could be coming from middle management, work in a more, transparent and accountable and inclusive environment. To finish, opportunities could be coming from high management, work in a more, transparent and accountable and inclusive environment.

Sexism and sexual harassment

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Situation

Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia is obliged to follow the national regulations according to which sexual harassment is not allowed in labor relations (Law of Georgia on Gender Equality, Article 6(1b) and labor relations shall prohibit any type of discrimination including sexual harassment (Organic Law of Georgia, Article 2(3), 2(4)).

The foundation does not have any particular policies and initiatives addressing sexual harassment. The relevant research showed that there were no reported cases of harassment in 2017, 2018, 2019. On the one hand, the situation may seem unproblematic. But on the other hand, it is important to underline that no reporting mechanisms have been put in place at the foundation so far. For that reason, sexual harassment might have gone unreported. Herewith, it is worth mentioning that most employees do not have information about the availability of counselling for gender – based offenses and harassments.

Main problems

- Lack of information with reference to sexual harassment.
- Lack of reporting channels. According to the relevant research, there were no measures taken to elicit reporting formally gender/sexual harassment in 2017,2018,2019.
- The absence of specific policies/ guidelines on the preventions of sexual harassment. The problem of gender-based offence/ and harassment may arise at any time.

Objective(s)

Two objectives have been identified. They are to be prepared if such a case occurs and, in case of gender-based offences and harassments, employees will know who to turn to.

Possible solutions

- Contrasting gender harassment by adopting some policies and/ or anti-harassment guidelines. In terms of the content, they should preferably include clarification of what sexual harassment is, types of sexual harassment at the workplace, information concerning national policies, information concerning reporting procedures, etc. Adopting such policies will contribute to prevent harassment before it occurs.
- Providing/Integrating mechanisms for reporting. This will ensure that all employees at the foundation know which appropriate department, unit or individual to contact.
- Conducting trainings/ informational activities that aim at raising awareness on this issue. This is of crucial importance for sexual harassment prevention.

Resistances

The expected resistances are coming from internal stakeholders. Resistances might come both from high management, middle management and the administration, but not from the rules or structure of the organization. The possible resistances are as follows: low priority - within the organization sexism/sexual harassment is not a topical issue at present; there are not enough human resources and/or financial resources at the foundation. No resistances come from external stakeholders.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first argumentative actions like to make gender initiatives and enhance the gender equality willingness, in other words, enhance the gender awareness. Next, strategies could touch the rules of the organization such as to keep gender issues on the institutional agenda and engage both women and men in any gender-related activities. Other actions could be organized like to develop institutional culture that values gender equality (this is important because sexual

harassment/sexism is type of gender discrimination) and collaborate with appropriate organizations at institutional, national, international levels.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first coming from internal stakeholders. There are no specific rules or regulations at the foundation that can contradict adoption of anti-harassment policies. This leaves room for establishing internal workplace policies that aim at prohibiting sexual harassment and makes it possible to maintain a workplace that is free of gender-based harassment. Once the anti-harassment guideline or policy is in place, the administration/middle management/ high management can ask the employees to read it. This will contribute to the dissemination of the guideline/ policy within the foundation. Secondly, some opportunities are expected coming from external stakeholders. They could be coming from civil society such as NGOs, Women's organizations, and International organizations.

Synthesis of stakeholders to involve

To overcome the described resistances and use afore-mentioned opportunities the following stakeholders need to be involved: the high-level management, the legal and administrative department and the middle management to change the organizational rules and to accept and implement the proposed strategy; people who will be impacted by the strategy (the staff of Foundation, the one from the academia, universities, and research centers). External stakeholders also need to be involved, especially stakeholders from the civil society, NGOs, Women's organizations, the Government of Georgia, and the Ministry of Education and Science of Georgia.

Some actions to be taken to ensure stakeholders' collaboration (both internal and external) are first organizational change actions such as creating consensus between the stakeholders on different issues, to develop commitment to gender equality. There could also be information actions like raising awareness of the effects of potential changes and gender equality significance among the stakeholders, reasoned posing and explaining the problem to the relevant authorities and scientific community, to provide training to general staff on gender equality and other structural inequalities; organizing formal and informal meetings to engage the whole institution, mapping the institution/people and the context better. To continue, there could also be engagement actions such as organizing meetings, workshops, etc. to raise awareness about gender equality, organization of specific training and informational activities in collaboration with respective entities, such as UN Women, respective National institutions and NGOs with respective experience in order to increase awareness of intersectoral approach. Finally, joint projects/activities could be organized like the involvement of different stakeholders in working and implementation process.

2.3 Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava² (RPO)

Human resources

Scenario 1: maximal resistance

Work environments and working conditions

Situation

² STU BA initially organized its scenarios not by topic but by the level of difficulty of the actions. The structure of the report has been slightly modified to adapt it to the standard structure of the deliverable. This is the reason why, for some topics, there are not three scenarios: for some areas STU BA did not identify 'maximal resistance' or 'low resistance' to the possible solutions.

There is a disinterest of management and employees to change related to the introduction of new approaches in the field of human resources.

Main Problems

There are resistances to change as the introduction of gender policy would mean introducing and learning new processes which some employees might consider redundant and complicated, low awareness of the benefits of gender policy.

Objective(s)

To increase the interest of managers and employees in gender equality policy and reduction of resistance to change.

Possible solutions

Internal and external communication by the faculty to support the idea of gender equality among employees and management, awareness-raising activities aimed at faculty employees and management.

- To inform employees and management of the faculty about possible ways how to raise gender equality awareness by posting motivation pictures (shareable content) on the internet and within the faculty so they are more interested and open-minded towards gender equality topic.
- To motivate the management to apply policy considering gender equality.
- To motivate employees to point out what issues they have in relation to gender equality in the field of human resources.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first coming from internal stakeholders. It could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization such as individual motivation. Other resistances could come from the administration because there is no gender equality policy. Middle and high management could have resistances because they have low knowledge of the benefits of the benefits of gender policy and for organizational efficiency. There might also be resistances coming from researchers that may consider the gender equality issues as unimportant and may not want to join the discussion about this topic and apply changes. To finish, some resistances could be coming from students as they have low knowledge of the benefits of gender policy, they may show a little interest in gender equality issue. Resistances can also be expected from external stakeholders. Coming from the academia, resistances could come from the fact that there is insufficient exchange of experience. Others could come from civil society as they have less knowledge of the benefits of gender equality and a little interest in the gender equality topic. Because the government/public sector have non-transparent gender policy, there might be resistances. To finish industrial stakeholders could have resistances because they do not know about the benefits of gender equality policies.

Possible strategies for overcoming resistance are first argumentation action such as the explanation why gender policy is important. Next, they could touch the rules of the organization like motivation for the awareness-raising, better communication. Finally, other actions such as information sharing within the internet to make the awareness-raising topic popular among people could be done.

Measures needed to ensure cooperation between stakeholders (internal and external) are first argumentation action such as defining clear objectives and benefits of education gender equality. Next, there are measures related to organizational change, motivation and definition of tasks. To continue, information events like workshops could be organized.

Career support and development strategies

Situation

The proportion of male professors is much higher than the female one.

Main Problems

There is a small number of women with the title of professor.

Objective(s)

increase in the number of women with the title of professor.

Possible solutions

Take in consideration and support of women with children in science activities and career growth at the university:

- Supporting women in further science activities at university, especially shortly after the parental leave by remote work (home-office).
- Considering the measures to take parental leave periods into account when measuring performance/scientific excellence or researchers with caring responsibilities leading to career progression.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first coming from internal stakeholders. It could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization because there is as medium personal interest as most leading positions are represented by men. Other resistances could come from the administration because there is medium interest in science work from female administrative workers; the possibility of remote work (home-office) is not officially defined during the full-time contract (there has already been some improvement caused by the pandemic); taking parental leave into account when measuring performance requires changes in the actual process, a new way of paperwork. Middle and high management could have resistances because there is medium support for women scientists with children. There might also be resistances coming from female researchers share only some tasks in households and with raising children with husbands, a little time is reserved for science work. To finish, some resistances could be coming from students as they have medium interest in science among female students, they prefer working in the private sector (which is usually better paid). Resistances can also be expected from external stakeholders. Some could come from civil society as they have low interest of females in science, females prefer family to science, a strong bond of a child to mother. To finish, government / public sector might have low interest in female scientists' support.

Possible strategies for overcoming resistance are first argumentation action such as support female scientists research and gender equality. They could touch the rules of the organization like adaptation of workplace conditions to the presence of a child. Men could be motivated to go on parental leave.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first coming from internal stakeholders. To start, they could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization that have medium personal interest to rise the number of females in leading positions. Next, they could come from the administration as they have medium interest in science work from female administrative workers. To continue, the opportunities from high and medium management is that they have medium support for women scientist with children. The opportunities

coming from researchers is that some women decide to spend some time for science work, women share some family tasks and children care with husbands.

Stakeholders to involve to rely on the opportunities (through collaboration/information/argumentation etc.) are the ones who will be impacted by the strategy like faculty management, employees, husbands of the employees with children.

Measures needed to ensure cooperation between stakeholders (internal and external) are first organizational change actions like the adaptation of workplace conditions to the presence of a child. To continue, information events, like workshops, and online presentations could be organized.

Scenario 2: Low resistance

There is no low resistance scenario for the topic Human resources.

Scenario 3: Intermediate resistance

Recruitment procedures

Situation

The percentage of women working in 2019 at academic level = 25%, at administrative level = 50% at other levels = 33%

Main Problems

little number of women at the academic level; the absence of any gender-sensitive protocols for recruitment and hiring

Objective(s)

Make the STEM field more attractive to women, to reach a 50% share of women at the academic level within 5 years.

Possible solutions

- Promote the STEM field to make it more attractive to women so that they decide to study and work in it.
- Create gender-sensitive protocols for recruitment and hiring.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first coming from internal stakeholders. In general, a medium interest in the topic has been identified. From the rules of the organization, it is about gender-sensitive protocols for recruitment and hiring as well as medium interest in STEM promotion and event organization. From the administration, it is about the fact that new gender-sensitive protocols for recruitment and hiring will require extra work with implementation and learning new procedures; events organization requires administrative preparation. Coming from students there is a low interest of female STEM students in science and teaching, they prefer (usually better paid) job in business. Secondly, some resistances are expected coming from external stakeholders. Coming from the academia there is a competitiveness for students among STEM faculties (amount of money given to the faculty from state depends on the number of students of the faculty). Coming from civil society there are prejudice about the male-female fields of study. To finish, the industries/business stakeholders fear of losing employees (who would choose science and teaching instead of a business).

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first argumentative like to present STEM field from point of view more interesting for women (application of STEM subjects in daily life) and promote gender equality. Other could come from the rules of the organization such as to start promoting the STEM field

among students to increase the interest in science and teaching (instead of a business) and create gender-sensitive protocols for recruitment and hiring within the MTF STU. Other actions could be to raise awareness about the benefits of gender equality by the Internet.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first coming from internal stakeholders. Coming from the administration there is an interest in the topic of gender-sensitive protocols for recruitment and hiring within the MTF STU. Coming from researchers there is motivation of female researchers for further study, teaching and research in the STEM field. To finish, some opportunities are coming from students such as interest of females in research and PhD study. Secondly, some opportunities are also expected from external stakeholders. The main opportunities are coming from civil society, females interested in STEM field and science.

Stakeholders to involve in strategies (through collaboration/information/argumentation etc.) are first internal stakeholders. To start, there are the one who have the power to decide to change the organizational rules/to accept the proposed strategy, the dean in agreement with the head of the specific workplace about the need to hire to which position (e.g., just a woman); faculty PR manager decides communication strategy, faculty HR manager creates gender sensitive protocols for recruitment and hiring within the MTF STU. Next, there are the one who will implement the strategy: PR, HR departments lead by dean. To finish, there are the one who will be impacted by the strategy (positively or negatively): public, students, employees, direct superiors. Secondly, some external stakeholders need be involved. To start, some are from the academia. Other universities are influenced by possible lowering of the number of researchers/students (if they prefer to study/work for MTF STU due to the existence of gender-sensitive protocols for recruitment and hiring and other GE actions); other universities can join the idea of implementing some gender-sensitive protocols for recruitment and hiring or other GE actions. Civil society should also be involved such as females interested in STEM field and science can be persuaded to work at MTF STU via new communication and promotion actions and existence of gender-sensitive protocols for recruitment and hiring and other GE actions. From the business/industry there could be possible lowering number of employees (by raising their interest in science and teaching via the application of gender-sensitive protocols for recruitment and hiring and other GE actions). To finish, the government/public sector should be involved, institutions, such as labor office, who can promote STEM field among females - thanks to gender-sensitive protocols for recruitment and hiring and other GE actions, they have more reasons for persuasion.

Actions to be taken to ensure stakeholders' collaboration (both internal and external) are first argumentative action like the explanation of gender equality benefits to open mind of present employees to this issue; motivate women to study, do science and teach in the STEM field. Other could be organizational change actions such as to find out and customize the faculty premises and organization to females' needs to make it more interesting for women; create gender-sensitive protocols for recruitment and hiring within the MTF STU. To continue, information actions could be organized such as the promotion of the research work benefits at the faculty among females. To finish, engagement actions could be done like social network communication, online meetings with potential female employees and students

Career breaks and job reintegration

Situation

100% of employees on parental leave were women in 2019 in our faculty.

Main Problems

Interruption of research and career growth during parental leave.

Objective(s)

In case women are interested, adapting the workplace to the presence of the children.

Possible solutions

Adaptation of the workplace to the presence of children :

- Creating a faculty kindergarten – this is a long-term process, requires more paperwork and approval from the state.
- Creating a playroom/playground with a nurse/babysitter caring for the children – to find/create a room(s) within the university area where parents can safely leave their children (after the pandemic situation).

Resistances

The expected resistances are first coming from internal stakeholders. Some could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization like medium personal interest as the adaptation would require extra costs. Others could be coming from the administration and researchers such as medium interest in taking children to work and there is more administrative work when adapting the workplace to the children presence (new employees, space, safety rules, etc.). resistances that could come from middle and high management is that there could be medium interest in such measures from those with no children. Some resistances are also expected coming from external stakeholders. A common resistance has been identified coming from the academia, civil society and the government/public sector. It is a medium support and interest of female scientists with children.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first argumentative actions such as to support female scientists research and gender equality. Another one is in the rules of the organization like the adaptation of workplace conditions to the presence of children. To finish, a possible solution could be trying to motivate husbands to go on parental leave (with couples where both work at the faculty).

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from internal stakeholders. Some of the administration and researchers have interest in taking children to work. Another opportunity is that middle and high management have interest in such measures. The opportunity coming from the rules of the organization is that the adaptation would raise the number of female professors. Secondly, some opportunities are expected coming from external stakeholders. There are interested females in science coming from the civil society. Opportunities could come from the business/industry as they support and encourage women in science.

Actions to be taken to ensure stakeholders' collaboration. First, there are argumentative action such as making the workplace adapted to the presence of children, it would be more attractive for employees and partners. There could also be organizational change actions like the preparation for the adaptation of workplace conditions to the presence of children in a way of a playground with babysitter/kindergarten and further promotion towards public after the playground creation. There could also be information actions like the promotion of the benefits among mothers

Governance

Scenario 1: maximal resistance

Enhancing women leadership and access to top positions (academic and administrative levels)

Situation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

The average distribution of women in recruitment or promotion boards / panels in 2009 = 40%

Main Problems

Low number of women in STEM decision-making bodies.

Objective(s)

Increase the number of women in decision-making positions at the university

Possible solutions

Making the STEM area more attractive to women :

- Continuously include the issue of increasing the number of women in leading positions on the agenda of the university management.
- A specific strategy and concrete steps to motivate women.
- To set quotas precisely for women in leadership positions (we suggest 50% in the governing bodies, now there is a higher representation of men - 5men ,2 women-28% in the management of the faculty, in the academic senate- 14 men, 7 women-33%, in the scientific council 25 men, 3 women-11%).
- Leadership should have a strategy to support women to the governing bodies before elections.
- The condition for more women depends on the increase in the number of women employed at technical universities. Therefore, it is important to actively work on motivations for women's employment.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first coming from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization such as the administration. The legislation will not allow the objectives to be met quantitatively (% increase in the number of women in management), the appointment system is based on qualitative requirements. Others could be coming from middle management as they have medium interest in female promotion among male colleagues, lack of interest in the benefits of gender policy. There might be barriers in legislation, medium interest in female promotion among male colleagues, lack of interest in the benefits of gender policy. To finish, students and researchers might have resistances as they have medium interest of females in STEM field and science sector. Resistances are also expected coming from external stakeholders. To start, some could come from the academia as they have low knowledge of politics, medium trust in females' expertise in STEM field and leadership skills. Others could be coming from civil society because they have medium interest in gender equality topic, some prejudice about the female leadership skills. To finish, some resistances could come from industries/business stakeholders since there are doubts about the benefits of gender equality, medium trust in females' leadership skills.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first argumentative action like to promote STEM field of study among females and promote gender equality. Next, there might be strategies that touch the rules of the organization like to increase the interest in studying and doing science in STEM, reduce the prejudices by presentation of successful female leaders. To finish, other actions could be done like to improve the promotion of the benefits of gender equality policy, launch a new website, organize WS, cooperation between basic and secondary schools and the faculty to raise interest of girls/women in STEM from the young age.

Opportunities

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Same opportunities as point 2 in Human resources.

Actions to be taken to ensure stakeholders' collaboration are first argumentative action like the explanation of gender equality benefits. Next, there are organizational change actions such as to improve the promotion of the benefits of gender equality policy, launch a new website, organize WS, ambassador for gender policy, support females' interest in STEM field, science and leading positions. To finish information actions could be done like the promotion of STEM field among girls on basic and high schools

Engagement actions: online presentation, videos, games with STEM topic.

Small proportion of women in decision-making positions

Situation

In 2019, fewer of women held positions as heads of the institute, or other decision-making bodies.

Main Problems

Low number of women in management in the field of STEM.

Objective(s)

Increase the number of women in management positions at the university to 50%, increase the interest in gender policy, to understand the benefits of this policy.

Possible solutions

Making the STEM field more attractive to women :

- Changing policies and experiences can change attitudes towards the status of women.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first coming from internal stakeholders. To start, some could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization such as legislative barriers and medium individual motivation. Same resistances could be coming from high and middle management like the attitudes of people to the gender policy, medium interest in female promotion among male colleagues and a lack of interest in the benefits of gender policy. To finish, resistances could be coming from researcher and students such as medium interest of females in STEM field and science sector, medium interest of females in science for family reasons. Resistances are also expected from external stakeholders. Some could be coming from the academia like medium trust in females' expertise in STEM field and leadership skills. Next, resistances could come from civil society such as medium interest in gender equality topic, some prejudice about the female leadership skills. To finish, there might be doubts, from the industries/business stakeholders, about the benefits of gender equality and medium trust in females' leadership skills.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first argumentative actions such as to promote STEM field of study among females and promote gender equality, improving communication on the benefits of gender policy. Next, there could be some in the rules of the organization like to increase the interest in studying and doing science in STEM, reduce the prejudices by presentation of successful female leaders. Other actions could be the cooperation between basic and secondary schools and the faculty to raise interest of girls/women in STEM from the young age, ambassador for the gender policy.

Opportunities

Same opportunities as point 2 in Human resources.

Actions to be taken to ensure stakeholders' collaboration are first argumentative actions like the

explanation of gender equality benefits. Next, there are organizational change actions such as to support females' interest in STEM field, science and leading positions. To continue, there are information actions like the promotion of STEM field among girls on basic and high schools. To finish, some engagement actions could be online presentation, videos, games with STEM topic.

Scenario 2: Low resistance

There is no low resistance scenario for the topic Governance.

Scenario 3: Intermediate resistance

Situation

About the representation of women in the management of the faculty (MF), there is a higher representation of men - 5men ,2 women-28% in the management of the faculty, in the academic senate- 14 men, 7 women-33%, in the scientific council 25 men, 3 women-11%).

Main Problems

Low number of women represented in leading positions at the faculty.

Objective(s)

Increase the number of women in leading positions at the university.

Possible solutions

- The development of a long-term strategy:
 - Offering both personal and scientific mentoring activities.
 - Help mothers with the comeback to science from parental leave.
 - Support of the project from the government.
- To motivate women to apply for leading positions and change the approach to women's employment.
- Increase the advertisement of the benefits of gender policy at the university (by workshops and social media to prove women are good leaders).
- Launch of a new website for women in STEM achievements promotion (to prove their abilities and success in science).
- Ambassador for gender policy.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first coming from internal stakeholders. To start, some might be coming from the rules or structure of the organization, the legislation of some suggestions may be difficult to change due to the regulations which must be approved by higher institution than MTF STU dean/senate, eg. criteria for academic growth), medium individual motivation. There is a medium interest in female promotion among male colleagues who might feel endangered by losing a position. Secondly, some resistances are expected coming from external stakeholders. The main resistance coming from the academia is the little trust in females' expertise in STEM field and leadership skills. There is a medium interest in gender equality topic, they also have some prejudice about the female leadership skills. Coming from industries/business stakeholders, there are doubts about the benefits of gender equality, medium trust in females' leadership skills, attitudes of people to the gender policy, ignorance of the benefits.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first argumentative such as better communication,

establishment of an ambassador, promote STEM field of study among females and promote gender equality. In the rules of the organization, the interest in studying and doing science in STEM could be increase, and there is the need to reduce the prejudices by presentation of successful female leaders. Other actions could be cooperation between basic and secondary schools and the faculty to raise interest of girls/women in STEM from the young age.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first coming from internal stakeholders. Middle and high management have interest in female promotion among male colleagues who see opportunities in gender equality. There is interest of female researchers and students in STEM field and science sector, high interest of females in science despite the family life. Secondly, some opportunities are expected coming from external stakeholders. Some are expected from civil society as female are interested in STEM field, science and leading positions. Others could come from the government/public sector such as ministries - current legislation of the Slovak Republic.

Actions to be taken to ensure stakeholders' collaboration are first argumentative action such as the explanation of gender equality benefits. Other actions could be organizational change ones such as to support females' interest in STEM field, science and leading positions. There could also be information actions like the promotion of STEM field among girls on basic and high schools. The last one could be engagement actions like online presentation, videos, games with STEM topic.

Research

Scenario 1: Maximal resistance

There is no maximal-resistance scenario for the topic Research.

Scenario 2: Low resistance

Situation

No research projects, engineering and dissertation works dealing with gender equality topics for the years 2017-2019.

Main Problems

Low interest in the topic of gender equality in the field of STEM.

Objective(s)

Raising awareness of gender equality at the university and achieving it.

Possible solutions

Raising awareness of the gender equality. An understanding of the gender-specific needs can add new perspective on to the collection of data about gender policy. The researchers, companies, policymakers and researchers need to better understand the role that gender policy . These measures will achieve the goal of increasing the number of theses and projects on gender equality.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first coming from internal stakeholders. Same resistances have been identified coming from the rules or structure of the organization, the administration, middle and high management. There is medium interest in the topic of gender equality, especially coming from male colleagues, there is also an ignorance of the benefits of gender policies. There is also a same resistance

identified coming from researchers and students that is a medium self-confidence of some female students, medium superior feeling of some male students, false belief that the current behavior is correct and normal, medium interest in gender equality topic in theses and projects. Secondly, some resistances are also expected from external stakeholders. The academia, civil societies, industries/business and the government/public sector have a false belief that the current behavior is correct and normal.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first argumentative actions such as to promote gender equality topic, both male and female rights. Other are in the rules of the organization like to increase the interest in gender equality topic, reduce the prejudices about genders. Other actions could be cooperation with non-profit and other organizations that deal with gender equality.

Opportunities

Same opportunities as point 2 in Human resources.

Additional information is that there is a little self-confidence of some female students, medium superior feeling of some male students, false belief that the current behavior is correct and normal, medium interest in gender equality topic in theses and projects.

Actions to be taken to ensure stakeholders' collaboration are first argumentative action like to rise the interest about the gender equality issue, promote awareness of women about their value and rights. Next, there could be organizational change actions such as apply gender equality plan and delegate a person to solve gender equality issues, propose changes in legislation. Next, there could be Information actions like to rise the interest by internet and within faculty, new position of ambassador. To finish, some engagement actions could be organizing more projects and theses with the gender equality topic.

Situation

Low participation in projects with gender issues.

Main Problems

Less awareness of the benefits of gender policy, less interest in gender policy.

Objective(s)

Higher participation in projects and gain new partners.

Possible solutions

- Communication with new organizations, proposals for new, better communication.
- Projects, new knowledge about the benefits of gender policy.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first coming from internal stakeholders. To start, some are based on the rules or structure of the organization like less motivation, legislation. Next one could be coming from the administration such as knowledge gaps. Coming from senior management there is only a partial understanding of the benefits for organizational efficiency. To finish, researchers have less interest of modeling the objectives of new projects and students have less understanding of the benefits of gender policy. Secondly, resistance could also come from external stakeholders. They could be coming from academia because of less interest of new projects, less motivation. Coming from civil society and industrial/commercial stakeholders, there is a less understanding of the benefits.

Possible strategies for overcoming resistance are first argumentation such as understanding why gender policy is important. Other are in the rules of the organization like motivation for the goals of new projects.

Other actions could be greater promotion of the benefits of gender policy, better communication, the establishment of an ambassador in this area.

Measures needed to ensure cooperation between stakeholders (internal and external) are first argumentation action like defining clear objectives. Other measures are related to organizational change like motivation and definition of tasks, promotion of the benefits of gender policy, better communication. To finish, there could be involvement actions like the understanding of a theme for the projects.

Scenario 3: Intermediate resistance

There is no intermediate-resistance scenario for the topic Research.

Teaching

Scenario 1: maximal resistance

There is no maximal-resistance scenario for the topic Teaching.

Scenario 2: Low resistance

There is no low-resistance scenario for the topic Teaching.

Scenario 3: Intermediate resistance

Situation

Teacher education should include the area of gender equality. Teachers' expectations of girls often exacerbate long-term prejudices and gender stereotypes. If a student chooses to study and work in an area that is not traditionally associated with this gender, they encounter ridicule, attacks, and misunderstandings.

Main Problems

Lack of information about gender equality policy and its implications. The hypothesis that gives rise to the problem is that schools do not include gender issues in the curriculum. There is also the problem of insufficient awareness of the importance and efficiency of gender equality issues.

Objective(s)

To integrate gender issues into the university's policy and to include gender equality activities in the study curriculums.

Possible solutions

- Development of information and educational materials.
 - Schools - Introduce programs, expand their work in this area to address inequalities in access to both sexes.
 - Availability of Guides and/or Workshops on the integration of gender equality and diversity issues in curriculum design, learning activities and/or program of study, as support for teaching staff.
 - Development of introductory and advanced training tools/courses in all Schools/levels (BA, MA, PhD) on sex and gender variables.
 - Specific courses available for students on gender equality and soft skills in their study curricula.

Resistances

The only resistance that has been identified is coming from an internal stakeholder, more specifically from researchers. Resistances might appear due to the increased attention to the topic. Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are the organization of auxiliary meetings with employees, the establishment

of an ambassador for the issue of gender equality, open communication, a feeling of constant support from the Faculty/ University, the availability of information on the effectiveness of this issue and a positive impact on students.

Students and services to students

1. Increase and maintain the interest of female students in STEM studies.

Scenario 1: maximal resistance

There is no maximal-resistance scenario for the topic Students.

Scenario 2: Low resistance

There is no low-resistance scenario for the topic Students.

Scenario 3: Intermediate resistance

Situation

Lack of a platform for presenting the work successes of women who have achieved in their professional careers.

Objective(s)

To contribute to a greater motivation of women to study the STEM studies.

Possible solutions

- Organization of lectures, projects and exchange of experiences on successful practice.
- Research and projects in the field are a tool that can bring the change. We think that the very nature of “success” entry is a sufficient attraction for students. By its very nature, success is one of the basic goals of human. In addition, its interesting presentation and sufficient motivation.
- The method of transferring information to target groups such as current students and especially potential students is based on the use of technical tools. We will divide them into two groups.
- The first group will be passive tools in the form of videos disseminated by Internet platforms, writing posts on a newly created blog, using social media, etc.
- Active tools consist of organizing live interviews and meetings, the recordings of which will also be disseminated in a suitable way to young people.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first coming from internal stakeholders. The administration could have resistances because it could rise administration issues. Students might also have resistances such as medium interest due to that this information about such activities does not reach them. Resistance is not seen due to lack of interest, but due to non-use of a suitable communication tool to promote these activities. Secondly, there might be some resistances coming from external stakeholders. They are the same resistances as the one from scenario 2 of the first topic in the governance part.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first argumentative such as better communication, establishment of an ambassador, promote STEM field of study among females and promote gender equality. In the rules of the organization: the interest in studying and doing science in STEM could be increased and the prejudices should be reduced by presentation of successful female leaders. Other actions could be done like the cooperation between basic and secondary schools and the faculty to raise interest of

girls/women in STEM from the young age.

Transfer to Market

Lack of motivation of female students to work in the STEM sector

Scenario 1: maximal resistance

There is no maximal-resistance scenario for the topic Transfer to market.

Scenario 2: Low resistance

There is no maximal-resistance scenario for the topic Transfer to market.

Scenario 3: Intermediate resistance

Situation

Declining representation of women in patent outputs

Objective(s)

Direct integration of female students into the company's process / system due to the variability of the business environment and its understanding.

Possible solutions

- Knowledge of business processes with a link to the theoretical side allows further development of students and supports them in the courage to engage in research.
- Within the cooperation, the requirement of women's representation as role models will be set. The next step will be the creation of motivational videos, the subject of which will be interviews with students, which will present their experiences and recommendations.

Resistances

No resistances have been identified coming from internal stakeholders. However, there are some coming from external stakeholders. There could be some prejudice about the female leadership skills coming from civil society. There could also be capacity problems such as lack of human resources and budget coming from the industries/business stakeholders.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are the participation of external stakeholders in the so-called the industrial council of the faculty, through which external entities will be directly involved in the management of the faculty in terms of qualification development of students.

Demotivation of women to work in the field of STEM

Situation

Supportive communication programs for women

Main Problems

Women can feel in the background in this area and do not see much application in it.

Objective(s)

To communicate openly on the topic of gender equality.

Possible solutions

- Create blogs, Podcasts on equality and equal opportunities for women
- Support for women in finding employment in sectors with a lack of qualifications, especially in the sectors of technology, IT, artificial intelligence.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first expected from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from the administration such as resistance due to rising of administration agenda as it was not plan. There is a little interest from female students and researchers in STEM field and science sector. secondly, some resistances are expected coming from external stakeholders. There is a medium trust in females' expertise in STEM field and leadership skills. There is a medium interest in gender equality topic, some prejudice about the female leadership skills. Resistances could be coming from industries/business stakeholders as they have doubts about the benefits of gender equality, medium trust in females' leadership skills, attitudes of people to the gender policy, ignorance of the benefits.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first argumentative action such as better communication, establishment of an ambassador, promote STEM field of study among females and promote gender equality. In the rules of the organization the interest in studying and doing science in STEM should be increased, the prejudices should be reduced by presentation of successful female leaders. Other actions could be the cooperation between basic and secondary schools and the faculty to raise interest of girls/women in STEM from the young age.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first coming from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from middle and high management as there is interest in female promotion among male colleagues who see opportunities in gender equality. They could also be coming from researchers and students as they have interest of females in STEM fields. Secondly, some opportunities could be coming from external stakeholders. They could come from civil society as there are female interested in STEM field, science and leading positions. Some opportunities could also be coming from the government/public sector, ministries - current legislation of the Slovak Republic. The actions to ensure stakeholders' collaboration are the same as the one from scenario 3 of the first point of the Governance part.

Communication

1. Internal communication

Scenario 1: maximal resistance

There is no maximal-resistance scenario for the topic Communication.

Scenario 2: Low resistance

There is no low-resistance scenario for the topic Communication.

Scenario 3: Intermediate resistance

Situation

The use of normative language resulting from national legislation, which is then applied to the faculty process at the level of teaching, administrative communication, and research.

Main Problems

Insufficient awareness of gender-sensitive communication

Objective(s)

To explicitly address gender equality as one of the main goals of the organization

Possible solutions

- Emphasize the issue of gender equality, e.g. on the organisation's website or in its publications. The website offers a wide range of information, such as news, examples of good practice and other tools.
- Examine and adjust all the university's public relations activities to ensure the use of gender-sensitive language and to avoid gender stereotypes
- Provide appropriate training to employees responsible for working with the public
- Distribute gender-sensitive language guidelines to all employees in the organization.

Resistances

Intermediate level of resistance is expected coming from internal stakeholders. It is due to the obligation to respect university rules and request a change stating the reason for these changes. For the external stakeholders, there might be resistances coming from civil society as there are some prejudices about the changes. Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are to increased communication in this topic by the faculty management and justification of the positivity of changes with the possibility of opinions input from employees.

Intersectionality**Scenario 1: maximal resistance**

There is no maximal-resistance scenario for the topic Intersectionality.

Scenario 2: Low resistance

There is no low-resistance scenario for the topic Intersectionality.

Scenario 3: Intermediate resistance**Situation**

The feeling of interfering with personality integrity is observed on two levels. The first level is in contact with the colleagues from abroad, where the cultural prejudice of underestimation of women still persists. The second level lies in the silent expression of prejudice, where colleagues internally disagree with the other party, who is a woman. The hidden form of resistance creates obstacles to the smooth cooperation and acceptance of research results reached by women.

Objective(s)

Create a support base for women on how to cope with the situation.

Possible solutions

- Creating the position of ambassador for the issue of gender equality, who must have skills in dealing with such situations.

Resistances

No resistances are expected coming from internal nor external stakeholders.

We do not see any resistance in this matter, given that resolving these situations through the ambassador has a positive effect on resolving disputes in the workplace. This relies especially to the second situation

stated above. In this case, this action can evoke the increase in the quality of the working environment, which is in the interests of all involved. The role and position of the ambassador also in the position of mediator will be crucial.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first coming from internal stakeholders. High motivation is observed from the rules of the organization, middle and high management. The opportunity coming from researchers is that the advantage lies in the development of transparent relationships leading to the acceptance of research results with their further dissemination in the spirit of professional communication. Secondly, some opportunities are expected coming from external stakeholders. Academics and the business industry are interested in creating a model.

Sexism and sexual harassment

Scenario 1: Maximal resistance

There is no maximal-resistance scenario for the topic Sexism and sexual harassment.

Scenario 2: Low resistance

Situation

No sexual harassment was recorded at our faculty in past 5 years.

Main Problems

Possible sexual harassment which was not recorded.

Objective(s)

Encourage women not to be afraid to report sexual harassment, to realize their value.

Possible solutions

- Raise awareness of the issue and severity of sexual harassment.
- Having a confidential person in this area.

Resistances

The same main resistance has been identified coming from both internal and external stakeholders. This resistance is the medium interest in the topic of sexism and sexual harassment, some fear from possible consequences if one points out some sexism and sexual harassment. Possible strategies to overcome the resistance are first argumentative such as to promote gender equality topic, both male and female rights, explain the issues of sexism and sexual harassment. In the rules of the organization the interest should be increase in gender equality topic, raise interest in the topic of sexism and sexual harassment, limit fear from possible consequences if one points out some sexism and sexual harassment. Other actions could be cooperation with non-profit and other organizations that deal with gender equality, sexism and sexual harassment topic, appointment of a confidential person for this topic.

Opportunities

The opportunity that has been identified coming from both internal and external stakeholders is that there is individual motivation and interest about the topic of sexism and sexual harassment, some fear from possible consequences if one points out some sexism and sexual harassment and there is some acceptance of the benefits of gender equality. Some actions to be taken to ensure collaboration action as point 1 of Human resources.

Scenario 3: Intermediate resistance

There is no intermediate-resistance scenario for the topic Sexism and sexual harassment.

2.4 Université libre de Bruxelles³ (RPO)

Human resources

Situation: Low proportion of women in the academic staff of STEM faculties

The number of women in the academic staff of the STEM faculties (Faculty of Science and EPB) is much lower than the number of men. The proportion of women in the academic body is 8.6% at the EPB and 23.52% at the Faculty of Science (all departments).

It is important to note, however, that the comparison between these two faculties must be made with caution given the difference in size between them. The Faculty of Science is a very large faculty composed of eight departments⁴. According to the interviews and focus groups carried out, there are significant differences between the departments in relation to the proportion of women to men in the academic body, with women being particularly in the minority in computer science and physics. However, figures on the gender proportion within the departments are not available.

According to the overall analysis of recruitment files for the last 3 years (2017-2018 to 2019-2020) the proportion of men and women recruited for full-time academic vacancies (profiled flesh) was around 50% of each gender. This happens even though there were fewer female applicants overall (23-32% female applicants vs. 68-77% male applicants)⁵. The proportion of women on the *short lists* was also slightly higher than the number of female applications.

If ULB considers the disciplinary field (human and social sciences, STEM or health), the proportion of women recruited in the two STEM faculties (Faculty of Sciences and EPB) is only 36% for the 3 analyzed years (vs. 50% in social and human sciences and 50% in health). This can be explained in part by the low number of female applications received for STEM vacancies (14% in STEM vs. 33% in SHS and Health). The proportion of women in the *short lists* was 22% in STEM vs. 40% in SHS and health sciences.

Regarding recruitment commissions, the *Coordinated Text of Provisions on the Careers of Scientific and Academic Staff* (2018) establishes that commissions must be composed of at least 1/3 of members of each gender (33%). According to the overall analysis of recruitment files, the proportion of women was 39% in 2017-2018 (all commissions combined). This percentage was 38% in 2018-2019. However, although the minimum representation of women in the commissions seems to be respected overall, this is not always the case when considering each commission individually. In 8 out of 48 commissions (16%) the male/female ratio established in the regulations was not respected⁶, with men being in the majority: three commissions of the Solvay Business School and Management, one commission of the Faculty of Medicine, one commission of the School of Public Health and three commissions of the Brussels Polytechnic.

Main problems

Many measures to promote gender equality in recruitment are included in the Diversity Plan, such as the use of non-sexist language in job advertisements, the production of a video to combat discrimination in

³ ULB has first identified the main problematic situations in each topic and then has developed three scenarios (maximal resistance, low resistance and intermediate resistance) for each situation. Each scenario includes different solutions for the problematic situation according to the level of resistance that each action may arise.

⁴ Organism Biology; Molecular Biology; Chemistry; Interfaculty School of Bio-Engineering; Geosciences, Environment and Society; Informatics; Mathematics; Physics.

⁵ These figures are an estimation, the gender of the candidates on the *long list* was not always available.

⁶ The gender of the members is unknown in 4 out of 48 commissions (8.3%). However, the proportion is respected in 36 commissions out of 48 (75%).

selection and promotion commissions and the standards stipulated in the *Coordinated Text* mentioned above, including the gender composition of the commissions and the establishment of evaluation grids to objectify the selection process. However, according to the interviews, focus groups and surveys conducted, several problems persist despite the measures put in place:

- There are no figures on the male-female ratio at the departmental level (particularly relevant in the Faculty of Science). However, there are many differences between departments.
- Assessment grids are sometimes filled in by the recruitment committees *after the fact* (once the person has been selected) and often only the grid of the person recruited is completed. For the commissions, this is a rather cumbersome procedure. At the same time, it sets a standard and the recruitment process becomes more professional.
- The evaluation grids establish general criteria that must be concretized by the commissions for each vacancy. This is where gender bias (and other types of bias) can impact the recruitment process. At the same time, it is not possible to further define these criteria because they vary greatly from one discipline to another. In addition, selection criteria are often related to how 'excellence' and 'meritocracy' are understood, and these are not neutral and objective concepts.
- Many committee members are not familiar with the video on bias in recruitment despite the fact that it should be sent to all members prior to any selection and recruitment process.
- In the faculties where there are few women (STEM), the same women are mobilized to participate in all the commissions in order to reach the representation of one third of each gender. However, this increased participation implies an additional workload for them, preventing them from dedicating time to research and teaching, which are fundamental tasks for the development of their careers.
- Sometimes there is resistance to the establishment of certain binding measures such as quotas for recruitment.
- As regards maternity leave, there are no regulations concerning such leave at the time of recruitment of academic staff. In order to be able to do so, candidates would have to be asked if and when they have children, which cannot be done.

Objective(s)

The main objective is to increase the proportion of women recruited in the academic staff of STEM faculties.

Scenario 1: maximal resistance

Possible solutions:

- The redefinition of selection criteria in recruitment: Further define the selection criteria for the recruitment of academic staff in order to avoid as much as possible gender bias in the interpretation of the criteria and establish different criteria according to different "academic profiles"
- To establish gender quotas as a temporary corrective measure in STEM services or departments where there are very few women.
- Set up a system of external observers of the commissions to sound the alarm if prejudices are involved in the recruitment process.
- Faculty policy to empower women (commissions and governance): The participation of women in committees and decision-making positions could be taken into account in promotions (if they have not been able to advance as much, it is because they have been in high demand). This would be

one way of guaranteeing the conditions for the real participation of women in decision-making bodies.

Opportunities:

Opportunities have been identified. First, the "slow science" movements are increasingly rooted in universities. A growing number of academics are questioning the current model of the university. Next, the quota is a measure implemented in other universities and prestigious universities (i.e. Harvard): the results of these experiences can be used as an example of good practice to convince of the relevance of quotas. Finally, there is a clear desire in STEM faculties to balance the gender proportion in the academic body.

Resistances:

The expected resistances are first that it would take a lot of time to do an important substantive debate, which is necessary. Next, there are hundreds of commissions so ULB would need hundreds of observers. Moreover, these observers should be experts in gender and recruitment, there should be gender-trained people who are also familiar with the discipline of the vacancy. Next, there may be significant resistance from committee members: this can be considered as inquisition. Another resistance is a widespread resistance against quotas, measure not well understood and/or accepted: idea that women are recruited based on their gender and not their skills, feeling of injustice on the part of men (perceived as "reverse discrimination"), impression that the imbalance will resolve itself over time. To finish, if more human resources are needed, there may be a financial constraint.

The strategies that could be use are first to initiate a fundamental debate on the notion of "excellence" and the selection criteria for recruitment. Next, instead of having one external observer in each, one member of the recruitment committee could be designated as a "bias keeper".

Actions to be taken to ensure stakeholders' collaboration are argumentative. The implementation of quotas must be accompanied by a great deal of education/awareness-raising for the measure to be accepted as much as possible. Another one is showing current figures on the imbalance, using good practices from other (prestigious) universities, emphasizing that competences are taken into account. To finish, awareness should be raised on the importance of women's participation in commissions and decision-making bodies (studies on the benefits of having more diverse bodies).

Scenario 2: Low resistance

Possible solutions:

- Faculty gender monitoring of STEM academic body to collect systematically each year the proportion of men and women at the level of department/services.
- To promote role models by making more visible the women scientists already working in STEM fields at ULB in order to attract more women for the STEM vacancies at the University.
- To send a message (email) to the members of each committee to make them aware that applicants may have taken time off to care for children (maternity and parental leave) and/or other people or to look after themselves (illness) and that these situations reduce the productivity of researchers. Since a "gap" in a CV raises questions, there is a need to raise awareness of these realities.
- To highlight in the job offer for academic vacancies the advantages of women's academic career and what is put in place at ULB to attract them (i.e. for childcare).

Opportunities:

The opportunities that have been identified are first that it is "non-sensitive" data (RGPD) and it is relatively easy to collect. Moreover, gender-disaggregated data are already available at ULB at other levels (practice already in place and accepted). Another opportunity is that the CALIPER project already foresees the production of a video with a *role model* for each partner of the consortium. ULB has also already produced

a video on how to avoid bias in recruitment processes. This video can also be sent in the message. Finally, many services at ULB for the reconciliation of work and family life (nursery, children's university, etc.) already exist.

Resistances:

Expected resistance might be that the indicators could become criteria for stigmatization (the aim is not to show that the good or bad pupils are). Perhaps there may also be resistance from some men to present only women in *role models*. Finally, there are daily too many emails sent and received so there is the risk of ignoring the message sent to members of committees.

Strategies to overcome those resistances could be a visible support from the faculty authorities and the University and clearly explained that if the aim is to attract more women to STEM vacancies, women should be represented.

Scenario 3: Intermediate resistance

Possible solutions:

- To promote critical reflection on how the notions of "excellence" and "meritocracy" are understood within the University, particularly among members of the recruitment committees.
- Add "the promotion of gender equality" to the selection criteria by asking candidates to provide a "gender project" in the recruitment file (together with research, teaching and internationalization projects) explaining how they intend to integrate gender into their management, research and teaching practices.
- Organize gender awareness training for committee members to reduce bias. This awareness raising could also address other types of bias (origins, socio-economic status, disability...).
- Setting *targets for the* proportion of women that it would be desirable to recruit by the STEM commissions.

Opportunities:

The "slow science" movements are increasingly rooted in universities and it is seen as an opportunity because a growing number of academics are questioning the current model of the university in our local context. Another opportunity is that ULB has produced a video on how to avoid bias in recruitment processes, so it is ready to use.

Resistances:

Some resistance may occur. First, the notions of "excellence" and "meritocracy" are deeply rooted in the academic world. There may be resistance from academics and scientists to question these fundamental principles of the university and their professional identity. Next, there may be a reluctance on the part of some members of the academic community who think that gender (and diversity) issues have nothing to do with the academic profession. Another resistance is that there is a risk of giving the impression that the University puts the responsibility for establishing a culture of gender equality on new recruits, rather than providing a framework of equality to which to adhere. Next, there are hundreds of commissions every year; virtually the entire academic body participates. Organizing face-to-face awareness training would be very cumbersome and difficult. Finally, those actions may be seen as too weak a measure by people who are very committed to gender equality. It can be seen as a purely aesthetic action.

Some strategies have been identified to overcome the resistances. First, major changes, by definition, involve moments of destabilization and what is important is to support/guide the destabilization so that it is positive/constructive. Another strategy is to argue that research and teaching are social practices rooted in social contexts and they can be biased and produce discrimination. In addition, the academic profession also involves managing teams of people who are also situated in social relationships. The university cannot

ignore these issues in its internal functioning; its mission is to contribute to the improvement of society, including the university itself. Another argument that can be use is the fact that, by establishing the promotion of gender equality as a selection criterion, the university would already be building this culture of equality. This would therefore not be inconsistent. Next, with regard to the lack of time, a single, short training course should be designed, with the possibility of carrying it out over several days. A last strategy is that if, after an analysis of the situation, resistance against quotas is *currently* too high (risk of undesirable effects), *target* setting can be considered as an intermediate and temporary alternative. If these *targets* are set by university and faculty authorities, they send a strong message to the members of the commissions. To be consistent, authorities should accompany this action with other effective measures to promote the recruitment of women at all career stages.

Situation: "Leaky pipeline" throughout the scientific career in STEM

The "leaky pipeline" is a metaphor that refers to the erosion of gender balance in universities. This erosion, or "loss of women", is particularly significant in STEM disciplines.

At ULB the proportion of women in the academic body was 32% in 2017, 33% in 2018 and 34% in 2019. It is therefore lower than that of men and has remained stable over the last three years. In the STEM faculties, the proportion of women in levels A and B is 13% and 12% respectively for the EPB and 26% and 26% respectively for the Faculty of Sciences (year 2019-2020). The number of women is therefore very low in the highest levels of the academic career in STEM disciplines. Not only is the proportion of women low, but there is also a "loss" of women throughout the career: the percentage of women in doctoral theses was 23% in the EPB and 34% in the F. of Sciences in the same year.

The Glass Ceiling Index (GCI) is 3.3 for the EPB and 4.4 for the Faculty of Science.

Main problems

Adopted in the 2016-2017 academic year, the "Cascade" measure establishes that the distribution of women/men among those promoted and upgraded must be at least equal to the same proportion in the previous career level (proportions at institutional, not faculty level). The aim is to combat the erosion of the gender balance at university ("leaky pipeline"). This measure applies to promotions to professorships and ordinary professorships. According to the latest data for the year 2018-2019, the measure is respected: the overall proportion of women promoted within the University is slightly higher than the overall proportion of women in previous levels.

However, when looking within the different disciplinary fields, the number of promotions of women has been equal to or higher than that of men in the humanities and social sciences and health sciences over the last three years (2016-2017 to 2018-2019), but lower in the STEM fields. Specifically, at the EPB no women were promoted in the same period (100% promotions of men). However, no women at the EPB applied for promotion during this period. This is partly explained by the very low number of women who could have done so. Inter-faculty differences can then be observed which are attributable to the proportion of women to men starting and not to the "Cascade" measure per se.

Indeed, the "Cascade" measure aims at gender balance in promotions within the academic body, but it does not address recruitment in the previous levels of the "pierced pipe" (doctorate, post-doctorate, first assistant/lecturer):

1. The *Coordinated Text* does not establish selection criteria for the recruitment of members of the scientific body.
2. Figures and interviews show that the "after thesis" is a key moment in women's careers: many women leave the academic career after finishing their thesis, a moment that coincides with the age of having children. Although the *Coordinated Text* no longer requires a postdoctoral stay abroad, but rather "international experience", this is often expected. This is common practice. Many committee members are not even aware that such a stay is no longer an obligation. It is also

difficult to demonstrate international experience without a stay abroad.

- There is little funding for a postdoctoral stay in Belgium. ULB has postdoctoral mandates for assistants.
- In disciplinary fields where women are in the minority (STEM), the number of applications from women is very low. This is particularly the case in computer science and physics. In these cases it is difficult to recruit women if there are no binding measures (i.e. quotas).
- Some sectors (technical staff) or disciplines (computer science, physics, and engineering) are very male-dominated, which discourages women and makes their integration difficult. There are often sexist comments and remarks.

In terms of experiences, according to the survey, 49% of women in the academic and scientific professions have experienced discrimination in the workplace (compared to 24% of men). Furthermore, women are less willing than men to pursue an academic career. Only 28.10% of women (compared to 41.10% of men) intend to apply for a permanent academic position at university in the near or distant future. However, there is no difference in the perceptions of men and women as to the likelihood of their application being successful. These data seem to indicate that, even if they are not sure of their success, men are more willing to apply for academic vacancies, and probably do so to a greater extent, than women. Women also consider more than men that sexism exists in the academic career.

The proportion of people who report having experienced discrimination at work is higher among academics (41%) than among scientists (31%). This may be due to the fact that the career of academics has been longer than that of scientists (usually young researchers). With regard to disciplinary fields, staff in the humanities reported more often having experienced discrimination at work (41%) than staff in the health sciences (36%), social sciences (33%) and STEM (30%). It is important to note, however, that this point in the survey reflects subjective discrimination and requires the victim to identify the received behavior as discriminatory. Therefore, the differences can also be explained by the level of awareness of the respondents. With regard to the perception of sexism in academic and scientific careers, both women and men think that the level of sexism at university is "average" (average = 3.48 on a scale from 1 = nothing to 7 = a lot). However, women perceive more sexism than men (statistically significant difference).

Both women and men feel a conflict between their personal/private life and their professional life (average = 4,204 on a scale from 1 = never to 6 = always). However, women experience this conflict more than men (the difference is statistically significant). Within a relationship, the division of household tasks between partners had a negative influence on the work performance of 23% of women and only 11% of men.

Both women and men are fairly satisfied with their work (average = 4.90 on a scale from 1 = not at all satisfied to 7 = very satisfied). There is no statistically significant difference between women and men in terms of job satisfaction. There is also no difference in the perception of professional recognition reported by women and men. However, women reported feeling more exhausted and stressed physically and emotionally than men in the three months prior to the survey (women reported lower well-being than men).

Objective(s)

The general objective is to decrease the proportion of women dropping out of STEM scientific careers.

Scenario 1: High resistance

Possible solutions:

- To support women to continue their academic career after their thesis by allowing postdoctoral stays abroad (i.e. measures so that they can go with their family) or in Belgium (i.e. through local scholarships).

Opportunities:

The opportunities come from looking at good practices from other universities (i.e. in the United States) that already do this action.

Resistances:

Expected resistances have been identified. The main obstacle is financial: the University does not have the resources and there is little local funding to carry out post-doctoral stays. Another resistance is that, if post-doctoral research is carried out in Belgium, these women may have a less competitive profile in the international context.

The strategies to overcome these resistances are first, the search for external funding and/or to develop partnerships with universities that have more resources and/or with research funding agencies. Another strategy could be to lobby for more research funding with a gender perspective. Finally, for post-doctoral research carried out in Belgium; ensure that it is part of an international project that gives women this much valued perspective.

Scenario 2: Low resistance**Possible actions:**

- To create a mixed reference group in each faculty where problems related to scientific careers can be raised without the risk of repercussions or judgements.
- To extend the network of gender contact persons at the level of departments (Faculty of Science) and services (EPB).
- To set up a gender commission/cell that would bring together the different bodies of staff and students.

Opportunities:

Two opportunities have been identified. First, past experiences have shown that explicitly displaying an openness/sensitivity to certain themes (LGBTQI+, gender) encourages people to seek help and to speak out. Secondly, gender contact persons already exist at institutional and faculty level and this is a well-received and inexpensive measure.

Resistances:

Expected resistances have been identified. There is the risk of differentiating/stigmatizing those who are gender-sensitive and those who are not. Also, If It is not a "compulsory" commission; participation is on a voluntary basis so volunteers must be found to set it up.

The strategies to overcome those resistances are first; clarify the fact that not showing support should not be interpreted as opposition to this type of policy, but rather as the absence of an *active* stance on the issue. Next, ULB should emphasize the importance of gender contact persons and establish an optional system for valuing them. Another strategy could be to organize training for people who are interested in filling the position but are not trained to do so. Finally, ULB needs the support from the faculty authorities to make it visible and legitimate.

Scenario 3: Intermediate resistance**Possible actions:**

- To carry out an in-depth study in order to better understand the decision-making processes in two key moments: 1) between master and doctorate and 2) between doctorate and post-doctorate.
- STEM faculties can be proactive in researching and identifying women both in studies and in academic careers. In particular, recruiting the right female master's students to pursue a scientific

career.

- To ensure good supervision of women during the thesis, not only concerning the research activity but also career development strategies.

Opportunities:

The identified opportunities are that the CALIPER budget (operating costs) is available and that many brilliant women are already there among the students.

Resistances:

Expected resistances have been identified. First, additional financial resources should be provided. Next, it is not enough to identify these women; they must be accompanied so that they can pursue a scientific career. There is also a risk of patronizing support for women. Finally, there may be resistance to incorporating a gender perspective if the training is already very dense (little time and lots of topics to discuss).

Several strategies have been identified to overcome those resistances. First, accompany researching and identifying women with other measures (i.e. mentoring) to overcome obstacles in their careers. Next, make training compulsory in areas where there are few women and/or value it in a special way. Finally, ULB have to think about a training modality to address gender issues without making the training more cumbersome. Highlight the importance of good supervision of the thesis if scientists are to continue their careers - particularly important for fields where there are few women.

Situation: Highly male-dominated specialized career staff

For the PATGS, although women are the majority of staff in both Level 1 and Level 2 (60% women, 40% men), men are in the majority among Level 1 specialist career staff (73% men, 30% women). Specialized careers at level 1 are mainly professions related to the STEM fields of engineering and IT. Women are in the majority among staff in non-specialized careers at both levels.

Main Problems

The sector (technical staff) and disciplines (computer science, engineering) are very male-dominated, which discourages women and makes it difficult for them to integrate. There are few applications from women for these positions.

There are often sexist comments and remarks.

Objective(s)

The main objective is to increase the proportion of women in specialized career staff (engineering and IT).

Scenario 1: High resistance

Possible solutions:

- To establish quotas as a temporary corrective measure for level 1 specialized career staff (engineering and IT) in order to balance the gender proportion in these highly masculinized sectors.
- To redefining PATGS categories: the definition of what is considered a "skilled trade" and the level is gendered so that level 1 careers correspond to traditionally male trades and level 2 careers to traditionally female trades. The question arises as to what impact this may have on the remuneration of women and men.

Opportunities:

Opportunities have been identified. First, quotas measure implemented in other universities and prestigious universities (i.e. Harvard): the results of these experiences can be used as an example of good

practice to convince of the relevance of quotas. Secondly, there is a clear desire in STEM faculties to balance the gender proportion in the academic body.

Resistances:

Several resistances have been identified. First, there is a widespread resistance against quotas, measure not well understood and/or accepted: idea that women are recruited on the basis of their gender and not their skills, feeling of injustice on the part of men (perceived as "reverse discrimination"), impression that the imbalance will resolve itself over time. Next, for some functions, there is a lack of female candidates (difficult application of quotas). Finally, there may be resistance from university authorities if the revision of the classification of PATGS categories implies an increase in the salary of certain categories (limited financial resources).

Strategies to overcome those resistances have been identified. First, ULB could use argumentation paths such as showing current figures on the imbalance, using good practices from other (prestigious) universities, emphasizing that competences are taken into account, deconstructing the "invisible privileges" of men and stressing that this is a temporary action until the balance is achieved. Next, if the procedure for approving the measure is too long, ULB may consider including it in the second version of the PEG. Finally, ULB could initiate a debate on the issue in order to start sensitizing the authorities and the academic community on the impact of the definition of professional categories on the *gender pay gap*.

Scenario 2: Low resistance

Possible solutions:

- To organize training and/or awareness campaigns to change mentalities with regard to gender and engineering and IT professions (deconstructing the male image of these professions, addressing the prevention of sexism in these contexts).
- To create a mixed reference group in each faculty where problems related to scientific careers can be raised without the risk of repercussions or judgements.
- Promotion of *role models* of women scientists among secondary school students.
- To deconstruct the image of scientific and technical professions by focusing on societal aspects (societal application of technology) to attract more girls

Opportunities:

The main opportunity that has been identified is that campaigns targeting to change mentalities with regard to gender, engineering and IT professions already exist elsewhere. This can be a source of inspiration/background on which to build the campaign.

Resistances:

The expected resistance is that there is a risk that the campaign will not reach enough people, that it will be ignored.

The strategy to overcome this resistance is to carry out an awareness-raising campaign that attracts attention. Include figures in relation to the current situation and positive testimonials.

Scenario 3: Intermediate resistance

Possible solutions:

- Promote internships for female students in departments where there are few women because women may be afraid to start working in a much-masculinized world.
- In departments where there are few women, accompany teams and coach them in order to raise their awareness of sexist practices (i.e. avoid sexist remarks).

Opportunities:

The main opportunity is that the faculty authorities are motivated.

Resistances:

Expected resistances have been identified. First, there is difficulty in finding internships because it involves an investment of time by the company tutor. Next, the participation of departments is essential but it is not always easy to create motivation. Finally, this would be an important investment by the University so there would be a risk of losing the people trained.

Strategies to overcome these resistances have been identified. First, if the internship is well designed, it can be an important help in services with a high workload. Next, ULB should establish clauses that avoid abandonment. Finally, well-being at work has to be ensured, a good working environment.

Governance***Situation: Some ULB decision-making bodies remain very masculine (institutional level)***

According to the latest available data (June 2019), the gender composition of ULB's management bodies changes significantly depending on the type of body.

Among the University managers, ULB finds 52% women and 48% men. However, this proportion varies significantly depending on the type of position. The positions of President, Vice-President and Rector are held by men. On the other hand, the Director General is a woman. In the deaneries, men are in the majority (33% female deans and 42% female vice-deans vs. 67% female deans and 58% female vice-deans). In the general departments there are 55% female directors and 45% male directors. On the other hand, the faculty administration is predominantly headed by women (91%).

The governing bodies (Plenary Assembly, Governing Board, Academic Council and its Bureau) are globally composed of a balanced proportion of men and women. Only in the Board of Governors office are women in the minority (29%).

Some advisory bodies are still very male-dominated. The Research Council and the Commission for Student Affairs are predominantly male (75% and 80% men respectively), while the male-female proportion of the Research Council and the Cultural Commission are more balanced (50% women-50% men in the first case, 41% women, 59% men in the second case).

The social consultation bodies (works council, committee for prevention and protection at work and the trade union delegation) achieve gender balance in their composition.

In the nomination and promotion commissions, the ATGS staff commissions are globally balanced from a gender perspective, but this is not the case in the academic staff commissions where men are in the majority: men are 64% of the members of the Interfaculty Scientific Evaluation Commission, 62% of the members of the University Grading Commission and 100% of the members of the Enlarged Rectors' Commission.

Main Problems

Quotas are not very well understood, in general there is a lot of resistance. So what is in place at the ULB is an electoral law that imposes parity in the people who present themselves on the lists. But then the delegations have to elect representatives from among these people for the Academic Council and the Board of Directors (they could choose only men). There is a kind of "natural segregation" in place: in the Academic Council there is a majority of women participating, while in the Board of Directors there is a majority of men. In the composition of these two boards many variables have to be taken into account, including the balance between disciplines. If gender is also added, it becomes a puzzle.

The problem with quotas is that sometimes women show up but then they do not participate (in the case

of student offices) and in the end there are only men. Quotas are not enough; there is a need for support, to deconstruct these spaces, to equip women to participate.

Objective(s)

The general objective is to increase the participation of women in ULB decision-making bodies where they are under-represented.

Scenario 1: High resistance

Possible solutions:

- Establish gender quotas in the different decision-making bodies of the ULB. This would redress the balance.
- Without aiming at the Board of Directors as such, obliging delegations to propose representatives in a proportion of at least one third of each gender (when two or three people have to be proposed).

Opportunities

No expected opportunities have been identified.

Resistances:

There are many expected resistances that have been identified. First, there is much resistance against quotas because it is measure not well understood. It is also something difficult to put in place because there are other variables to be taken into account for the composition of certain decision-making bodies (notably the balance between disciplines). We also have to be aware that, sometimes, women show up but then they do not participate and in the end there are only men. There is also a resistance coming from women because they feel that with the quotas measure, they are chosen based on their gender. Next, there are invisible biases in favor of men. Finally, quotas are not enough; the conditions must also be guaranteed for women to be able to participate effectively.

Strategies have been identified to overcome those resistances. First an institutional debate on quota policy should be open to prepare the ground for a possible introduction of quotas. Next, if the resistances are considered too high at this stage, they can be considered for the second version of the PEG. Finally, women should be accompanied.

Scenario 2: Low resistance

Possible solutions:

- Organizing support for women, equipping them to participate in decision-making bodies. Begin at doctoral, post-doctoral and newly recruited levels.

Opportunities

There are training courses for researchers at doctoral and post-doctoral level, as well as training for those who have just been hired (academic staff). A module on participation in decision-making bodies could be added. This could also be added as an important dimension of the mentoring program. Another opportunity is that members of the academic community with a lot of experience in decision-making bodies (men and women) could become "godparents" and accompany women in these bodies.

Resistances:

The main expected resistance is a possible lack of time/motivation of women and those who have to accompany them.

The strategy that has been identified to overcome that resistance is to emphasize that this is not just a representative role, but that it is part of an institutional objective: to promote gender equality.

Scenario 3: Intermediate resistance**Possible solutions:**

- Open an institutional debate on gender quota policy before its possible implementation. This would force reflection on gender inequalities and candidate lists and would have an awareness-raising effect

Opportunities

Opportunities have been identified. Gender quotas are an effective short-term action to balance the historical imbalance in women's participation in decision-making. It is also a measure encouraged by the European Commission.

Resistances:

The main expected resistance that has been identified is that there is a risk that the debate will quickly become polarized between those who oppose and those who support this type of action.

Several strategies to overcome this resistance have been identified. First, to make a topo on affirmative action and quota methods in order to get to know them better (deepen the debate, bring nuances, avoid caricatures). Next, to present a complete vision of this type of action: advantages and limits. Another strategy could be to identify a respected person who is an expert in the field to frame the debate. Finally, an inventory of good practices should be build: experiences of quotas in other (prestigious) universities and results obtained.

Situation: Men hold the majority of decision-making positions in STEM faculties

The deanships of the Faculty of Science and the EPB are occupied by two men. In the Faculty of Science there is also a vice-dean, while at the EPB there are three vice-deans and one female vice-dean. As far as the chairpersons and heads of departments/services are concerned, the proportion of women is 18% and 28% respectively in the Faculty of Science and 0% and 12% respectively in the EPB.

Main Problems

Low number of women (academic body): by imposing parity, this imposes on the few women present to be presidents of courses or heads of department, deans. It is difficult to be so present in these roles with so few women.

Objective(s)

The general objective is to increase the participation of women in decision-making positions in STEM faculties.

Scenario 1: High resistance**Possible solutions:**

- As highlighted in the situation analysis, gender quotas in commissions and other decision-making bodies (department chairmanships, juries, etc.) can have a perverse effect on women in faculties where they are few in number (STEM faculties). In these faculties, women are overburdened in order to achieve a gender-balanced proportion. In order to ensure a balanced presence of women on committees and in decision-making positions, faculty policy could be put in place that relieves these women of other responsibilities.

Opportunities

No opportunities have been identified.

Resistances:

Expected resistances have been identified. First, if women are relieved of certain activities, it should be

foreseen who will carry out these activities in their place so as not to create an overload of work for others. Next, if more human resources are needed, there may be a financial constraint. There may also be resistance against the measure if it is not well understood (impression that women are given "privileges" or resistance from women who prefer to be involved in other activities - research, teaching).

Strategies have been identified to overcome the resistances. First, it would be necessary to consider how to share these burdens and/or provide more human resources. Next, awareness should be raised on the importance of women's participation in commissions and decision-making bodies (studies on the benefits of having more diverse bodies).

Scenario 2: Low resistance

Possible solutions:

- Organizing support for women, equipping them to participate in decision-making bodies. Begin at doctoral, post-doctoral and newly recruited levels.

Opportunities

Several opportunities have been identified. Firstly, there are training courses for researchers at doctoral and post-doctoral level, as well as training for those who have just been hired (academic staff). A module on participation in decision-making bodies could be added. Next, this could also be added as an important dimension of the mentoring program. Finally, members of the academic community with a lot of experience in decision-making bodies (men and women) could become "godparents" and accompany women in these bodies.

Resistances:

The main expected resistance that has been identified is a possible lack of time/motivation of women and those who have to accompany them.

The strategy to overcome this resistance is to emphasize that this is not just a representative role, but that it is part of an institutional objective: to promote gender equality.

Research

Situation: Lack of gender dimension in STEM research

During the academic year 2018-2019, the ULB Archives and Libraries Service have encoded the final dissertations and doctoral theses on a gender-related theme. A total of 189 dissertations and 9 theses have been identified. All these research works were carried out within the framework of masters and doctoral programs in the human and social sciences, none in STEM.

Currently, ULB does not have a database containing research projects whose main theme is gender and/or which integrate the gender dimension.

An estimate of the number of gender-mainstreamed publications was made by searching for the keywords "gender", "sex", "male/female", "male/female" and "LGBT" (in English and French) in the title of publications in the ULB Di-Fusion digital institutional repository in the years 2017, 2018 and 2019. Although not very accurate, these results allow us to come to some conclusions:

- The vast majority of publications whose main theme is gender belong to the fields of humanities, social sciences and health sciences.
- The keywords "gender", "masculinity/femininity" are more used in the titles of publications in the humanities and social sciences, while the keyword "sex" is more used in the health sciences, indicating the different perspective adopted in each disciplinary field.
- The gender perspective is generally absent in STEM publications. Publications on sex have been

identified, but they refer to the sex of animals and plants in biology, zoology, etc. Only two articles can be considered as having a gender perspective in the STEM field.

Main Problems

Training for the integration of the gender perspective in research projects (to apply for funding) and/or in research content do not exist at ULB.

Specific funding for gender research projects do not exist at ULB.

ULB is very sensitive to gender issues and takes action to correct prejudices and gender inequalities. However, the University is reluctant to target specific research topics through specific funds or other means. There is no allocation of funds for specific programs on gender studies, but such funds do not exist on any other subject either. The reason for this is that the freedom of researchers is a fundamental value of ULB; the University cannot set a specific research program.

There are no policies or guidelines on the integration of gender analysis in research at ULB. The research department fears that this could become an additional administrative burden for researchers, who already have to deal with a lot of administrative formalities (ethics, RGPD, etc.). Moreover, this perspective might not be relevant for all types of research (i.e. basic research in mathematics) and should therefore not be imposed by default on all researchers. Sometimes the relevance of the gender perspective in STEM research is not fully clear/understood. It could be positive to start a reflection and discussion on the issue. This would help to identify in which specific areas of STEM (i.e. applied research) the gender perspective could have an impact. This could be an objective of the PEG CALIPER.

This vision is shared by other key informants interviewed during the focus group. The gender perspective is generally absent from STEM research. However, a first step would be to clarify when the gender perspective is relevant or not in STEM. What does gender mainstreaming in research mean? Does it mean mainstreaming gender or avoiding prejudices? It is not the same thing. Key moments in gender mainstreaming should be identified.

An important element to be taken into account is that European funding is placing increasing emphasis on gender mainstreaming in research projects. It may become a strategic interest for the ULB Research Department.

As the analysis of the figures shows, however, the gender perspective is very much present in research in the humanities and social sciences at the ULB. STEM research could possibly benefit from the gender knowledge that already exists within the University.

Objective(s)

The main objective is to promote the incorporation of the genre perspective in STEM research.

Scenario 1: High resistance

Possible solutions:

- To integrate a humanities and social sciences course into bachelor's degree courses in the exact sciences where gender (and diversity) issues are addressed.
- To make interdisciplinary calls for projects to promote collaboration between STEM, SHS and health sciences.
- To promote collaborative projects between ULB researchers and the industrial world with a gender perspective.

Opportunities:

Several opportunities have been identified. Firstly, there is a strategic interest because European funding is placing increasing emphasis on gender mainstreaming in research projects. Next, it is perspective

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

increasingly encouraged by scientific journals (i.e. *Nature* will take this into account and therefore select according to this criterion). Another opportunity is that mainstreaming gender can account for a great deal of variability in the study and have significant added value without complicating the experience. There is also the fact that courses on gender already exist in the SHS faculties of the ULB so they could be offered as optional courses. Finally, ULB has gender and diversity experts in the academic and scientific bodies (SHS disciplines) who could support the development of a course on gender (and diversity) in STEM.

Resistances:

Expected resistances have been identified. First, there is a difficulty to place this course in the curriculum: to add one course would have to remove another - possible resistance from the STEM academic body. Then, there is a geographical separation at ULB of the faculties (STEM, SHS and Health Sciences are in three different campuses: La Plaine, Solbosh and Erasmus respectively). Another expected resistance is that often the languages of STEM and SHS are very different: sometimes interdisciplinary understanding is not easy. Finally, there is a lack of ULB's own funding.

Strategies to overcome those resistances have been identified. Firstly, the course could be offered as an elective. Next, ULB could offer a course that already exists (SHS faculties). The teachers of this course should be supported so that they are not overwhelmed if a large number of STEM students enroll in it. Finally, interdisciplinary dialogue days could be organized to discuss gender mainstreaming in different disciplines. The days could be organized on different campuses.

Scenario 2: Low resistance

Possible solutions:

- To organize workshops to have an in-depth discussion/reflection on the integration of the gender perspective in STEM research (usefulness, relevance, specific fields of application).
- Creation of a repertoire of studies demonstrating the added value of incorporating gender in STEM research in order to raise awareness of this perspective and encourage researchers to integrate it.
- To organize an exhibition with posters and videos to invite reflection on the integration of gender in STEM research in a playful way.

Opportunities:

Several opportunities have been identified. Firstly, there is a strategic interest because European funding is placing increasing emphasis on gender mainstreaming in research projects. Next, it is perspective increasingly encouraged by scientific journals (i.e. *Nature* will take this into account and therefore select according to this criterion). Another opportunity is that mainstreaming gender can account for a great deal of variability in the study and have significant added value without complicating the experience. Finally, the "Gender innovations" site (Stanford University) presents *case studies* that show why gender needs to be integrated into research.

Resistances:

There are expected resistances coming from STEM researchers. Little interest is expected because of the difficulty to see the "human" aspect of research in STEM. They could also have the fear of adding to a search a criterion that ULB does not fully master. Regarding the exhibition, it cannot take place if the confinement continues.

Several strategies have been identified to overcome the expected resistances. Firstly, interdisciplinary collaboration between STEM and the human and social sciences could be promoted. STEM studies where the gender perspective is adopted could be presented to show the added value of this approach without this involving additional work (it is a question of changing a perspective -androcentrism- rather than adding a subject of study). It would also be necessary to designate a person responsible for the directory to ensure

that it is kept up to date. Finally, within the framework of CALIPER, the ULB has a budget for operating costs that could be used.

Scenario 3: Intermediate resistance

Possible actions:

- To develop a guide for the incorporation of a gender perspective in STEM research.
- To develop and implement training for researchers to integrate gender in STEM research.
- Award of a "Gender and STEM" prize to the best studies carried out at ULB in the STEM fields with a gender perspective. Several categories can be created: master thesis, doctoral thesis, post-doctoral research.

Opportunities:

Several opportunities have been identified. Firstly, there is a strategic interest because European funding is placing increasing emphasis on gender mainstreaming in research projects. Next, it is perspective increasingly encouraged by scientific journals (i.e. *Nature* will take this into account and therefore select according to this criterion). Another opportunity is that mainstreaming gender can account for a great deal of variability in the study and have significant added value without complicating the experience. Finally, guides are available on incorporating a gender perspective into research.

Resistances:

The expected resistances are the lack of human resources (lack of time, work overload, need to have knowledge of STEM and gender) and limited financial resources.

Strategies to overcome the resistances have been identified. A working group with several people with different profiles (STEM/SHS-gender) could be created to distribute tasks and complement perspectives. It would also be a working group whose members may change from one year to the next, but the action could be placed at the institutional level to ensure its sustainability. Next, the Research Department could be involved. Finally, training and the publication of the guide must be accompanied by actions to encourage the adoption of a gender perspective in STEM research.

Teaching

Situation: Lack of consciousness/awareness about sexism and androcentrism in education (STEM)

It is important to note that this issue is not limited to STEM disciplines, but affects the whole University. The analysis and courses of action focus on the institutional level and not on the two STEM faculties.

Over the last three years (2016-2017, 2017-2018, 2018-2019), the training "*Is my teaching gender-biased?*" has been organized by the CAP three times (once a year) with a total of 16 participants (11 women and 5 men).

Around twenty courses on gender currently exist at ULB, notably in the humanities and social sciences. No such courses have been identified in the STEM fields. Numerous seminars, workshops and conferences on gender have been organized at ULB over the last three years: 30 in 2016-2017, 30 in 2017-2018 and 42 in 2018-2019. These activities have been organized or co-organized by STRIGES (Maison des sciences humaines). No such activities have been identified in the STEM fields.

Interviews and focus groups show the presence of sexist remarks or jokes, different/condescending treatment of girls and the almost exclusive use of male examples in the course content.

Main Problems

The Centre d'Appui Pédagogique (CAP) offers the workshop "*Is my teaching sexist?*" to all teachers on integrating the gender perspective into teaching. This training focuses on the curriculum, teachers'

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

interaction with students and the evaluation of teaching. It is carried out once a year on a voluntary basis. The problem is that most of the participants in the training are women, already engaged or activists, and not the general public. This is the case in the social and human sciences and in STEM as well.

The CAP is in the process of developing a guide on gender in education. A first version has been sent to different actors in the University for review, but the guide is not yet finalized. It is an ongoing project. The guide will be aimed at ULB teachers, but it will also be shared with members of the CAP pedagogical network. A nice brochure will be produced.

The problem is the same for gender equality training and pedagogy training in general: teachers feel they do not need it (they feel they are already good pedagogues). With gender, the same thing happens: teachers feel that the problem of gender inequality has already been solved. They are not opposed to equality, but think that it has already been achieved. Moreover, they usually have very little time for training.

Objective(s)

The main objective is to prevent and reduce sexism and androcentrism in STEM education.

Scenario 1: High resistance

Possible solutions:

- Make training on sexism in education compulsory.
- Add a question on gender mainstreaming in EVALENS (student evaluation of teaching). This would allow students to denounce bad practices and promote awareness of the problem among teachers.

Opportunities:

The opportunities that have been identified are first that EVALENS is a tool already available and widely used by students anonymously. The inclusion of an additional question in the questionnaire is easy from a technical point of view. Secondly, Teachers whose gender mainstreaming in teaching needs to be improved could be invited to attend the training "Is my teaching sexist? ».

Resistances:

Expected resistances that have been identified are first that there is, in general, a lot of training and members of the academic and scientific bodies do not have the time to train themselves. Resistances could be coming from teachers; they may not see the value of including this type of question in a pedagogical evaluation (perception that gender has nothing to do with the quality of teaching).

Strategies to overcome the expected resistance are first, on the short term; start with the training of new recruits. Next, in the medium/long term, change the institutional culture to enable people to train. Another strategy is that careful thought should be given to how questions on gender (and diversity) are formulated and accompanied by a text on concepts, definitions and objectives (i.e. what is meant by "sexism", what would be improved, etc.).

Scenario 2: Low resistance

Possible solutions:

- Carry out a communication campaign (posters, videos) to raise awareness of the importance of adopting a gender perspective in teaching in order to encourage teachers and assistants to participate in gender training.
- In student offices and circles, to appoint a person dedicated to gender (and diversity) issues in order to mobilize students so that they become a means of pressure. This would be a kind of "gender contact person" in the student body.

- Integrate the gender dimension into all teachers training instead of gender-specific training.

Opportunities:

Several opportunities have been identified. First, ULB has past experience of campaigning against sexism, homophobia and transphobia. Next, general student are interested in gender (and diversity) issues. Raising awareness of gender issues during the welcome day for new students (session for all faculties) is already carried out in other universities (University of Paris Diderot). Finally, ULB's Pedagogical Support Centre has gender expertise.

Resistances:

Expected resistances have been identified. First, it may target a specific community (teachers) and they may feel "under attack" (sexism exists everywhere, not only in education). There is also a risk that this could become a "witch hunt" for teachers. Finally, it is difficult to address all aspects of gender in education without specific training in this area.

Strategies to overcome the resistances have been identified. First, the campaign should focus on teaching as practice rather than on the people who teach. Next, the purpose and role of this "gender" person must be well defined. Next, gender mainstreaming should be combined in general pedagogical training with gender-specific training.

Scenario 3: Intermediate resistance

Possible solutions:

- To set up a curriculum review/counselling service to identify gender bias/bias. For courses given in English: the "ULB languages" service reads and analyses the curricula.
- To make an online/MOOC course version of the training "Is my teaching gender-biased? ». This would give participants more flexibility in terms of time, allowing them to follow the training at times when they are available and at their own pace.
- Setting up 'communities of practice' (CoP) on gender in education. This consists of strengthening the culture of a small group of volunteers who discuss and learn together on a subject.

Opportunities:

The opportunities that have been identified are that knowledge on the gender perspective in education exists at the CAP (Pedagogical support center) and that ULB has already set up MOOC courses (growing experience).

Resistances:

The main expected resistance that has been identified is the lack of human resources. It could be the case for the CAP to carry out this type of action (it would take a long time to review all the curricula), for the Pedagogical Support Centre because designing an online training course takes time and there is also a need to monitor/supervision of the training, and finally, it can be difficult to find volunteers at the beginning (lack of time for teachers).

Strategies that have been identified to overcome the resistances are first, to design a checklist for self-evaluation of curricula by teachers. Next, to accompany the launch of online training with other actions to raise awareness of gender bias in education. Finally, it should start with a small group of highly motivated people in each STEM faculty. Involve teachers interested in inclusive education and teachers trained in gender (and diversity).

Students and services to students

Situation: Low proportion of female students in STEM disciplines

The proportion of students enrolled in undergraduate studies varies by discipline area. In 2018-2019⁷, female students accounted for 59% of the student body in the humanities and social sciences and 58% in health disciplines. However, only 30% of the student body was female in science and 21% in technology and engineering sciences.

In post-graduate studies, the proportion of women enrolled is increasing in almost all fields. In 2018-2019, the proportion of female students was 66% in the humanities and social sciences, 62% in health disciplines and 45% in the sciences. However, in technology and engineering sciences the proportion of women is still 21%.

Main Problems

There are a few initiatives to promote women in STEM disciplines, but there has been no official campaign within the two STEM faculties to attract girls. "Yes, she can" is an initiative launched by two female students of the Brussels Polytechnic to encourage girls to become engineers. They organize FB campaigns and have produced inspiring videos. A conference against moral and sexual harassment was organized at the EPB by a doctoral student. In the Printemps des sciences there are often activities targeting young girls.

However, the gender perspective is not very present and/or systematically taken into account in activities to promote science among secondary school pupils, but those responsible for them are open to establishing collaboration with the CALIPER project. This is notably the case of InforSciences (a department of the Faculty of Sciences to promote science among secondary school students), the Ateliers Jeunes Ingénieurs and Clipedia (EPB). InforSciences shows a lack of knowledge regarding the incorporation of the gender perspective in its activities.

Participants in focus group 1 have the impression that there are many local initiatives to attract female students to STEM (role models, bringing together girls and women scientists), but this does not seem to be working. They suggested looking at what is happening elsewhere, particularly in Scandinavian countries. However, participants in focus group 2 stressed the importance of role models.

With regard to information/guidance for future students, ULB also has a study guidance service for these students: InforÉtudes. The gender perspective is not explicitly implemented in the counselling service (through gender-specific initiatives or actions, with the exception of a conference organized in 2018) but the service is attentive to these issues.

According to InforÉtudes, the choice of studies is made during rhetoric (the last year of Belgian secondary education) but interest in a subject builds up much earlier in school. There are often blocking mechanisms among girls: if they are interested in a scientific subject, they often find the environment very masculine, they think it does not suit them. There are therefore two ways to attract girls to STEM subjects: to arouse their interest during their school years and to build a university environment that is able to accommodate them, not too "masculine".

According to InforÉtudes, the reasons and timing for dropping out are different at the EPB (engineering) and the Faculty of Science. Girls drop out of science studies very early, from the first year of studies, and the reasons are not related to the difficulty of the studies but to the fact that they do not find their place. It is a very masculine environment that does not suit them (La Plaine campus). It is a very masculine campus where the boys are always together and it is very difficult for the girls to integrate. There is no real co-education.

Engineering students drop out later and this is often due to the difficulty of this type of study. This happens later, not in the first year. Boys drop out less often, and when they do, it is related to external factors such

⁷ The figures are stable for the last three years.

as the issue of funding. For girls, other reasons are added: the desire to do something else, the question of meaning, the need to reorient themselves so as not to work afterwards "in a man's world".

With regard to information/guidance for students and graduates, InforEmploi is ULB's career guidance service for students and graduates. The gender dimension is only taken into account in the composition of the expert panels of the discussion forums. They strive to make them as representative as possible. But apart from that, there is no explicit gender perspective in the work of InforEmploi. However, the head of the service stresses that they "make no distinction", welcoming both men and women.

InforEmploi has no data on the careers of women graduates of STEM because there is no individual support service. It is mainly a collective approach (they work with groups). However, InforEmploi's actions are mainly followed by women, who make greater use of the service. Women are more daring to ask questions and ask for help, while men show more self-confidence, which can also work in their favor when looking for a job.

Companies do not ask for any collaboration to implement a gender equality policy in hiring. Companies are afraid to say that they want to recruit more women. This is interpreted as discrimination [reference to quotas]. It is taboo. However, companies emphasize the desire to recruit people with special needs. This is emphasized in a very positive way.

InforEmploi would like to launch a program to help students develop a career plan from the beginning of their studies, but there is a significant lack of resources and support to do so. InforEmploi is open to working with CALIPER to implement gender-sensitive measures in student guidance.

In the same vein, the *focus group* participants also stress the existence of a general lack of knowledge about the scientific professions. One solution could be to focus on the societal aspects (societal application of technology), which could attract more girls. We need to break down clichés to attract more people (girls and boys): research is collaborative, it is useful, and it is not just theory. And there is also great diversity in research professions, the fields are very broad. It is necessary to focus on the human meaning of what ULB does.

A point of concern raised by several key informants is how to carry out communication campaigns to attract more girls to STEM disciplines without falling into stereotypes and clichés or targeting only girls. The lack of awareness among some teachers was also raised, as well as the need to focus on subject areas where women are really not present, such as computer science and physics. There is a need to deconstruct the imaginary around science.

Objective(s)

The general objective is to increase the number of girls enrolled in STEM studies, particularly in computer science, physics and polytechnic.

Scenario 1: High resistance

Possible solutions:

- To organize mixed classes (i.e. via interdisciplinary courses) to create a more girl-friendly environment.

Opportunities:

The main opportunity that has been identified is to use the already existing SHS courses (i.e. on gender) and offer them to STEM students.

Resistances:

The main resistance is that there is an increasing tendency towards the (even geographical) separation of disciplines.

The strategy that has been identified is to set up pilot experiments to convince people to stress the value of interdisciplinary.

Scenario 2: Low resistance

Possible solutions:

- Promotion of *role models* of women scientists among secondary school students.
- Deconstruct the image of scientific and technical professions by focusing on societal aspects (societal application of technology) to attract more girls.

Opportunities:

Opportunities have been identified. Firstly, the CALIPER project is already planning to produce a video to promote *role models* for women scientists. The *role models* could be integrated in all ULB activities for the promotion of science ("Après-midi inédit", "Printemps des sciences"). Another opportunity is that (young) ULB graduates could be invited to visit the schools to talk about their studies and the career prospects that have opened up for them after leaving university.

Resistances:

No expected resistances have been identified.

Scenario 3: Intermediate resistance

Possible solutions:

- Work with/train/awareness-raising secondary school teachers (from lower secondary level) to make sense of the subjects and avoid gender bias (i.e. give female examples when explaining physics).
- To develop a collaborative project with the ULB actors who promote STEM among secondary school students in order to deconstruct the image of these disciplines and attract more girls to these subjects.
- Accompanying female students from the first year of study to help them find their place and reduce the "impostor syndrome".
- To propose to all first year students a training module in September to encourage the construction of the meaning of STEM studies ("professional project").

Opportunities:

Several opportunities have been identified. Firstly, secondary school teachers are required to attend a compulsory training course of 2 days per year (6 hours/day), ULB could offer training on gender bias in STEM teaching. Next, the InforScience department (Faculty of Sciences) is implementing many initiatives to promote science and is already involved in CALIPER. Finally, InforEmployment service appears to have motivation.

Resistances:

Expected resistances have been identified. Firstly, there are internal resistances such as limited human resources; it can be difficult to find the person(s) at ULB to carry out this awareness/training once a year (preparation of contents + dispensing). Next, some schools do not wish to participate in this type of activity. There is also a possible lack of time for training by InforSciences staff.

The main strategy that has been identified is to train volunteers among gender/STEM students at ULB.

Transfer to Market

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Situation: Low participation of women in knowledge transfer to the market and in entrepreneurship

On average, the proportion of female “principal researchers” in research projects was 28% in 2017, 27.9% in 2018 and 28% in 2019 at ULB (the figures are therefore stable). However, there are important differences between disciplines, with the share of women in the leadership of research projects in the STEM faculties being particularly low. In 2019, while the proportion of “principal researchers” was 69.6% in public health, 54.8% in motor sciences and 53.5% in law and criminology, it was only 6.9% in the EPB and 27.1% in the Faculty of Science. However, in these two faculties these percentages are similar to the (low) proportion of women in the academic body (8.6% and 23.5% respectively) which is not often the case in the humanities and social sciences⁸.

With regard to the amounts of research projects awarded, the amounts awarded to women at ULB are also lower than those awarded to men: 22.6% of the total amount of research contracts in 2017, 24% in 2018 and 25.4%. The inter-faculty differences identified in the research contracts are also to be found in the amounts awarded.

When considering research collaborations, only 20% of the Faculty of Science projects and 24% of the EPB projects are carried out with partners outside the University, especially with other universities. Non-university players (i.e. industry, public authorities, etc.) are included in only 9% and 10% of projects respectively. As is the case with the research contracts presented above, the proportion of women participating in these different types of projects reflects the proportion of women in the academic staff of each faculty (23.5% in the F. of Sciences and 8.6% in the EPB). The participation of women in “mixed” collaborative research projects (academic and non-academic actors) at the EPB is slightly lower than the proportion of women in the academic body of this school.

The proportion of women on research patents over the last three years (2017, 2018, 2019) averaged 28.59%. This corresponds to the proportion of women in STEM.

However, the share of women in ULB spin-offs was only 16% in the last three years (2017, 2018 and 2019) (figure 18), a particularly low percentage. It should also be pointed out that, according to the Research Department, ULB's participation in spin-offs and in innovation and knowledge transfer in general is especially low compared to other universities. There is little entrepreneurship at ULB. This can be partly explained by the high workload of the academic and scientific staff.

Main Problems

Numerous training courses are available at ULB for the development of a scientific career, the transfer of knowledge and the valorization of research: mentoring programme, summer school “Boost your career”, scientific popularization competition “My thesis in 180 seconds”, seminar “How to publish a scientific article? How to increase its impact” seminar. Training in “prior art research” (Picarré), Training in intellectual property (TTO). In all of these training courses, the proportion of women attending has been slightly lower than that of men (47% vs. 53%) over the last three years. It is interesting to note that the proportion of women participating in the seminar “How to publish a scientific article? How to increase its impact” varied greatly according to discipline: while the percentage of women was 58% and 62% in the humanities and social sciences and health sciences respectively, it was only 27% in STEM. For the other courses, the breakdown of data by discipline is not available.

⁸ For example, in psychology women represent 40% of the academic staff but only 28.5% of the research contracts. This difference between disciplines could be explained by the fact that research in the humanities and social sciences is less funded than research in STEM, which increases competition and difficulty in obtaining funding. This may discourage women from applying.

The university does not have a database of collaborative research projects with a gender dimension. This type of project exists but it is very difficult to say how many of them there are. As is the case with research content, ULB is reluctant to encourage a subject or perspective in the transfer of knowledge to the market.

In relation to the low number of women, there are two types of problems. An "external" problem is that external donors (FNRS, etc.) are not very sensitive to gender inequalities. The "internal" problem is that women are less likely to apply for projects and grants. In addition, patents and spin-offs do not have a positive influence on careers. It is publications that take precedence, not patents. Collaboration with companies has no impact on career because there is little academic recognition.

Objective(s)

The main objective is to increase the proportion of women participating in the transfer of knowledge to the market.

Scenario 1: High resistance

Possible solutions:

- To establish a "one-stop shop" at the administrative level for all questions that academics ask themselves (setting up collaborative projects, spin-offs) in order to be directed towards the most appropriate people to solve them and to be able to delegate tasks to competent people.
- To establish a gender balance (at least one third of people of each gender) in the juries that select the projects to be funded (spin-offs, university-industry collaborative projects).
- To ensure that the drafting of calls is gender sensitive and include actions that would favor the selection of women, as is the case for ERC projects.

Opportunities:

The main opportunity that has been identified is that the ERC projects could serve as a model.

Resistances:

The expected resistances that have been identified are that there are no calls for projects specific to ULB for the financing of spin-offs and collaborative research, these are external funders and ULB has little room for intervention in this area and there is a possible lack of financial resources from donors to include certain actions to support women.

The main strategy to overcome the resistances is to establish collaborations with donors to promote the establishment of gender-balanced juries.

Scenario 2: Low resistance

Possible solutions:

- To take stock of the participation of women in the collaborative projects RW (Win2Wall, 5 competitiveness clusters) and Innoviris.

Opportunities:

The main opportunity that has been identified is that in fact, this has already been done.

Resistances:

No resistances have been identified.

Scenario 3: Intermediate resistance

Possible solutions:

- Awakening the interest of researchers and students in entrepreneurship, while paying

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

attention to the gender dimension.

Opportunities:

The main opportunity identified is that external partners promoting entrepreneurship are already involved in the Hub (Innoviris - spin-offs).

Resistances:

Expected resistances have been identified. First, there is a problem of mobilising the academic community (overall deficit at ULB): there were information sessions but it didn't work at all at ULB, perhaps because academics do not think it is relevant to their field. Next, academics also have the feeling that they are overwhelmed (linked to the lack of means). There is an unbalanced division of labor between administration and teaching/research. Finally, entrepreneurship and collaboration with external partners is not a priority for the academic CV (emphasis on teaching, publications, number of supervised theses).

Some strategies have been identified to overcome the resistances. First, to inform on the areas where one can undertake (repertoire of experiences?). Next, to relieve academic staff of administrative tasks, especially those related to the setting up of projects. Finally, to look for other ways of valuing entrepreneurship (i.e. focus on its societal usefulness/impact).

Communication

Situation: The “masculine” image of STEM persists in communication

We have analyzed in detail the websites and the FB page of the Faculty of Science and the Brussels Polytechnic regarding the use of gender-sensitive language and the representation of women. The main conclusions are that inclusive language has started to be used, but that there is still a long way to go to achieve equal representation of women and men in both faculties. The visual representation of the EPB is, in general, very "masculine" (with colors and style traditionally associated with masculinity - black - and many images of men). Although on some occasions the names have been feminized, the masculine form remains. However, the images used do illustrate ethnic diversity. In addition, the titles of Master's degrees are very masculine (i.e. "Engineering Sciences"). The visual representation of the Faculty of Science is more 'feminine' in terms of color and style and the inclusion of images of women, but male forms of language remain dominant.

Main Problems

At the institutional level, within the framework of the Diversity Plan, some measures are aimed at inclusive communication: the use of non-sexist language in job offers; training in communication modalities accessible to people with special needs; the writing and dissemination of articles on different diversity themes in internal communication tools; the feminization of the names of ULB premises according to outstanding women rooted in ULB's history and values. The University also has guidelines on inclusive communication. This guideline is available to all staff members on the University's intranet. It provides basic knowledge and different ways of implementing inclusive communication.

However, the use of inclusive language is not mandatory (it cannot be), it is a recommendation and, according to interviewees, it is not very detailed. However, there is no specific training for staff on how to use inclusive language. In STEM faculties, the “masculine” is often used in communication with students on the grounds that it is an “epicene” form⁹, whereas this is not the case.

Objective(s)

The main objective is to build a more inclusive imaginary around STEM in faculty communication.

⁹ An epicene word is one whose form does not vary according to gender. For example, "skilful" is an epicene adjective.

Scenario 1: High resistance**Possible solutions:**

- Change the title of the EPB Masters Courses to avoid using the masculine form.

Opportunities:

The opportunities that have been identified are that gender equality in STEM is a policy priority of the Minister of Higher Education and that there is a gender commission in ARES (Academy of Research and Higher Education).

Resistances:

The main resistance that has been identified is legal constraints to change the official title of university courses.

The main strategy to overcome this resistance is to discuss this with the Minister of Higher Education.

Scenario 2: Low resistance**Possible solutions:**

- Organize a focus group with students to carry out an in-depth review of the faculty websites (text and visuals) from a gender and diversity perspective in order to better identify specific modifications to be made.
- Making visible feminist faculty initiatives (i.e. yes she can, seminar for gender inclusion in STEM research).

Opportunities:

The opportunities that have been identified are the motivation and availability of faculty communication managers and the increasing number of such initiatives.

Resistances:

No expected resistances have been identified.

Scenario 3: Intermediate resistance**Possible solutions:**

- To organize training courses to train administrative staff who are in contact with students (e-mails, websites) in the effective use of inclusive language.

Opportunities:

The main opportunity that has been identified is the existence of the inclusive writing guide that can be promoted.

Resistances:

Several resistances have been identified. First there is the resistance to change. Next, inclusive language makes sometimes reading difficult. Another resistance is that the staff has little time to train. Finally, inclusive language is often seen not as a priority.

The strategies that have been identified to overcome those resistances are to include this measure in Polytech's Strategic Plan and to open the debate on the representation of diversity in writing.

Intersectionality

Situation and Main Problems: Lack of data and difficult operationalization of intersectional actions

Several social relations are addressed in the ULB Diversity Plan (gender, origin, age, disability and social class), but in isolation, not in interaction. That is to say, there are measures that focus on gender equality (i.e. the "Cascade" measure) and others on the situation of disability, etc. But it is very difficult to implement truly "intersectional" measures: actions that take into account *the interaction of* these variables. On the one hand, data on the origins and the situation of disability are not available and are not easy to obtain. In both cases, this is ethically and legally sensitive data. While the classification of persons according to gender is accepted and naturalized, classification according to other criteria is much debated or even rejected. This is particularly the case for ethnic origin. Data concerning disability are private medical information. Currently the ULB has set up a project to explore how this type of data could be obtained in order to improve existing indicators.

On the other hand, it is sometimes difficult to design actions that take into account the interaction of several axes of discrimination. For example, how can ULB ensure that the "Cascade" measure respects not only the ratio of men to women in promotions but also the ratio according to origins? This would meet with a lot of opposition. And ULB does not have ethnic statistics to be able to implement this type of measure.

However, intersectionality is currently mobilized in the way of thinking and reflection (for example, when ULB thinks about putting subtitles in a video promoting gender equality for deaf people). In March 2020, ULB organized a day of reflection on intersectionality at the University where these issues were debated.

In view of the difficulties described above, the work on intersectionality will consist of 1) continuing to improve the indicators (origin and situation of disability) and 2) for each PEG CALIPER action that will be proposed, examining the possibility of integrating the intersectional approach into the design and/or implementation and integrating it where possible (analysis and design of actions with the "diversity glasses").

Sexism and sexual harassment

It is important to note that all issues related to sexism and harassment are not limited to STEM disciplines, but affect the whole University. The analysis and courses of action focus on the institutional level and not on the two STEM faculties.

Situation: Lack of knowledge of ULB protocols and services for the prevention and treatment of case of sexism and harassment.

According to the survey on sexism and sexual harassment, out of 110 people (90 women and 20 men) who reported having been sexually harassed, 89.4% of women (N=42) and 100% of men (N=9) of scientific staff and 100% of women (N=20) and 87.5% of men (N=7) of academic staff did not report the event.

The main reasons for not reporting the incident seem to be the consideration that it was not so serious and the desire to put the incident behind us. Indeed, this question was asked of all respondents who answered "yes" to one of the behaviors, regardless of its seriousness. It is therefore possible that for less serious incidents (i.e. an isolated sexist joke) it was not necessary to report the incident to any service.

With regard to knowledge of university services to deal with this type of problem, only 106 respondents (out of 1,627 respondents) were aware of the existence of contact persons in each faculty and only 19 were aware of the prevention advisers/trusted¹⁰ persons.

Main Problems

¹⁰ When contacted, the role of the faculty contact persons is to direct the person concerned to the prevention adviser or trusted person.

Numerous measures exist at ULB to combat sexism and sexual harassment, such as a project to combat sexism and sexual harassment at the university in collaboration with the University of Geneva, the modification of the Disciplinary Regulations, a poster campaign, a network of gender contact persons, the student collective FRESH to combat sexual and sexist harassment on the ULB student party scene, a website, a survey and counselling services. Since September 2020, a new unit (CASHe) is the contact point for students. The advantage of this unit is that it is independent of ULB, so it is easier to complain if it is to someone outside the institution.

One aspect to be highlighted is the fact that despite the number of existing initiatives and services to combat harassment, many members of the University are not aware of them. As far as students are concerned, ULB needs to ensure that they know who to talk to and how to distinguish between acceptable and unacceptable behavior. Information is available on the website, but there is too much information. It is difficult to know who to talk to. We need to go beyond a chapter in the student guide or a leaflet at the beginning of the academic year. We need a simple, easy, clear and accessible mechanism.

In addition, deans may not necessarily be aware of the problem (complaints go through other channels). The authorities tend to minimize the facts, which is very difficult for the victim. The authorities need to be sensitized and trained to have the right reflexes and to take cases seriously.

Objective(s)

The main objective is to improve knowledge of the protocols and access to ULB services for dealing with cases of sexism and harassment.

Scenario 1: High resistance

Possible solutions:

- To add a question on harassment in EVALENS (evaluation of student learning) of the type "have you witnessed or experienced a problem of gender-based harassment?" and redirect to the page for reporting harassment.

Opportunities:

The main opportunity that has been identified is that EVALENS is a tool already available and widely used by students anonymously. The inclusion of an additional question in the questionnaire is easy from a technical point of view. Anonymity could encourage students to report situations of sexism and harassment.

Resistances:

Expected resistances have been identified. First, there is teachers resistance, they may not see the value of including this type of question in a pedagogical evaluation (perception that gender has nothing to do with the quality of teaching). They may think that students are not competent to judge this and fear the consequences. Secondly, this action has to be approved by a certain body and it will take time.

The main strategy identified is that careful thought should be given to how the question is formulated and accompanied by a text on concepts, definitions and objectives (i.e. what is meant by "sexism" and "harassment", why is the question asked, etc.).

Scenario 2: Low resistance

Possible solutions:

- Put a button/banner on the ULB website to report cases of harassment (similar to the one on the UNIA website for cases of discrimination), accessible in French and English.
- Have permanent posters on what to do in case of harassment, not a temporary poster campaign.

- To create a brochure adapted to the needs of students, scientific bodies, PATGS, academics, etc.

Opportunities:

Opportunities have been identified. First, a *chatbot* on sexism and harassment could be carrying out as a year-long project in computer science done by the students. Secondly, the brochure could be put in the bag given to students at the beginning of the school year.

Resistances:

The resistances that have been identified are that there is a big quantity of display and information at ULB (both physical display but also on the website) and financial resources would have to be requested.

The strategies identified to overcome the resistances are finding the right way to make information visible in the long term and producing digital brochures to be placed in a visible way on the University's website.

Scenario 3: Intermediate resistance

Possible solutions:

- To inform year/section delegates of procedures, protocols and services in the event of sexism and harassment so that they can act as a focal point.
- Equipping the faculty authorities (deans and vice-deans) to raise their awareness and to inform them about existing protocols and services.
- To introduce students to the protocols and services available at ULB to prevent and deal with cases of sexism and harassment at the JANE or in courses for large audiences (at the beginning of a course).
- Training/awareness-raising for assistants in order to identify and prevent cases of harassment, as they have a privileged link with the student body.

Opportunities:

Opportunities have been identified. Firstly, there is a training weekend for new assistants in the first year, a module on sexism and harassment could be included. Secondly, there is a real Interest/motivation of the faculty authorities.

Resistances:

Expected resistances have been identified. First, those who behave inappropriately will not be sensitive to the problem. Next, it is increasingly difficult to find year delegates. There is also a lack of time of the faculty authorities. Finally, it is not easy to find volunteer teachers to introduce students to the protocols and services available at ULB to prevent and deal with cases of sexism and harassment in larger classes.

Strategies to overcome the resistance are finding the right arguments, do not limit it to the delegates, but also inform all student groups, offices, and circles and finally, to identify allies and committed teachers for gender equality and support them in the design of the presentation.

Situation: Difficult use of available information on sexism and harassment at the University (complaints and 2018 survey data).

University authorities are concerned about the (often inappropriate) treatment of cases of harassment at ULB by the media. The University is aware that harassment exists (as is the case in most organizations) and does not try to deny or hide it, as the measures described above show. But when a case comes to the media's attention, it is often treated in a disrespectful manner, revealing details that should not be made public (these are disciplinary procedures that are legally subject to secrecy) and/or describing the University as an institution that tolerates harassment. Although some media may have good intentions and a desire to contribute to the fight against harassment, they make the university's task even more difficult. ULB is making a lot of efforts to fight harassment and the relationship with the media should be based on collaboration. How to establish such a collaborative relationship could be further explored during the course of the project.

The data from the survey on sexism and harassment published in the CALIPER report demonstrates the University's desire for transparency and its commitment to combating such behavior within the institution. However, these data should be interpreted with caution. They confirm that cases of harassment do indeed occur at the University according to a typology of behavior. But without having a point of comparison (for example with the situation a few years ago or in a few years' time or with the situation in a similar university that used the same survey), ULB cannot yet draw many conclusions as to the extent of the phenomenon and the effectiveness of the measures put in place. Further research is needed.

Objective(s)

The main objective is to use available information to effectively combat sexism and harassment.

Scenario 3: Intermediate resistance

Possible actions:

- Organize a day of reflection with different actors (especially with the media, but also with other universities, companies, etc.) to discuss how to deal publicly with cases of harassment, exchange good practices and identify avenues for collaboration.
- Repeat the survey on sexism and sexual harassment conducted in 2018 to have a point of comparison and assess the evolution of the situation. This data could then be published in a report.

Opportunities:

The main identified opportunity is that there is a growing interest of some media/programmers in combating harassment.

Resistances:

The expected resistances are first that the authorities might be reluctant to overburden the academic community and there might be limited human resources. The main strategy is to define what is the optimal frequency for carrying out this type of survey.

2.5 National Technical University of Athens – School of Electrical and Computer Engineering (RPO)

Human resources

1. Recruitment procedures

Situation

In the ECE-NTUA women are underrepresented in tenured academics as well as in research. 5 female Faculty members out of 61 in total Faculty members. Furthermore, according to data provided by the Institute of Computers and Communication Systems (ICCS), in 2017,2018,2019, the Institute has signed

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temporary contracts with 607 persons, of which 170 were women, and 437 were men (28% vs 72% respectively).

ECE-NTUA does not have specific gender-sensitive protocols for recruitment and hiring in ECE-NTUA. Candidates are assessed on their capabilities and experience, while the gender dimension is not considered. The procedures for hiring administrative, technical, and academic (permanent) personnel, as defined by the relevant legislation, do not involve any gender sensitive criteria. The “election” criteria established refer to the academic profile and background of each candidate, but no gender-relevant issues are considered. Furthermore, there are no gender sensitive protocols and/or criteria as regards selection and hiring of researchers (non permanent personnel).

Main problems

Few women academics and researchers further strengthen the existing stereotypes that Engineering is more a “men’s job”, while also there is a lack of role models. These two parameters could possibly result to the unequal distribution between male and female students in the School (14% of the enrolled undergraduate students are female). Finally, this underrepresentation leads to more male candidates for research and/or academia therefore creating a repetitive circle.

Another consequence of female under representation in ECE-NTUA is the low rate of females in recruiting boards/panels. The participation of women in the recruiting and promotion boards (tenure boards, Faculty promotion, Teaching and Laboratory staff promotion, Technical staff promotion) ranges between 4-14%, percentage which further follows the female to male ratio in the Faculty members. Moreover if it was to include more women in academic promotion/ election panels during the present situation, it will probably end up in taking up more of their time than their male counterparts. Furthermore, another problem is the horizontal and vertical segregation that appears in the administrative staff. While all other permanent staff categories exhibit a female underrepresentation, in the administrative staff the majority of staff is female (2 male and 40 female administrative staff).

As regards the academic personnel ECE – NTUA cannot put in place gender sensitive protocols for their recruitment and hiring, as the Ministry of Education and Religious Affairs is eligible for this procedure and criteria are specifically established by Laws. Regarding the selection and hiring of non-permanent personnel and post doc researchers, theoretically the gender issue is not taken under consideration as all the recruitment and hiring procedures are based on merit. However, sometimes strong stereotypes may be hidden behind merit, therefore developing gender inequalities.

Objective(s)

Main objective is to increase the number of female students, female researchers and post-doc researchers in the School, in order to increase the growth potential of tenured researchers and academics. This increase, along with further gender sensitive protocols in recruiting and hiring procedures of researchers, will indirectly enhance the potential candidates for academic positions.

Also, another objective is to gradually increase the number of male administrative staff, in order to reach a more balanced ratio and decrease horizontal and vertical segregation.

Possible solutions

- Activities to increase the number of students:
 - Dissemination and communication activities regarding the School’s content and the career path a graduate may follow,
 - Cooperation with vocational guidance offices that operate in the framework of the secondary education,
 - Videos of female role models (researchers and academics from the School)

- disseminated in the external environment,
- Enhancement of the School's Communication Office role,
- Enhancement and stronger dissemination of the present activities.
- Activities to increase the number of female researchers:
 - Set gender sensitive criteria in the recruitment and hiring procedures of researchers,
 - Increase the number of research/post doc positions for female researchers, through a predetermined target - ratio between male and female researchers and post-doc researchers.
 - Communicate the opening of new research positions in a more gender sensitive way, to attract more female researchers.
 - Take advantage of researcher's and students exchange programs (ERASMUS, AISEC) to maximise international recruitment of researchers.
 - Establish a guide framing research and post – doc education conditions in the School, in order to create a more solid environment.
- Activities to increase the number of male administrative staff:
 - Set internal targets to gradually attract more male administrative personnel to the School.

Resistances

As regards the increase of female students, the only identified resistances from internal stakeholders may come in the form of displeased administrative personnel as the administration employees will undertake extra workload.

In terms of increase of female researchers, resistances may come from different sides. First, researchers (male or female) might feel that it is unfair to increase the number of positions just for female researchers, because that merit would be undermined and that might feel that female researchers are treated as a minority. Secondly, resistances may appear in an unconscious way as a reaction to the existing stereotypes. Doubts whether women may succeed in more "hands on" jobs, or whether they will manage successfully male workers, what will happen if they get pregnant etc. Such resistances are very difficult to categorise as they can be expected by all internal stakeholders. Thirdly resistance may appear from high level and middle level management in the form of finding the framework guide for research and post-doc education unnecessary. Lastly and fourthly, there might be resistances by middle level management' and researchers (by heads of labs/ research groups) who might feel that such policies might make it difficult to engage the most qualified researchers relative to their limited funding

In terms of increase of male administrative personnel, resistances may come from high level and middle level management as they might feel that such an increase is unnecessary and redundant. It also might come from administrative personnel as they might feel that the present balance in the working environment will be disturbed.

There are no resistances identified coming from external stakeholders.

Strategies to overcome the above resistances involve argumentative strategies, in the rules of the organisation or other strategies. Argumentative strategies resume communication activities that are based on dialogue, in order to explain the problem and the main objectives. It could also be explaining why it is important to keep a balanced male to female ratio in all categories (tenured and not) of the School's personnel. Another one is explaining why predetermined targets and/or quotas are necessary in the beginning of a change process. The last one could be involving researchers in the process of setting the

gender sensitive criteria, in the recruitment and hiring procedures. In the rules of the organization: involving the high-level management to provide incentives (even moral) to the administrative employees, towards handling the extra workload. Other actions identified are educational activities in order for everyone to realise why the underrepresentation of women in the School is a problem and trainings and seminars regarding best practices of other Universities.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from different areas. First, the rules or structure of the organization such may further encourage schools visit the NTUA premises in order for students to familiarise with engineering and STEM and to develop actions in cooperation with schoolteachers who are responsible for guidance and counselling on the career opportunities and studies. The administration may enhance the School guide with further information about the disciplines, the career goals and job opportunities. Members of the Erasmus committees should assist in the foreign students' recruitment. The high management can develop and adopt internal targets as regards the female and male students ratio set by the School and reviewing policies on e.g. working conditions. Women researchers already in research projects should be made more visible, special strategies to attract women to research positions and create teams of volunteers that will visit schools and communicate the possibilities that appear from engineering. Finally, students may create teams of volunteers that will visit schools and communicate the possibilities that appear from engineering.

2. Work environments and working conditions

Situation

The situation in this section is derived by the same issues as in the recruitment procedures, though it leads to problems related to the work environment and working conditions, as described further on.

Women are underrepresented both as academic personnel and as researchers. 5 female Faculty members out of 61 in total Faculty members, while in research the sex ratio on permanent contracts is 7% female and 93% male and on temporary contracts is 18% female and 82% male.

Furthermore, as regards non permanent researchers, it has been observed that there is no solid framework describing possible rights, benefits and/or support measures.

Main problems

Deriving from the above many women have claimed that a lack of a solid framework describing working conditions/benefits, obligations and work life balance measures creates insecurity and insecurity does not lead to a healthy, stable working environment.

Moreover, female underrepresentation can also lead to insecurity as there have been occasions where women were doubting whether they have been asked e.g. to participate in a committee, because of their value or because of a certain quota/ratio that needed to be fulfilled. Additionally, underrepresentation may lead to occasions where different behaviors to men and women have been noted. In a "mostly-men" environment reactions to behaviors tend to be different according to the gender of the person having the behavior. E.g., a woman shouting at work might be considered as overreacting, while a man doing the same would not be judged at all.

Objective(s)

The main goal is to create an inclusive environment and improve the working conditions, in order to create a stable working environment, eliminate insecurities and discourage sexist behavior.

Possible solutions

- Activities to eliminate insecurities and improve the working conditions include the following:
 - Increase the number of female researchers and academics (see recruitment procedures

section).

- Within the guide for post-doc education in the School, specifically dedicate a section referring to the work-life balance measures that are available for researchers (eg parental leaves, maternity leave etc), as well as related rights and obligations.
- Development of a guide regarding gender neutral behavior in the working environment, in order to eliminate sexist behavior.
- Implementation of training activities to all members of the ECE NTUA School in order to understand the content of gender neutral behavior and how to implement it.
- Establishment of a formal, structured mechanism to handle incidents of bias and sexist behavior in the working environment, as well as in other sections (teaching, communication intersectionality) explained further on.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first from some internal stakeholders. All categories of internal stakeholders could have resistance in the forms of denying that such incidents could exist in the School environment, or that the possible solutions are redundant. They can also find training activities time consuming and unnecessary. More precisely, administrative personnel and/or other tenures categories could have resistances as they might feel threatened by the increase of rights and work-life balance measures of non-tenured personnel categories. Secondly, for external stakeholders, resistances may come from other researchers working in other institutions and/or the private sector that might feel that the same employment sector enjoys different benefits / obligations. These resistances might appear as protests regarding the rights of self-employment and how these could be undermined. This kind of resistance could influence the discourse/climate in which the School operates and delay the necessary change.

The possible strategies identified to overcome the resistances are first argumentative strategies. There could be communication activities that are based on dialogue, in order to explain the importance of having a stable framework for non-tenured researchers and post doc researchers, communication of the importance of using gender neutral communication in the working environment and involving researchers in the process of setting the measures of work-life balance and/or rights and responsibilities. Strategies identified in the rules of the organization could be involving the high level and middle level management as regards the application procedures and methods of the above. Other actions are to organize educational activities and training on how to apply gender neutral communication and dissemination activities on the establishment and application of the formal mechanism to handle incidents of bias and sexist behavior in the working environment.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first coming from the administration like effective practices that already exist (for the permanent staff) such as the Greek National Laws and to take advantage and use the trainings implemented within the framework of the National Centre for Public Administration and Local Government. Secondly, the Gender Equality Committee of NTUA could inform about issues such as parental leave, equal payment, child-care services and the Gender Equality Committee of NTUA could also inform on best practices implemented in other NTUA Schools. Thirdly, there are research projects with a high proportion of women participation.

3. Appraisal systems for career evolution

Situation

The promotion policy of all categories of permanent staff is aligned with the common promotion policy of the Greek public administration. The criteria used are not flexible and are defined by Laws. Faculty promotions are based on research performance, teaching experience and years at the position. Promotion

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ratio follows the pattern derived by each personnel category female to male ratio. However, there is no specific promotion policy for non permanent personnel and researchers. Promotions for these categories (wage promotions) can occur through experience (years of experience), scientific expertise (PhD nomination and other scientific work) and other related criteria, but not in a systematic and structured way. The application of flexible criteria depends on the negotiation and agreements with the research supervisor (e.g. project principal investigator, research group leader, etc.), and the informal norms established in each research group and laboratory.

Main problems

The above, in combination with the lack of solid framework defining possible rights, benefits and/or support measures, described in the work environments and working conditions, may result in researchers' insecurity and therefore possible female underrepresentation.

Objective(s)

The main goal is to create a specific appraisal system for the development of researchers and non permanent staff, in order to establish a more stable environment, eliminate insecurities and discourage female underrepresentation.

Possible solutions

- Development of a guide (or a section within the guide for post-doc education in the School) which will create a solid appraisal system for researchers and non-permanent personnel.
- Definition and introduction of gender parameters to be integrated in the appraisal system(eg. between junior and senior researchers)

Resistances

Resistances may come from internal stakeholders firstly. Resistances may occur from male and female researchers objecting to a cascade system of appraisal, as they might feel that it is unfair and not based on merit. Other resistances might be towards change itself. Secondly there might be resistance from external stakeholders. Resistances may arise from other researchers working in other institutions and/or the private sector that might feel that the same employment sector enjoys different benefits / obligations.

The possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative such as augmenting on the importance of having an appraisal system for both male and female researchers / non-permanent personnel, including all researchers in the preparation phase of the guide regarding the appraisal system and the gender parameters and to communicate how the cascade system works. Possible strategies are also in the rules of the organization like involving the high level and middle level management as regards the application procedures and methods of the above. Other possible strategies could be dissemination activities and training activities.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from different areas. First, the rules or structure of the organization can support the appraisal system and give incentives for the implementation of the guide. Secondly, the administration can provide information about the guide and best practices from measures of the public administration. Thirdly, researchers may encourage the appraisal system and to communicate the importance of having a stable working environment without insecurities.

Governance

1. Enhancing women leadership and access to top positions

Situation

In ECE NTUA women are encouraged to undertake leadership and decision making positions. Women take

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part in most committees and scientific boards, including being Directors of undergraduate studies, Heads of undergraduate studies committee, Members of the Deanery, while at the administrative level heads of administration, heads of the secretariat for undergraduate studies, heads of the Communication Office, heads of the finance office, heads of the secretariat for postgraduate studies etc.

At a School level there are no mentoring or coaching activities/services for leadership positions dedicated to women. However, at an institutional level, the liaison-student services office is co-organising, participating and/or disseminating various events with a gender equality dimension.

Main problems

As mentioned in the previous sections, women academics are underrepresented in the School. Therefore, no matter how much they participate in decision making and leadership positions, there is a limit in how many responsibilities they can undertake. To this end most interviewees on the internal assessment responded that either no such actions are in place in a School level, or they did not know whether they exist.

Moreover, additionally to the lack of mentoring/coaching activities at a School level, the activities implemented at an Institutional level are not effectively disseminated.

Objective(s)

The main goal is to increase the number of women participating in leadership and decision making positions.

Another goal is to initiate the organization of coaching activities at a school level, in order to further enhance women leadership. Additionally there is a need to strengthen the dissemination and communication of the activities taking place at an institutional level.

Possible solutions

- Increase the number of women faculty members in the ECE – NTUA School (See Human Resource section).
- Put into practice Law 4386/2016 on “Regulations on research and other provisions” which foresees that, regarding evaluation and selection committees and advisory bodies in the field of research, technology and innovation, at least 1/3 of the members of these advisory bodies and scientific councils of research institutes must be from either sex, “as long as the candidates have the necessary qualifications as required by each position”, where applicable.
- Elaboration of at least 1 Annual Event (Workshop/Seminar) regarding female leadership implemented at a School level.
- Increase the dissemination of the activities at an institutional level, through the use of web channels.

Resistances

The expected resistances are from internal stakeholders. If Law 4386/2016 is actually put to practice, resistances may appear from all categories of internal stakeholders as a way of reacting to specific quotas. The internal assessment exhibited that quotas are not a favourable measure within the School. There can also be resistance from the administrative personnel which will undertake more workload for the organization of the annual events and the further dissemination of activities occurring at the institutional level. No resistances coming from external stakeholders have been identified.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative like communication activities and dialogue on why quotas are necessary in the beginning of change process and communication of the importance of having women in leadership positions. They can also be in the rules of the organization like involving the high level management to provide incentives (even moral ones) so that the administrative

personnel can handle the extra workloads. Other action can be dissemination activities.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities would be coming from different areas. There should be opportunities coming from the rules or structure of the organization: when possible, to put into practice Law 4386/2016 on “Regulations on research and other provisions”. Law 4604/2019 Promoting Substantive Gender Equality, Preventing and Combating Gender-Based Violence - Provisions for Granting Citizenship -Provisions for Elections of Local Authorities- Other Provisions”) on gender budgeting. The Law determines that academic Institutions shall send a relevant report through the Ministry of Education, to the General Secretariat for Gender Equality (GSGE), including data on activities which contribute to the fulfilment of the institutions’ objectives, as well as their plans for the coming year, in terms of gender equality. This will assist in the implementation of activities. There should also be opportunities coming from the administration such as improving the use of web channels in order to inform female members of the current activities regarding female leadership at a school level and encouraging the participation of women faculty members in leadership and decision-making positions. Other opportunities should be coming from middle management like using successful female academics as role models and communicate their achievements further. To finish, there should be opportunities coming from high management such as further encourage female academics and personnel to undertake decision making positions and providing incentives (even moral ones) so that the administrative personnel can handle the extra workloads.

2. Gender disaggregated data collection at the institutional level

Situation

The School of ECE – NTUA, through its registry, collects gender-disaggregated data that are sent to the Ministry of Education and other public organisations upon request. No other procedure or tool embed a gender dimension in data collection processes in ECE-NTUA.

Main problems

At this point the administration of the School as well as its high level management consider that the implemented data collection is sufficient. However, collecting data on inequalities (gender inequalities, intersectionality) assists in gaining sufficient knowledge on the measures and activities that need to be implemented for a more gender sensitive working and studying environment.

Objective(s)

Start collecting gender disaggregated data beyond the standard types of information (gender, religion, nationality).

Possible solutions

- Implementation of an anonymous, annual, questionnaire for students and personnel to collect respective data.
- Involve students’ and researchers associations for the collection of data through questionnaires.
- Enhance the data collected through the registry.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first by internal stakeholders. They come from students’ associations and students arguing the necessity of personal data provision, for GDPR, being afraid for the ultimate use of the provided data and denying the provision of gender sensitive data. They can also come from the administrative staff or whoever else will be responsible for the design of the questionnaires and the data collection through the registry. The high-level management might feel that these kinds of activities are unnecessary and go beyond the School’s scope. Secondly, external stakeholders can have resistance such as students’ associations and students of other Universities arguing the necessity of personal data provision,

for GDPR, having fear for the ultimate use of the provided data and denying the provision of gender sensitive data.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances can be argumentative like the to communicate and explain the importance of data collection in the change process, to ensure all the interested parties that the data collection methods used will be completely anonymous and guarantee the personal data safety and to involve students and student associations in the change process and ask for their assistance and ideas. Strategies can touch the rules of the organization such as involving the high-level management for the questionnaires' distribution in a central way, in order to reach all students and give a more "formal" character to it. Other actions could be dissemination activities.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from different areas. They could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization like the implementation of Greek National law. They could also be coming from the administration such as taking advantage of the knowledge on the existing registry in order to prepare the framework on collecting more data. Finally, they could be coming from students like involving students and student associations in the change process.

Research

1. Research contents and methods

Situation

In ECE NTUA, there are no gender studies since the whole university is technical with a focus on engineering. Therefore, ECE-NTUA has a low level of integration of the gender dimension into research. In particular, the percentage of research projects that take into account gender issues in relation to all research issues (the last 3 years) is below 1% in ICCS-NTUA and approximately 5% in NTUA (ELKE). Only 2% of the undergraduate thesis integrate a gender dimension in their subject matter, while this percentage reaches almost 4% in the PhD thesis. Finally, the scientific publications that include a gender dimension in their subject matter are approximately 0,3% - as indexed by google scholar and 0,6% as indexed by Scopus.

Main problems

Main problem is the low integration of gender dimension into research that is derived by the lack of a formalised practice, or other policies or guidelines at a School level, which would ensure the integration of the gender dimension into research in a systematic way.

Moreover, this low integration could also be caused by the lack of allocation of funds for specific programs on gender studies, while another related issue is the fact that the majority of project leaders and PIs is male.

Objective(s)

Main objective is to set a target of gender equality integration into the School's research (eg. 10% in the next 10 years).

Possible solutions

- Create a framework (at a School level) that will include guidelines on how to integrate the gender dimension into research and teaching.
- Raise awareness on gender equality issues and why it is important to integrate them into research.
- Strongly underline the importance of integrating aspects of gender equality parameters in Thesis and PhDs.
- Help researchers include the gender dimension throughout a research project and eliminate gender

bias in research projects and stereotypical images of masculinity and femininity.

- Promote more gender balanced research teams.
- Promote PhD fellowships which may support women (since they are the underrepresented) and increase the number of female researchers (also see Human Resources section).
- Add the particular indicator “Number of thesis/PhD’s/research projects with a gender dimension in their content” as part of the School’s performance assessment.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first from the internal stakeholders. It can come from researchers and students as they might feel that the gender dimension is irrelevant to the content of their research, by middle level management as they might feel that the gender dimension cannot be integrated to their field of expertise. The content of the School's research is not always flexible to the integration of gender equality parameters. It could also come from high level and middle level management that might feel the design of a framework unnecessary. No resistances from external stakeholders have been identified.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative such as to communicate and explain the importance of gender integration into research, to help researchers understand the “gender and science” issue and make them more sensitive towards the gender dimension in science and to involve students, researchers and academics into the design of the guidelines on gender dimension integration into research. Other strategies can touch the rules of the organization like to involve the high level management in order to add the performance indicator to the School’s assessment and involve the high and middle level management in the guideline’s application. Another action could be communication activities on the importance of gender integration into research as well as on ways on how to integrate it.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from different areas. They could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization such as making use of the Greek Strategy for Gender Equality, which refers to mechanisms for promoting and monitoring gender equality. These include the possibility of combined training programmes and funding incentives, including some for the integration of gender in the content of scientific research. They could also be coming from middle management like the Gender Equality Committee can assist towards the integration and from academics that can integrate the gender dimension into their scientific subject can be more involved. There is a possible cooperation with the School of Architecture and other Schools of NTUA, cooperation with other Universities from abroad. Next they could be coming from high management like rewarding effective practice such as awards for laboratories that demonstrate effective leadership on gender equity or like adding the particular target in the School’s evaluation process. Opportunities could be coming from researchers, as there have been cases of the gender dimension integration. These cases need to be further disseminated. Finally, they could be coming from students like rewarding effective practice such as awards for research institutions that demonstrate effective leadership on gender equity.

Teaching

1. Gender sensitive teaching

Situation

In the ECE-NTUA School gender is not integrated into the curriculum, neither in teaching, nor in the examination methods. Moreover, there is no mechanism on handling possible cases of bias in teaching. To this end, even though no gender bias has been evident during the implementation of lectures, some interviewees recognised that students interact with male and female faculty members differently.

Main problems

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Currently, there is no specific policy or set of guidelines for the integration of a gender dimension in the curriculum at the ECE-NTUA, while the gender dimension is not yet considered into the School's curricula. The fact that there are no specific guidelines makes it difficult to integrate gender into studies, especially when the School is more technical.

Furthermore there is no mechanism to prevent gender bias in teaching while also no training and/or information activities are in place, in order to assist the mechanism's application. Professors and lecturers follow the code of ethics, some might use gender-sensitive language, but all the above depend on their own goodwill. Faculty members and researchers also involved in the teaching process have not received any gender sensitive training on what to do in case of gender bias incidents during teaching.

Objective(s)

The main goal is to integrate gender into teaching through specific targets (at least 3 lectures in a course annually regarding gender issues – 1 at an undergraduate level and 2 at a postgraduate level) employed at a School level and the implementation of a selective course on gender issues open for all students of NTUA within the following 5 years.

Furthermore, another goal is the implementation of a mechanism preventing incidents of gender bias in teaching (guidelines, seminars and trainings) for the benefit of both students and professors.

Possible solutions

- Development of guidelines on how to integrate the gender dimension in the curricula,
- Development of guidelines on gender sensitive teaching, that will assist in avoiding gender bias in the classrooms,
- Creation of a solid mechanism dealing with gender bias in teaching,
- Trainings on gender sensitive teaching and on gender integration in the curricula,
- Encourage the creation of mixed (male and female) groups of students for the implementation of assignments.
- Set a target of at least 3 lectures in a course annually regarding gender issues – 1 at an undergraduate level and 2 at a postgraduate level.
- Set a target on the implementation of a selective course on gender issues open for all students of NTUA within the following 5 years.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first from internal stakeholders. Resistance could come from students reacting to an additional (even though elective) course, due to the already heavy curriculum or them considering that gender integration into teaching is irrelevant to the subject of their studies. It could come from middle level management considering that gender integration into teaching is irrelevant to their teaching material and research interest. Finally, it could come from researchers, middle level and high-level management complaining that training activities and workshops on the matter are time consuming and an extra burden to their heady daily program. No resistances have been identified coming from external stakeholders.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative such as to communicate and explain why the integration of gender into teaching is important and beneficial for all parties and to communicate that the courses content enhancement will not be for the student's discomfort and that the additional course will be selective, to discuss the benefits of a mechanism to handle gender bias and involve all members of the School in the construction of its framework, parameters and issues to consider, to explain that workshops and trainings on the implementation of the mechanism could be time consuming but they are a crucial part for the improvement of the teaching itself. Strategies could touch the rules of the

organization like involving the high-level management in order to give incentives to the personnel to attend the relevant trainings and workshops and it includes the targets set in the School's annual assessment. Other actions could be to provide information material as evidence on the necessity of gender integration into teaching.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from different areas. They could come from the rules or structure of the organization like following the Law 3896/2010 (Official Government Gazette, 2010) on integrating the gender dimension in all aspects of academia and into the curricula of universities, to take advantage of the Greek Strategy for Gender Equality which calls for the integration of gender courses in academic, research institutions and applying Law 4604/19 which refers that higher education institutions, such as ECE NTUA, ensure the promotion of gender equality at all levels and processes of academic life. They could also come from middle management like from the Gender Equality Committee can assist towards the integration, the professors have expressed that there is a need for training in gender sensitive teaching and the involvement of the middle level management on the implementation of guidelines on gender sensitive teaching. Opportunities could be coming from high management such as adding the adopted targets as part of the School's evaluation. Finally, they could be coming from students like having "welcoming" gender-sensitive teaching and the respective mechanism.

Students and services to students

Situation

In ECE-NTUA the undergraduate percentage of female students is almost 16%, while this percentage tends to increase in post graduate studies ranging between 25% and 45%, according to which post graduate program they attend. As regards the percentage of female PhD candidates this lays between 23% and 22% for the last 3 academic years.

ECE-NTUA School does not have a specific strategy on attracting girls to the Electrical and Computer Engineering field. However, several schools from secondary education visit the campus and get a guided tour of the premises and all the labs and available services.

At an NTUA level, the Liaison– Student Services Office develops activities and established actions that favor equality policies and equal access in education. The Office retains professionals to provide counselling and psychological support to NTUA students in need, for free. The Office also organizes, participates in and communicates events and activities referring to gender equality issues. It also includes career counselling.

Main problems

The absence of a specific strategy on attracting girls into to the Electrical and Computer Engineering field does not help solving the problem of underrepresentation.

Furthermore, services that aim at aiding and counselling enrolled students in any kind of matter, including possibly gender equality issues, are not widely known. The role of the Liaison– Student Services Office requires further dissemination.

Objective(s)

The main goal is to set specific targets not only for the increase of female students (eg. 23% in the next 5 years) but also set a specific framework on to how this increase will be achieved.

Furthermore, main goal is to further promote, communicate and disseminate the gender equality policies and actions to all students, implemented by the Liaison– Student Services Office, while also retaining its professionals that provide counselling and psychological support to NTUA students in need, for free.

Possible solutions

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- Activities on increasing the female students in the School (also see the Human Resources section),
- Setting up a strategy/policy on how to attract more girls in the School with specific targets,
- Increase the role of the Liaison – Student Services Office through dissemination and communication of its activities,
- Dissemination and communication activities at a School level as well.

Resistances

The expected resistances are from internal stakeholders. They are expected by the administrative personnel due to the extra workload the dissemination and communication activities at a School level require, by the administrative personnel at a School level reacting to the dissemination of activities of other Offices at an Institutional level, by the high level and middle level management thinking that a strategy at a School level on how to attract more girls in the School with specific targets is something not feasible and in the responsibility of the Ministry and by the high level and middle level management thinking that the present activities are more than enough and that extra activities might require unavailable resources. No resistances from external stakeholders have been identified.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative such as to communicate and explain the importance of elaborating more activities at a School level, in order to attract more girls, to increase the teamwork spirit at an institutional level and to involve all members of the School in the design of a strategy/policy on how to attract more girls in the School with specific targets. Strategies could touch the rules of the organization like involving the high-level management to provide incentives to the administrative personnel (even moral ones) regarding the extra workload they have to undertake. Other action could be dissemination and communication activities.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from different areas. They could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization such as dissemination through the Liaison – Student services website. Encourage more students to use the counselling services to deal with gender equality issues. Ensure the confidentiality as well. They could also be coming from the administration like enhancing the existing collaboration with the Liaison – Student services office and to further disseminate activities targeted to students. Other opportunities could be coming from middle management like the Gender Equality Committee of NTUA could also assist on the activities of attracting more female students in the School, as well as on the upgrade of student services provided at an NTUA level. Next, they could be coming from high management like doing guided tours to the ECE premises, female academics on crucial positions/roles. Coming from researcher's educational activities could be organized. Finally coming from students could be doing communication.

Transfer to Market

Situation

The commercial exploitation of research outputs in collaborative projects is usually the responsibility of the private sector partners. The ECE-NTUA itself does not exploit research outputs commercially, nor does it create research-based spin-offs.

However, the NTUA Innovation and Entrepreneurship Unit provides some support to student-led startups, which can be assumed that they exploit some of the know-how provided by the School. Students are also supported to start apprenticeships in the private and public sector and are also supported by the NTUA career office.

Main problems

The number of female speakers in Conferences on STEM follow the pattern of female underrepresentation.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Nearly 10% of Professors speaking in STEM Conferences are female, while in 2020 there has been a significant increase in the number of female PhD students speaking in STEM Conferences (40% in 2020, in contrast to 10-15% during 2017-2019).

Objective(s)

The main goal is to increase the number of female speakers (Professors, PhD students and researchers) in presenting outcomes in STEM conferences, as well as to enhance the activities of the NTUA Innovation and Entrepreneurship Unit.

Possible solutions

- Increase the number of female students and female researchers in the School (please refer to the Recruitment procedures of the Human Resources section).
- Further communicate the activities undertaken by the NTUA Innovation and Entrepreneurship Unit.
- Provide incentives to students, researchers etc to exploit the know-how provided by the School.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first internal stakeholders. Resistance could come from high level and middle level management believing that activities to enhance transfer to market might be perceived as trying to cash off academic knowledge. It could also come from students accusing the School's organization that it is trying to trade academic knowledge. No resistances have been identified by external stakeholders

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative like to communicate and explain that activities to enhance the activities of NTUA Innovation and Entrepreneurship Unit will be beneficial for students, to communicate and explain that activities to enhance the School's extroversion do not imply trading of academic knowledge. It can touch the rules of the organization like involving the high level management to provide incentives to students and researchers to exploit the know-how provided by the School.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from different areas. They could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization like the existing initiatives and research programs to enhance the School's extroversion. They could be coming from high management such as academics' contribution, providing incentives to students and researchers to exploit the know-how provided by the School. Finally, they could be coming from researchers like promoting a stronger dissemination/communication

Communication

1. Gender sensitive institutional communication

Situation

From a brief overview of the ECE's communication material, it appears that in general, it reflects a level of diversity, in terms of sex, age and sometimes ethnicity and disability but not in a systematic manner. As all the announcements are related to academic progress and achievements within the School – Institution, their content depends on the achievement itself. Moreover, ECE-NTUA social media promotes gender equality through announcements regarding the scientific and/or academic achievements of female students and/or teaching staff when it occurs, however there is not a social media strategy tailored to gender equality. The administrator (who is a woman) tries to keep a balance on gender equality issues, however there is lack of official in-school guidelines/protocols on gender-sensitive and non-biased communication/language.

At the level of internal communication, the General Secretariat of Gender Equality (GSGE) elaborated the first version of the "Guide of using non-sexist language in administrative documents" but it is not used at a

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School level.

As regards promotion and organization of awareness raising campaigns, relevant activities have been organized and disseminated for participants among all Schools at an NTUA level, through the Liaison and Student Services Office.

Main problems

There is a lack of an official policy/guidelines on the use of gender sensitive language to the School's external communication (website, social media), while as regards the internal communication, even though a good basis for the use of non-sexist language in administrative documents, it is not used. Additionally, there are no official complaint mechanisms in cases of gender-biased/sexist communication. Finally, even though relevant activities to promotion and organization of awareness raising campaigns are being implemented by the Liaison and Student Services Office, these could be further enhanced by activities at a School level.

Objective(s)

The main goal is to create a framework/mechanism for the promotion and protection of gender sensitive external and internal communication. To this end the organization of at least one (1) annual event on the promotion and organization of awareness raising is also necessary.

Possible solutions

- Establishment of guidelines on gender-sensitive and non-biased external and internal communication/language.
- Application of the "Guide of using non-sexist language in administrative documents".
- Establishment of a formal, structured mechanism to handle incidents of bias and sexist behavior in communication, as well as in other sections (teaching, working environment, intersectionality) explained in previous sections.
- Provision of incentives to the administrative employees to attend the relevant workshops and trainings of the National Centre for Public Administration & Local Government
- Organisation of trainings on the implementation of the guidelines gender-sensitive and non-biased external and internal communication/language, for all members of the School (students, professors, administrative staff, researchers) to facilitate their elaboration.
- Implementation of 1 annual event on the promotion and organization of awareness raising on gender-sensitive and non-biased communication (possibly in combination with the event on women leadership).

Resistances

The expected resistances are from different internal stakeholders. Resistances are expected by the administrative personnel as the implementation of the guides on both internal and external communication will mean extra workload, by high level management reacting to the fact that participation of administrative personnel to workshops and seminars will mean absence from work, also by all members of the School as they might feel that the participation on workshops and training on the use of gender-sensitive and non-biased external and internal communication/language is unnecessary, extra workload and redundant, and to end by the high level and middle level management as they might feel that creation of a mechanism to handle incidents of bias and sexist behaviour is a way of admitting that such incidents do happen in the School. No resistances coming from external stakeholders have been identified.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative such as the communication of the importance of gender sensitive communication at an internal and external level and involving all interested parties in the implementation of the guide on internal and external communication. Other strategies touch

the rules of the organization like involving the high-level management to provide incentives to the administrative personnel, as well as the other members of the School, on the attendance in Workshops and Trainings. Other actions identified are dissemination and communication activities.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from different areas. To start it could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization such as the application of the “Guide of using non-sexist language in administrative documents” contains comments, instructions, recommendations, advice, and specific suggestions for the use of non-sexist language. Next it could be coming from the administration like the School’s Dean or the School’s Secretary handle possible cases of bias in communication directly, therefore already showing the necessary sensitization and the administration could further enhance the cooperation with the Liaison and Student Services Office and disseminate the relevant activities. Then it could come from middle management like the ECE web media administrator and head of the communication office is already focusing to contain announcements relating to both male and female genders and keep the respective balance. It could also be coming from high management like providing incentives for the use of the Guide of using non-sexist language in administrative documents. Finally, it could be coming from researchers like promotion of the use of gender-sensitive language at their research and coming from students such as using gender-sensitive language at social media dialogues, etc.

Intersectionality

Situation

In ECE-NTUA, there are no formalised institutional measures addressing intersectionality. However, at an institutional level the Liaison-Student Services Office supports, organises and disseminates various activities for minorities and different marginalized social groups.

Main problems

At a School level there are no institutional measures that consider gender in conjunction with other discriminations. There are some efforts that have been put in place for people with disabilities at an NTUA level. However, these activities implemented by the the Liaison-Student Services Office are not as known as they should, hence further dissemination is strongly needed.

Objective(s)

The main goal is to establish measures that will address the issue of intersectionality.

Possible solutions

- Create measures to deal with intersectionality issues and at the same time take advantage of governmental measures, such as Law 3896/2010.
- Strengthen the Liaison-Student Services Office activities and disseminate them further.
- Stronger dissemination among the students, as students tend to be harder among students.
- Improve the data collection process and start collecting data regarding intersectionality by all members of the School.
- Develop guidelines as regards the provision of certain facilities to people with disabilities.
- Improve and adjust the existing facilities.
- Receive external contribution by civil society, non-profit organizations.
- Organise trainings and information days within the School.
- Organise teams of volunteers (student members and a faculty member as supervisor) and assign

them a category of intersectionality to address.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first from internal stakeholders. Resistances are expected by the high level and middle level management that they might feel that such measures are too much and by the high level and middle level management and by researchers reacting to the attendance in workshops and information days, due to their heavy schedule. It is also expected by the high-level management as there is lack of financial resources to improve the existing facilities, intersectionality might not come as a priority. Finally, resistances are expected by the administrative personnel being unwilling to undertake the workload that might come with the extra data collection and/or guidelines on the providing facilities and by students being indifferent to the issue of intersectionality. Secondly, from external stakeholders, resistances are by members of the extreme right parties (civil society) that do not recognize the issue of intersectionality.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first argumentative like to communicate the importance of addressing the issue of intersectionality and to involve as many members of the School as possible in the measures design. Secondly, strategies could touch the rules of the organization such as involving the high-level management to suggest the implementation of more targeted data collection, involving the high level management to provide incentives for the extra workload and the participation in trainings and information days and involving the high level management to provide a small percent of the annual budget for repairing and improving the existing facilities. Other actions could be the implementation of dissemination and information activities.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from different areas. First, it should be coming from the rules or structure of the organization: Law 3896/ 2010 (Official Government Gazette, 2010) includes a specific article dedicated to the principle of equal treatment and the prohibition of discrimination which can be the basis for all the possible activities and solutions. Next, it should be coming from the administration like to use the already developed knowledge on data collection in order to expand it in ways to include data on intersectionality and strengthen the existing cooperation with the Liaison – Student services Office. Then, other expected opportunities are coming from high management, the current high level management is already trying to maintain the current facilities at their best conditions. Finally, opportunities are expected to come from researchers and students such as promoting a stronger dissemination/communication on the matter.

Sexism and sexual harassment

Situation

There are no formal bodies or mechanisms dealing with sexual harassment or gender violence issues in ECE - NTUA. Complaints are usually communicated to the Dean's office, where they are handled directly. At an Institutional level the Liaison-Student services Office offers psychological and psychiatric support to all the enrolled students and sometimes to employees, since there is no specific counselling service for persons involved in, or victimised by gender violence / sexual harassment. However, this support does not take preventive actions or initiate any other processes.

However, 10.6% of the survey respondents claimed that they have experienced sexual harassment, while 3.5% did not wish to respond. The ones that answered yes, also responded that they did not disclose it to the competent authority within the university. They also clarified that there is no such authority to go to or that they were afraid of the stigma. Others described that they were sure that they wouldn't find a solution to the issue, so they dropped it, or they dealt with it alone. 21.6% have witnessed sexual harassment, and 78.4% have not. From the ones that did see such an event, 74.4% did not take any further action, while 25.6% reported it themselves or encouraged the victim to do so. Regarding the question of whether there is counselling on gender-based offences, the 84.8% does not know whether such a service

exists, and 15.2% knows that it does not exist. Regarding whether the responders themselves have used the counselling service, in case they know it 97.8%, said no, and 2.2% that they do not want to answer.

Main problems

The fact that there are no formal bodies or mechanism dealing with sexual harassment or gender violence issues creates an insecure environment. Without any policies or initiatives aiming at addressing sexual harassment students and employees are not aware of how to handle any possible case of discriminatory treatment. Furthermore, there is no specific counselling service. Finally, another issue is that whoever wants to report any complaint, he/she might hesitate because of the fear of the stigma.

Objective(s)

The establishment of an official body/mechanism to handle gender violent/sexual harassment issues (maybe also within the framework of the mechanism for sexist behavior and bias in teaching, research etc mentioned earlier) and provide specific counselling service (psychological and psychiatric support). Rather important is that this formal mechanism should guarantee the appropriate confidentiality and handle the fear of stigma.

Possible solutions

- Development of a structured mechanism (committee and/or complaint desk) to address issues of sexual harassment and sexism (maybe in combination with the mechanism on gender bias in teaching and in communication).
- Establishment of a complaint box or an anonymous reporting procedure for sexual harassment and sexism incidents.
- Increase awareness on sexual harassment and sexism through information days and workshops.
- Provide more information on the issue in order to eliminate the fear of stigma.

Resistances

The expected resistances are from internal stakeholders and more precisely from the high level management and middle level management claiming that no such issues exist in the School. No resistances coming from external stakeholders have been identified.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative such as providing data on the number of people that have experienced and/or have witnessed sexual harassment and sexism, to communicate the importance of dealing with the issue for the establishment of a stable working and studying environment for all and to involve all members of the School in the development of the mechanism. Other strategies touch the rules of the organization like involving the high level management to provide incentives for the implementation of workshops and information days. Other strategies are communication and dissemination activities.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from different areas. First, it is coming from the rules or structure of the organization, NTUA has to take advantage of Law 3896/2010 which addresses the issue of sexual/gender harassment in the workplace and use it as a basis for the possible activities and take advantage of the Greek Strategy for Gender Equality 2016-2020, which further promotes activities regarding the information and sensitization of the academic and research society on issues like gender inequalities, violence, harassment, sexism, and stereotypes and use it as a starting point for the implemented activities. Next, opportunities are expected coming from the administration such as strengthening the existing cooperation with the Liaison-Career Office, initiating respective procedures for intervention, charges and/or punishment. There are also opportunities coming from high management, as the high-level management is the one dealing with incidents of sexual harassment they already have the

necessary sensitization that these matters need. Finally, opportunities could come from researchers and students such as the cooperation among students, development of confident relations.

Sythesis of stakeholders to involve

Stakeholders to involve in strategies are, on the one hand, internal stakeholders who have the power to decide to change the organizational rules/to accept the proposed strategy (high level management), as well as the ones who will implement the strategy (administration, researchers, academics) and the ones who will be impacted by the strategy (positively or negatively) (researchers, academic personnel, administration). On the other hand, external stakeholders that should be involved in strategies come from different environments: the academia, researchers from other universities, academics from other universities; the civil society such as societies that support women engineers (e.g. EDEM, ELEGYP, WYCA of Greece), civil society groups active on gender equality and gender sensitization and from the government/public sector such as the National Centre for Public Administration and Local Government and the private and industrial sector. The Ministry of Education and Religious Affairs can also be implicated in some actions.

In order to ensure stakeholders' collaboration several actions can be carried out: presentation of other institutions' experiences, discussion of best practices from other universities, organization of information days by members of the R&I Hub, with more expertise in the gender equality area, the organization of joint events regarding the importance of gender-neutral behavior in the working environment, training programmes on gender equality issues, further networking and collaboration, organization of joint events regarding the importance of an appraisal system in terms of equality, to communicate and explain the importance of data collection in the change process, cooperation with the private sector for the provision of incentives (financial or other) for the integration of gender into research, the implementation of common (joint) research papers with other Universities, networking and collaboration about the strategy on how to attract more girls in school, communication and dissemination activities with other academic institutions so as to eliminate the "stigma" of cooperation with the private sector, to provide guidance on the implementation of Laws and the Greek Strategy for Gender Equality 2016-2020, the creation of a structured mechanism addressing issues of sexual harassment. Collaborative actions with schools can also be very positive.

2.6 Institute for Research in Biomedicine¹¹ (RPO)

Human resources

Scenario 1: High resistance

Work Life Balance (WLB)

Situation

Although there are some WLB measures in place, there is room for improvement. In addition, the existing WLB measures can be better communicated to the employees.

Main problems

Not a complete knowledge within the members of the IRB, in regard to these policies.

Ojective(s)

¹¹ IRB initially organized its scenarios not by topic but by the level of difficulty of the actions. The structure of the report has been slightly modified to adapt it to the standard structure of the deliverable. This is the reason why, for some topics, there are not three scenarios: for some areas IRB did not identify 'maximal resistance' or 'low resistance' to the possible solutions.

Improve the WLB measures in place. It is extremely important that the rules are flexible, thus covering the needs of all the units in the Institute (scientific, core facilities, admin).

Possible solutions

- Information and Communication campaigns to improve well-being within the members of the IRB.
- To introduce new WLB measures.

Resistances

Resistances could come from internal stakeholders. Some WLB measures can be perceived as hard to manage due to the high demand that excellent scientific work needs. No resistances have been identified from external stakeholders.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative such as broadening scope of existing and new WLB measures.

Stakeholders to involve in strategies (through collaboration/information/argumentation etc.) are internal stakeholders. First, the one who have the power to decide to change the organizational rules/to accept the proposed strategy: HR, high Management. Next, the one who will implement the strategy: HR. Finally, the one who will be impacted by the strategy (positively or negatively): IRB community. No external stakeholders have been identified to be involved.

Scenario 2: Low resistance

Recruitment procedures

Situation

Measures, policies and protocols are not well known among the scientific community.

Main problems are

Lack of knowledge of existing recruitment documentation within the members of the IRB Barcelona.

Objective(s)

Broadening the knowledge of recruitment measures, policies and protocols for all the IRB Barcelona community.

Possible actions

- Creation of recruitment checklist/guideline every time a position is opened. These checklist/guidelines should be shared with Hiring Managers and whoever is involved in the process. It is important to take into consideration that throughout the recruitment process Hiring Manager have the responsibility to be aware of the measures.
- Expand information in the IRB Barcelona intranet and other internal outlets (give a better visibility)
- Express certain documents as “compulsory/mandatory” to read when sent to Hiring Managers. This will get a better attention of existing procedures.
- Highlight some of the measure and existing documentation in Job adverts

Opportunities

The expected opportunities could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization such as defined recruitment policy in place and coming from the administration and middle management like the involvement in the process to better understand and communicate recruitment process.

Stakeholders to involve in strategies (through collaboration/information/argumentation etc.) are internal stakeholders such as human resources staff commitment, lab managers, programme secretaries, project managers and ATS (Applicant Tracking System) software. No external stakeholders have been identified to

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be involved.

Actions to be taken to ensure stakeholders' collaboration (both internal and external) are argumentative action such as creating awareness of existing measures in the Institute.

Even tough implementations to actions in this point have minimal resistances, some resistances might appear such as time that plays an important resistance. A sense of urge comes in when a position is opened. There is also a Lack of awareness and recruitment policies may be considered as a process only related to Administration.

Career Progression

Situation

In terms of career progression, no gender-sensitive protocols are in place at IRB Barcelona

Main problems

The perception that gender is not taken into consideration in career progression.

Objective(s)

To give a gender-sensitive approach upcoming protocols

Possible actions

- Create training sessions and seminars on career progression and leadership for women

Opportunities

Generate awareness in gender sensitive topics in regards career progression at all levels.

Stakeholders to involve in strategies (through collaboration/information/argumentation etc.) are internal stakeholders such as human Resources staff commitment, lab Managers, programme Secretaries and project Managers. No external stakeholders have been identified to be involved.

Actions to be taken to ensure stakeholders' collaboration (both internal and external) are argumentative action like to give a gender-sensitive approach the career progression process.

Situation

Training/mentoring for leadership skills can be improved to foster career progression.

Main problems

It is unclear if the existing set of training activities (related to leadership) are enough.

Objective(s)

To offer a robust set of training sessions related to leadership skills to female scientist

Possible solutions

- Offer training sessions and seminars on career development and leadership for women
- Reinforce existing mentoring programs

Opportunities

The expected opportunities could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization, administration, management, there is already an existing mentoring programme. It could also be coming from researchers, students, participants: possibility of getting feedback on how to develop better topics according to specific needs.

Stakeholders to involve in strategies (through collaboration/information/argumentation etc.) are first internal stakeholders. There are the one who have the power to decide to change the organizational

rules/to accept the proposed strategy: high and middle management. There are also the one who will be impacted by the strategy (positively or negatively): The institute's community, especially women at all levels. Secondly, external stakeholders to be involved are possible mentors that are invited to the training programs.

Actions to be taken to ensure stakeholders' collaboration (both internal and external) are argumentative action such as to encourage the existence of professional development programs.

Work-Life Balance

Situation

Not all of the work- life balance legal measures are well known by the IRB Community.

Example: 72% of the survey participants claims not to know clearly about Leaves (Maternity paternity, adoption, parental/family)

Main problems

Lack of knowledge within the members of the IRB, especially since the measures do exist, and are complying with national law.

Objective(s)

Developing mechanism to expand the knowledge of the existing policies and create awareness in this topic.

Possible solutions

- Communication campaigns
- Involving internal stakeholders raising awareness on this topic.
- Give visibility on the intranet (policies, procedures)
- Highlight WLB measure in the recruitment and onboarding sessions.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from internal stakeholders such as the administration, more precisely the communications department: recommendation/tools on how to give better exposure to information.

Stakeholders to involve in strategies (through collaboration/information/argumentation etc.) are internal stakeholders. First, there are the one who have the power to decide to change the organizational rules/to accept the proposed strategy: HR and high management. Next, the one who will implement the strategy: HR. Finally, the one who will be impacted by the strategy (positively or negatively): IRB community. No external stakeholders have been identified to be involved.

Actions to be taken to ensure stakeholders' collaboration (both internal and external) are argumentative action like ensuring that all the community understands the existence of WLB measures and information actions such as communication campaigns.

Scenario 3: intermediate resistance

Recruitment procedures

Situation

A dedicated gender sensitive recruitment protocol is not in place.

Main problems

Lack of knowledge within the members of the IRB of the general recruitment process

Objective(s)

Ensure that the all the recruitment processes are not biased and that a gender sensitive scope is included in the process.

Possible actions

- Elaborate a gender general sensitive recruitment protocol
- Communicate the existence of a new protocol.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first coming from internal stakeholders. There is a lack of general awareness in bias (at all levels). Next, time plays an important resistance. A sense of urge comes in when a position is opened. Resistances could come from the administration, middle management, high management, and researchers. No resistances coming from external stakeholders have been identified.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative such as to try to assure that recruitment processes are not biased and creating awareness that an effort is being done in this matter

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from internal stakeholders such as creating awareness trough involvement. No opportunities have been identified coming from external stakeholders.

Stakeholders to involve relying on the opportunities (through collaboration/information/argumentation etc.) are internal stakeholders such as human resources staff commitment, lab Managers, programme Secretaries and project Managers. No external stakeholders have been identified to be involved.

Actions to be taken to ensure stakeholders' collaboration are argumentative action: try to assure that recruitment processes are not biased and creating awarness that an effort is beign done in this matter.

Career Progression**Situation**

In terms of career progression, no gender-sensitive protocols are in place at IRB Barcelona.

Main problems

The perception that gender is not taken into consideration in career progression.

Objective(s)

To give a gender-sensitive approach upcoming protocols.

Possible actions

- Creating a guideline or checklist would be proper way to create gender sensitive documentation in career progression.

Resistances

Expected resistances are coming from internal stakeholders. They are Coming from the rules or structure of the organization: How to develop and apply a gender perspective career progression considering that most part of the IRB positions (PhD Students and young postdocs) leave the institute "naturally" (after completion of their "IRB period") and do not expect any career progression at IRB.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative like to provide a gender-sensitive to career progression.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from the administration: HR department guiding the process with

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the support of the Equality and Diversity Committee

Governance

Scenario 1: High resistance

Situation

Under-representation of female participants in the IRB decision-making bodies

Main problems

Women are under-represented in some decision-making bodies of the IRB

Objective(s)

To increase the participation of women in the decision-making committees/bodies

Possible solutions

Consider implementing changes in the existing criteria for accessing such positions (Extreme/severe resistance)

Resistances

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative such as increasing the participation of women in the decision-making committees/bodies.

Stakeholders to involve in strategies (through collaboration/information/argumentation etc.) are first internal stakeholders. There are the one who have the power to decide to change the organizational rules/to accept the proposed strategy: High management. There are also the one who will be impacted by the strategy (positively or negatively): IRB community, especially women. Secondly, there are the external stakeholders. The composition of several governing bodies (including the Board of Trustees, the External Advisory Board, and the Business Advisory Board) is regulated by IRB Barcelona statutes. The members of these bodies are decided by external founding.

Scenario 2: Low resistance

Situation

Under-representation of female participants in the IRB decision-making bodies

Main problems

Women are under represented in some decision making bodies of the IRB

Objective(s)

To increase the participation of women in the decision-making committees/bodies

Possible actions

- To recruit women group leaders in the following years following the gender sensitive protocol of recruitment that was set up in 2020, in order to increase “the size of the pool”. Minimum resistance to apply this possible solution, although PI positions are not regularly open.

Opportunities

There are expected opportunities from internal stakeholders coming from the rules or structure of the organization like to recruit women group leaders in the following years

No stakeholders to involve in strategies (through collaboration/information/argumentation etc.) have been identified.

Actions to be taken to ensure stakeholders’ collaboration (both internal and external) are argumentative

action like leveling up the Under-representation of female participants in the IRB decision-making bodies.

Scenario 3: intermediate resistance

Situation

Under-representation of female participants in the IRB decision-making bodies

Main problems

Women are under represented in some decision making bodies of the IRB.

Objective(s)

To increase the participation of women in the decision-making committees/bodies

Possible solutions

- Raise awareness of this issue among men occupying leadership positions at the institution.

Resistances

Expected resistances have been identified. There is the resistance to change from internal stakeholder's resistance to change coming from the rules or structure of the organization and coming from high management

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative such as leveling up the Under-representation of female participants in the IRB decision-making bodies

The expected opportunities are from internal stakeholders: involvement and raising awareness coming from the administration, coming from middle management, coming from high management and coming from researchers.

Research

Scenario 1: High resistance

Main problems

Lack of awareness/knowledge within the members of the IRB of what integration of the gender analysis into research is.

Objective(s)

The objectives that have been identified are first to offer training sessions on the integration of the gender dimension into research and second to develop a toolkit/guideline on the integration of the gender dimension into research.

Possible actions

- Raising awareness campaigns to reinforce the knowledge of the topic and its importance
- Creation of an "Integration on the gender dimension into research & innovation" working group, involving members of the Equality and Diversity Committee + researchers.

Resistances

There are expected resistance first coming from internal stakeholders such at resources-related resistances like involving female + male experimental animals in the studies from the very beginning is more expensive and time consuming than including only one sex. It may also be difficult making sure that the internal research staff is trained and makes use of toolkits/checklists or gets support in doing. Finally, there may be resistance to change. Secondly there might be resistance from external stakeholders because the gender dimension has not been considered until now, therefore there is a massive number of scientific articles that did not consider this topic.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative such as raising awareness campaigns + Creation of an “Integration on the gender dimension into research & innovation” working group

Stakeholders to involve in strategies (through collaboration/information/argumentation etc.) are first funding entities (even the prestigious ERC) that are including the importance of the gender dimension into research content in their agendas. The inclusion of the gender dimension into research content is specifically requested in the proposal template of some calls for proposals and it is considered in the evaluation. Next, some scientific journals ask for the sex dimension in the mice studies and/or request the author(s) to endorse a “Diversity Statement”. Finally, interesting and robust resources on the integration of the gender dimension into research & innovation content publicly available.

Scenario 2: Low resistance

Main problems

Lack of awareness/knowledge within the members of the IRB of what integration of the gender analysis into research is.

Objective(s)

The objectives that have been identified are first to offer training sessions on the integration of the gender dimension into research and second to develop a toolkit/guideline on the integration of the gender dimension into research.

Possible solutions

- Raising awareness campaigns to reinforce the knowledge of the topic and its importance
- Elaboration of an intuitive-friendly toolkit on how to integrate the gender dimension into research & innovation and disseminate it among the researchers

Opportunities

The main expected opportunity is raising awareness of the gender analysis into research coming from middle and high management, coming from researchers and coming from students.

Stakeholders to involve in strategies (through collaboration/information/argumentation etc.) are internal stakeholders. First, the one who have the power to decide to change the organizational rules/to accept the proposed strategy: High Management. Next, there are the one who will implement the strategy: Scientific units. Finally, there are the one who will be impacted by the strategy (positively or negatively): IRB researchers. No external stakeholders have been identified to be involved.

Actions to be taken to ensure stakeholders’ collaboration (both internal and external) are argumentative action like raising awareness.

Scenario 3: intermediate resistance

There is no intermediate-resistance scenario for the topic Research.

Teaching

See section ‘Students and services to students’ below.

Students and services to students

Scenario 1: High resistance

There is no high-resistance scenario for the topic Students.

Scenario 2: Low resistance

Situation

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

HR department is in charge of imparting an induction programme to explain to new employees the rules, regulation, committees and protocols, among others, the ECD Committee and Health & Safety protocol

Objective(s)

The situation can be used to implement a more gender sensitive approach to the onboarding process.

Possible solutions

- Reinforce communication and information channels with human resources and other stakeholders involved.
- Establish secondary onboard session or a QA channel with new comers

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from students: A broader perspective from the Institutes rules, regulation, committees and protocols, among others. Additionally, feedback sessions from the students can result in better knowledge of what they expect from an onboarding session.

Stakeholders to involve in strategies (through collaboration/information/argumentation etc.) are internal stakeholders: the HR and internal stakeholders (newcomers). No external stakeholders have been identified to be involved.

Actions to be taken to ensure stakeholders' collaboration (both internal and external) are argumentative action like providing a broad perspective from the Institutes rules, regulation, committees and protocols, among others Organizational change actions and information actions such as onboarding sessions.

Even though this action has "minimal resistances" to implement, some resistances may come up such as overloading information on newcomers and, if a basic gender equality information /training is delivered in the induction courses, it can loss specificity and be perceived as "just one thing more".

Scenario 3: intermediate resistance

There is no intermediate-resistance scenario for the topic Students.

Transfer to Market

Scenario 1: High resistance

Situation

Lack of awareness/knowledge within the members of the IRB of what integration of the gender analysis into innovation is.

Objective(s)

The objectives that have been identified are first to offer training sessions on the integration of the gender dimension into research. Secondly, there is the objective to develop a toolkit/guideline on the integration of the gender dimension into research. The last one is to develop gender sensitive product design, patenting, female led spin outs, etc.

Possible solutions

- Raising awareness campaigns to reinforce the knowledge of the topic and its importance.
- Elaboration of an intuitive-friendly toolkit on how to integrate the gender dimension into research & innovation and disseminate it among the researchers.
- Creation of an "Integration on the gender dimension into research & innovation" working group, involving members of the EDC + researchers.

Resistances

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

There are expected resistance from internal stakeholders such as resistance to change and making sure that the internal research staff is trained and makes use of toolkits/checklists or gets support in doing it may be difficult.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative like including gender dimension into innovation.

Stakeholders to involve in strategies (through collaboration/information/argumentation etc.) are funding entities (even the prestigious ERC) that are including the importance of the gender dimension into research content in their agendas. The inclusion of the gender dimension into research content is specifically requested in the proposal template of some calls for proposals and it is considered in the evaluation. Some scientific journals that ask for the sex dimension in the mice studies and/or request the author(s) to endorse a “Diversity Statement”. Interesting and robust resources on the integration of the gender dimension into research & innovation content publicly available.

Scenario 2: low resistance

There is no low-resistance scenario for the topic Transfer to market.

Scenario 3: intermediate resistance

Situation

There is no concrete system to keep track of the participation/results of women in transfer to market

Main problems

Sex-disaggregated data collection not implemented on the innovation results.

Objective(s)

To have a method/procedure for the collection of disaggregated data. This may show how the participation/involvement of women in innovation results is.

Possible solutions

- Put in place a method/procedure to keep track of the participation of women in transfer to market/innovation (Data collection).

Resistances

Expected resistances have been identified from internal stakeholders. There is not a current system dedicated to this use.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative: Keep control a the results of Transfer to Market/innovation in order identify inequalities

The expected opportunities are first from internal stakeholders such as to use data to detect possible scenarios that can be optimize and have control of the evolution of the innovation results. The innovation department is happy to collaborate. Secondly, some resistances are expected from external stakeholders like to understand if a solution has been put in place from Institutes with similar structure to the IRB.

Communication

Scenario 1: High resistance

There is no high-resistance scenario for the topic Communication.

Scenario 2: Low resistance

Situation

There are no defined policies or guidelines that take into consideration gender sensitive communications

(internal and external).

Main problems

There are no defined policies or guidelines that take into consideration gender sensitive communications (internal and external).

Objective(s)

To achieve a gender sensitive and inclusive use of communication tools (language, images).

Possible solutions

- Provide training to the Communications Dept staff on inclusive and gender sensitive language.
- Raise awareness on inclusive and gender sensitive language.
- To build some general guidelines/toolkit and disseminate them through all the IRB Community

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from the administration, middle management and high management such as the willingness to collaborate and implement change.

Stakeholders to involve in strategies (through collaboration/information/argumentation etc.) are first internal stakeholders: the communications department and the whole IRB community. Secondly, there are external stakeholders like the input/feedback from stakeholders with strong expertise on the subject that will be useful.

Actions to be taken to ensure stakeholders' collaboration (both internal and external) are argumentative action such as the consideration of gender sensitive communications (internal/external).

Scenario 3: Intermediate resistance

There is no intermediate-resistance scenario for the topic Communication.

Intersectionality

Scenario 1: High resistance

There is no high-resistance scenario for the topic Intersectionality.

Scenario 2: Low resistance

Situation

Inside the IRB and through the actions of the Equality and Diversity Committee, the scope of equality has been evolving to a broader vision in which intersectionality is considered as a way of taking into account other aspects that influence gender equality.

Main problems

- The HR/ECD staff is still not skilled enough on intersectionality.
 - Intersectionality is still not integrated in the data collection process. "Intersectionality" as a topic is not well known in the IRB community

Objective(s)

The main objective is to give a broader approach to intersectionality expanding the equality scope to a more than a binary approach

Possible solutions

- Provide training to the HR/EDC members on intersectionality/diversity

- Raising awareness campaign on intersectionality.

Opportunities

There are expected opportunities that could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization like the involvement of the Equality and Diversity Committee. It could also be coming from the administration such as collaboration on awareness campaigns from internal stakeholders, HR and communications department. Finally, opportunities could come from high management like the involvement of Group Leaders that show interest in the intersectionality topic.

Actions to be taken to ensure stakeholders' collaboration (both internal and external) are argumentative actions such as including intersectionality as a topic in the Institute.

Scenario 3: Intermediate resistance

Situation

Inside the IRB and through the actions of the Equality and Diversity Committee, the scope of equality has been evolving to a broader vision in which intersectionality is considered as a way of taking into account other aspects that influence gender equality.

Main problems

The main problems are:

- The HR/ECD staff is still not skilled enough on intersectionality.
- Intersectionality is not still integrated in the data collection process "Intersectionality" as a topic is not well known in the IRB community.

Objective(s)

Give a broader approach to intersectionality expanding the equality scope to a more than a binary approach.

Possible solutions

- Improve data collection systems.
- Increase awareness among the IRB staff.
- Embed diversity in the institutional communications (including imagery)

Resistances

Expected resistances have been identified coming from internal stakeholders. They are expected to be coming from the rules or structure of the organization. The resistances are that the current databases of the IRB are not designed to take intersectionality into account, data collection may lead to LOPD issues and to Identify/prioritise the fields to be tracked to better address intersectionality may be difficult.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first from internal stakeholders. They are coming from the rules or structure of the organization such as the involvement of the Equality and Diversity Committee. Opportunities could be coming from the administration like collaboration on awareness campaigns from internal stakeholders (HR and communications department). Finally, they could be coming from high management such as involvement of Group Leaders that show interest in the intersectionality topic. Secondly, opportunities are accepted coming from external stakeholders such as learning from best practices and methods to include intersectionality into the equality scope.

Stakeholders to involve to rely on the opportunities (through collaboration/information/argumentation etc.) are internal stakeholders: the Equality and Diversity Committee, HR and the IRB community. Actions to

be taken to ensure stakeholders' collaboration are argumentative action such as including intersectionality as a topic in the Institute.

Sexism and sexual harassment

Scenario 1: High resistance

There is no high-resistance scenario for the topic Sexism and sexual harassment.

Scenario 2: Low resistance

Situation

Even though the Institute has a policy/protocol on this matter, some employees are not clear on the measures and support given in case a situation of harassment occurs

Main problems

Employees are not clear on which support is given to within harassment situations.

Objective(s)

The objectives that have been identified are first to raise awareness on the issue of sexual harassment in the workplace and second, to improve the knowledge of the IRB staff about the existing protocol and the mechanisms in place.

Possible solutions

- Communication campaigns of the existing protocols.
- Specific training addressed to Managers, HR and EDC staff.
- Raising awareness campaigns on sexual harassment with a focus on prevention.
- Aligning strategies with other research centers (CERCA) and using awareness material such as video/printed material.

Opportunities

Collaboration in implementing actions special coming from Equality and Diversity Committee, Human Resources department and the Institutes Directorate.

Stakeholders to involve in strategies (through collaboration/information/argumentation etc.) are first internal stakeholders: HR, EDC, IRB Directorate and the IRB community. Secondly, there are external stakeholders to be involved: tools from other research centers may be implemented as well, such as videos and printed material. Actions to be taken to ensure stakeholders' collaboration (both internal and external) are argumentative action: to raise awareness on the issue of sexual harassment in the workplace.

Scenario 3: Intermediate resistance

There is no intermediate-resistance scenario for the topic Sexism and sexual harassment.

2.7 Executive Unit for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding in Romania (RFO)

Human resources

1. Gender sensitive protocols/policies for recruitment and hiring

Situation

The investigation on the existence of gender sensitive recruitment protocols/policies in UEFISCDI, highlighted that most employees are not aware of them. Most employees in the organization are women,

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therefore there is no discrimination based on gender when recruiting employees. However, when asked, out of 21 respondents, only 6 were aware that there are specific gender recruitment policies/protocols (11 answered “NO” and 4 answered “It depends”). However, the institution has in place a procedure that states that all selection activities take into account the non-discrimination principle (the selection process will not allow / encourage discrimination of sex, nationality, ethnicity or religion). The problem seems to be that there is a lack of information on sensitive gender recruitment policies. We believe that the obstacle might be an inefficient communication between the HR and Communication departments, as there are no specific strategies regarding these protocols.

Main problems

The main problem is that the employees are not aware that there are gender sensitive recruitment protocols/policies.

Objective(s)

The goal is to make the gender sensitive recruitment protocols/policies more visible through communication.

Possible solutions

- A possible solution to achieve this goal could be to better communicate the existing recruitment policies regarding gender sensitive protocols and to develop trainings regarding gender discrimination and stereotypes identification for the hiring and evaluation committees prior to the evaluation of the candidates.

Resistances

The expected resistances are coming from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from the structure of the organization: the communication team could be convinced about the importance of clearly communicating the gender sensitive recruitment protocols; benefits for all employees, including them. They might object to additional workload, their resistance being passive and not related to gender specific, individual and personal.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative such as to enhance the importance of the subject, to explain to the communication team the lack of knowledge from the employees' side and gain their support in developing a better understanding of the subject for all employees. Other actions that could be taken could be to organize workshops and presentation on gender discrimination, present case studies, and send articles to be published in the internal newsletter.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization, other staff from the communication department that understands the need to emphasize gender sensitive recruitment protocols. They could also be coming from middle management, gain the support of women with attributions in middle management. Secondly, opportunities could come from external stakeholders. They could be coming from civil society such as NGO's with experience in gender sensitive issues and discrimination that can highlight the existing bad practices.

2. Career progression

Situation

There is no specific legislation in place regarding the implementation of quotas or targets for promoting the underrepresented gender in management positions and committees (For example, before elections, usually there are some discussions about the topic, like in the electoral legislation for Parliament in, when there was a provision which stated that political parties were not allowed to have only one gender representative on their lists. However, there were parties running only with men for Parliament).

Main problems

The main problem is that there are no national policies on implementation of quotas or targets for promoting the underrepresented gender in management positions and committees.

Objective(s)

The objective is to propose to the UEFISCDI's top management to implement targets/quotas regarding balanced gender representation in management chain.

Possible solutions

Possible solutions could be to adopt specific targets/quotas regarding the balanced gender representation in internal management chain.

Resistances

The expected resistances could come from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from the top and middle management, the gender balance is currently in favor of women so it might be difficult to adopt specific targets and quotas seeing that the number of men employees is smaller than the number of female employees. There is no legislative framework to help implement such quotas; therefore it could be very difficult to make the desired institutional change.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative such as to explain reasons in the proposal. For instance, the EC new Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025 includes finalizing the legislative process for finally (after 9 years) approving the directive on gender quotas in the boards of companies (both private and public). It shows that the issue is controversial, but there is renewed and explicit consensus from EC, which is promising.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities could be coming from external stakeholders. They could be coming from the academia, women in top management in RPOs and HEIs. Opportunities could also be coming from civil society, NGO's for gender equality. To finish, some others could be coming from industries/business stakeholders, media, and women in top management in business.

3. Work environments and working conditions

Situation

Work-life balance has not been a priority area for national policy makers, even if such measures and interventions are widely acknowledged as vital for gender equality and women's empowerment. For maternity/paternity leave, UEFISCDI is acting in line with the legislation and respects the decisions of the parents related to the period chosen for maternity leave (maximum 2 years). During the interviews, employees mentioned that at internal level, staff acts according to the collegiality principle which allows people to take the time to solve their problems when this is the case. People benefit from their legal leaves. The hours of working are respected as well as the official holidays. There is an internal habit to have a short day on 1st or/an 8th of March, when Spring Day and Women Day are celebrated. Also, it was mentioned that employees do not experience the fear that leave (annual leave or without payment leave) will not be approved. Regarding the projects, the work is more flexible, and people can make the schedule according to the tasks and the working hours of foreign partners.

Main problems

Despite the fact that the measures described above are known to the employees, there is a lack of internal procedures & internal communication that would help them equally benefit from these opportunities (for ex: reduction and/or flexible hours to care for family dependents, etc).

Objective(s)

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Harmonize the internal procedures and practices across the different departments and ensure equal access to them for the employees (Reduction and/or flexible hours for other family dependents' care - elderly, other; reduction and/or flexible hours for other reasons (e.g for final exams, measures to support victims of gender-based violence).

Possible solutions

- To create an internal procedure regarding the above-mentioned measures
- To increase the communication efforts
- To better explain to the employees their choices/opportunities for such situations and at the same time, convince the middle management about the importance of having a flexible mindset.

Resistances

The expected resistances are from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from the organizational structure: internal procedures are being developed; however they lack specificity and allow head of departments to apply them discretionary.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative such as having a more coherent communication flow between the HR department and the rest of the employees regarding their benefits. Equal opportunities decrease chances that some employees might feel discriminated. Other actions could be learning from researches and studies done by other organizations/countries.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first coming from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization, female in top and in middle management. Other opportunities could be coming from middle management, head of departments. Opportunities could secondly be coming from external stakeholders. Some could be coming from the academia, researchers involved in gender and work-life balance studies, other could come from civil society, NGOs and to finish, opportunities could be coming from industries/business stakeholders such as professional psychologists, therapists, mentors, family counsellors and media.

Governance

1. Mentoring for women or the under-represented gender in leadership position

Situation

At institutional level there are not mentoring programs, but all the employees can access all the trainings held at internal level or different training opportunities from partners or external collaborators. There is a lack of mentoring programs for both sexes due to the Romanian organizational culture that exists in public administration. Sometimes leadership programs are organized, but they are not focused on gender equality. Both sexes are targeted equally.

Main problems

The institution has a lack of mentoring programs.

Objective(s)

The objective is to organize mentoring programs dedicated to women or the under-represented gender.

Possible solutions

- The initiation of a mentoring program

Resistances

The expected resistances are coming from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from middle and

top management: the program is taken into consideration and subjected to further debate. Resistance is passive and implicit, but non-gender specific. It, most likely, will be individual and personal.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative; there are present benefits of the mentoring programs and to show examples of good practices in other countries.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first coming from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from middle and high management, more precisely, women in middle and high management. Secondly, opportunities could be coming from external stakeholders. They could be coming from civil society such as NGOs and women associations.

2. Gender Equality Body

Situation

At UEFISCDI, there is no formal Gender Equality Plan. Until CALIPER project there are no data related to training activities on gender issues. During the internal interviews, 16 out of 21 respondents did not know whether a gender equality plan was established or not; 5 out of 21 respondents negated its existence, and only 2 persons knew about its existence and were well informed about it. Common belief was that there was never the need to develop such a document because the employees are mostly women, the recruitment criteria are transparent and take into account non-discrimination based on gender, age, etc.

Main problems

The main problem is that each institution should have a Gender Equality Plan that states rules and regulations needed to be followed so that gender discrimination is avoided and a gender equal/gender sensitive working environment is promoted

Objective(s)

The goal is to develop a Gender Equality Body that will take the necessary actions to prepare, develop and implement GEP also after the project's conclusion.

Possible solutions

- To take the necessary internal actions that lead to the establishment of the GEP Body (these internal actions include discussions where to best place it in the organizational chart, what skills/profiles are needed, other operational issues, what resources are needed and available).

Resistances

The expected resistances are coming from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from high and middle management, there is a lack of interest or available time from the top's and middle's management to be part of this body.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative like to explain the benefits of developing such a body; have one-to-one meetings with top & middle management representatives and convince them about the importance of this structure.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first coming from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization: HR and Legal department (they understand better the importance of developing the body). Secondly, some opportunities are expected coming from external stakeholders. Some could come from the academia like learning from similar initiatives taken by other institutions. Others could be coming from civil society such as NGOs and, to finish, some could be coming from industries/business stakeholders, also learning from similar initiatives taken by other institutions.

Research

1. Research funding

Situation

UEFISCDI manages 20% of the national funds for research. The texts of the calls are approved by the executive public administration bodies (ministries) and they are standard texts (UEFISCDI cannot make updates or amendments to them during implementation). Sometimes, upon request, UEFISCDI can make recommendations on specific subjects. So, gender equality is promoted as a funding requirement, but it is not mandatory. There is a recommendation in place to assure gender balance teams in projects, but this is the task of the project manager.

Main problems

When employing evaluators, UEFISCDI cannot make gender mandatory criteria. Moreover, it is not possible to introduce gender quotas and targets in evaluation procedures because in Romania, the number of female evaluators is smaller than the number of male evaluators. The process of becoming an evaluator is conducted by a special structure in the executive public administration bodies (e.g. special department in the Research and Innovation ministry). UEFISCDI has a large database of evaluators (Romanian and foreign) which is used when implementing various projects. The database (BrainMap.ro) contains all the evaluators that took part in UEFISCDI's projects and is divided in various categories, depending on age, gender, expertise, field of actions, etc.

In the next period, however, gender balance will play a more important role in development, implementation and evaluation of the projects (according to European Commission Gender Equality Strategy for 2020-2025 and ERA priorities).

Objective(s)

The goal is to raise awareness on the topic of gender balance as future criteria to be included in call texts and research content it would also be beneficial to adjust the evaluation procedures and determine if gender balance can become mandatory criteria in projects evaluation as well.

Possible solutions

- Possible solutions could be to write a policy paper / recommendation in which to explain to the executive public administration bodies the importance of including gender balance in the information package of call texts, of the research content and in the evaluation procedures (where possible).
- Complementary, another solution could be to conduct an analysis among evaluators data base and investigate the domains where female evaluators are underrepresented (find out possible causes, identify possible solutions). Explore how women researchers could be encouraged/motivated to apply for becoming evaluators.

Resistances

The expected resistances are coming from external stakeholders. They could be coming from the academia such as a lack of interest in the gender balance subject in comparison with other problems of the R&D domain (funding, lack of equipment, brain drain etc.). Other could be coming from the government/public sector, it is seen as not important in relation to other problems of the research area (insufficient funding, equipment, etc).

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative actions like to explain reasons why the subject is important and stress benefits; provide examples of good and bad practices when gender balance was not included in research with negative impacts on the results. Other actions that can be done could be to join similar projects or initiatives.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first coming from internal stakeholders. To start, they could be coming from middle management, top management (especially women in top positions). Next, opportunities could be coming from high management, middle management and heads of departments. To finish, some could be coming from researchers like women researchers involved in similar studies. Secondly, some opportunities could be coming from external stakeholders. Some could be coming from the academia, organizations that support the policy recommendation. Other could come from civil society such as NGO's. To finish, some opportunities could be coming from industries/business stakeholders, organizations that support the policy recommendation.

Transfer to Market

1. Innovation ecosystem: Cafeneaua de Inovare (Innovation Café)

Situation

Cafeneaua de Inovare (Innovation Café) is an initiative of the Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding (UEFISCDI), taking place twice or three times per year: a flexible networking framework aiming to facilitate the exchange of experience and the dialogue between innovative entrepreneurs, investors, venture capitalists and other actors active in the innovative entrepreneurship ecosystem in Romania. More than 800 stakeholders were involved in the 12 editions that took place until now: entrepreneurs, researchers, public authorities, investors, business facilitators. Cafeneaua de Inovare (Innovation Café) is UEFISCDI's main project targeting the Romanian entrepreneurial innovation ecosystem. Until now gender balance was never taken in consideration and no efforts were made in this regard in organizing the event.

Main problems

The main problem is that gender balance is not taken into consideration when inviting speakers or targeting the audience and no gender sensitive subjects were on the agenda of any event.

Objective(s)

The goal is to increase the visibility of gender balance issues in the Romanian innovation ecosystem, as well.

Possible solutions

- Possible solutions could be to write an internal procedure in which to integrate quotas/targets related to gender balance when organizing the event (in terms of choosing panelists or speakers) and to address gender dimension related issues in STEM topics, when possible.

Resistances

The expected resistances are coming from external stakeholders. Some could be coming from the academia such as a lack of interest in the gender balance subject in comparison with other problems (funding, etc.). Others could be coming from the government/public sector: not important in relation to other problems of innovation ecosystem.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative actions such as to provide examples of good practices and situations when gender balance was taken into consideration and stress the positive results. Other actions could also be organized like organizing events dedicated to women innovators or researchers.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first coming from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from high management, top management (especially women in top positions). Opportunities could also be coming

from middle management and head of departments. To finish, they could be coming from the industries/business, from women innovators. Secondly, some opportunities could be coming from external stakeholders. Some opportunities could be coming from the academia such as organizations that support the policy recommendation. They could also be coming from civil society such as NGO's to finish, others could be coming from industries/business stakeholders like organizations that support targets in events.

Communication

1. Internal communication

Situation

In terms of communication, the institution, without having formal training on sensitive gender language, tried to be as gender sensitive as possible. There is a need to develop a guideline/protocol regarding the use of gender sensitive language.

Main problems

The main problem is that there are no guidelines or protocols regarding gender sensitive language. The language is used informally – according to the level of knowledge and awareness of the staff member; although there are no internal official guidelines or protocols for gender sensitive communication, the employees are aware of the international recommendations relating to gender inclusive language.

Objective(s)

The goals are to adopt a Guideline/protocol on gender sensitive non-biased communication/language use and to inform and train the employees according to its rules.

Possible solutions

- To write a guideline on the rules and regulations regarding the gender sensitive language.
- To train the employees according to the guideline.
- The trainings should be included in the kit for gender sensitive communication packages developed for new employees.

Resistances

The expected resistances are coming from internal stakeholders. They are expected to be coming from the rules or structure of the organization, it could be small resistance from the employees' perspective (the guideline is not used on a regular basis).

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative actions like to explain the importance of having a Guideline/protocol on gender sensitive non-biased communication/language use.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first coming from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization such as other departments that had to use gender sensitive language and understood its importance in communication. Secondly, some opportunities could be coming from external stakeholders. They could come from the academia like CALIPER project (and/or similar ones)

Intersectionality

Situation

Inside the organisation gender equality is correlated with non-discrimination and ethics and it is part of the organizational culture. Looking at the projects funded and at the organizational culture, gender is taken into consideration in relation with age, ethnicity, all these being part of the non-discriminatory policy promoted.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Main problems

The main problem is that the concept of intersectionality is not well known to all employees. There is always the possibility that one person could be biased (consciously or not) when evaluating the others and being and becoming aware of these stereotypes is a first step in combating discrimination.

Objective(s)

The goal is to raise awareness about the “intersectionality concept” and to make it visible in correlation with the non-discrimination gender policies.

Possible solutions

- To clearly explain the concept in the gender policy communication kit.
- Conduct specific internal trainings to all employees about awareness and ethics of the topic in connection with other concepts.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first coming from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization, natural resistance to a new topic/subject that is being taught. Other resistances could be coming from middle & high management, the subject is not that important in comparison with other management challenges (ex: impact of Covid pandemic on the working environments, etc). Secondly, resistances could be coming from external stakeholders. They could be coming from the academia, not being familiar with the concept, a lack of practice. Others could be coming from the government/public sector, not being familiar with the concept, a lack of practice.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative actions such as to explain the concept and stress its importance in correlation with other non –discrimination gender policies; provide examples of good practices with positive results

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first coming from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from researchers such as studies and researchers on the subject. Next, could be coming from external stakeholders. They could be coming from the academia, the similar research and studies about intersectionality. Others could be coming from civil society: NGO’s with focus on gender equality.

Sexism and sexual harassment**1. Sexual harassment****Situation**

UEFISCDI follows the Code of Ethics mentions in Article 17: „It is considered a deviation from the Code of Ethics and is sanctioned according to the legislation in force the following: (...) sexual harassment”. The institution acts according to the law and to the Code of conduct/ethics, sanctioning any attempt of sexual harassment. No cases of gender/sexual harassment have been reported, thus no counselling for gender-based offences and harassment has been conducted.

Main problems

The main problem is that even if the internal analysis proved that no cases or complaints about harassment (sexual or other type) were ever recorded in the organisation, it is very important to clearly define the concept and to devise reporting procedures that ensure the complainant’s safety and anonymity.

Objective(s)

The goal is to clearly define and explain types of harassment in the gender communication kit and to update the internal procedures to report it in order to make sure they ensure anonymity and safety of the

complainant.

Possible solutions

- Conduct specific internal trainings to all employees about raising awareness and identification of harassment's types.
- Concomitantly, clearly explain the concept (definition, limits, etc) in gender communication kit.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from top and middle management, as the high & middle management are formed mostly of females (80%) and the rest of employees are also mostly females (60%) and no cases of harassment (sexual or other) ever happened, they might consider the subject not so important in comparison with other institutional challenges. They could also be coming from the rules or structure of the organization, it could be a difficult and quite sensitive topic to explain and be understood. Secondly, some resistances are expected coming from external stakeholders. Similar resistances are expected coming from the academia, the government/public sector and the industries/business stakeholders. It could be the resistance in dealing with the subject (as it is a very sensitive one) and refusal to participate in any theme related events.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative actions, even if it is a very sensitive topic, discussions must be initiated, and employees should become aware of the subject and its importance. Other actions could be organized such as to organize workshops and discussions (at first in smaller groups) until employees become familiar with the topic and are ready to surpass the natural /cultural inducted reluctance towards the issue.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first coming from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from high & middle management, women in high & middle position who can become initiators of discussions. Secondly, some opportunity could be coming from external stakeholders. First, some could be coming from the academia, researchers that are conducting studies on harassment. Next, there are the one coming from civil society, NGOs with focus on gender violence, on gender equality, on social issues. To finish there are some coming from industries/business stakeholders, similar initiatives that could be used as good practices or examples.

Synthesis of stakeholders to involve

To overcome the described resistances and use afore-mentioned opportunities the following internal stakeholders need to be involved: the top and middle management and HR, Communication departments, heads of departments to change the organizational rules and to accept and implement the proposed strategies; people who will be impacted by the strategies (the employees, women in UEFISCDI's management chain). External stakeholders also need to be involved, especially stakeholders from the academia such as researchers and universities, the civil society such as NGO's with experience on gender sensitive issues and discrimination; funding agencies; Departments in the Ministry of Research; National Agency for Equal Chances for Women and Men (ANES); and CALIPER project' international consortium.

Actions to be taken to ensure stakeholders' collaboration (both internal and external) are argumentative actions like to inform and convince employees about the importance of gender discrimination and one-to-one discussions with relevant decision makers. Other actions could be organizational change actions like to adopt the new procedures regarding gender sensitive protocols/policies for recruitment and hiring. There could be informative actions such as presentations, articles and case studies; workshops and public debates; women in organization in top management and/or middle management who would publicly support and explain the need to have gender sensitive recruitment protocols. Finally, there could be

engagement actions like workshops on gender issues.

2.8 Yasar University (RPO)

Human resources

1. Recruitment procedures

Situation

There are articles to prevent gender bias in recruitment in Turkish Labour Law (No: 8425). “The principle of equal treatment” (article 5) of the Labour Law states that “No discrimination based on language, race, color, gender, disability, political thought, philosophical belief, religion and sect and similar reasons can be made in the labour relationship. Unless the biological reasons or characteristics of the work require, the employer cannot make any direct or indirect treatment to a worker in the conditions of the employment contract, its implementation and termination due to gender or pregnancy. For a work of the same or equal value, lower wages cannot be agreed due to gender. The application of special protective provisions due to the gender of the worker does not justify the implementation of a lower wage.”

Besides the Labour Law mentioned above, at Yaşar University level, there are no gender sensitive recruitment protocols/policies or any policies to prevent gender bias either academic or administrative level recruitment. However, there is “Administrative Staff Recruitment Procedures and Principles” document which lists the objective promotion criteria, and it mentions (article 5, b) “equal opportunity” in “promotions and appointments”, however, there is no similar article in the academic staff recruitment procedures.

Recruitment and hiring are done based on the principles set out in above-mentioned the documents for procedures and principles of academic and administrative staff regardless of gender. Human resources department also encourages gender-sensitive recruitment processes by referring female candidates to units which are male-dominated or whose managers primarily prefer male candidates. There are no specific procedures for providing gender equality in recruitment processes.

Main problems

The main problem is the lack of gender sensitive recruitment protocols/policies or policies to prevent gender bias in recruitment.

Also, while the administrative recruitment process is transparent and egalitarian, it does not have any measures or provisions to provide the recruitment of under-represented gender in some specific research units or administrative units.

Furthermore, the 51% of the survey participants thinks that the institution does not adopt gender sensitive protocols/policies for recruitment and hiring and 46% thinks it does. The following is a comment made by one of the survey participants:

“For the academic posts, I think the institution looks for the qualities of the candidate meeting with the criteria of the post rather than gender of the candidate. On the other hand, I do not think the institution has defined any protocols and protocols or policies for gender sensitive issues.”

Objective(s)

The goal is to ensure more balanced distribution of genders in all departments and units of the institution by adopting gender sensitive recruitment protocols/policies and policies to prevent gender bias in both academic and administrative recruitment.

Possible solutions

- The integration of principles to the recruitment procedures of the institution in order to prevent

gender bias and to increase awareness of the unit managers about providing more balanced representations of genders.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first from internal stakeholders. Administrative unit managers could criticize and object the action by using extra workload, lack of enough time & resources and/or bureaucracy as excuses. Secondly, resistances could come from external stakeholders. Due to the lack of autonomy of higher education institutions in Turkey integrating gender quotas for academic positions might be very difficult during recruitment and promotion.

The following strategies could be used to overcome the resistances. The main strategy is to convince higher management, the following arguments can be used. First, the integration of gender equality into the recruitment process could put YU ahead of other universities in Turkey since it will be compulsory in the near future in compliance with EU regulations. Next, gender Equality (GE) will also be integral part of the new funding programme of the EU, Horizon Europe, therefore in order to benefit from it, YU needs to adopt GE measures. Another argument is that GE creates better work environment and increases staff's productivity. Next, the integration of GE principles to the recruitment procedures of the institution could help YU to attract and retain talents and expertise in the academia. Finally, GE could also contribute to the excellence and quality in research which contribute to the competitiveness of the YU in the academic field.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from different areas. First, they are coming from the rules or structure of the organization: University's strategy for the upcoming 5 years, regulations regarding recruitment procedures. Next, they could be coming from the administration: The administration is eager to promote gender sensitive recruitment and employment in the institution. Opportunities could also be coming from middle management: Generally managers are non-discriminating towards gender and non-gender specific posts are listed. Next, they could be coming from high management: High management would like to promote gender equality as a value in the strategic plan and the newly established gender studies center is an example in this regard. Finally, opportunities could be coming from researchers: Researchers are aware of the gender issues and would like to see more gender equality rules, procedures and implementation during recruitment and appointment processes.

2. Work environments and working conditions

Situation

In terms of work environment and working conditions the university aims to improve the work-life balance and reconciliation of work and family life.

The provisions of Labor Law No. 4857 are applied to academic and administrative staff in terms of employee rights, annual leave, other legal leaves and excuse leaves.

Staff members are entitled to the rights and privileges stated in the Turkish Labour Law. The working life is regulated according to the "Academic Staff Employment and Evaluation Directive and "Administrative Staff Employment Procedures and Principles".

Most of the staff involved in the survey indicated that they are satisfied with their work environment and job, in general terms. However, there is lack of information on gender dimension and relevant policies of the institution.

In terms of gender & perception of work climate; 57% of the participants define the climate in the work environment as "positive" and 34% define as "neutral", and only 9% define as "negative".

Main problems

According to survey, more than 40% of the staff has concerns about their work- life balance. While the work conditions are equally designed for all staff in the institution, specific provisions according to the

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specific requirements of the women are not available. Therefore, individual measures or opportunities are provided based on the decisions of the unit managers.

Objective(s)

The goal is to make institutional regulations and procedures more gender sensitive and to guarantee providing same rights for all staff in terms of work environment and working conditions.

Possible solutions

- Possible solutions could be the preparation of a GEP and specific institutional regulations.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first coming from internal stakeholders. On one hand, the administration especially male directors and managers could argue that providing specific working provisions for women could create inequality and could be considered favoring of women by men. On the other hand, top management could use lack of similar implementations and privileges in many of the other HEIs as an excuse for inaction. Secondly, resistances are expected coming from external stakeholders. Work environments and working conditions are internal issues of the YU, but it is directly affected by national regulations of the external bodies such as Ministry of Family, Labour and Social Services and YÖK (Turkish Higher Education Council). Therefore, it could be difficult to make changes if those changes are not in line with the national regulations. While these two bodies would not directly resist proposed changes, their regulations affect the process.

Some strategies could be used to overcome the resistances; arguments can be used to convince decision-makers. To start, in the long term, these changes could reduce staff workload. Next, improving work environment and working conditions would be beneficial for both women and men. Another argument is that these provisions improve working climate of the university. There is also the fact that better environment and working conditions could attract highly qualified candidates. To finish, by improving work environment and working conditions Yu could become a leading/exemplary institution in gender equality among HEIs.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from different areas. First, they could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization, working life is regulated by internal regulations to prevent discrimination. Flexible working and teleworking opportunities were introduced due to Covid19 Pandemic and it is likely that these could be implemented in the future for staff members wishing to have a more balanced working life. Next, they could be coming from the administration, same as high management. Opportunities could also be coming from middle management; managers are instrumental in providing individual measures or opportunities regarding specific work conditions. They are the links between the employee and the high management. They could also be coming from high management; high management is eager and aware of the need for a healthy work-life balance. Vice-rector interviewed stressed the importance of supporting female researchers to get back into research rhythm following pregnancy and maternity leave. The gaps in research for female researchers are a subject to be addressed. Finally, they could be coming from researchers, they are aware of their legal rights and according to the survey results, the measures taken by the institution such as teleworking/remote work, part-time employment, various types of leaves and other forms of work arrangements are affecting the work-life balance of staff members in a positive way.

3. Appraisal systems for career evolution

Situation

In terms of the career evolution there is no gender specific procedures. The priority is merit, competence and seniority. There is no gender-based evolution. Promotion/tenure criteria for academic staff is transparent and fixed and based on the national regulation set the by Council of Higher Education (YÖK).

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Career development of the administrative staff is made by unit managers and their top managers. There are no written or fixed criteria. The priority is merit, competence and seniority. Gender-based evolution is not done.

In the interviews one high level executive noted that the ratio of “women researchers who took an associate professorship and progressed in their career is balanced in Turkey when compared to other countries.”

Human resources director suggests that to ensure flexible and transparent promotion criteria, “equal number of female and male candidates can be evaluated by the senior management while evaluating candidates for the relevant unit managers during recruitment and career development and report regularly.”

Main problems

While the career evolution procedures are transparent and based on merit for academic staff, career planning for the staff of administrative units is made by unit managers and their top managers. These are not written and static. In academic units, still the ratio of A level female researchers is lower than A level male researchers.

Furthermore, there are no gender sensitive flexible criteria that take into consideration major life events like childbirth, care work for relatives or continuing education as well as individual performance. Also, there are no fixed criteria (e.g. fixed number of years) for accessing the following stages for administrative staff.

Objective(s)

The goal is to support career evolution of the women in the research areas or high-level positions where they are underrepresented and provide clear career evolution pathways for administrative staff.

Possible solutions

- Setting up career evolution procedures for the administrative staff and designing mentoring or support programs for the female researchers to support their career evolution process.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first from internal stakeholders. Resistances are expected from middle management, administrative unit managers could object to changes by denying the need for change in the existing system. They are also expected from male researchers that could also resist changes due to feeling threatened or fear of losing their positions. Secondly, resistances are expected from external stakeholders that are coming from the government/public sector: Governing bodies such as Council of Higher Education (YÖK) and Ministry of Family, Labour and Social Services’ legal regulations could prevent setting up new procedures.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first argumentative such as to convince top management creating arguments such as providing career evolution support to women attracts qualified staff that leads to the academic excellence. They could also be in the rules of the organization such as engaging all internal actors into revisions of the appraisal system to gain their support. Other actions could be collaborating with HR and Career Centre to develop training and support programmes tailored for the female researchers.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities could be coming from different areas. First, they could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization, academic promotion procedures are egalitarian and transparent. They are based on the national regulation set the by Council of Higher Education (YÖK). Next, they could also be coming from the administration, the strategy involves the following allies: Rectorate and board of trustees; Gender Equality Working Group members, HR Department, Career Centre. Opportunities could also be coming from middle management, more than half of all deputy deans are female at Yasar

University. Furthermore, in the administrative units there is a high level of female representation in middle management in terms of heads of units or chiefs. This is a great opportunity for the institution to revise and implement gender sensitive promotion procedures. Next, they could be coming from high management: High management is eager and aware of the need for a revision for appraisal system. They stress the current inequalities for women researchers in career progression and would like to see concrete action in the form of new systems and implementation of measures. Finally, resistances could be coming from researchers; the rate of female researchers at Yasar University is 58%. This rate creates an opportunity for the ownership of measures related to career progression.

4. Career support and development strategies

Situation

The situation shows that there are no specific measures addressing (gender) inequalities in career progression (e.g. soft quotas, targets, female professorships positions). There is no specific career support mentoring or training programme for the underrepresented gender, either. The specific rules and procedures for promotion are applied to all academic staff without taking gender into account.

During the interviews one high level executive stressed that “women researchers have more responsibilities outside of work like childcare. Male researchers do not have such difficulties and this creates a general inequality” for progression in research.

Main problems

The main problem is the lack of specific measures addressing (gender) inequalities in career progression both for academic and administrative staff. Furthermore, there is no consultancy body for the career support of the staff. As a result, the career evolution is based on the individual capacity and the decision of the unit managers.

Objective(s)

The goal is to support career evolution of the women in the research areas or high-level positions where they are underrepresented.

Possible solutions

- Setting up specific institutional mentoring or support programs for the female researchers to support their career evolution process and establishing basic criteria to address (gender) inequalities in career progression for both academic and administrative staff.

Resistances

The expected resistances are from internal stakeholders. Resistances could be coming from middle management; middle management could argue that it creates extra workload. They could also be coming from researchers; male researchers could resist arguing that it creates inequality

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative like to convince top and middle management using arguments such as work on gender equality benefits all staff, not only women. Other strategies touch the rules of the organization such as to initiate co-creation of a new career evolution and support system involving all relevant stakeholders. Other actions could be to organize awareness raising trainings for the staff (especially males).

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from different areas. First, they could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization, academic promotion procedures are egalitarian and transparent. They are based on the national regulation set the by Council of Higher Education (YÖK). Opportunities could also come from the administration, the strategy involves the following allies: Rectorate and board of trustees; Gender Equality Working Group members, HR Department, Career Centre. They could also be coming from

middle management, more than half of all deputy deans are female at Yasar University. Furthermore, in the administrative units there is a high level of female representation in middle management in terms of heads of units or chiefs. This is a great opportunity for the institution to revise and implement gender sensitive promotion procedures. Opportunities are also expected coming from high management: it is eager and aware of the need for a revision for appraisal system. They stress the current inequalities for women researchers in career progression and would like to see concrete action in the form of new systems and implementation of measures. Finally, opportunities could come from researchers: the rate of female researchers at Yasar University is 58%. This rate creates an opportunity for the ownership of measures related to career progression.

5. Career breaks and job reintegration

Situation

In terms of the career breaks and job reintegration the analysis shows that the procedures for the career breaks and job reintegration in the institution are managed according to the national rules (Turkish Labour Law) and provisions. There is no specific institutional document/regulation about career breaks and job reintegration procedures that consider gender dimension.

Main problems

The main problem is the lack of unified institutional approach to career breaks and job integration. The processes about the career breaks and job integration are mostly designed according to the preferences of the unit managers. Consequently, in some cases some individuals may deprive from these rights or privileges.

Objective(s)

The goal is to provide equal opportunities to all employees in the cases they need to have career breaks due to their individual reasons by adopting an institutional regulation for career breaks and job reintegration procedures.

Possible solutions

- To design and implement general procedures for the whole institution about career breaks and job reintegration.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first from internal stakeholders. Resistances could be coming from high management: Top level management can resist arguing that there are no similar implementations and privileges in many of the HEIs. Secondly, resistances are expected from external stakeholders. Resistances could be coming from the government/public sector, National regulations regarding labour and academic recruitment could prevent setting up new rules.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first argumentative such as creating arguments to point out that having an institutional regulation for career breaks and job reintegration could help YU attract female talents in the academia. Secondly, other actions could be done like organizing one-to-one meetings with top and middle management to provide information and raise awareness.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from different areas. First they could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization, there is a written procedure and regulation of the institution for the sabbatical leaves. Opportunities could also be coming from the administration, University administration is evaluated mostly positively to extend unpaid leave of female employees due to their special requirements such as maternity leave. They could also be coming from high management; top management follows national laws and regulations on career breaks and reintegration. HR manager states that they work

individually on requests and try to accommodate the needs of units/departments and the staff members equally. Finally, opportunities could be coming from researchers, they are aware of their legal rights.

Governance

1. Enhancing women leadership and access to top positions (academic and administrative levels)

Situation

Interviews with academics and managers of the institution clearly point out that there is an urgent need for more women in decision-making bodies. Looking at the academic units, 8 of 11 vice-deans, 3 of 9 deans and 25 of the 47 department heads are women. Yet, vice rectors in senior management and the members of the board of trustee are predominantly male. While senior management seeks opportunities to highlight female employees, the participation of women in decision-making remains low. Considering the structure of the board of trustees and the vice-rectorships, it becomes evident that women should be represented more in decision making.

Main problems

The main problems are the dominance of the researchers from the STEM fields in the decision-making system of the university and these are the fields where the ratio of females is lower than males. Also, there is no plan or guiding principles to provide gender equality in decision making.

Furthermore, the participation of women in decision-making is low due the lack of representation / existence of women in the top-level bodies and commissions.

Objective(s)

The goal is to ensure equal representation of men and women in decision making bodies of the university by adopting a gender equality plan or guiding principles.

Possible solutions

- The preparation and implementation of a concrete plan or guiding principles for providing gender equality in decision making bodies.

Resistances

No expected resistances have been identified from neither internal nor external stakeholders.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities could be coming from different areas. First, they could be coming from the administration; the administration is looking for ways to increase women in top-level management positions. Interviews with HR department reflect a high level of awareness about gender in top-level management. Next, they could come from middle management; there is a higher-level representation of women in the mid-level management bodies and units which are steppingstones on the way to top-level management. Opportunities could also be coming from high management, high management stresses the importance of having more female managers in the top level and acknowledges that it is not the case at the moment but there is a plan to change the current structure. Finally, they could be coming from researchers; researchers acknowledge the need for learning leadership through top-level management positions. They think that academic success is enriched through management experience. Female researchers are interested in top-level positions and show ambition towards attaining more high-level positions in the organization.

2. Gender disaggregated data collection at the institutional level

Situation

There is no gender disaggregated data collection procedure in the university and these types of data were

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collected for the first time by CALIPER analysis process.

Main problems

Due to the lack of gender disaggregated data the situation of the university in terms of gender issues is not clear which also hinders development of a sound and evidence-based strategies for gender.

Also, gender has not been a strategic priority for the previous institutional strategies of the university.

Objective(s)

The goal is to develop evidence-based policies for gender equality in the institution and to monitor the implementation of the policies on gender equality by assuring gender disaggregated data collection at all levels.

Possible solutions

The integration of gender disaggregated data to the data collection procedures of the university (such as performance assessment, strategic planning, and annual activity reports etc.)

Resistances

The expected resistances are coming from internal stakeholders. Resistances could be coming from middle management, it could be resistances claiming it creates extra workload and it is time-consuming.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative like convincing top and middle management using arguments and framing and could touch the rules of the organization such as proposing new regulation for gender disaggregated data collection.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from different areas. First, they could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization, gender is integrated to the institutional strategy of the university for 2020-2025. As a result, it is necessary to collect gender disaggregated data for measuring strategic goals periodically. There is a specific unit of the university for the data collection and analysis. Next, they could be coming from the administration, most of the units and departments in the university are very motivated to prepare gender disaggregated data and believe the necessity of it. To continue, opportunities could come from middle management most of the units and departments in the university are very motivated to prepare gender disaggregated data and believe the necessity of it. To finish, they could be coming from high management, high management is aware of the need to collect gender disaggregated data to measure KPIs for strategic plan.

Research

Situation

There are no funds for specific programs on gender studies. However, the university allocates funds for Scientific Research Projects, called BAP. These projects are expected to contribute to the technological, economic, social and cultural development of the country, economy and arts at the national and/or international level as well as to the establishment and development of scientific research and research infrastructures.

According to the interviews held with academics/researchers, a lack of funds for gender research is a major issue. One researcher noted that, "in an institutional context, top-down management should demonstrate that it advocates gender equality. It is necessary to ensure that male researchers, academicians and employees are attracted to this issue. Special project supports should be provided for these issues."

Vice-rector responsible for research, innovation and funds stated that the awareness of the management regarding the lack of funds for gender studies and adds "It is necessary to reflect this to research, development, innovation and entrepreneurship. When YU looks at the scientific research projects, it is seen

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that there are more women project managers/principle investigators. Women benefit more from internal funds. However, large projects often come from engineering departments, and the project leaders in these departments are generally male researchers. There are teams and research hubs working in various fields such as EU, entrepreneurship, digitalization, migration, agricultural sciences etc. The university also has a strategy of identifying research teams and providing them with extra funds. Gender research team will be one of these research hubs.”

Furthermore, there is no specific policy to integrate gender analysis into Yasar University’s research system or to enhance gender awareness and sensitivity.

The interviews with academics point out that there is a lack of policies, guidelines on the integration of the gender analysis into research. They think that researchers need to develop a gender perspective first. Then, the management should encourage the concept of gender in new research, projects and units to be established. They also believe that the integrating gender in research remains at the level of individual effort. Some academics are interested in these subjects, so they are offering courses on the subject or integrating gender as a theme to a course. But there is not any collective effort.

Main problems

The gender issue has not become a major component of the research process at YU. The initiatives (projects, publications and thesis) are randomly designed rather than being a part of an institutional plan. The gender research is highly concentrated in certain scientific fields and underrepresented in STEM research. Also, gender is not considered as a specific research priority for the allocation of the institutional budget for research projects.

Objective(s)

The goal is to increase the number of researches and research projects on gender and to produce more knowledge on this issue by integrating gender into institutional strategic plan and institutional funding mechanisms.

Possible solutions

- The integration of gender subjects into the institutional strategic plan and institutional funding mechanisms as one of the strategic research priorities.

Resistances

The expected resistances are from internal stakeholders. Resistances could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization: the institutional funding system of the university does not have areas of priority.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first argumentative like convincing top and middle management using arguments (see actions sections for arguments). Some strategies touch the rules of the organization such as proposing integration of gender into institutional funding system of the university. To finish, there could be other actions such as organizing workshops on the integration of gender analysis and gender dimension into research for academic staff and graduate students.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from different areas. First, it could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization, gender is identified as one of the institutional priorities in the university's strategies. Next, they could come from the administration; the establishment of Gender Equality Working Group contributes to the promotion of gender in research. To continue, opportunities could be coming from middle management; female researchers constitute a majority of heads of departments (academic) and deputy deans. Collectively, they have the power to influence decision making in terms of research. Their presence can be utilized to include a gender dimension in research. Opportunities could also be coming from high management, the vice-rector responsible for research, innovation and funds, states that

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the university should identify gender as a research topic and provide researchers working on gender with extra funds. This demonstrates an institutional approach to encouraging research on gender. Next, they could be coming from researchers; the university has high-qualified researchers who specialize in gender. Furthermore, the level of cooperation between different departments and faculties is high. Therefore, the incorporation of gender in research can be done effectively and interdisciplinary. Finally, opportunities could be coming from students, with the introduction of gender as a priority research area, students will be directed to produce research / incorporate gender dimension in their research.

Teaching

Situation

There are no policies, guidelines/checklists on how to integrate the gender dimension into curricula, and this was underlined by the researchers participating in the interviews for the internal assessment. They believe that more attention should be paid to gender issues in the development of course contents. Likewise, there are no gender-sensitive teaching guidelines for professors/lecturers. This increases the likelihood of potential gender bias in teaching and calls for more awareness on the subject. The researchers believe that gender-sensitive teaching remains at the individual level. The necessity of creating an environment in which joint action, interdisciplinary studies, and information sharing are stressed. There is a need for academic gender mainstreaming.

Main problems

- Lack of institutional strategies and guiding documents on adding a gender dimension to the curriculum and course contents or gender sensitivity.
- Lack of institutional orientation or training for academic staff on gender sensitivity and communication with students.
- Lack of department and field specific courses or activities on gender.

Objective(s)

The goal is to create an institutional culture in which gender dimension is incorporated in teaching, tutoring, and overall educational approach. To achieve this, the awareness of academic staff should be raised so that the curriculum reflects gender issues, the potential gender bias in teaching are eliminated, and specific study fields and gender, in general, can be linked through a diverse range of newly developed courses.

Possible solutions

- The development and adoption of institutional principles for integrating the gender dimension into curricula, training of academic staff according to these institutional principles.
- A pilot implementation of a curriculum with a gender dimension can be started with one department from each faculty. The pilot implementation results can be shared with the university staff, and a gradual requirement for including a gender dimension in curriculum development can be put into place.
- Departments can also be encouraged to design new courses combining their specific fields with gender.
- Information materials for academic staff on gender sensitivity in communication with students can be prepared.
- Specific questions regarding the academic staff's potential gender bias in teaching and gender-sensitive communication skills can be added to the students' end-of-semester academic staff reviews to monitor the situation and take necessary steps to improve.

Resistances

No expected resistances have been identified from either internal or external stakeholders.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from different areas. First, they could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization, there are some university elective courses on gender studies. Next, they could also be coming from the administration; the university has experienced human resources that teach on gender issues. Other opportunities could be coming from middle management, middle management is eager to capture innovative teaching methods and updating curriculum. Some could come from high management, high management places importance on gender in terms of teaching and educational approach. Finally, they could be coming from researchers: There is a high level of awareness among the teaching staff on the lack of and necessity to incorporate a gender perspective in teaching and curriculum development. Teaching staff is eager to learn more about gender sensitive communication tools.

Students and services to students

Situation

YU's internal assessment revealed that there are no specific initiatives or programs offering information, guidance, or counseling to prospective or enrolled students with a gender-sensitive approach. Gender equality and gender perspective are handled within a broader theme of equality and emphasis on progressive policies of the institution. There are also no specific initiatives for attracting female students to STEM studies.

Main problems

- There are no institutional principles or policies for informing and raising awareness of the students on gender issues.
- A gender perspective is not included in the first-year student orientation processes.
- There are no counseling services offered to students specifically on gender issues.
- Gender topic is not visible in the student services area.

Objective(s)

The goal is to create an environment where gender issues are considered and incorporated in the general work of departments that offer support and guidance to students, such as student affairs, career and alumni center and psychological counseling and guidance unit so that students can gain awareness about gender mainstreaming in each service of the university.

Possible solutions

- Collaborating with high schools during regular promotion visits or seminars about encouraging more female students to STEM education to attract prospective students.
- The incorporation of gender into the first-year student orientation program.
- Organizing awareness raising and informative sessions for the staff members working in student services departments, for the enrolled students through various student clubs' involvement.
- Preparation of informative guidelines for students about gender issues together with academic and related departments such as student services, psychological counseling and guidance unit, and the career and alumni center.
- Role models from alumni can be invited to share experiences in the business world and inspire female students. Students can be informed about different counseling and support mechanisms

present at the university.

Resistances

No expected resistances have been identified.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from different areas.

First, they could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization, central Student Activities Unit is eager to incorporate gender into 1YS orientation and part-time student placement program. Career and Alumni Center encourages female candidates for internships at various SMEs. Izmir, the city where YU is located, has a positive image and reputation regarding gender issues. Next, they could be coming from the administration; the administration is willing to incorporate gender issues into student services and initiatives. To continue, opportunities could come from middle management, middle management is willing to incorporate gender issues into student services and initiatives. Some are expected coming from high management: High management is willing to incorporate gender issues into student services and initiatives. Next, some are coming from researchers; the staff members interviewed expressed their willingness to incorporate gender issues into students' initiatives, such as the first-year student orientation program. Finally, there could be some coming from students; there is a general balance in the number of female and male students at the university.

Transfer to Market

Situation

There are no collaborative research projects with a gender dimension in research and technology development content. Furthermore, there are no gender sensitive/gender specific measures/actions on enhancing transfer to market of scientific research results.

During the interviews, the Vice Rector at YU who is responsible for the Knowledge and Technology Transfer Office provided a general framework of gender equality in the collaborative research projects. He mentioned that while gender balance and equality is achieved in international projects, projects with NGOs, private sector and municipalities, women researchers still face obstacles when it comes to projects with public bodies. He thinks that gender inequality is felt "in the male-dominated public part of the quadruple helix. We see that relationships are more distant, and women are not invited to some environments. In such projects, there is an official environment and an informal environment. This is how the network develops. While there is no gender discrimination in formal channels, but there is gender discrimination in informal channels."

Operating under Yaşar University Information and Technology Transfer Office, Minerva Incubation Center supports all innovative entrepreneurs, especially students and academicians at Yaşar University since 2015. Vice Rector for research and innovation observes that "there are very few women-intensive teams in Minerva Incubation Center. We started positive discrimination in the entrepreneurship group. Gender equality should be observed in those who settle down as entrepreneurs at the center. The situation here seems to be against women."

Main problems

The main problems are the lack of collaborative research projects with a gender dimension in research and technology development content, and lack of gender sensitive/gender specific measures/actions on enhancing transfer to market of scientific research results.

Objective(s)

The goal is to integrate gender dimension in research and technology development at the YU.

Possible solutions

The development of an institutional plan/guideline for the integration of gender dimension in research and technology development and adoption of gender sensitive/gender specific measures/actions on enhancing transfer to market of scientific research results.

Resistances

No resistances are expected from neither internal nor external stakeholders.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from different areas. First, opportunities are coming from the rules or structure of the organization, the presence of a vice-rectorate with three departments that focus on internal funds, national funds and EU & international funds. University's strategy for the upcoming 5 years. Next, they could be coming from the administration, the general awareness on the importance of gender and gender equality in research. Other opportunities could be coming from high management, high management is eager to increase the gender dimension in research and technology development. The vice-rectorate on research and innovation pays close attention to the balance of project teams and internal/external collaboration structures as well as the distribution of entrepreneurs in the incubation center in terms of gender. Finally, they could be coming from researchers, the university has high-qualified researchers who specialize in gender with extensive external network.

Communication

Situation

Although the external communication in terms of social media is regulated with specific procedures and principles that refer to gender equality and UNDP's gender-sensitive communication guide is used by the staff members working in digital media, there are no principles or guidelines on gender awareness in institutional communication. 61% of the internal survey participants do not know whether the institution promotes awareness-raising campaigns aiming at fighting stereotypes while 72% of the participants are not aware whether any complaint mechanisms in cases of gender-biased/sexist communication are available to them or not. These point out to a general lack of awareness towards the effects of gender in institutional communication. Furthermore, there are no policies or training for staff members on gender sensitive language in administrative communication. However, the national capacity building training of CALIPER project has resulted in two important institutional communication changes. Firstly, part-time student employment application forms now include the option "I do not want to specify" for gender, and the human resources department sends out greeting cards with gender neutral colors following each birth by personnel. This shows that staff members are enthusiastic about change and they can adopt policies following trainings on gender.

Main problems

- There is a lack of regulations and guidelines on gender awareness in internal communication.
- Gender issues need to become more visible incorporate awareness and social responsibility projects.
- Gender equality needs to be clearly expressed in the institutional identity and values.
- There is a lack of complaint mechanism in cases of gender-biased/sexist communication.
- There is a lack of awareness about the importance and necessity of having specific regulations or guidelines on gender awareness due to seeing gender as a part of a broader concept of equality.

Objective(s)

The goal is to officially incorporate gender equality as a core value and a part of institutional identity

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through developing a gender-sensitive institutional communication strategy that will provide a foundation for visual, written, and online communication of the institution and the communication between its staff members.

Possible solutions

- The completion and implementation of CALIPER Gender Equality Plan, development and implementation of gender-sensitive institutional communication principles, and training of all staff members on the subject.
- A complaint mechanism can be put into place for complaints on gender insensitive communication between staff members with a possible mediation service.
- Gender equality should be made an internal part of the institutional identity and values.

Resistances

No resistances have been identified from neither internal nor external stakeholders.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from different areas. First, they could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization, the external communication in terms of social media is regulated with specific procedures and principles that refer to gender equality and UNDP's gender-sensitive communication guide is used by the staff members working in digital media. This can be transferred to internal communication as well. Next, opportunities could be coming from the administration, the university places extra attention on communication and one of the deputy secretary generals of the institution is responsible for communication. Opportunities could also be coming from middle management, the national capacity building training of CALIPER project has resulted in two important institutional communication changes. Firstly, part-time student employment application forms now include the option "I do not want to specify" for gender, and the human resources department sends out greeting cards with gender neutral colors following each birth by personnel. This shows that units are enthusiastic about change and they are able to adopt policies following trainings on gender. Others could also be coming from high management, the university places extra attention on communication and one of the deputy secretary generals of the institution is responsible for communication. Finally, they could be coming from researchers; the researchers have a high level of awareness on the need for a gender dimension in internal communication.

Intersectionality

Situation

Both interview and focus group participants think that it is of high importance to consider gender in relation to other discrimination forms. They suggest that there should be a discrimination office at the university, which will be responsible for facilitating the adaptation of the women, men, newcomers, people with communication problems, foreign staff, and senior (elderly) staff.

In the interviews, one researcher notes that "definitions such as LGBT individuals or concepts such as sexual orientation in Istanbul Convention concern conservative people" however, these identities are a reality in every society.

All interviewees agree that as a research institution, the university should encourage academic research about gender and provide a free environment for academic research. One researcher thinks that with "libertarian approach environment can be created in which everyone respects each other and has equal opportunities. This dynamic then should be conveyed to the students and transferred outside the campus. It is necessary to be aware that different identities exist." Another researcher adds that going beyond a binary distinction is "the reason why we call gender equality anyway." She adds "we used to say that women's right is a human right, and now we say that the right to gender equality is a human right." She

thinks that different identities create different realities by commenting “the experiences of a woman or an LGBT individual living in Mavişehir (an affluent neighborhood in Izmir) will not be the same as the experiences of a woman or an LGBT individual living in Bayraklı. (a lower-class neighborhood in Izmir. Exclusions cause new areas of discrimination. All this should be under the umbrella of gender equality.” Another researcher stressed that in order to go beyond a binary understanding, “we have to admit that there are individuals other than men and women and LGBT individuals need to be accepted.”

One researcher also expressed that “due to the current political climate, it might be difficult to go beyond this dual understanding.” However, he thinks that a broader approach to gender is very important for the internationalization of the university.

Another researcher pointed out that it is rather difficult to leave this binary understanding when discussing gender equality.

One focus group participant states that the increase of awareness of gender equality “will have positive spillover effect on other types of inequalities. Instead of focusing on one type of discrimination, focusing on intersectionality is more effective. We should bring together different points of views.”

Another participant emphasized that LGBT issues should be more visible and talked about.

However, currently there are no institutional measures or guidelines to integrate various dimensions of gender equality into policies and practices.

Main problems

The main problem is the lack of consideration of gender in conjunction with other discriminations/structural inequalities in the institution.

However due to the current political climate, it might be difficult to go beyond this dual understanding and cultural and traditional values might hinder going beyond the binary understanding of equality.

Objective(s)

The goal is to create guidelines and institutional measures to take gender into account in conjunction with other discriminations/structural inequalities."

Possible solutions

- To be encouraging academic research about gender and provide a free environment for academic research and promoting a broader approach to gender.

Resistances

No resistance could be expected from external stakeholders.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from different areas. First, they could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization, having specific unit for students with disabilities, having Quality Management System, and occupational health and safety standards might be useful. Next, they could be coming from high management, High management supports efforts towards eliminating discrimination or harassment and aware of the various dimensions of gender. Other opportunities could be coming from researchers; researchers stress the importance of addressing other forms of inequality and discrimination in connection with gender issues. For this, the idea of “discrimination office” was put forward to tackle all forms of inequalities stemming from gender identity, sexuality, disabilities, ethnic and racial background. To finish, they could be coming from students, there are different student clubs that deal with discrimination or inequality. There is awareness among students.

Sexism and sexual harassment

Situation

The situation regarding sexism and sexual harassment within the organization can be summarized as below:

In “Administrative Personnel Disciplinary Procedures and Principles” document of the university harassment regarded as a disciplinary act that requires termination of employment contract. In “Academic Integrity Policy”, it is stated that the university does not condone harassment in any form. However, there is no specific mechanism or procedure regarding sexism and sexual harassment.

While there were no negative experiences mentioned regarding gender-based offenses and harassment during the interviews and focus group; 4% of the survey participants have indicated that they experienced gender/sexual harassment within the organization and only 1% stated that have reported it to the competent bodies in the organization. Furthermore, 7% of the survey participants indicated that they have witnessed gender/sexual harassment within the organization and while 13% stated that they did not take any action, only 4% stated that they take actions such as reporting to competent bodies or encouraging the victim to do so. The followings were given as the reasons why they did not take any action:

- My complete conviction that this would not be taken seriously as an issue. (Head of department, Male)
- I thought that as the person doing this has a close relation with the high-level managers of the university he would be protected. I was also concerned about losing my job. (Dr. Lecturer, Female)
- (because of) The threat that my academic life will be ended. (Research Assistant, Female)
- The person who did this was a foreign faculty member from a Western country and I threatened him to complain to the Rectorate if he approached me more than 3 meters again. I think he was afraid and he never got closer again. So, the issue ended there. If this situation persisted I would be complaining. (Dr. Lecturer, Female)
- The victim herself (prevented me). (Head of department, Female)
- I am not sure that the subject would result in my favor, as the person who does it has someone powerful behind him. (Staff of administrative offices, Female)
- Because I think this will be of no use or no one would care. (Staff of administrative offices, Female)

On the other hand, the survey participants were also asked if they are aware if any counselling service is available for gender-based offences and harassment and results show that most of the participants (74%) do not know if it is available.

The existence of the institutional rules and policies against harassment can be mentioned as a positive aspect regarding sexism and sexual harassment.

Main problems

The main problems are the absence of specific institutional rules and policies against sexism and sexual harassment and lack of clear mechanisms for counseling and complaint in case of gender-based harassment or offences in the workplace.

Objective(s)

The goal is to create guidelines against sexism and sexual harassment and counseling and complaint mechanisms in case of gender-based harassment or offences.

Possible solutions

- The establishment of clear mechanisms for reporting sexual or gender-based harassment.
- The creation of guidelines against sexism and sexual harassment.

Resistances

No resistance could be expected from external stakeholders.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from different areas. First, they could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization: Internal, “Administrative Personnel Disciplinary Procedures and Principles” and “Academic Integrity Policy” External: Turkish Criminal Law and Labour Law. Next, they could be coming from high management: it is devoted to providing a safe and harassment free working environment to all staff members. The results of the survey were taken very seriously, and top management stressed the importance of changing perspectives in terms of how sexual harassment is handled in the organization. Finally, opportunities could come from researchers; the researchers are aware of many forms of harassment and vocal about their past experiences on the issue.

Synthesis of stakeholders to involve

To overcome the described resistances and use afore-mentioned opportunities the following internal stakeholders need to be involved: Board of Trustees, Senate, Board of Directors, Rectorate, HR Department, Gender Equality Working Group members, the Education Commission, the Gender Studies Center, the Innovative Teaching and Learning Unit, Gender Researchers, Student Clubs to change the organizational rules and to accept and implement the proposed strategies; people who will be impacted by the strategies (all academic and administrative staff). External stakeholders also need to be involved, especially stakeholders from the academia such as other HEIs that have already established GEPs might be useful in convincing high-level management; platform of Izmir Universities (a joint initiative between the 10 HEIs located in Izmir city); business and industry and public sector organizations that have a good reputation in gender equality measures (useful to present them as good practice examples); H&R departments of local businesses, industries, and trade associations; YÖK (Turkish Higher Education Council) and Ministry of Family, Labour and Social Services (two main central public bodies that regulate labour and working conditions); NGOs working on gender, gender equality, discrimination, human rights, women’s rights, youth; TÜBİTAK (The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey).

Some actions to be taken to ensure stakeholders’ collaboration (both internal and external) are delivering awareness raising trainings (joint activities with other HEIs, NGOs, companies and public bodies can be organized to raise awareness); organizing one-on-one meetings with the involvement of Gender Equality WG members; creating a clear communication strategy with internal and external stakeholders to present the proposed changes; collecting the best practice examples HEIs both from Turkey and Europe.

2.9 Salento University (RPO)

Human resources

1. Recruitment procedures

Situation

Sex ratio on type of contract for academics is very evident: "Men 60,29% - Women 39,71%, that is accentuated by moving from lower to higher career positions: Grade A: men 80,18% - women 19,81% - Grade B: men 62,70% - women 37,30% - Grade C: men 68,17% - women 31,83%".

Quite the same about the proportion of women grade A/B/C staff: UNILE has to note that there is not a profile in staff; among staff grade B UNILE has 60% men and 40% women; among staff grade C, UNILE has 54,47% men and 45,53% women. In the administrative field, UNILE can note that only a few women are in a leadership position.

We can note that female professors are more numerous in humanistic areas, than in scientific areas; in the

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biologic area UNILE has a similar distribution between female and male professors, while in the other areas, male professors are more numerous than female professors, above all in mathematics, physics and engineering. The only exception is in antiquity sciences, literary philology and artistic history areas, in which female professors are always more than male professors.

Main problems

According to the internal assessment the main issues that were identified regarding recruiting procedures are the followings: 1) recruitment boards are mainly composed by males (68,32% men members of recruitment or promotion boards and 31,68% women; only 33% of recruitment boards have a woman as President. In 10% of recruitment boards, there are only men); 2) success rates of man and women applicants are quite unbalanced among the different departments.

Objective(s)

The goal is to redress the balance by sensitizing every level of the University to a more gender-responsive approach.

Possible solutions

- Since the internal regulations are linked to the national ones, UNILE are collaborating with technical and discussion tables and groups for the possible changes.
- UNILE will promote the organization of webinars/seminars for sensibilization of personnel in the didactic and research departments of the university. They will also encourage the implementation of some guidelines for hiring committee members with notes on the gender issues and needs.
- UNILE will keep updated the Rector, the General Director and the head of the human resources department on the internal situation and figures concerning the men/women personnel ratios

Resistances

The expected resistances are first from internal stakeholders. Resistances are coming from the rules or structure of the organization: the internal regulatory structure is still too much based on strong neutrality, leaving no room for positive action. The way Unisalento's organization is structured, particularly at the middle/upper level: there is a strong cultural resistance to using administrative discretion in favor of modifying structures that could contribute to achieving equal opportunity. Resistances are also coming from the administration: still too few women occupy positions of leadership, highlighting a strong resistance to opening to gender equality at top levels. Even if for a public structure like Unisalento the two aspects between organization and administration are deeply intertwined, highlighting similar resistance. The middle management tends to comply with top management decisions and, therefore, there is no resistance, other than that identified for top management. Other resistances could be coming from high management: the resistance that is evident is primarily cultural, as noted above. There are also resistances coming from researchers, in this area, too, there is evidence of cultural resistance linked to the limited space left in favor of positive action by the internal regulatory structure. Finally, there is no evidence of resistance from students; on the contrary, student organizations are sensitive to gender issues.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first argumentative. In Unisalento a cross-departmental group has been set up (connected to the Unisalento+ project) in favor of the implementation and awareness of gender policies, coordinated by the rector's delegate for gender policies. These actions should be implemented since only by raising awareness of gender policies it is possible to hope for innovation in internal regulations. There are also strategies touching the rules of the organization like to modify internal regulations in favor of gender policies. Other actions have been identified such as actions for the dissemination of gender culture provided by the three-year plan for positive actions year 2020/2022, and its possible intertwining with the performance plan of Unisalento. In Unisalento a cross-departmental group has been set up (connected to the Unisalento plus project) in favor of the implementation and

awareness of gender policies, coordinated by the rector's delegate for gender policies.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are from internal stakeholders. Opportunities could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization, a modernization of the rules in favor of a more flexible organization. They could also be coming from the administration, encourage the use of administrative discretionary power in a technical and not pure sense, and thus encourage an approach that objectively evaluates the skills of candidates for a role, overcoming gender bias. Other opportunities could be coming from middle and high management, researchers and students. It is to overcome gender-related biases with reference to grade level.

2. Working environments and conditions

Situation

To start, most of parental leaves are taken by women. The percentage of leave days used by women is equal to 93,32% and teleworking is also used by a greater percentage of women. To continue, no policies on equal pay are in place, so that for example, women administrative manager work for a pay 1,93% lower than man's pay; and with regard to academics, UNILE notes a not-negligible gap between man and woman, with peaks of 5.66% difference to the disadvantage of women among grade C professors under a fix-term contract. Next, there is a quite high % of employees are not aware of work-life balance measures. Not all employees are aware of existing work-life balance measures: teleworking/remote working (more than 65%), part time posts (more than 60%), leave (maternity, paternity, adoption,...) (more than 75%), sabbatical leave (more than 70%), with even lower percentages if UNILE talks about other measures, as ones to support return (after leave) (about 15%); reduction and/or flexible hours for childcare (more than 30%); reduction and/or flexible hours for other reasons (more or less 30%); job sharing (only 10%). Even a percentage of respondents – even if low (generally less than 10%) – think that the work-life balance measures listed in the survey are not available in the institution, with peaks of more or less 20% regarding to measures adopted to support return (after leave), reduction and/or flexible hours and job sharing, who reaches 30%. To finish, negative evaluation of working environment (according to the survey): there is a non-negligible percentage of the respondents to the survey (21,6%) thinks that the climate is negative and a 15,6% declares not to be satisfied with the job, alongside another 8% of responses with a negative content (so and so, not always, it depends...). Even the percentage of people satisfied with the workplace is quite low, only 62,2%; the remaining percentage expresses a negative evaluation, not only who chooses to answer “no” (33,3%), but also all the others (14,5%), who give open answers to underline negative aspects.

Main problems

Work-life balance measures are mostly enjoyed by women, not all university employees are aware of the measures available and the burdens of care seem to be carried predominantly by women.

Objective(s)

The goal is to rebalance the situation, sensitizing every level of the University to an approach more oriented towards gender equality.

Encourage the construction and permanence of a serene working environment free from discrimination, abuse of power and interpersonal conflicts, where diversity is perceived positively as a source of personal and professional enrichment and not as an element of negative competition.

Possible solutions

- To promote information seminars on existing measures of work-life balance and stimulate with questionnaires a greater awareness of the use of these measures in a more balanced measure between men and women and of the need to ensure adequate reconciliation not only in relation to the burden of care for children, but also for the elderly.

Resistances

The expected resistances are coming from internal stakeholders. First, the internal regulatory structure is still too much based on strong neutrality, leaving no room for positive action. As the Unisalento organization is structured, especially at the middle/upper level, there is a strong cultural resistance to using administrative discretion in favor of modifying structures that could contribute to the achievement of equal opportunities. Resistances from middle and high management and researchers are the same as in the previous topic.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first argumentative as for the previous topic. There could be also other actions like to make transparent and knowable the existence of all the measures developed by Unisalento to improve work-life balance through appropriate forms of publicity: not only those already known as telework/distance working, part-time and the different types of leave; but also and especially those less known as those in support of return after leave, reduced and/or flexible hours for childcare, reduced and/or flexible hours for other reasons. In Unisalento a cross-departmental group has been set up (connected to the Unisalento plus project) in favor of the implementation and awareness of gender policies, coordinated by the rector's delegate for gender policies. These actions should be implemented since only by raising awareness of gender policies it is possible to hope for innovation in internal regulations.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are from internal stakeholders. In Unisalento there is already a community - composed of individual professors, researchers, administrative staff, students - that is particularly sensitive to working wellbeing, overall attentive to gender policies, even if, as indicated in other sections of the report, there are still situations of great imbalance. Therefore, the implementation of the desired actions would lead to a greater and further consolidation of respect and inclusiveness in the different areas of the community of Unisalento, for example, the introduction of career alias for transgender students

3. Career support and development strategies

Situation

According to the internal assessment, with reference to the career progression (economic or formal) the problem that emerged is that the institution takes measures that are governed by the national regulation and by national collective labour agreements. Such measures do not include any specific actions concerning female career progression.

Main problems

There are no specific measures to support women's careers.

Objective(s)

To redress the balance by sensitizing every level of the University to a more gender-responsive approach.

Possible solutions

- The issue could be further explored through a survey of the steps and timing of the evolution of women's careers in university in correlation with significant events in personal and family life.

Resistances

The expected resistances are from internal stakeholders. First, they could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization such as inertia in the activation, implementation, and development of internal regulations in a manner favorable to staff needs. Same resistances could be coming from the administration and middle management; in a public structure like Unisalento, the two aspects of organization and administration are deeply intertwined, highlighting similar resistance. No resistances are expected coming from high management (an inclusive trend is indicated), from researchers (if not limited

to particularly delicate sporadic cases) and from students.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first argumentative as in the previous topics. There could be also other actions like actions for the dissemination of gender culture provided by the three-year plan for positive actions year 2020/2022, and its possible intertwining with the performance plan of Unisalento.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are from internal stakeholders. In Unisalento there is already a community - consisting of individual professors, researchers, and administrative staff, students - that is particularly sensitive to working wellbeing, overall attentive to gender policies, even if, as indicated in other sections of the report, there are still situations of great imbalance. Therefore, the implementation of the desired actions would lead to a greater and further consolidation of respect and inclusion in the different areas of the community of Unisalento.

4. Career breaks and re-employment

Situation

in the last 5 years, 4 women and just a man chose a career break, without pension entitlement. UNILE does not count people who left the university to be recruited by other administration.

In 2019, UNILE had career breaks both among administrative staff and professors not because of discrimination/mobbing, but only due to voluntary resignation and assignment in other administrations or to career changes, aimed at best chance of work-life balance (better remuneration, home proximity, more adjustable work schedule).

Concerning the female researchers' career, UNILE has no specific data about the reason of their resignation. But, according to the national trend in STEM, it can be due to a male oriented cooptative culture, or to the strictness of promotional criteria and awards, or to the lack of funds and measures appropriate to their support.

Main problems

In general, the trend noted above is due to a male-oriented co-op culture, or the rigidity of promotional criteria and rewards, but also to the lack of adequate funds and measures to support them. There is no adequate career protection for women in conjunction with pregnancy and childbearing, in part because of the lack of services such as crèches and study support services, as well as a more explicit focus on skills when assigning a role.

Objective(s)

To redress the balance by sensitizing every level of the University to a more gender-responsive approach.

Possible solutions

- Since in many cases the causes of career interruption are unknown, a study could be promoted to investigate through an exit questionnaire for instance.

Resistances

The expected resistances are from internal stakeholders. The same types of resistances have been identified coming from the rules or structure of the organization, the administration, high and middle management and researchers (see previous topics).

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first argumentative. In Unisalento a cross-departmental group has been set up (connected to the Unisalento plus project) in favor of the implementation and awareness of gender policies, coordinated by the rector's delegate for gender policies.

Opportunities

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

The expected opportunities are from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization, a modernization of the rules in favor of a more flexible organization. Others could be coming from the administration like to encourage the use of administrative discretionary power in a technical and not pure sense, and thus encourage an approach that objectively evaluates the skills of candidates for a role, overcoming gender bias. Opportunities coming from middle and high management, researchers and students are the same; to overcome gender-related biases with reference to grade level.

Governance

1. Enhancing women leadership and access to top positions (academic and administrative levels)

Situation

While in the delegate positions there is substantial parity between men and women, the top positions (Rector, Administrative Director and The President of the Auditors) are occupied by men. The largest gap is noted within the following bodies: the academic senate, that consists of 4 women and 16 men, and the Board of Directors, that is composed of 2 women and 8 men.

The Heads of Department are all men but one. In the administrative sector, between the 21 units' administrative heads, 11 are assigned to women. Only a couple of top positions are held by women (as rectoral programs coordinator and advocacy).

Main problems

The main problem is the under-representation of women in all governing bodies and leadership positions:

The number of full women professors is less than 20% of the total and they are often not sufficiently encouraged or supported to apply for (elective) leadership positions.

There is also a cultural problem, linked to the tendency to consider leadership positions more suitable for men.

Objective(s)

The goal is to increase the percentage of women in governing bodies, even though the starting numbers are much lower. Insert gender constraint in votes where a double preference must be expressed (this requires a change in the bylaws).

Possible solutions

Possible strategies that could lead to a reversal of the trend and, therefore, to an overcoming of the critical points noted are:

- modify the mechanisms and regulations that lead to the election and appointment in governing bodies and top positions (action at the national level), cooperating with and encourage and support female colleagues for application for senior government positions;
- annual gender budget that photographs the situation;
- information action leading to involvement and cooperation among women in departments and at the university level;
- seminars/courses on unconscious biases and mentoring program

Resistances

The expected resistances are from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization. There is a potential passive, implicit, gender-related personal resistance, both individual and group, both internal and external, with a predominantly cultural origin, due to the tendency to consider women unsuitable for leadership; as well as there exist very strong personal or group interests for which inserting women could be seen as a "diminution" of power. Next, resistance is expected at the

administrative level due to the existence of national laws and hiring and promotion methods that do not favor women. To finish, resistance is expected from men in higher academic career positions.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative; the existence of national laws prohibiting discrimination can be a valuable tool to support the actions you want to propose.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are from internal stakeholders. First, they could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization. One significant opportunity is related to the policies of the new Rector, who has shown more attention to female representation among the delegates and has appointed a female vice-Rector. Support for the initiative may also come from the delegate for gender equality and the CUG. In particular, he reinstated the delegate for gender policies. Secondly, opportunities could be coming from middle management. It is expected that several women within the University who are aware of the situation and eager to implement change will support these initiatives.

Research

1. Research contents and methods (gender as a dimension to be considered in framing research questions and designing research methods)

Situation

There were just a few research projects and theses integrating a gender dimension in the last 3 years, and all of them in Humanities Department. Nothing to report for other departments.

There were no post-doc research fellowships for gender studies.

Allocation of funds addressed to gender issues has been provided by the CUG (Unique Guarantee Committee), which promoted investigations generally about work-life balance, but not on the research content.

There wasn't any training on the integration of gender analysis into research in the last 3 years.

Main problems

- Gender integration into research content is not applied in UNILE.
- Institutional policies or guidelines on the integration of gender analysis into research have not been set until now.

Objective(s)

Carry out gender or gender-sensitive projects.

Possible solutions

- To implement the exchange with other higher research institutes (like INFN and CNR)
- To encourage the exchange of best practices, in order to facilitate joint design on gender issues or gender-sensitive criteria.
- To promote raising awareness campaigns to reinforce the knowledge of the topic and its importance.
- To elaborate an institutional procedure on the integration of the gender dimension into research & innovation.

Resistances

The expected resistances are from internal stakeholders. They are expected to be coming from the rules or structure of the organization: there is a potential for active, explicitly gendered, institutional, and especially

group-based resistance.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first argumentative. On the initiative of the Delegate of the Rector to gender policies, A.M. Cherubini, it is planned to organize cycles of seminars involving researchers from centers of excellence at the international level, aimed at the exchange of best practices and knowledge of each other's projects, methodologies, actions. Next, possible strategies could touch the rules of the organization, plans are being made to modify internal regulations in favor of gender policies. To finish, there could be other actions such as actions for the dissemination of gender culture provided by the three-year plan for positive actions for the year 2020/2022, and its possible intertwining with the performance plan of Unisalento.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are from internal stakeholders. First, some opportunities could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization and the administration like the aging of the rules in favor of a more flexible organization can be considered an opportunity. Secondly, some opportunities could also be coming from middle and high management, researchers and students. The opportunity is that UNILE will be able to leverage the willingness to overcome gender bias found at this level of the organization.

2. Gendered roles in research delivery (also very relevant for HR -career progression)

Situation

On 207 projects, the 20,29% of projects managers are academic female investigators. In general, in each department or research center, women managers are represented in a very low percentage, lower than 30%. Only in Humanistic Studies Department, academic female investigators with project manager rules reach the 77%.

If UNILZ considers the total data of the last 3 years (2017-2019), the percentage of women in patenting research is equal to 50%, with a percentage of 54% in 2019. But if UNILE considers each department, UNILE can observe that in Biological and Environmental Sciences and Technologies, the number of women is quite higher than men, with a percentage of more than 70%. Women are equally represented in patenting research in Mathematics and Physics Department, with 50% of women and 50% of men. In Innovation Engineering Department, women reach 43% in patenting research. Nothing to report for others Departments.

In UNILE a Gender/women's studies department that may support relevant activities exists. It is the Woman Observatory (Osservatorio Donna), a study centre that includes both university staff (academic and administrative) and people outside the university. It was founded in 1990 to investigate gender issues, diversity and equal opportunities.

Certainly a positive aspect is that at least in the humanities area there is a large percentage of projects coordinated by female colleagues, reflecting the higher percentage of women in those types of (non-STEM) departments.

Main problems

- The problem is related on one hand to the lower percentage of women who continue their academic careers in STEM departments and on the other hand to the lack of adequate tools to support design, also in relation to the greater family and personal burdens that are typical of women. These issues are driven by the lack of adequate policies to support women in their careers.
- Also the share of female PIs and project leaders in STEM projects is very low. There is also a cultural problem for female students and young researchers (precarious) related to the misconception that there are greater difficulties in being able to assert themselves as women, mainly related to the misconception that men have more charisma, authority and competence in management and leadership roles related to STEM disciplines.

Objective(s)

The goal is to have a balance in the management and coordination of research projects between men and women, across all departments.

Possible solutions

- to set up training courses, starting as early as compulsory schooling, but especially focused on PHD students or postgraduate students willing or interested in pursuing a research career in which the foundations can be laid for eliminating misconceptions and prejudices and making girls more aware of their abilities and possibilities for acquiring roles and skills identical to those of men. Pathways should involve both male and female students and families.

Resistances

The expected resistances are from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization.: passive and implicit resistance, both internal and external, is reported, mainly related to the implicit tendency for men to assume leadership and/or management positions, at the same career level.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative; change is in the hands of women researchers, since there is no specific decision, but attitude and mindset.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are from internal stakeholders. Opportunities could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization, support may come from colleagues who endorse this vision.

Teaching**Situation**

In the last two years (2018 and 2019), there was a training course promoted by UniSalento Osservatorio Donna and addressed to deans, office heads, administrative and didactics coordinators, to increase knowledge and awareness of non-sexist use of language. The initiative had so much success that the next year it will be suggested to all university staff.

There were no training courses/workshops for researchers which focus on the gender dimension in research content in the last 3 years.

There were 4 university courses addressing gender issues in the last 3 years.

There were few gender specific courses in History, Society and Human Studies Department.

There were no PhD seminars on gender studies in the last 3 years.

Main problems

- Gender issues are the subject of study in some departments of the humanities (department of history, humanities and cultural heritage), thanks to the sensitivity and attention paid to these issues in particular by some teachers.
- There is not a widespread awareness of the transversality of these issues with respect to the different courses, as regards teaching methods, methods of evaluation, use of language and communication.
- Interesting initiatives, such as the interdisciplinary didactic project UniSalento+, aimed at deepening through seminar meetings themes such as Gender Issues, Sustainable Development, Peace and Rights, Inequality and Racism, remain isolated initiatives, as they are based exclusively on the adhesion and voluntary contribution of individual teachers in charge of seminar

interventions.

Objective(s)

The goal is to achieve a greater widespread awareness of the transversality of gender issues, not necessarily in terms of content of disciplinary research, since as such it could be congruent only with some and not with all scientific fields, but rather as a factor related to teaching methodologies, assessment techniques, language choices.

Possible solutions

Promoting initiatives of an informative and formative nature that can promote this greater awareness among teachers. This could take place not only on purely thematic issues, but also on the best practices adopted (both in our University and in other academic realities) in the sign of adopting a gender sensitivity in teaching, including through the establishment of a Committee for the enhancement of Gender Sensitive Teaching. This Committee could be the promoter of structured and ongoing initiatives, and could identify and enhance the best practices that already exist, so that they represent a catalyst for greater widespread awareness.

Resistances

The expected resistances are from internal stakeholders. First, they could be coming from middle management. A potential widespread cultural resistance should be noted, which could manifest itself both in implicit and explicit terms, on the part of those who see this aspect on a secondary level, as became clear in some of the interviews conducted. Setting up a committee, on the other hand, could make the importance of gender-sensitive teaching official, inducing an implicit perception of monitoring of teaching action (which in the university, on the other hand, is protected by the freedom of teaching content, always referring to the frames of the scientific disciplinary sectors). Secondly, resistances could be coming from high management, as with any change that adds to the workload, it is possible that the project will come up against some resistance, both explicit and implicit.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative. An important argument in favor of the change to be proposed is the need to adapt to an evolution that is already taking place at the European level, given that the adoption and implementation of the GEP, and therefore of concrete measures aimed at ensuring gender equality, will soon become a necessary requirement for access to sources of European Community funding.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization. A significant opportunity may be represented by the sensitivity of teachers who have joined the GEP working group and who are already working to implement gender-sensitive methodologies. Others could be coming from researchers; probably some sensitivity to these issues could be manifested by researchers in departments engaged in teaching disciplines, which could promote in their research an in-depth study of these issues and best practices. To finish, opportunities could be coming from students, significant curiosity, and attention to gender-sensitive teaching is expected by students. Secondly, some opportunities are expected from external stakeholders. Opportunities could be coming from the academia; significant opportunities could arise from collaboration with other university clusters that have implemented appropriate measures in their gender equality plans and might be willing to engage in a constructive exchange of experiences on best practices in use.

Students and services to students

Situation

In the last 3 years, the percentage of female university students enrolled in STEM is always 24%; the remaining 76% is enrolled in Humanities. The trend is constant.

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In 2019/2020 in scientific degree courses, there were enrolled 2837 male students (equal to 58%) and 2038 female students (equal to 42%). Among the PHD Students in the same year UNILE has 79 male (equal to 55%) and 64 female (equal to 44%). With regard to the distribution per STEM field and level, UNILE can observe that in engineering there is the evident prevalence of male students over female students, with 76% and 62% of male in degree courses and doctorate courses respectively.

In mathematics and biology, on the contrary, there is a more balanced distribution, but slightly in favour of female students.

Concerning the collected data, interesting insights are offered when comparing the STEM higher education students at national level and the ones at UNILE level, since in the first case females are the minority (35,6%) while in the second one the great majority (73,2%).

Observations on the initial situation :

It should be noted that the prevalence of the female component within the University is mainly due to the prevalence of humanistic courses over scientific ones. But, in fact, the prevalence of the female component is not a constant within the various courses of study: for example, the prevalence of the female component observed in the Biology courses cannot be observed in the Engineering courses. The latter, in particular, are those in which the presence of the female component is particularly minority.

Main problems

- UNILE is not following a plan of systematic initiatives that offer gender-sensitive information/guidance to prospective students.
- Although the choice of a university course is now more free than in the past, the fact that in various cultural and professional fields male examples prevail in some cases, and female examples in others, can condition high school students to not adequately value their own aptitudes when choosing a university course.

Objective(s)

The objective is to avoid that the choice of university study path may be subject to gender bias, encouraging and supporting the access of male and female students to courses where they are respectively less represented.

Possible solutions

- The strategy that is considered useful to achieve the objective is to give greater visibility to the less represented gender in the areas of study where gender disparity is most evident, through the presentation and the enhancement of significant examples of the less represented gender alongside those of the more represented gender.
- To this end, it is proposed to carry out continuous seminars of information and dissemination in high schools, presenting representative figures of both genders in different scientific-disciplinary areas, in collaboration with representatives of the productive world and/or civil society, telling their stories.
- In a broader vision, which takes into account the relevance of multiple discrimination, the presentation of examples of differently endowed people who have made a significant contribution to the scientific-disciplinary or professional field of belonging could also be valued.
- the establishment of 2 scholarships, each to be awarded on merit among female and male students respectively, for example to promote the choice of courses of study in which the respective genders are less represented, or to reward dissertations in disciplines chosen less frequently by the respective gender. The scholarships could be funded by the Municipality, the University's SPIN OFFs or external companies.

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Resistances

The expected resistances are from internal stakeholders. Resistances could be coming from the administration. There may be some implied resistance stemming from skepticism about the relevance of gender conditioning to university choice and more explicit resistance related to the organizational difficulties involved in implementing any new project or initiative.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are touching the rules of the organization. The University's Guidance Office is sensitive to issues of inclusion and overcoming gender disparities and this will likely be a strength in the implementation of these outreach initiatives.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are first coming from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from the administration. The guidance office has shown itself to be sensitive in promoting suitable activities to encourage the orientation of high school students and therefore could willingly welcome an initiative that increases the effectiveness of its action and mission. Opportunities could also be coming from students; it can be assumed to have the availability of the students of the last years of the course and of the doctoral courses to promote informative and popular initiatives in the schools. Secondly, opportunities are expected coming from external stakeholders. First, they could come from civil society; public entities could be involved in funding scholarships. Next, opportunities could be coming from the government/public sector; the schools will welcome the initiative with interest as it supports one of their tasks, which is to encourage the orientation of students to the choice of university studies. To finish, some opportunities could also be coming from industries/business stakeholders, they could be involved in funding scholarships.

Transfer to Market

Situation

UniSalento is very active in terms of spin-offs, even though legal representatives are almost exclusively males.

In the last year, UNILE have had less than 10% of female speakers, less than 20% of women invited and less than 30% of oral contributions from women. Nothing to report for the other departments.

As for the Department of Mathematics and Physics, in the last three years (2017-2019), 80.4% of the speakers were men and only 19.6% were women.

In 2017/2018, 66 students applied to participate in Contamination Lab Classroom: 44% of them were female students. 51% of those admitted were women, but the percentage of boys (53%) who completed the activity was higher than the percentage of girls (47%). In 2018/2019 the number of all students who applied was much higher: 143 applications were in fact submitted. 45% of them were girls; 48% of admitted students were female, but this time the percentage of female students (55%) who carried out the activity was higher than the percentage of boys (45%). In 2019/2020, 74 students asked to participate: 44% of the applications came from girls, and the same percentage were admitted. Again more girls than boys did the activity: 54% were girls and 46% boys.

Main problems

- UniSalento has many collaborations in place with research projects, and it also organizes training activities focusing on knowledge transfer to innovation. However, it does not take any measures regarding gender when transferring scientific results to the market. Also there is currently no adequate institutional language in regulatory and administrative documents.
- A great imbalance is visible when considering participants to STEM conferences since speakers are mainly male.
- In relation to the 14 teams of the university spin-off, it can be noted that the relevant positions

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(legal representative of the company or member of the University within the board of directors of the company) are occupied by men, with the exception of only one relevant position occupied by a woman.

- In the Department of Mathematics and Physics, the women involved in collaborative research projects co-financed / co-managed with companies or other stakeholders are 28%.

Objective(s)

Increase the percentage of women with leading roles in spin-off initiatives, and increase the percentage of women participating in conferences in such a way as to rebalance the situation, raising awareness at all levels of the University of an approach more oriented towards equality of kind.

Possible solutions

- Take some measures to encourage women, such as encouraging initiatives promoted by women;
- support incentives with promotional initiatives; entrust women with seminars and success stories led by women;
- encourage the issuing of calls by public administrations supporting initiatives promoted by women. Another solution to this problem could be to give women economic bonuses, such as that for babysitting.
- Joint activities can be planned with regional bodies, thanks to regional development policies and related funds, with a focus on innovation.

Resistances

The expected resistances are coming from internal stakeholders. First, they could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization: there is fear of taking initiatives in this direction, a lack of financial resources, cultural aspects, and reticence; bureaucratic, legal and administrative difficulties. Next, same resistances could be coming from the administration and middle management, in a public structure like Unisalento, the two aspects between organization and administration are deeply intertwined, highlighting similar resistances. To continue, they could be coming from high management. The Rector, the President of the Region, the University and the members of the Regional Council report that it was considered that it is not necessary to adopt measures sensitive to gender equality to improve the transfer to the market, because UNILE already exists, for example, the Contamination Lab that has this specific function. No resistances are expected coming from researchers, if not limited to particularly delicate sporadic cases. To finish, there is no resistance coming from students, on the contrary there is sensitivity in favor of gender arguments on the part of student organizations.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first argumentative (see description of Unisalento+ project in previous topics). Strategies could also address the rules of the organization such as to modify internal legislation in favor of gender policies and to create more links between research and the territory and more business opportunities. There could also be other actions like to create more opportunities for the area and increase the level of employment.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization. There is already in Unisalento a community that is particularly sensitive to work well-being, overall attentive to gender policies, even if, as reported in other sections of the report, situations of great imbalance still exist. Therefore, the implementation of the desired actions would lead to a greater and further conscious consolidation of respect and inclusion in the various areas of the Unisalento community.

Communication

Situation

With regards to protocols on gender-sensitive non-biased communication/language use, the institution itself does not have, but there is a guideline from the Ministry about the non-sexist use of language. Anyway, UNILE does not see much discriminatory effect in the choice of language or images. The visual part of the social media accounts promotes gender equality, with photos presenting both genders, and in some cases, more women than men. The content that is published through the posts includes any activities that are taking place in this respect.

Turning to the website content about gender equality, currently, there is not, but an institutional web page of Vice-Rector for gender equality and his team is in preparation.

During the last two years, significant initiatives have been carried out, like a communication training course, named 'The gender-oriented language in Public Administration', with 480 men and 636 women participating.

Also an event for University and High School Students, dedicated to Women in Stem and including a play about Women scientists was planned by the Vice Rector for Gender Policies for march 2020, but it has been postponed because of the pandemic.

Main problems

The examination of the current communication material, surveys and interviews show that there is individual sensitivity to communication. Precisely based on individual sensitivity, on the site and in the institutional communication materials produced centrally (posters, brochures and the like) attention is paid to images (presence of both men and women, attention to stereotypes, use of colours, etc.) and to language.

However, as it is not an institutionalized approach, this sensitivity is not uniform in all communications (forms, "decentralized" communications and others). There is a lack of guidelines establishing "binding rules" regarding the language and images to be used in official documents.

A few years ago, a course open to technical staff was held, called the "Summer School of Difference", in which numerous educational initiatives were promoted by teachers and employees.

But these gender equality awareness initiatives were not permanent and systematic. Even in the recent training initiative aimed at office managers, the attendance score was 0.

The institution's adoption of protocols on communication and sensitive and impartial linguistic use has not been demonstrated. For example, the institute does not organize training sessions on the use of gender-sensitive language in administrative communication.

Objective(s)

Draw up binding guidelines, which refer to the recommendations suggested in the national guidelines¹² and which integrate other related aspects of interest to the project. Make mandatory training and refresher courses on the subject to be organized annually for all university staff.

Within the guidelines, positive actions could be included regarding women in STEM (actions aimed at making the representation of women in STEM more frequent).

Possible solutions

¹²http://www.funzionepubblica.gov.it/sites/funzionepubblica.gov.it/files/documenti/Normativa%20e%20Documentazione/Dossier%20Pari%20opportunit%C3%A0/linguaggio_non_sessista.pdf;
https://www.miur.gov.it/documents/20182/0/Linee_Guida_+per_l_uso_del_genere_nel_linguaggio_amministrativo_del_MIUR_2018.pdf/3c8dfbef-4dfd-475a-8a29-5adc0d7376d8?version=1.0

- Apply binding guidelines for a "gender sensitive" use in institutional communication in all documents produced within the administration at all levels (from the change of name of the "history of society and human studies" department to the use of a gender sensitive language in documents and forms, etc.).
- A training could be envisaged to support the establishment of such guidelines/protocols on gender-sensitive communication, as well as establishing a complaints mechanism in cases of sexist/gender communication.

Resistances

The expected resistances are from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization, there could be laziness in the creation of new institutional documents, cultural aspects. Other resistances could be coming from the administration and middle management, the rector, General Manager, Academic Senate, Department Heads. Resistances could also be coming from high management, rector, General Manager, Academic Senate, Department Heads, Communications Delegate, Gender Policy Delegate, EOS Group, CUG.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first argumentative such as emphasising the fact that formalising good practices already in use can add value to them. Secondly, some strategies could touch the rules of the organization like supporting the drafting of guidelines based on existing good practice.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are coming from middle management. Some teachers and administrators are sensitive on this issue.

Intersectionality

Situation

At the moment in UNILE there are not any institutional measures where gender is taken into account in conjunction with other discriminations or structural inequalities

There was only an informative initiative addressed to students but open to others university members, promoted by the student component of CUG to raise awareness about other kind of discriminations not related with gender

Main problems

- There is no awareness of this issue. Discriminations are considered and treated in isolation, without considering them in their possible intersection, and therefore there is no collaboration and exchange between the various offices responsible for dealing with them.
- Diversity is not a reality of which there is awareness, also because numerically it is always insignificant.

Objective(s)

The objective is to promote greater awareness of the importance of multiple discriminations and the complex effects they produce when they intersect. Awareness of the theme of intersectionality can help to deepen and enhance the widespread sensitivity that the University constantly demonstrates in welcoming and taking charge of the uniqueness of each person with his or her specific needs, and to integrate and make more effective the good practices already in place in the management of differences.

It is proposed to overcome some structural and organizational limits of the internal functioning of the offices, making them more aware of the importance of integrating measures to support diversity and multiple inequalities (gender, disability, culture, religion, language, socio-economic status ...), to amplify the positive effects of this sensitivity already present in interpersonal relationships.

Possible solutions

To include intersectionality in data collection and to promote information, awareness and training actions aimed at all components of the academic world (administrative staff, teaching staff and students), connecting the various offices in charge (in particular, the integration office, the legal office, the office for the right to study ...) and enhancing - where present - their best practices.

Resistances

The expected resistances are first from internal stakeholders. Some resistances could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization, middle and high management, and administration. It is necessary to consider a certain explicit resistance inherent in all processes of change and which will presumably be put into play both at a purely administrative level, by the internal commissions of the various offices, and at management level (at various levels). Some resistances could also come from external stakeholders. They could be coming from civil society. It is necessary to consider the sensitivities of the students themselves and their families, who are directly or indirectly affected by the communication initiatives and measures to combat all forms of discrimination, implemented in the academic environment, as these actions lead to identifying and giving visibility to the diversity that exists. Implicit external resistance cannot be ruled out.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are argumentative. The strongest argument in support of these actions to promote a culture marked by intersectionality, is the opportunity to see enhanced and recognized at the institutional level a sensitivity already present - even if mostly without knowledge of European policies on intersectionality - in the actions put in place by the offices responsible for accepting the uniqueness of each case / situation within the University. Other actions could be done to overcome the resistances. It is possible to highlight the best practices that already exist, concerning: some cases of students who have brilliantly achieved the degree, facing and successfully overcoming the difficulties related to a learning disorder or a condition of socio-economic deprivation and precariousness; the collaborative projects carried out with the Prison of Lecce both to ensure the right to study and to promote integration projects through art-therapies; the studies on special education for integration; the thematic paths of study promoted by students, for example on sexual dynamics in relation to disability. It would be possible to carry out brief interviews with those who have personally benefited from these best practices, to give visibility in a more immediate and popular way on a page of the University website dedicated to the Project.

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from researchers, an interest in this topic can be expected from teachers interested in integration and special education and intercultural education, who should be involved in appropriate meetings for information and critical discussion of these issues. Others could be coming from students, a student working with the Integration Office, who is very sensitive to the issues of interest, could be involved with other students to collaborate with these synergistic actions.

Sexism and sexual harassment

Situation

UniSalento does not have any official policies and initiatives addressing sexual harassment yet. But anti-mobbing and anti-harassment regulations have been passed, and the trusted advisor will be appointed shortly.

In the meantime, Cug is the body in charge of receiving complaints about mobbing and harassment.

Main problems

- The institution hasn't put in place any complaint mechanisms in cases of gender-biased/sexist communication. It has disciplinary bodies and has the right to impose sanctions, following internal

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investigations. Of course, any person who suffers harassment also has the right to initiate formal external complaints.

- Institutional language in regulatory and administrative documents is not yet adequate.
- There is currently no adequate policy for the protection of students who are in the process of changing sex (transgender students).
- There is no gender balance in the presence of women and men in governance bodies and top positions, as noted in the human resources section.

Objective(s)

The goals are first to redress the balance by raising awareness at every level of the University for a more gender-equal approach. Next, it is to create an approach to the protection of victims of violence and raise awareness at every level of the organization for anti-mobbing and anti-harassment policies. To finish, it is to devise an appropriate privacy policy for transgender people.

Possible solutions

- the appointment of a focal point for bullying and harassment, such as a trusted adviser. This appointment should be followed by an effective information campaign.
- Preparation of internal regulations with binding guidelines that guarantee language that respects gender equality.

Resistances

The expected resistances are from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization. Resistance factors are inertia in the activation, implementation, and elaboration of the above-mentioned regulations. It should also be noted that, in the absence of a consolidated regulatory orientation on more innovative issues, such as the alias career for transgender students, a more conservative and restrictive interpretation prevails when it comes to implementing positive actions in this sense. Resistances could also be coming from the administration and middle management, in a public structure like Unisalento; the two aspects of organization and administration are deeply intertwined, highlighting similar resistance. No resistance is expected coming from high management; rather, an inclusive trend is indicated. There are also no resistances expected coming from researchers, except limited to particularly delicate sporadic cases.

Possible strategies to overcome the resistances are first argumentative (see description of Unisalento+ project in previous topics and the three-year plan for positive actions for the year 2020/2022).

Opportunities

The expected opportunities are from internal stakeholders. They could be coming from the rules or structure of the organization. In Unisalento there is already a community that is particularly sensitive to working wellbeing, overall attentive to gender policies, even if, as indicated in other sections of the report, there are still situations of great imbalance. Therefore, the implementation of the desired actions would lead to a greater and further consolidation of respect and inclusiveness in different areas of the community of Unisalento: for example, the introduction of career alias for transgender students.

Synthesis of stakeholders to involve

To overcome the described resistances and use afore-mentioned opportunities the following internal stakeholders need to be involved: the governing bodies of the University, bodies at every level of the administrative structure and the Student Council and Student Associations to change the organizational rules and to accept and implement the proposed strategies; people who will be impacted by the strategies (each organizational structure so research, teaching, administration and representation). External

stakeholders also need to be involved, especially stakeholders from the public sector (governing bodies at the local and national levels); high schools (principals, teachers, students and their families);

Some actions to be taken to ensure stakeholders' collaboration (both internal and external) are working tables to share project results, gender budget and positive action plans; to redesign and adapt the action plan to support internal policies and initiatives; training/information actions on gender issues; to involve leaders; to build relationships and partnerships with institutions and external groups to promote and facilitate networks; to involve sensitive, active and proactive teachers in the planning of information initiatives; to disseminate information on best practices implemented in other academic contexts; to involve schools in information and awareness activities aimed at families; and training / information actions regarding the fight against sexism, harassment and gender-based violence.

3 Results of the multi-stake holder dialogues

3.1 Set-up of R&I Hubs

CALIPER R&I Hubs have been established during task T2.2 (one Hub per partner). The description of the external stakeholders that are part of each Hub is presented in the RPOs/RFOs corresponding sections (see sections 3.3 to 3.11). These stakeholders participated in the first round of multi-stakeholder dialogues described in this document. Other stakeholders can also join in the future.

For the establishment of the R&I Hubs, most partners proceeded with the creation of informal networks of stakeholders but are considering to eventually formalizing them by the adoption of a Memorandum of Understanding (see Annex).

In the next section, we present some aggregated data regarding the participation in the multi-stakeholders dialogues.

3.2 Aggregated data

Overall, 212 women and 49 men participated in the multi-stake holder dialogues (Figure 1). According to this, women seem to be more involved than men.

Figure 1. Gender of overall external stakeholders

The stakeholders that participated in the multi-stake holder dialogues come from different areas: academia, industry and professionals, civil society organizations, ministries and government and the public sector. Figure 2 represents the type of the stakeholder that participated in the dialogues. The two most present types of stakeholders are members of academia (76 participants) and industry actors and professionals (65 participants). 32 participants come from civil society organizations. The public sector, ministries and governments, are represented by 21 and 19 participants respectively.

213

Figure 2. Type of external stakeholders

Figure 3. Number of possible collaborative actions by type of stakeholders and by area¹³

A number of potential collaborative actions between the RPOs/RFOs and external stakeholders were explored. Regarding the type of collaborative actions by type of stakeholder (figure 3), most of the possible actions involve members of the academia, especially in the areas of human resources, students and student services, teaching and research. Many explored potential collaborative actions involve also the industry, especially in the areas of transfer to market and student services. Some collaborations have been explored with civil society organizations, especially in the areas of student services and teaching. A few collaborative actions involve the public sector, ministries and governments.

¹³ Some actions are included twice because they involve more than one stakeholder.

3.3 University of Zagreb – Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing (RPO)

Description of the R&I Hub

The R&I Hub is formed by 6 stakeholders from the academia, 7 companies, 3 stakeholders from the ministries and government, 3 stakeholders from the public sector and 2 civil society organizations.

Type of stakeholder	Stakeholders
Academia & universities (6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faculty of Philosophy, University of Rijeka • Croatian Science Foundation • Faculty of Organization and Informatics, University of Zagreb • Faculty of Science, University of Zagreb • Faculty of Mining, Geology and Petroleum Engineering, University of Zagreb • Faculty of Transport and Traffic Sciences, University of Zagreb
Industry (6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • STEMI • Q agency • Ericsson Nikola Tesla • MamforceCROZ • Visage Technologies • Končar - Inženjering za energetiku i transport d.d.
Ministries/Government (3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Central State Office for the Development of Digital Society of Republic of Croatia • Gender Equality Office of Republic of Croatia • Ministry of Science and Education
Public sector (2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agency for Science and Higher Education • Agency for Vocational Education and Training and Adult Education
Civil society organizations (2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Women in Engineering Croatia • Penkala

Description of the workshops

The two workshops for the multi-stakeholder dialogues were carried out on the 10th and 11th March 2021. They lasted 2 hours and 24 people participated in total (22 women and 2 men). All the types of stakeholders participated in each workshop. The same topics were discussed in the two workshops: human resources, governance, research, transfer to market, education, student services, harassment, and intersectionality.

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At the beginning of the dialogues, all participants presented themselves, their organizations and expressed their expectations. Most of the participants declared to be familiar with the topic of gender equality and wanted to contribute. In both dialogues, the participants formed quite a heterogeneous group, coming from different organizations (public organizations, academia, NGOs and private companies), education background and positions in organizations (university professors, CEO-s, human resources experts, R&I employees, policy advisors, middle managers).

Then, a project team member presented the project CALIPER and results of the *Internal and external gender equality analysis of UNIZG-FER*. They presented the main findings for each topic explored in analysis: human resources, governance, research, and transfer to market, education, student services, harassment, and intersectionality. They chose to cover all topics in both dialogues because the group of participants was quite heterogeneous in both dialogues and they wanted to get their feedback on the topic that they are the most familiar with. As this was their first multi stakeholder dialogue they could not predict their preferences and experiences, so the University of Zagreb opted to cover all topics in both dialogues.

They discussed the results of the analysis of UNIZG-FER, the current situation in their organization and what are the possible actions could be undertaken together.

Not all the topics covered in the CALIPER project raised equal attention in the multi-stakeholder dialogue. Therefore, they could not envisage joint synergies for every topic after the dialogue. The general attitude is that external stakeholders should not influence internal institutional process of an academic institution such as UNIZG-FER. One reason is that the independence of an academic institution is guaranteed by the law and another that UNIZG-FER is perceived as very successful institution which does not need external involvement. There were doubts expressed that internal change of UNIZG-FER is needed, since the roots of the problem of lack of women in STEM come from the society. The result of these opinions is that most of the envisioned joint synergies are focused on external change and organization of events in which the participation is voluntary.

Shared challenges for gender equality

All involved stakeholders agree that there is a problem: the low number of women in STEM related jobs. For private companies and RPOs, it is very hard to find qualified candidates to fill available job positions. Therefore, higher participation of girls in STEM studies is our joint challenge. It is a general opinion that the lack of women in STEM has its roots in society and not at universities. Glass ceiling is noticeable at RPOs and private companies in STEM. However no collaborative actions were proposed during the multi-stakeholder dialogues. It was reported that the number of female PI is not satisfying, however it remains to be determined which actions could comply with Croatian legal system. As for teaching, it would be interesting to explore the topic of gender sensitive teaching and curricula in STEM courses. It is a concept that university professors are not familiar with but are willing to explore more.

- Cross-cutting challenges: lack of awareness for gender equality, glass ceiling, lack of women in STEM fields.
- Specific challenges:
 - **Human resources**
 - All RPOs face low number of female students in STEM faculties, exceptions are programs for high schools' professors in STEM.
 - Companies have a low number of female employees in STEM related jobs.
 - **Governance**
 - Companies and RPOs have a low number of women in management positions.

- RPOs and RFO do not have a Gender Equality Plan.
- **Research/research funding**
 - RFO reports a low number of female principal investigators in STEM, however there is a high number of women employed at the Croatian RFO.
- **Teaching**
 - RPOs do not know what is gender sensitive teaching and curricula.

Portfolio of strategic opportunities

Most of the participants declared to be familiar with the topic of gender equality and wanted to contribute. Some of them declared that they are familiar with the measures for gender equality in place in their institutions and that they have participated in awareness raising actions. Most of participants are willing to propose new measures for gender equality in their institutions, but do not have their own suggestions now. Some organizations participate in European projects which aim to attract girls and women in tech jobs and to raise awareness about prejudices in STEM. After the dialogues, university of Zagreb can conclude that participants showed the most interest in organizing actions for attracting women in STEM, to learn more about which internal measures for gender equality are possible to implement the Croatian legal frame and to jointly develop practices for gender sensitive teaching and curricula in STEM courses.

The following strategies have been identified in each topic:

- **Human resources**
 - Collaborative actions for attracting women in STEM (role models, access to high school students). RPOs, private companies, NGOs expressed their interest in participating. These actions should be developed together in future webinars. Stakeholders are willing to participate but it is expected that CALIPER team will organize these events. Private companies and RPOs envisage their participation by finding suitable employees that can be female role models. NGOs can use their communication channels to advertise external collaborative actions.
- **Governance**
 - To help other RPOs establish their own Plan for Gender Equality, in collaboration with RPOs and Ministry of Research and Education. Considering that European Commission imposed new eligibility condition for applicants for Horizon Europe funding, it is an emergency for RPOs develop their Gender equality plans. The RPOs would like to learn from UNIZ-FER therefore the project team would be responsible for organizing workshops.
- **Research**
 - Enable discussion with RPO and RFO about possible measures for empowering female researchers in STEM. The goal is to have higher number of principal investigators in STEM. It is not clear if quotas or other measures that are in place in EU can be introduced because there are no examples of good practices in Croatia; it is unknown what is legal. Project team should organize the collection of examples of good practices in EU and organize webinar to report on these findings to the interested national stakeholders. RPO's and RFO expressed willingness to lean about the possible measures but cannot commit to the implementation now.
- **Teaching**
 - Training with RPOs about gender sensitive teaching and curricula. The notion of gender sensitive teaching is not well known, and it is unclear how this can be applied to STEM topics. Project team should organize training and with professors from other RPOs. Some participants are STEM university professors of didactics and methodic and their input could be valuable. In fact, there are

no professors of didactics and methodic at UNIZG-FER, therefore knowledge can be shared both ways between the organizers, internal and external participants.

Summary of possible collaborative actions

The following collaborative actions have been identified:

- Collaborative actions for attracting women in STEM, with RPOs, private companies and NGOs. These actions should be co-created in future dialogues. The CALIPER team will organize these events. Private companies and RPOs can recommend female role models. NGOs will advertise external collaborative actions.
- Joint trainings with RPOs about gender sensitive teaching and curricula. These actions should be co-created in future dialogues. The CALIPER team will organize these events. UNIZG-FER does not have professors of didactics and methodic. Some stakeholders are STEM university professors of didactics and methodic and their input could be valuable. The knowledge can be shared both ways between the organizers, internal and external participants.

3.4 Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia (RFO)

Description of the R&I Hub

The R&I Hub of the SRNSFG is formed by 18 stakeholders from the academia, 1 from the industry sector, 1 ministry, 5 stakeholders from the public sector and 2 civil society organizations.

Type of stakeholder	Stakeholders
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Academia (18)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University (state) • Petre Shotadze Tbilisi Medical Academy (private) • Georgian Technical University (state) • Caucasus University (private) • University of Georgia (private) • Tbilisi State Medical University (state) • Ivane Beritashvili center of experimental biomedicine • Batumi Shota Rustaveli State University (state) • Georgian Academy of Science (state) • East European University (private) • Caucasus International University (private) • Iakob Gogebashvili Telavi State University (state) • Ilia State University (state) • Tbilisi Vano Sarajishvili State Conservatory (state) • Georgian Institute of Public Affairs (private) • Georgian National Museum (state) • Akaki Tsereteli State University (state) • G. Eliava Institute of Bacteriophages, Microbiology and Virology
Industry (1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Georgian Farmers' Association
Ministries/Government (1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Education, Science, Culture and Sport of Georgia
Public sector (5)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Georgian Innovation and Technology Agency • Korneli Kekelidze Georgian National Center of Manuscripts • Enterprise Georgia • National Food Agency • National Intellectual Property Center of Georgia
Civil society organizations (1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Center for Social Sciences • Gender Studies Institute

Description of the workshops

Two workshops for the multi-stakeholders' dialogues were organized on the 10th and 11th March 2021 and they lasted 4 hours each. A total of 37 people participated (34 women and 3 men) from the academia, the public sector, and the civil society. All the topics (human resources, governance, research, transfer to market, education, student services, harassment, and intersectionality) were discussed in each workshop.

The events were conducted via online platform (ZOOM). SRNSFG together with participant stakeholders held workshop/ dialogue on integrating gender dimension in STEM. The first part of the meeting included

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project presentation and overviewing current gender equality situation in SRNSFG, opportunities and challenges in this regard. The second part of the meeting was dedicated to revision of strategic change scenarios, implications, common problems, and possible collaborations as part of the roundtable discussion format.

Shared challenges for gender equality

Under cross-cutting challenges section challenges which are in place at SRNSFG were reviewed and shared with other stakeholders according to each topic (human resources, governance, research, communication, intersectionality, sexism, and sexual harassment). Under specific challenges section challenges which are specific for different stakeholders according to each topic were discussed (human resources, governance, research, communication, intersectionality, sexism, and sexual harassment).

- Cross-cutting challenges:
 - **Human resources:** Most of stakeholders shared the same challenges as SRNSFG in Human Resources sector (non-existence of gender-sensitive recruitment protocols/policies at organizational level; internal measures for the improvement of work-life balance; appraisal systems for career evolution; internal policies/regulations for the career support and development).
 - **Governance:** Most stakeholders share similar challenges in governance, since they have no strategies/policy to foster gender balance in the decision-making process, lack of clarification in gender equality regulatory documents/articles, non-existence of policy for female career advancement and gender equality body, which ensures gender balance in the organization and on the top positions, hereby monitors gender equality situation inside the organization.
 - **Research:**
 - Stakeholders do not administer targeted gender specific programs.
 - No requirement for gender equality in research teams and gender dimension in research content.
 - **Communication:**
 - Existing stereotypes about the capacities of women.
 - not sufficient policy on institutional communication.
 - **Intersectionality:** The stakeholders agreed that there is a misconception of the intersectional approach within the organizations, as well as the lack of specific skills and experience to deal with the topic among the members of the organizations.
 - **Sexism and sexual harassment:** Through the workshops, some common challenges have been identified: The lack of information, problem awareness and the absence of a specific prevention policy; Low priority issue.
- Specific challenges:
 - **Human resources:** Gender sensitive data is not collected.
 - **Governance:** Non-existence of structural unit, responsible for specifically gender data collection and analysis; not regulated remuneration policy for maternity leave in private sector organizations (varies in accordance with organization's will from).
 - **Communication:** unawareness of society on some gender related issues (intersectionality/sexual harassment).
 - **Research/research funding:**

- Already existing internal regulation which prohibits discrimination on the grounds of sex, but do not imply a preference for gender, including in research.
 - There are no special guidelines on gender equality for researchers and grant applicants.
 - No requirement for gender quotas in the projects.
 - Gender experts are not involved during project implementation procedure.
- **Intersectionality:** no specific challenges have been identified; all participants shared the same challenges as SRNSFG
- **Sexism and sexual harassment:** In the case of some stakeholders, the main challenge is ineffectiveness of the existing mechanism.

Portfolio of strategic opportunities

Under cross-cutting strategies section, strategies identified by SRNSFG and shared by other stakeholders according to each topic (human resources, governance, research, communication, intersectionality, sexism, and sexual harassment) were analyzed. Under specific strategies section strategies which are specific for the different stakeholders according to each topic (human resources, governance, research, communication, intersectionality, sexism, and sexual harassment) were discussed.

- Cross-cutting strategies¹⁴:
 - **Human Resources:** Most of stakeholders shared the same opportunities as SRNSFG in Human Resources sector (no need to have special decrees of supervisor bodies, in case of new regulations no contradictions with the existing legislation system) which will help to implement the necessary changes, such as improvement of working conditions and work life balance and adoption of gender-sensitive policies and regulations.
 - **Governance:** Elaborating specific policy to support female career advancement and set priorities in this regard; Creating opportunities for positional promotion of female employees.
 - **Communication:**
 - To organize specific seminars and to conduct raising awareness campaign.
 - To use all communication tools: media, webpages, sites, context tailored publications.
 - Ministry's active role in gender balance-oriented events.
 - Jointly organize activities related to gender sensitive relationships and raising awareness.
 - To encourage gender research program, under which various sub-programs will be implemented (targeted activities / activities).
 - To link a specific section of the Foundation's website to other stakeholder websites / analytics.
 - To set apart and highlight gender statistics from other data.
 - Extract gender component from the competition statistics as a separate statistic.
 - To organize events focused on gender specific issues and raising awareness, to plane events for the targeted audience.

¹⁴ For instance, a cross-cutting strategy to overcome the lack of 'volunteers'/time to carry out gender equality work could be to integrate the gender dimension at all levels of the institution so that gender equality efforts are not an 'extraordinary' task, but an 'ordinary' one,

- To integrate gender component in civil education.
- To organize online trainings.
- To ensure the possibilities for choice (online training/onsite training).
- **Research:**
 - Development of gender specific programs and grant calls (STEM and other).
 - Creating guidelines on gender stereotypes and unconscious bias to evaluators.
 - Promoting gender dimension in the content of scientific research by integrating gender dimension in current programs and calls for proposals.
- **Intersectionality:** Most of the stakeholders agreed that a broader legal framework about gender equality in the country does not restrict the organizations to initiate the tailor-made policy and elaborate specific institutional mechanisms that consider gender in conjunction with other discriminations.
- **Sexism and sexual harassment** - Adopting a prevention policy; Setting up a realistic reporting mechanism for sexual harassment in the workplace as well as a monitoring mechanism in order to register complaints; Identifying a special group, position or body that will work on the issue of sexual harassment; Conducting/Attending trainings on this topic (Civil Service Bureau of Georgia is currently developing a specific module for organizing such kind of trainings); Organizing campaigns/activities that aim at raising awareness on the issue.
- Specific strategies:
 - **Human resources** - Existence of Training Center increasing the qualifications of HR staff; Provision of gender sensitive health insurance (during pregnancy and post-partum) and additional funds and conditions; Existence of teleworking and part-time positions.
 - **Governance** - Raising qualification of HR personnel towards gender related topics; Elaborating specific recommendations for gender career advancement; Gender related issues to be envisaged as a criterion in accreditation process for HEIs and other organizations; Monitoring of fulfillment of gender equality policy implementation.
 - **Communication:** Some Georgian Universities have remarkable progress related to the raising awareness, by organizing gender related events such as: Celebrating Women's History Month, Celebrating a 16-Day Global Campaign, the History of Women Scholars, public lectures of women researchers, Festival - "Women and Music" and concert. Some state universities are marking series of events dedicated to Georgian women researchers, successful female researchers' achievements. The private sector, as Georgian business association, has a specific rubric of successful women, rubric of products produced by women, their coverage and promotion.
 - **Research:**
 - To organize and create relevant events/materials:
 - Webinars - women in science, with the participation of foreign colleagues.
 - Trainings.
 - Brochures about gender equality in research and science.
 - Videos to promote women in research and science.
 - Promoting STEM fields in secondary schools.
 - Active involvement of external international actors in the process of raising awareness

activities.

- Dissemination of gender-related issues (collection and dissemination of personal experiences of individuals / researchers) and promoting publicity.
 - Create a written document for the protection of gender sensitive language.
 - Implement gender sensitive budget.
 - Adopt gender quotas system in the projects and programs.
 - Support and encourage female scientists and researchers to hold higher positions.
- **Intersectionality:** Some positive steps are already in place in several organizations, such as: a document on Prevention of Violence towards Women, Gender Equality Regulating document, maternity leaves to women (with 6 months of payment). These could present as opportunities to the other organizations to initiate similar changes within their organizations considering the specificities of their field. Additionally, possible strategies might include number of proposals identified by the participants such as: establishing task force which will provide recommendations on adoption of an intersectional approach; encouraging staff to become more open towards an intersectional approach; sharing experience, including international one, on how to raise awareness on intersectional approach, formulate it properly and gradually adopting it; planning joint events/discussions on practices of intersectional approach.
- **Sexism and sexual harassment:** Several important steps have already been taken by some of the stakeholders. For instance, some stakeholders check whether its employees have any criminal conviction records against sexual offences by requiring the relevant certificate. Some of the stakeholders also have internal regulations ensuring general safety in the workplace and others have an ethics commission responsible for harassment matters.

Threats:

- Lack of interest and motivation among the staff of the organization.
- Lack of awareness and low priority of the issue.
- Breaking stereotypes concerning women in top positions as an uncomfortable factor for male coworkers.
- Different perception and differently implemented gender equality policy and supporting female career advancement in the organizations.
- Additional duties and responsibilities for staff in the organizations.
- Possible internal and external contradiction for the integration of changes.
- Lack of resources.
- Not sufficient readiness to introduce changes.
- Risks of misperception of topics (intersectionality/sexual harassment).

During the dialogue, the strategies to overcome the threats were briefly discussed. Main strategies mentioned were raising awareness and promotion of different activities for the popularization of the issue. Some collaborative actions mentioned in next paragraph are also addressing the issue. Besides that, stakeholders discussed different examples of other countries dealing with same threats.

Summary of possible collaborative actions

The following possible collaborative actions have been identified with different stakeholders:

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Academia & Universities

- Collaboration between stakeholders' top managements in the format of workshops/meetings to initiate the changes in legislative and regulative documents.
- Provision of awareness raising joint activities.
- Creating representative council of the organizations and regular meetings to share information regarding the gender policies and implementation of relevant activities.
- Plan joint events and activities.

Public sector

- Participation in the elaboration process of National Strategy for Human Rights from 2021.
- Sharing experience and provision of recommendations and consultations.
- Plan joint events and activities.

Civil Society

- Creation of the mechanisms that would foster establishing a common ground among the stakeholders with an aim of gradually adopting an intersectional approach.
- Start collecting the intersectional data within the organization (sex, ethnicity, age, disabilities).
- Collaboration in terms of developing gender-specific programs.
- Plan joint events and activities.

3.5 Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava (RPO)

Description of the R&I Hub

MTF STU organized two dialogue meetings. The date of dialogues played an important factor determining the composition of the workshop's participants. The invitation was supported by telephone interviews and the presentation of the internal and external analysis results and conclusions of the project issues carried out in Slovakia. The dialogues were led by members of the project team, with the participation of working group members. The diversity of the organizations contributed to a greater degree of involvement and to the application of the so-called brainstorming way of conducting dialogues.

Type of stakeholder	Stakeholders
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Academia (19)

- Faculty of Industrial Technologies, Trenčianska univerzita Alexandra Dubčeka v Trenčíne
- Faculty of Management, University of Presov
- Faculty of management and economics, Tomas Bata University in Zlin
- Faculty of Business and Economics, Mendel University in Brno
- Faculty of Manufacturing Technologies with the seat in Prešov, Technical University of Košice
- Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, University of West Bohemia in Plzeň
- Faculty of Economics and Management, Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra
- University of Constantinus the Philosopher in Nitra,
- Department of Geography and Regional Development
- Faculty of Electrical engineering and informatics, Technical University of Košice
- University of Zilina
Faculty of Operation and Economics of Transport and Communications
- University of Chemistry and Technology, Institute of Economics and Management
- Faculty of Corporate Strategy, Vysoká škola technická a ekonomická v Českých Budějovicích
- Faculty of Mining, Ecology, Process Control and Geotechnology, Technical university of Kosice
- Faculty of European Studies and Regional Development, Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra
- Slovak Academy of Sciences
- EIT RawMaterials Regional Center Kosice
- Research Centre, University of Zilina
- Kempelen Institute of Intelligent Technologies

Industry (14)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lear Voderady Ltd • Autoservis Béhr & Béhr – Citroën Ltd. • VUB Leasing Corp. • MKB servis Ltd. • CESys Ltd. • SEPS Corp. • Lexis Ltd. • ANTRE Ltd. • Performance Consultants Ltd. • Orange Slovakia, a.s. • Boge Elastmetall Slovakia a.s. • Schaeffler Slovensko, spol. s r.o • Stellantis N.V. • Slovnaft, a. s.
Ministries/Government (3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of the Slovak Republic • Trnava Self Region • Trnava City
Public sector (2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institute of Geodesy and Cartography • Všeobecná zdravotná poisťovňa, a.s
Civil society organizations (0)	

Description of the workshops

Two workshops for the multi-stakeholders' dialogues were organized on the 4th and 19th March 2021 and the first one lasted 2 hours while the second one lasted 3 hours. A total of 51 people participated (29 women and 22 men) from the academia, the public sector, the government and companies. The following topics were discussed; human resources, governance, research, teaching, communication and intersectionality. Those topics were discussed in each workshop.

The organization and course of the two dialogues meetings differed significantly. The reason was the variability of the way of conducting the dialogue in order to capture the outputs as widely as possible. MTF STU (hereinafter also the "faculty") is connected with external entities, primarily on the basis of research results implementation and the transfer of knowledge. Mentioned topics including gender diversity and equality were also key in the workshops. The discussion then covered other topics, such as management in the creation of a scientific council at the faculty from stakeholders. It is an important condition in terms of the progress of the faculty, when external partners are invited to the scientific council of the faculty in order to connect the needs of practice with the theoretical level. This increases the effectiveness of the interaction of all parties involved. Gender equality is a key issue for balancing gender balance and the creation of the Scientific Council should be respected as a part of the faculty's GEP.

Another topic was the issue of communication and intersectionality, i.e. how events should be communicated to the outside of the faculty, especially in connection with external entities and as events that are exclusively within the competence of the faculty, which is an internal matter. At the beginning of both dialogues it was found that the issue in meaning of gender equality was known to the stakeholders, but they had no experience with the specific implementation of gender plans and this policy. At the same time, on the other hand, it was emphasized that they were interested in the given topic and would like to implement the applicable research conclusions themselves.

The first workshop: at the beginning, the aim of the meeting was explained and then the participants were invited to present themselves and their experience with gender policy within their institution. The individual institutions were represented by participants, who have connected with management and were competent to act as a link between STU BA and their institutions in order to implement gender equality support actions. Subsequently, STU BA presented the conclusions of analysis performed at MTF STU and the further direction of the project. Research and teaching dialogues were more intense than other topics. The possibilities of cooperation and the project outputs implementation in their institutions were discussed. Not all stakeholders expressed interest in this regard, but they offered research support as information providers. More interest in collaboration was expressed especially by institutions from the academia sphere and the government body. All in all, the discussion was very interesting and beneficial for all participants, according to the statements at the end of the meeting.

The second workshop was organized with a larger number of diverse participants from various institutions. Even cooperating partners from abroad, from a neighbouring country - the Czech Republic, which is not directly involved in the project, they were also actively involved as Best Practice. The basis for the organization of this workshop was the premise of experience with gender equality, which created a broader premise for the development of dialogue. The purpose of the Open dialogue was to obtain more information given the advanced stage of implementing this issue in practice. HEIs (RPOs), companies, insurance organization, self-government body of the City of Trnava and Trnava self-governing region were represented. In this case, the dialogue was supported by the main input topics from practice, in which dialogues were subsequently conducted. Again, the main topics were concerning research and teaching, particularly equality, diversity, and inclusion at the workplace.

The aim was to briefly present the CALIPER project, its current state and overview of the challenges at the beginning of the meeting. After that, the vice-rector of the University international relations and public relations presented the topic of "Interconnection of research and innovation with aim to support gender equality and diversity at STU in Bratislava". She expressed her willingness to support gender related actions at the university. After that, the vice president of Board of Healthy Insurance presented the topic of "The role of women in top position" with really positive feedback from the participants. The next presentation was done by the vice dean for internationalization from Faculty of Business and Economic in Brno, titled "Women in science are still on half way" with relevant gender recommendation in their institution. After that, the topic "Women in top positions in corporations" was done by CFO of Schaeffler Slovakia, Ltd. The last presentation belonged to the dean of the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, titled "Research and innovation with aim to support gender equality and diversity in Mechanical Engineering, West Bohemian University in Pilsen with best practices". During the final discussion, common topics were identified with stakeholders and other partners as well as best practices and strategies were exchanged and further opportunities for cooperation explored.

Shared challenges for gender equality

The analysis and dialogues did not reveal a too low proportion of women in STEM studies at STU BA. Earlier, a declining trend was subsequently found in the research and government of RPO. This problem has its origins in history and society as a whole. The MTF STU itself supports the STEM study, and several ways to improve communication in all areas have been identified. In external organizations themselves, this problem is the same and is not caused by employers, although the Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic

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regularly publishes statistical outputs that present lower salaries of women in the national economy in comparison with men, this difference being more than 15 %. Based on the conducted research, it was found that women are afraid to "ask" for a pay raise.

The second overall problem is set by the social system, where female PhD. students are not entitled to maternity benefits from the social system as they have not yet directly contributed to GDP.

Overall, it was considered that there is a need to support the increase of women's representation in qualified and managerial positions in the field of STEM in order to achieve the balance of the ecosystem within the internal and external environment of each institution. No specific conclusions or steps were seized at the meeting to take steps to increase this representation. However, the common denominator was open communication and readiness to actively work on this topic supported by top management of involved institutions.

- Cross-cutting challenges:

Raising awareness of the effectiveness of gender mainstreaming, improving communication in this area, increasing the representation of women in management positions. The challenges for dialogue on the part of stakeholders are to maintain attention in the field of gender equality without misinterpretation in relation to feminism. An important challenge is to connect the professional areas in which the faculty operates with the policy of gender equality and in the framework of Trnava research on the market, as well as in the field of professional training of students in synergy with raising awareness in the field of gender equality. The interview emphasized the observation of stakeholders with a low representation of women in leadership positions.

- Specific challenges:

- **Human resources**

1. In this area, it is an important precondition for the modification of the legislative aspect in the gender area in relation to the adjustment of formal and procedural rules by the inclusion of a gender-sensitive language. We see the challenge in a formal uniform approach applied with a historical background.

2. To increase the representation of girls in professional STEM studies and maintain representation in the study of management

- **Governance**

The need for statistical reporting of gender issues in relation to research is not implemented in reporting, nor is the function of a body for the administration of gender issues specifically fulfilled. Although this issue is promoted by government authorities through specific non-profit and non-governmental organizations through calls and competitions such as "Entrepreneur of the Year", there is still no automatic implementation of this issue in both social life and professional functioning of various institutions operating in Slovakia.

- **Research/research funding**

The challenge that has been identified is the need to fund research to address practical issues and to find ways to activate projects with gender issues financed from sources other than grant schemes

- **Teaching**

The challenge in the field of teaching is to educate students so that they have established ethical principles in the field of gender and can automatically apply them in practice. Although the university no longer operates at the level of student education, we still feel the need to reintegrate this aspect into the teaching process.

Include topics devoted to gender issue and diversity in curricula more.

➤ **Students and services to students**

The subject area has been assessed at a relatively sufficient level, although there is always room for improvement. Communication is the key to a successful institution, keeping in mind that communication entails outgoing and ingoing information that is both delivered and received in a lucrative manner. The golden rule to communicating effectively is that the communication is collaborative, not competitive. No matter how brilliant and invaluable the idea, it is worthless unless we can share it with others. For this reason, effective communication is crucial at every level of the faculty. It is therefore necessary to streamline the communication activities in the form of presenting the faculty externally, so that the faculty is perceived as one with an established gender equality strategy both by external entities, but especially by potential and current students. The second level is internal communication, which effectively uses communication channels within the internal environment in order to increase awareness of gender policy.

➤ **Intersectionality**

Intersectionality is rather presented by the Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic, which monitors the area of remuneration of women and men, while pointing out the still persistent difference. This problem was not directly registered directly in the indoor environment of stakeholders.

Portfolio of strategic opportunities

- **Cross-cutting strategies:**

One of the conclusions was the adoption of the intention to raise awareness of the gender issue in each participating institution. Highlight the effectiveness of this policy, entrust those responsible for managing this policy within the institutions and engage in research on gender equality issues on an ongoing basis.

- **Specific strategies:**

➤ **Human resources**

1. External communication of the faculty in matters of gender equality will be preferred, which will increase awareness and motivate women to study at STEM and to increase their qualification growth.
2. One of the conclusions was to increase the awareness of the value of the acquired STEM knowledge and its implementation in practice among girls, which would lead to breaking down prejudices.
3. Opening the promotion of the study by role models - women successful both in research and in practice, where cooperation with external stakeholders is needed.

➤ **Governance**

1. Given the strict criteria for skills growth, the strategy we propose is to focus on supporting women in how to be successful in achieving their goals, setting up a support system through the ambassador. This will remove low representation of women due to family obstacles, because of the slow progress in career growth and failure to meet the criteria required to represent the position.
2. Assistance of high management of the faculty and the university as well as in setting up a gender equality plan.

➤ **Research**

The first problem that emerged from the dialogues was the low involvement of women in research compared to men as members of a team. In this case, it is not possible to set an internal policy in the definition of quotas within the ratio of women and men working on projects in terms of the legislative process, as this could be considered discrimination within the professional level if the limits restricted work on the project from the point of view of gender equality. The strategy should only be about motivation. The second issue is the involvement of gender equality in research, the use of grant schemes that are "listed" in

the context of gender equality, as well as distinguishing between research and projects focused exclusively on gender equality and professional projects with the gender equality context.

➤ **Teaching**

Updating of curricula based on practical experience in gender issues and setting practical needs for colleagues of professional teachers. We would like to achieve this by providing professional lectures for colleagues and students in individual events. We see the benefit of lectures for colleagues in the fact that we would increase their awareness in this area, point out the new possibility of connecting the professional side of subjects with the issue of gender equality. Lectures, or events, would be organized by guests - experts in this field.

➤ **Students and services to students**

We see improvement through the adjustment of communication, directing students' attention to the possibility of engaging in open dialogue in this area. Opportunity to express oneself not only on the basis of their own findings, but by presenting specific topics that would be compiled directly by gender experts in order to increase the conformity of students in interpersonal relationships and increase the sense of balance in their lives. The overall process should take a casual form using their close means of communication and leave them the certainty of anonymous expression when needed.

➤ **Communication**

The faculty uses basic means of communication. Stakeholders have shown willingness to promote the project with an emphasis on pointing out the benefits of gender strategy. Based on this, a strategy of open communication with stakeholders was developed in the representation of academia, research centre, and government bodies with the possibility of direct participation in their professional events, which will spread awareness in this area. Students of the faculty will be directly involved in the improvement of communication, who will point out the possibilities of its improvement in terms of bringing its form and style closer to young people.

➤ **Intersectionality**

We will enable its inclusion in the gender strategy by establishing the position of an ambassador who will monitor this area.

Summary of possible collaborative actions

A joint promotion of transparent gender policy will be organized with the support of the project and project actions in order to attract women to STEM studies. The theme will be further developed in joint dialogues based on regular repetition. Continuation of cooperation is based on the sustainability of the future implemented strategy within the scope of shared experiences of external stakeholders. The principle of sustainability will be ensured by constantly reaching out to new potential stakeholders, who will present new experiences. Women's role models will be addressed in order to raise awareness of the value of education and its application in practice. The output of the project will be implemented into existing events organized by MTF STU as well as STU BA.

3.6 Université libre de Bruxelles (RPO)

Description of the R&I Hub

The R&I Hub of ULB is formed by 3 actors from the academia, 3 stakeholders from the industry and professional sector, 2 Ministries, 5 actors from the public sector and 3 civil society organizations.

Type of stakeholder	Stakeholders

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Academia (6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Université de Liège • Université de Mons • Université de Namur • Vrije Universiteit Brussels • Fonds de la Recherche Scientifique - FNRS (National Fund for Scientific Research) • L'Observatoire de la recherche scientifique - FNRS (Scientific research observatory)
Industry & professionals (7)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Réseau LIEU • Sopra Banking Software • Energy Business Line at TRACTEBEL • P&G • VIVAQUA • Solvay • Elia
Ministries/Government (3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direction de l'Egalité des Chances du Ministère de la Fédération Wallonie-Bruxelles (Directorate for Equal Opportunities - Ministry of the Wallonia-Brussels Federation) • Direction de la Recherche scientifique du Ministère de la Fédération Wallonie-Bruxelles (Directorate for Scientific Research – Ministry of the Wallonia-Brussels Federation) • Cabinet de Christie Morreale, ministre de l'emploi, de la formation, des droits des femmes en région Wallonne. (Christie Morreale office, minister of employment, of trainings and of women rights in the Walloon region.)
Public sector (5)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service public de programmation Politique scientifique - BELSPO (Public Programming Service for Science Policy) • Conseil Bruxellois de l'Egalité entre les Hommes et les Femmes (Brussels Council for Equality between Men and Women) • Actiris (regional employment policy body) • Public Education Department of the City of Brussels • Equal.Brussels (policy of the Secretary of State for Equal Opportunities for the Brussels-Capital Region)
Civil society organizations (3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amazone • Interface 3 Namur • BeWise (Belgian Women in Science)

Description of the workshops

Two workshops were organized on the 9th and 11th March 2021 with different stakeholders. A total of 20 participants (4 men and 16 women) participated in the workshops (some of them participated in both). In the first workshop the topics discussed were related to the internal functioning of ULB (human resources, governance, teaching, sexism and harassment, intersectionality). In the second workshop, the topics discussed concerned the relation of ULB with its R&I ecosystem (research and innovation, knowledge transfer, students and services to students, communication). In both dialogues, participants were members of RPOs, RFOs, professionals, industry, public sector, and the ministry. In addition to the external stakeholders, five members of ULB CALIPER team participated in the dialogues.

Each workshop started with a presentation of the CALIPER project, the introduction of the different participants and the description of the main gender equality problems identified during the internal and external assessment. Following the step, two rounds of discussion were held in which the participants were asked to answer the following questions: What actions and collaborations can be put in place to promote gender equality in the situations identified (including strategies to overcome resistances)?

Shared challenges for gender equality

Cross-cutting challenges:

- A cross-cutting challenge identified by the stakeholders is the fact that many gender equality initiatives exist already at ULB and at other RPOs, but these actions are often put aside of the institution, instead of integrated within its core. Therefore, these activities are usually perceived as ‘extraordinary work’ by the employees, who do not have time to carry them out on top of their everyday tasks. Thus, gender mainstreaming is needed.
- Very linked to that point, a difficulty shared by many stakeholders is the fact that, when gender equality work is not institutionalized, it becomes the responsibility of some motivated individuals. These people end up being very tired (gender fatigue) because they are always alone on the front line and have the impression that nothing changes (especially in front of benevolent sexism). Moreover, these people are often labelled as ‘activists’ and are not taken seriously. They report a loss of credibility.
- Stakeholders also reported that often the approval of gender equality measures depended on the ability of some individuals in key positions to convince the high management.
- Another shared challenge is the fact that often gender equality measures are not accompanied by sanctions if they are not respected.
- Regarding the exchange of good practices and the idea of having a toolbox, the members of the Hub agreed that this exchange can be very useful but at the same time they warned against the idea of ‘one-for-all solutions’ and highlighted that gender equality measures need to be tailored for each institution and each situation.
- Another point of attention is that the situation of women within the STEM disciplines is very similar to the situation of the social and human sciences (feminized disciplines) within academia. Women’s scientific careers in the SHS are not easy either and the unbalanced found in the SHS is linked to the unbalance found in STEM. Institutional change regarding gender equality in STEM needs to be linked to the situation in other disciplines as well.

Specific challenges:

➤ Human resources

- Stakeholders think it is very positive that ULB has an evaluation grid with criteria to

assess academics during the recruitment process. Some RPOs asked if it would be possible to share it with them. However, they also warned that the establishment of a grid can give the impression of objectivity, but does not necessarily avoid gender biases. This is especially the case of the criteria valuing an international career, which are gendered in the sense that it is often harder for women to do research stays abroad if they have a family.

- In this regard, stakeholders suggested to explore in depth work-life balance issues as this could be a barrier to women entering STEM careers. A pivotal moment in this articulation is the end of the thesis because fixed-term contracts are offered, so there is no long-term view. The instability of the research career after the PhD thesis has been underlined by the stakeholders as a barrier for the scientific career of women. However, some RPOs underline that ULB needs to be careful about the image it draw because not all women are mothers.
- Another point of agreement is the importance of rethinking how to evaluate the researchers' career. All tasks need to be valued, not only publication. The University of Ghent seems to have a more qualitative system which is not only based on numbers (number of publications, number of scholarships, etc.). However, the RPOs agreed that the reconceptualisation of the scientific evaluation system needs to be carried out by all the universities together because a single university cannot change the system.
- The topic of gender quotas has also been much discussed during the workshops. A way to increase the proportion of women who are in STEM academic positions would be to establish gender quotas in recruitment but there seems to be an overall resistance to them. Men can be afraid of losing their privileges. Women are often scared of giving the impression that they are in a position because of their gender. Quotas are also a problem in departments or services in which there are only few women: they are called to participate in every commission to respect the gender balance. Some small RPOs shared their concern about quotas as well: they do not recruit a lot of people (there are not a lot of open positions). There is the need to look for alternatives to quotas. From the legal point of view, quotas are allowed in Belgium but only in the private sector. Universities are apparently not included.
- Some RPOs shared a challenge when they wanted to implement a mentoring program for women. They encountered a lot of resistance from different members of the university that did not understand why women would be treated differently.

➤ **Governance**

- The problem of a gender ratio in decision-making bodies in faculties/departments in which women are a minority are shared by the stakeholders.

➤ **Research/research funding**

- Some stakeholders wonder if there is a better way to convince researchers to integrate a gender dimension in research than individual training. However, this personal training needs a lot of resources.
- It is important to have men and women in the commissions. For instance, the commission that selects FRIA's research PhDs projects is usually formed by only men: female students who submit projects find themselves in front of only men who evaluate them, that sends back the idea that the position is perhaps not for a woman.

➤ **Knowledge transfer**

- Some stakeholders drew a parallelism between the situation of gender issues within universities and the situation of the human and social sciences globally. There is a very masculine trend that depicts innovation as a task carried out by an active entrepreneur who is very competitive and looks for exponential growth. Many women do not feel at ease with this image. Also, the idea of spin offs and patents are somehow masculine. In this sense, the question could be whether we change women to make them adapt to this system or change what we value (horizontal collaboration, societal impact). The problem is that university services to society are not valued enough.
- This is reflected on project funding. In the Wallonian region, most calls for projects only focus on profit-making companies. The social economy has little recognition.

➤ **Teaching**

- In the inter-university masters' degree on gender studies the STEM disciplines are lacking. Overall, the importance of gender in STEM teaching and research is not understood.
- The gender perspective should be incorporated in all the pedagogic trainings.
- Regarding the idea of adding a question about gender/sexism in the pedagogical evaluations of teachers, some stakeholders warned that pedagogical evaluations are often a place for students to vent their anger and thus it could backfire on women. It would be important to know if students are aware of their own gender biases when evaluating teachers.

➤ **Students and services to students**

- The lack of girls in STEM studies is a problem shared by most of the RPOs. There is however an exception at the faculty of informatics of one RPO in which the proportion of girls is quite high. This may be explained by the fact that there are also female professors who act as role models for female students.
- All the stakeholders agree that the problem of attracting female (and male) students towards STEM studies must be tackled from the beginning of the problem: from primary and secondary education. A key moment identified by the stakeholders is between 15 and 17 years old.
- A shared challenge at the regional and national level is the overall lack of attractiveness that STEM studies have for students. According to the stakeholders, a fundamental problem is that primary and secondary school teachers are not trained on sciences and technology, so that they do not know how to teach them and awake students' interest. Science education in schools remains very theoretical, boring, and completely disconnected from sciences' societal applications. School teachers have a big influence on students; they can act as role models.
- Overall, there is the need of giving sense to STEM studies and professions to attract students. A 'safe space' for girls is also needed on campus.
- A problem underlined by some stakeholders is that ULB often makes the mistake of "sensitizing" girls with what works for boys: a motivational policy focused on men and not on women. We must pay attention to the girls who chose STEM studies and see how they make their choice, instead of applying to girls "what worked for boys". Girls simply choose in a different way (on average).
- Another important challenge is the communication service of the RPOs: gender-

sensitive communication is essential to attract more female students to STEM studies.

- Finally, there are also social barriers in the access to STEM studies beyond gender (social status, ethnic origins) that need to be addressed.

➤ **Communication**

- There is an overall problem in the type of role models that are often used in terms of accessibility: often they are focused on women who won prizes, CEOs, etc. Many girls encountered self-censorship and the glass ceiling.
- From the point of view of communication, several stakeholders share the challenge of how to attract more girls to the STEM field without reproducing stereotypes (e.g., the idea that girls are more motivated by science's social impact than boys).

➤ **Intersectionality**

- The intersectional point of view has been discussed often underlining the need to consider diversity in all the domains, especially in relation to accessibility (to job positions, to studies).

➤ **Sexism and sexual harassment**

- A study by the Observatoire de la recherche scientifique on the interruption of the doctorate reveals cases of abuse and doctoral students did not feel supported by their institution.
- The stakeholders agree that it is often not clear for most people what a sexist behavior is and what sexual harassment is. Training and communication campaigns are needed in this regard.
- They also claim that the existence of sexism and harassment at university is a barrier for the retention of women in STEM studies.

Portfolio of strategic opportunities

Cross-cutting strategies:

- Gender needs to be mainstreamed in all the levels of the institution to avoid it being a marginal topic. A strategy to deal with this issue could be to establish gender observatories at all levels of the hierarchy and to oblige everybody to be part of them at some point (people need to be trained beforehand). Another strategy for gender mainstreaming could be to establish a 'gender test' for decision-making: all the actions and measures that need a budget should assess their impact on gender. This is already done in the government.
- The role of the university's high and middle management is crucial: they should support the gender equality plan. Gender awareness-raising among this group is thus fundamental.
- Regarding gender equality work, these tasks could be included in the description of all the positions (administrative, academic and governance positions) as fundamental part of the work and they should be valued. The problem is that usually there are no consequences if this is not respected. An inspiring example could be that of the Flanders region. The Flemish government funds universities according to different parameters (publications, etc.). One of them is the 'diversiteit parameter': a bonus of 2% if gender and diversity issues are addressed by the universities.

- Any change promoted should be structural and mandatory. Otherwise, gender equality work will continue to be the fight of a few people (an individual fight).
- A suggestion is to combine equal opportunities policies with affirmative actions (this combination is possible from a legal point of view).
- Another important cross-cutting strategy could be to highlight ULB women's roles and contributions to attract more women's applications to STEM academic positions and more female students to STEM studies. For instance, there could be a dedicated website listing female experts in different domains that can be contacted by external people (e.g., female experts to deal with COVID).
- From the argumentative point of view, instead of making people feel guilty, the focus should be put on the advantages of gender equality.

Specific strategies :

➤ **Human resources**

- To avoid gender biases and cooptation during recruitment processes, applications could be anonymous (although this may be difficult because of the publication list).
- Job offers could be also reviewed before being published to make sure the offer does not include gender biases and the language used is gender sensitive.
- Regarding evaluation criteria, the European University Association develops a project on how to assess academic careers in a fair way.
- Gender quotas can be applied at recruitment and not within decision-making bodies to avoid the problem of extra workload for women when they are not many. However, an examination of what kind of quotas is possible from a legal point of view is needed. If quotas cannot be applied in universities, a joint lobbying action could be launched. It would be also useful to identify what is already done in other universities/organisations in Belgium regarding quotas to be used as an argument.
- In terms of career delivery, professors should have developmental obligations (in terms of gender issues) and there should be gender targets for deans that would be reflected in faculty reports.

➤ **Governance**

- It could be prohibited to organise meetings late in the afternoon and in the evening to promote work-life balance.
- In faculties/departments where there are only few women, the establishment of quotas in decision-making bodies can be problematic. A possible solution could be to identify allies for gender equality work, to train them in gender issues so that they can substitute for women in those cases.
- Given the fact that men are in most decision-making positions, it is essential that they become allies for gender equality so that they can support institutional change.

➤ **Research**

- Research funding agencies could set gender criteria for funding research projects. For instance, there could be a requirement to have gender-balanced teams.
- From the argumentative point of view, the gender dimension of research can be incorporated as an ethical aspect: it is about making science inclusive for everybody.

- The incorporation of the gender dimension in research could be an opportunity to promote research topics that usually out of the radar because of gender biases (e.g., research on endometriosis).
- A very useful tool that can be used to both raise awareness about the relevance of the gender perspective in STEM research and offer examples about how to integrate it is the website 'Gender innovations'¹⁵ (Stanford University). There are checklists for researchers or research evaluators. This website presents case studies that can be very inspirational.
- A study day can be organized on gender bias in artificial intelligence to show why it is important to include the gender dimension in STEM research.

➤ **Knowledge transfer**

- From an argumentative point of view, the incorporation of the gender dimension can be an advantage for marketing strategies (market segmentation - the profit argument can work in some contexts): it could be a good idea to look for companies which already have this policy to collaborate.
- Alternatively, ULB can also change our value system in relation to knowledge transfer: ULB can value more multidisciplinary initiatives and social innovation (innovation that has an impact on society, not on profit). An impact evaluation could be incorporated in research projects. This would also have an impact on research topics since research could be centered upon people's interests.
- In the Wallonian region, the project 'ESCAPE' focuses on social innovation.

➤ **Teaching**

- To convince about the importance of incorporating the gender perspective in STEM teaching and research, the focus needs to be placed on the effects, results, and consequences of STEM research.
- The trainings should not be focused only on gender and sexism, but these issues should be integrated into other trainings. Within these trainings, these topics should be addressed even in provocative way to start a dialogue and have more impact. For example, it could be interesting to do training in general cognitive biases and address gender inequalities at a later stage.
- We need to give these issues time to mature. That obviously makes it very difficult. Therefore, it must be ongoing education and not just one training.
- Adding a question about gender/harassment in student evaluations of teachers could be useful so that teachers can take sexism seriously in teaching and be motivated to get training.

➤ **Students and services to students**

- A team of 'science ambassadors' can be established to visit primary and secondary schools to encourage young people to pursue STEM studies. Female ambassadors could help disseminate the idea that STEM can be also for girls.
- School teachers have a mandatory training per year. This training could be used to help them develop skills on how to teach science and technology without gender biases.

¹⁵ <https://genderedinnovations.stanford.edu/>

Apparently, there is already an initiative of this kind at the UCL (RPO) that could be used as good practice.

- It could also be interesting to do a study in secondary schools to assess towards what type of university studies each school orients students. This could be the basis of a project to help schools to orient students towards other disciplines. A study can be also carried out to understand better how and why girls choose or not STEM studies.
- The intrinsic value of STEM can also be modified by highlighting its societal implications and uses.
- The Wallonian-Brussels Federation leads a project to deconstruct gender stereotypes in schools. This project does not focus on STEM disciplines yet, but there could be a focus on STEM.
- On the Flemish community there are two projects in which the feminist organization Amazon participated. First, the research project 'Female Engineer' in collaboration with a professor from the KULeuven and the think tank 'Vrouw en Ingenieur' of the KVIV (association of engineers). The project identified the obstacles that female engineers face in their careers, but also the obstacles that young girls face when they choose to become engineers (at that time STEM was not yet an issue). Second, the project "The world at your feet" for the Flemish government, of the KVIV (association of engineers), in which 16–17-year-old people were put in contact with real "role models" through "company visits", a seminar on the "world economy", a new teaching method: the Web-Quest, as well as school guidance.
- According to these experiences, the focus should be placed on 16–17-year-old people as there are already many girls in math and science classes at general secondary education: the biggest gap is in access to university and STEM higher education. In other age categories, the initiatives are not very effective. Young people of 16-17 years old should be put in contact with the "real world" by visits to companies, or engineers in front of the class, etc., not by films or brochures: they have been doing this for years at 'Vrouw en Ingenieur' without any results. The material hardly reaches the target group. Cooperation with business/professional organizations, public companies and large non-profit scientific institutions is also needed. We also need "normal" role models, not CEOs or "unattainable" profiles (this may motivate boys, but less so girls).
- We should raise the awareness of people who organize science events of the importance of gender issues. For instance, the organizers of the 'Spring of Science' want to attract students, but they do not think that girls and boys need to be approached differently.
- Non-university higher education institutions can also be targeted to promote STEM studies: they can work as leverage for universities.
- Regarding university studies, some stakeholders suggested that some women-only STEM courses may encourage girls to pursue this kind of studies by creating a safe space.
- One of the RPOs member of the Hub have a high proportion of female students in informatics and engineering shared their good practices to attract girls: they organize a regular cineforum about gender hosted by a professors in informatics, the dean and vice-dean of the engineering faculty are women, there are also many female professors and they organised a study day about exact sciences and women.

➤ **Communication**

- The name of the rooms of the STEM faculties at ULB could adopt women's names.
- To depict intermediate roles as role models.
- To present diversity within women when presenting role models (for instance, to show women with and without children, women from different origins, etc.).
- To train the communication departments in inclusive communication.
- At news events related to science or engineering, the university's communications teams can highlight women scientists who are experts in the field. Women scientists should be made visible in the media.

➤ **Intersectionality**

- To depict diversity in communication activities and role models (see Communication point above).

➤ **Sexism and sexual harassment**

- To establish safe spaces for girls on campus.

Summary of possible collaborative actions

The following collaborative actions have been identified:

- To create a joint initiative of 'science ambassadors' with different profiles (STEM university professors and researchers from different RPOs + STEM industry professionals + civil society organizations) to visit primary and secondary schools. Other RPOs and the industry members are interested in this action.
- To collaborate with the Wallonian-Brussels Federation to deconstruct gender stereotypes in secondary schools regarding STEM disciplines using the already existent programs and tools.
- To create a network of RPOs willing to train schoolteachers on science and technology and gender biases.
- To maintain and develop the dynamic created during this first round of workshops to keep on exchanging good practices for gender equality between the different actors and actresses, especially between the RPOs.
- To create a toolbox of good practices to share.
- To do inter-university lobby to reconstruct the academic landscape (shift of values: quality of research, impact to society).
- To establish a working group with several stakeholders (especially RPOs and Belspo) to explore gender quotas: what is possible in Belgium from the legal point of view, in which organizations they are already established and how, advantages and disadvantages and alternatives to quotas.
- The feminist association is ready to organize a webinar about gender equality in STEM based on its experiences in the two projects described above.

3.7 National Technical University of Athens – School of Electrical and Computer Engineering (RPO)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Description of the R&I Hub

The R&I Hub of NTUA is formed by 7 actors from the academia, 10 stakeholders from the industry and professional sector, 1 agency from the government, 1 policy organisation from the public sector and 4 associations.

Type of stakeholder	Stakeholders
Academia (7)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • University of Crete • University of Western Macedonia • Aristotle University of Thessaloniki • National Center for Scientific Research «Demokritos» • The American College of Greece • University of Western Macedonia • National & Kapodistrian University of Athens
Industry & professionals (10)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IEEE Women in Engineering Greece Section AG • Schneider Electric • Orfium • SG Digital • ITML • OTE Group • Microsoft • Finclude • MADE • Big Pi Ventures
Ministries/Government (1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research Center for Gender Equality
Public sector (1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hellenic Foundation for European & Foreign Policy
Civil society organizations (4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Greek Association of University Women • Hellenic Association of Operational Research • Greek Women's Engineering Association • Centre for Research on Women's Issues

Description of the workshops

Two 2-hour workshops with external stakeholders were carried out on the 4th and 10th March 2021 with a total of 32 participants (28 women and 4 men). In the first workshop, the participants were universities, industries, scientific associations, non-governmental organizations, a policy organisation, professionals, and the research community. The topics discussed included human resources, sexual harassment and gender

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

violence, governance, research. In the second workshop, the participants were a research center, universities, industries, NGOs, and governmental organizations. The topics discussed included communication, student services, teaching, intersectionality, and transfer to market.

The dialogues' structure consisted of two parts. In the first part, it was important to ensure the engagement of the stakeholders and reach a common understanding on the possible shared challenges and activities. For this reason, stakeholders with specific expertise, were asked to prepare a 5-10 min key point presentation on the topics of the session (e.g., Stakeholders from the industry discussed issues of transfer to market and human resources). After the end of each presentation there was a short time for discussion and quick questions, which further resulted in knowledge transfer and networking.

After this introduction, the second part of the Dialogues involved dividing the participants in smaller groups, to discuss each topic more extensively. A key point table was prepared by ECE-NTUA, which consisted of the various elements for each area from the draft scenarios (problems, solutions, strategies, resistances, opportunities – allies and common activities), while the instructions given to the stakeholders were the following:

- Review on the table's bullet points and modify (erase or further elaborate) them according to their knowledge, opinion, and beliefs on the matter.
- Highlight the most probable resistances as well as the most likely opportunities and allies.
- Identify further problems, as well as additional common activities.

As a result, the groups reconstructed and commented on the «realistic» scenario, which will include the most likely elements (and associated strategies) from each of the other two (maximum resistances, and maximum opportunities). By combining the information gathered from the first part, stakeholders were also able to identify, potential common activities.

Shared challenges for gender equality

During the 1st and 2nd Stakeholder Dialogue the main cross cutting challenges/problems addressed referred to the respective topics were:

- The low level of female representation in STEM (firstly in the education field and, consequently, in industry), which further leads to low representation of women in leading and decision-making positions, in academic positions, in research etc.
 - The need to provide work life balance measures whether in the public, or the private sector.
 - The need for more data collection on gender equality indexes.
 - The various stereotypes that exist regarding women and STEM, which further prevent women from attaining higher level careers in academia and industry.
 - The low priority given to gender equality issues in general.
 - The need for a secure and solid framework dealing with sexual harassment to motivate more women to say and denounce respective cases and complaints without the fear of stigma.
 - The importance of non-sexist language in an organisation's internal and external communication, as well as in teaching, in research etc.
 - The need for gender awareness activities as well as respective trainings.
- Specific challenges:

As mentioned in the previous section, the specific common challenges per topic were identified within discussions in smaller groups. Additionally, some challenges that the ECE-NTUA School faces are not

being shared by all participants. However, these were also discussed, as there was an opportunity to elicit best practices and potential avenues of action. During the discussions, stakeholders were given a previously prepared Table which consisted of the various elements for each area of the scenarios (problems, solutions, strategies, resistances, opportunities – allies and common activities). Through this the groups reconstructed and commented on the «realistic» scenario, which will include the most likely elements (and associated strategies) from each of the other two (maximum resistances, and maximum opportunities).

➤ **Human resources**

- The low representation of women in STEM is a challenge common not only in the various participating RPOs, but also in the industry.
- This low representation further leads to the low percentage of women taking part in promotion boards and relevant committees. An increase of the women participation in such boards, given the present ratio would only lead to an extensive and heavier workload.
- Specifically, as regards the RPO's the low representation of women in their premises further leads to an insecure working environment. This is caused as, unfortunately, there are different behaviours to men and different to women. Additional challenges in the treatment of respective issues refer to the denial that different behaviours exist, and even if they exist they are not that important. On the other hand, such incidents are more eliminated, as regards the Industry participating stakeholders, as they have adopted respective strategies that will be explained in 3.2.

➤ **Governance**

- A common challenge for all stakeholder categories was the under representation of women in leading and/or decision-making positions. Specifically, stakeholders described a situation where women prefer to undertake “back-office” positions, to not be involved and/or need to communicate with customers and other interested parties, to “keep a low profile” and to not communicate achievements and successes.
- Another challenge deriving from the female under representation in STEM, is the insecurity feeling that many women in STEM have. Stakeholders described incidents where women did not know whether they were invited to undertake leading positions because they deserved to or because they were fulfilling a certain gender equality ratio.
- Also, stakeholders agreed that there is a lack of activities that focus on training and guiding women to decision making positions.
- There is an absence of specific gender equality policies that refer to governance, while also there seems to be a disagreement towards a common orientation for these policies.

➤ **Research/research funding**

- One of the main common challenges that the RPO stakeholders identified is the low integration of the gender dimension into research.
- Furthermore, the RPO stakeholders agreed another challenge is the lack of policies and directions on the possible ways of integrating the gender dimension into

research. Additionally, the lack of financing targeted gender equality programs is also a challenge.

- Another challenge is the imbalance occurring in the structure (men and women ratio) of the research teams. There is also a “trust” issue when women undertake senior research positions, if they are going to succeed or not.
- RPO’s further highlighted the issue of bibliography regarding both STEM and gender issues. Such references might be difficult to track, there could be unavailable or limited.

➤ **Teaching**

- One of the main challenges in Teaching is the integration of the gender dimension. RPOs are not at the same level of integration, as some Universities have already implemented important steps (e.g., The Aristotle University of Thessaloniki has already implemented various gender studies courses).
- Furthermore, there is need for adequate training to academics and researchers, to provide them with efficient tools for gender equal teaching and how to avoid bias in teaching. This is important for all RPOs regardless their gender integration levels.

➤ **Students and services to students**

- A common challenge that has been identified refers to the absence of a specific policy on how to attract more female students in STEM.

➤ **Communication**

- Main challenge, especially among the RPOs is the implementation of the Guide for non-sexist language in the public documents. Also, the level of integration of the matter is different, according to the various RPOs. However, the integration of a gender-neutral language in the internal communication is of utmost importance.
- Another challenge refers to the absence of training regarding “anti-sexist” behaviour in the communication. Training is very crucial and will help in the implementation and adoption of the above.

➤ **Transfer to Market**

- A common challenge that the stakeholders recognized is the low representation of women in new businesses and start-ups and how this relates to the need for support towards enhancing female entrepreneurship.
- Another challenge is the poor interconnection to the market (transfer to market) that the RPOs, especially the Greek Universities, seem to have.

➤ **Intersectionality**

- Main common challenge recognized between the stakeholders is the absence of institutional measures regarding intersectionality. Here again the level of absence differs among the stakeholders which offers opportunities for best practices and knowledge transfer, as it will be described in the following sections.
- Finally, stakeholders agreed on the challenge of data collection on intersectionality. Except the stakeholders involved in Industry, no other stakeholders are collecting gender equality data.

➤ **Sexism and sexual harassment**

- Stakeholders identified the absence of a specific mechanism for the treatment of sexism and sexual harassment as an important challenge.
- Another challenge recognized referred to the absence of a consultive service, as well as the absence of information regarding what a consultive service should include.
- Finally, stakeholders agreed that the hesitation in expressing any relevant report/complaint due to the fear of exposure (stigma) is a serious challenge.

Portfolio of strategic opportunities

Cross cutting strategies, as well as specific strategies were identified with the process explained in the previous section. Namely, stakeholders were given a prefilled Table, with elements deriving from the ECE NTUA Scenarios (problems, solutions, strategies, resistances, opportunities – allies and common activities). Then stakeholders had the opportunity to discuss these topics, find common problems – or not, express their opinion and differences, add to, or erase the bullets of the Table, therefore reconstructing the most “probable” scenario, from each of the other two (maximum resistances, and maximum opportunities).

➤ Cross-cutting strategies:

Cross cutting strategies refer to general strategies which may affect multiple areas. This section briefly presents each general strategy and the relevant strategic opportunities and threats that were highlighted during the Dialogues. Specifically:

- As regards the under representation of women in STEM the strategy followed should focus from one hand on attracting more girls in the STEM academic fields, and on the other hand focus on how to retain these women into the STEM field professionally, either at an academic, or at an Industry level. Therefore, from the RPOs side there is a need for specific targets (if not internal quotas that are not required by the relevant legislation), to have an idea where they picture their female to male ratio in the following years. Also, there is a necessity to enhance the research positions (post doc, PhD candidates etc) for women, through specific strategies further depicted in the following section.

Opportunities: Allies towards this direction are the Gender Equality Committees of other RPOs, as well as the various research centres, the civil society organisations as well as the industry, which share the same challenge and have similar goals. Furthermore, the industry can provide further strategies that can be adequately adjusted and adopted in the public sector.

Threats: On the other hand, such a strategy could have threats such as the strong reaction people tend to have to the use of quotas – for the increase of the women researchers in the RPOs. On one hand women do not like to be treated as minorities, as social groups that need support, and on the other hand, there are reactions that characterise such measures as unfair, not promoting merit, and supporting low qualifications.

- Also, in relation to the low percentage of women taking part in promotion boards and relevant committees, as well as in leading and/or decision-making positions, an increase in the overall women in STEM would consequently increase the number of women in promotional boards etc.

Opportunities: Best practices and good examples may come from the private sector. These strategies can be adjusted adequately and adopted.

Threats: However, the strategy on increasing the women representation in promotion boards and relevant committees may hit on obstacles such as women that do not want to take part in such positions, not because they do not have enough time, but simply because they refuse to “come forward”.

- Furthermore, the implementation of quotas and training activities in order to understand their importance is another strategy towards an increase of women in STEM and, consequently, an increase of women taking part in promotion boards and in leading positions.

Opportunities: Opportunities may arise by the best practices and examples of other RPO's as well as best practices by the industry, that seems to face similar issues.

Threats: However, a challenge related to this is the strong reaction people tend to have to the use of quotas – as described previously. Main challenges towards training activities include time and workday constraints, the absence of correct guidance, as well as strong resistances, that come from both men and women not wanting to change the present situation.

- Regarding the insecure environment derived by the under representation of women, the respective strategy involves mechanisms on treating sexist behaviour, as well as further educational and training activities.

Opportunities: Other RPOs have implemented such strategies and are willing to transfer their knowledge and best practices.

Threats: However, obstacles to such a strategy could include the lack of time for the participation in such activities, as well as resistances regarding the actual need for such mechanisms.

- Training activities and further guidance is also necessary for the promotion of women in decision making positions.

Opportunities: Stakeholders were very familiar with such activities, having already implemented similar ones. Therefore, there is room for best examples and practices to follow.

Threats: This strategy entails challenges that refer to the lack of time that women appear to have, the absence of correct guidance, as well as strong resistances, from both men and women, regarding the actual need for such training.

- The low integration of the gender dimension into research requires a strategy targeting to the sensitisation of researchers, regarding the importance of gender issues.

Opportunities: The current social climate offers a positive opportunity, as there is a greater focus on gender issues in the public discourse. Also, the dimension of gender appears to play an important role in future research funding opportunities (e.g. future HORIZON calls).

Threats: Such a strategy would have obstacles such as possible reactions by academics and researchers to the absence (or perceived absence) of links between their research and the gender dimension.

- Implementation of a research funding policy favouring the integration of gender dimension at the national level. This could involve lobbying activities targeting national authorities, as well as providing support and positive publicity for such measures.

Opportunities: The new measures of the EC regarding the gender framework prerequisites for participating in HORIZON programmes can provide a positive example for national authorities to follow.

Threats: Serious threats could comprise the absence of resources and political will. Stakeholders agreed that those two parameters are crucial for such strategies.

- Stakeholders also mentioned that existing imbalances could be countered through a strategy of promoting more balanced work or research teams (regarding the male to female ratio), through quotas or internal targets.

Opportunities: the current situation in the country (#metoo movement, rising interest in gender equality issues) offers an opportunity for further change.

Threats: Reactions towards this strategy could refer to the qualifications of the team's members (e.g., the selection will not be based on meritocracy), while also there is a chance that the needed qualifications might not exist. Additionally, there is also the issue of "trust" when female researchers take over senior research positions (i.e., "Are they are going to succeed or not?").

- A strategy that would comprise both a mechanism for treating sexual harassment and incidents of sexism, as well as a consultation service was a tool to which stakeholders agreed.

Opportunities: Stakeholders from other Universities, as well as NGOs have valuable experience and seem to have made some steps forward on the matter. This experience can be shared and communicated through collaboration activities.

Threats: Such a strategy could be delayed and/or prevented by indirect resistances, such as arguments that the existence of such measures is an indirect way of admitting the existence of such incidents in the institution. Also, other resistances may be derived from arguments that such mechanisms are unnecessary and that they will not be used. Additionally, this strategy must give the opportunity to report an incident without obstacles such as the victim's fear regarding who will read and handle their complaint. The possible solution of anonymous reports/complaints might bring risks such as the possibility that such reports/complaints may not be taken seriously.

- Stakeholders underlined the importance of a strategy that would on one hand ensure the gender-neutral communication within the respective organisation, and on the other hand will make sure those workshops, training, and information days will take place for its correct adoption and implementation.

Opportunities: As regards the gender-neutral communication, there is an important opportunity as a Guide for the Use of Non-Sexist Language in the Public Documents already exists. However, even though it exists it has not been officially put into place as various obstacles appear in the way. The use of non-sexist language is a very powerful, political tool. The fact that the adoption of non-sexist language can support actual change is a strong argument against possible resistances.

Threats: On the other hand, obstacles are mostly derived from the fact that people have a difficulty in understanding the reason for such changes and are making false arguments, such as the wrong use of grammar, aesthetic arguments (nouns in the

female gender that "sound awkward"), arguments on the usefulness of such changes, as well as

arguments on the malfunction of the organisation. On the other hand, even though most stakeholders acknowledge the importance for respective training activities, they also mentioned various resistances that might occur. Those refer mostly to the lack of time, the heavy workload of the interested parties and the perceptions that there is no need to change.

- The stakeholders agreed on the importance of a strategy for complaint mechanisms for cases of sexist internal communication. This will further assure the correct implementation of a gender-neutral communication.

Opportunities: The current situation in the country (#metoo movement, rising interest in gender equality issues) offers an opportunity for further change, as well as best practices and examples coming from external partners.

Threats: However, this strategy might meet obstacles such as the perception that such provisions are not necessary and are a waste of resources.

- As regards the challenges regarding the transfer to market, the stakeholders agreed on a strategy that will offer mentoring and training activities, as well as an alumni network that will further assist in networking and transfer. The main goal is to receive feedback from old students that are currently working as employees or owners of technology businesses.

Opportunities: The timing for this strategy is very suitable, as one of the goals of the high-level management is to set up an alumni network.

Threats: However, stakeholders also identified an obstacle related to the lack of time of students or graduates.

- Moreover, as regards the low integration of the gender dimension into teaching it is important to implement a strategy that would assist in the integration of the gender dimension into teaching (e.g., through a Guide), the necessary training of the academic personnel and researchers on unbiased teaching, as well as a mechanism that would report incidents of bias in teaching.

Opportunities: The timing for the implementation of such strategies is appropriate as people in Greece seem more and more interested in gender issues and gender equality. It also must be noted that respective legislation for the integration of gender dimension into teaching already exists (Law 3896/2010 and Law 4604/2019), therefore comprising a very good starting point.

Threats: On the other hand, some obstacles might occur that refer to bureaucracy and the needed changes in the Curriculum and the limited existing resources (including human resources and time resources).

- Regarding services to students, a strategy that will comprise specific internal targets on what is the desired male to female ratio, in combination with activities to increase students in STEM was underlined.

Opportunities: The best practices and knowledge transfer from other Universities, in combination with the strategies (to be) developed by the NTUA Gender Equality Committee.

Threats: Main obstacles to this strategy could be the lack of resources, both in terms of time, personnel, and funding.

- Finally, regarding intersectionality, stakeholders highlighted the importance of a strategy that apart from the institutional measures, it will also contain adequate

spatial planning for the people that have access issues, as well as the appropriate supervision, if the implementation of respective works is necessary. Additionally, this strategy should include activities supporting data collection on gender equality and how it is perceived among the various members of the organisation.

Opportunities: Major opportunity is the formation of the NTUA Gender Equality Plan which has such issues high in its strategic agenda, as well as the best practices and knowledge transfer from other Universities and organisations occurring through the R&I Hub.

Threats: Possible threats could be the lack of resources (in terms of time, money, and human personnel), the mentality that such a strategy is not that necessary, raising GDPR issues, and issues of confidentiality.

➤ **Specific strategies:**

This section includes a portfolio of specific strategic priorities for the School, per each topic. The main objective of this section is to go beyond the strategies' generic description, opportunities and threats and identify specific priorities that can be elaborated in a GEP.

➤ **Human resources**

- Increase the number of female students.
- Set specific targets regarding the desirable male to female ratio in the School.
- Communicate the new research positions in a more gender sensitive way.
- Provide work life balance measures to all members of the School (permanent or not).
- Organise "Women's Meetings" where women will be able to exchange knowledge, experiences and promote their achievements.
- Promotion of role models.

➤ **Governance**

- Set specific targets (or quotas) with specific criteria (reasoning, arguments) regarding % of women and the % of women in leading positions.
- Set a rewards system (e.g., performance awards, evaluation).
- Implementation of training activities.
- Extensive dialogue to agree on common directions for policies to be developed and adopted.
- Collection of data on equality indexes.

➤ **Research**

- Set internal targets regarding the % of research entailing the gender dimension.
- Support of female researchers through scholarships, study awards and research awards.
- Application of mandatory quotas for research positions.
- Consultations for the use and acceptance of quotas.

➤ **Teaching**

- Implementation of a guide on how to integrate the gender dimension into teaching, that will also contain examples, best practices on a gender – neutral language in teaching and ways on how to avoid stereotypical thinking.
 - Implementation of training activities that will include experiential exercises and practical management of gender issues, to simulate several possible teaching situations and contexts, and further assist the academic personnel and researchers.
 - Organisation of information days for all the members of the organisation.
 - Implementation of a support mechanism that will assist in reporting and treating cases of bias and sexist behaviour in teaching.
- **Students and services to students**
- Creation of an internal policy guide that will contain the internal desirable targets on the female to male ratio, as well as measures to attract more female students in STEM.
 - Further enhancing and communicating existing activities.
- **Transfer to Market**
- Mentoring activities, e.g., from women with experience in the field, and podcasts / interviews with role models.
 - Creation of an alumni network, that will assist in networking activities, as well as experiences transfer.
 - Collaboration with private companies, in terms of internships and scholarships.
 - Feedback from male and female students on where they want to do their internships and establishment of respective collaborations.
- **Communication**
- Official application of the Guide for Non-Sexist Language in the Public Documents.
 - Implementation of training activities regarding non-sexist and unbiased communication.
 - Organisation of information days.
- **Intersectionality**
- Activities of spatial planning to ensure access to the amphitheatres and classrooms for all.
 - Further enhancement of the existing institutional tools and/or introduction of new institutional measures.
 - Creation of a gender map and collection of gender equality data that will further assist to understand how members of the organisation perceive gender equality.
- **Sexism and sexual harassment**
- Development of formal mechanism dealing and offering mediation services regarding cases of sexual harassment and sexism.
 - Operation of a support and guidance service.
 - Development of an online form for reporting sexual harassment and sexism

incidents.

Summary of possible collaborative actions

All stages of the CALIPER Dialogues' implementation helped to identify possible collaborative actions, implemented among the stakeholders. Particularly, stakeholders elaborated on the common activities that were presented in the first part of the session or included in the prepared tables for each topic in the second part. The participants also had the opportunity to add more, agree and disagree with the existing ones. In this way they interacted with the scenarios of ECE NTUA, while also assisting in the formation of the most "realistic" scenario.

➤ Human resources

- In cooperation with Scientific Associations, Professional & Research Community and the Industry, implementation of activities to highlight the profession of engineer as well as future career opportunities.
- In cooperation with all the categories of participating stakeholders' promotion of role models and dissemination in the external environment.
- Organisation of events between all the categories of the participating stakeholders for the exchange of knowledge and best practices.

➤ Governance

- Organisation of events between all the categories of the participating stakeholders for the exchange of knowledge and best practices, as well as methods to ensure security procedures for the collection of data.
- In cooperation with other Universities, Scientific Associations, Professional & Research Community and the Industry, organisation of an "Award" event for women in leading positions.
- In cooperation with the Gender Equality Committees of other universities, implementation of training activities and workshops to strengthen women in decision making positions.

➤ Research

- In cooperation with the participating RPOs, implementation of joint research papers.
- Organisation of events between all the categories of the participating stakeholders to exchange best practices on ways of integrating the gender dimension in research.
- In cooperation with the participating RPOs, creation of a forum for women per scientific field offering common activities, support for lobbying etc.

➤ Teaching

- In cooperation with the participating RPOs, implementation of Information and Dialogue days, to share best practices on the integration of gender dimension into teaching.
- In cooperation with the participating RPOs, NGOs and Governmental Organisations, realisation of joint training activities on how to avoid bias in teaching.

➤ Services to students

- Organisation of information days among the participating Universities, for the exchange of knowledge and best practices.
 - Communication activities implemented with the cooperation of the industry, targeting to further inform students.
- **Transfer to Market**
- In cooperation with all the participating stakeholders, implementation of Mentoring days, as well as podcasts of role models, within the framework of the R&I Hub.
 - Implementation of cooperation activities with the Industry, in order to further enhance internships, as well as to receive respective feedback by both ends.
 - Creation of an Advisory Board (with industry stakeholders) on gender equality in the transfer to market (entering the labour market or via entrepreneurship).
- **Communication**
- Organisation of communication activities, among the participating stakeholders, on the importance of a gender-neutral communication. Exchange of best practices and know-how.
 - In cooperation with other Universities, implementation of Workshops and training on the use of anti-sexist language and how to make it a habit.
- **Intersectionality**
- Implementation of an information day, within the framework of the R&I Hub, with the participation of all the stakeholders.
 - Organisation of “informal” events, among Universities, RPOs and other interested stakeholders for the exchange of best practices and know-how in this field.
- **Sexism and sexual harassment**
- Organisation of events between all the categories of the participating stakeholders for the exchange of knowledge and best practices.
 - Trainings, workshops in cooperation with NGOs and Governmental Organisations on sexual harassment.
 - Organisation of information days between all the categories of the participating stakeholders.

3.8 Institute for Research in Biomedicine (RPO)

Description of the R&I Hub

The R&I Hub of the IRB is formed by 8 members of the academia, 1 Ministry, and 5 civil society organizations.

Type of stakeholder	Stakeholders
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This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Academia (8)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centres de Recerca de Catalunya - CERCA (Catalunya Research Centres) • Institute for Bioengineering of Catalonia (IBEC) • Institut de Ciència de Materials de Barcelona - ICMAB-CSIC (Barcelona Institute of Materials Science) • Germans Trias i Pujol Research Institute (IGTP) • Barcelona Institute for Science and Technology (BIST) • University of Santiago de Compostela • Barcelona Biomedical Research Park (PRBB) • Centre for Genomic Regulation (CRG-CNAG)
Industry & professionals (0)	
Ministries/Government (1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministerio de Ciencia ,Innovation and Universities (Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities)
Public sector (0)	None
Civil society organizations (5)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asociación Catalana de Comunicacion Cientifica - ACCC (Catalan Association for Scientific Communication) • Asociación de Mujeres Investigadores y Tecnólogas – AMIT (Association of Women Researchers and Technologists) • Fundacion Catalunya la Pedrera (Catalunya la Pedrera Foundation) • Asociación Española Contra el Cáncer - AECC (Spanish Association Against Cancer) • Asociación para la Diversidad Afectivo-Sexual y de Género en Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación - PRISMA (Association for Affective-Sexual and Gender Diversity in Science, Technology and Innovation)

Description of the workshops

The two workshops were carried out on the 11th and 12th March 2021. In the first workshop, 12 people participated (12 women) from the academia, the civil society and the Ministry. They discussed about human resources, institutional communication, institutional governance, and young scientists (student services and teaching). In the second workshop 6 people participated (4 women and 2 men) from the academia and the civil society. They discussed about transfer to market, research, intersectionality and sexual harassment.

At the beginning of the dialogue sessions the CALIPER project was explained to the stakeholders providing information of the current phase/status of the project, the co-creation process design and the next phases of the project. The “situations” that generated the scenario elaboration were presented as individual points in order to start the dialogue/discussion. Each point opened the discussion to identify both common challenges and possible solutions to each of the challenges. The idea of the R+I Hub and the expected collaborations with each of the participants was highlighted during the session and with a follow-up email after the dialogue session to all of the participating stakeholders.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Shared challenges for gender equality

Only specific challenges were identified:

➤ **Human Resources:**

- Recruitment: Gender Sensitive Protocol in Recruitment: Bias recruitment processes. (CERCA-Academia & Universities).
- Recruitment: Work to eradicate gender biases.
- Recruitment: Amount of candidates per gender presented for open positions. Sometimes only candidates from one gender apply to certain positions (AMIT-Civil Society).
- Recruitment: Difficulty to conform gender equal panels (shared by all).
- Career Progression: Progression is closely related to the visibility of women in an institute. (AMIT, PRBB Civil Society, Academia & Universities).
- Work-Life Balance: lack of tools to better disseminate measures WLB measures (IBEC, Academia & Universities).

➤ **Governance**

- Underrepresentation of women in some decision-making bodies (Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities).
- Work overload of women in leadership positions when there are few women occupying these positions (shared by all).

➤ **Research**

- Integration of the gender dimension into research (Prisma, Civil Society).
- Need to incentivize gender balanced teams in research (Prisma, Civil Society).
- Necessity to implement training programs and create impact in gender dimension approach into research.

➤ **Transfer to Market/Innovation**

- Integration of the gender dimension into Transfer to Market/innovation (Universidad de Santiago, Universities)
- Data collection (sex/gender disaggregated) needs to be improved. No general data of evolution of women into transfer to market /innovation. This data could serve as an indicator to measure the evolution of gender/diversity in this area. (Universidad de Santiago, Universities)
- Tools to control the participation of women in transfer to market/innovation. (Universidad de Santiago, Universities).

➤ **Students and services to students**

- Additional counseling in career path topics needed.

➤ **Communication**

- Lack of existence of policies or guidelines that take into consideration gender sensitivity in internal/external communications.

- There is not a systematic and comprehensive gender-sensitive communications plan in place but specific initiatives.
 - Intranet as a tool does not provide proper visibility to information (shared by all).
 - Emails with important information about gender equality issues may be lost or perceived as unimportant (shared by all).
- **Intersectionality**
- Diversity is still not embedded in the development of all protocols and guidelines. (Prisma, Civil Society).
 - There is a need of developing tools to monitor the development of intersectionality in institutions.
 - Undefined secure channels for LGBTQ+ community (Prisma, Civil Society)
- **Sexism and sexual harassment**
- Communicating measures and how to deal if a situation happens. (CRG&PRBB, Academia & Universities)
 - Institutional support and structures to channel sexism and sexual harassment situations. (CERCA-Academia & Universities).

Portfolio of strategic opportunities

To ask the participants for possible solutions for the presented challenges, an explanation was given taking into consideration the elaboration of the internal and external assessment to better provide a context for each of the areas of analysis. Once the situation was explained, IRB communicated that some of the presented solutions could be considered as easy to implement (minimum resistance) and some of them could be classified as actions of “maximum resistance” depending on the complexity of their implementation. Finally, understanding some of the challenges were considered as shared, the possibility of common solutions was constantly suggested. The following specific strategies were identified:

- **Human Resources:**
- Recruitment: to provide training in gender perspective to people involved in recruitment processes. Even include a role-play situation.
 - Recruitment: to establish a percentage of applicants per gender in order to finish a recruitment process (max resistance).
 - Recruitment: to include gender-neutral language in all of the job adverts.
 - Recruitment: to have a gender balance panel in the recruitment process.
 - Recruitment: to give more visibility to women/diverse members in recruitment visual material.
 - Career Progression: implementation of mentoring /coaching programs focused on gender.
 - Career Progression: through communication/visual efforts give better visibility to women to incentivize career progression.
 - Work-Life Balance: to incentivise and involve all the community of the Institute through WLB and conciliation measures activities.

- Work-Life Balance: to build and communicate Conciliation policies targeted to all the employees regardless their gender.

➤ **Governance**

- To establish a Co-leadership structure in which women can be more involved in decision-making bodies. It is important that tasks and responsibilities can be shared and distributed. (Max Resistance)
- To development of a concrete career plan focus for women with the objective of having more female participation in decision-making bodies.
- To create “ad hoc” positions in order to reach equal representation. (Max Resistance)

➤ **Research**

- Mandatory gender dimension training /courses in research at the beginning of the scientific career (PhD level)
- To encourage research that addresses gender issues, not only in its title or in the disaggregation of data by sex, but also in its content and its consequences.
- To develop guidelines to give an inclusive/gender neutral language in research proposals
- To create opportunities to share good practices/examples in sex and gender dimensions in research proposals. Also provide visibility to these examples in the institutional website.
- To keep track of the role of funding agencies in regards gender dimension and take advantage of these opportunities.
- To foster the participation of Ethical Committees/ Research Integrity Committees and the role of keeping track and encouraging gender dimension in research.

➤ **Students and services to students**

- To provide specific training to students (young scientist) in gender dimension

➤ **Communication**

- To encourage giving more visibility to actions and gender related protocols/news/guidelines in the institutional website and not only on the intranet.
- Email campaigns should be sent from the Equality and Diversity Committee address and the content should be concrete and focused to news and actions.
- To use printed material as dissemination tools for news and actions.
- To develop a gender communication plan with a defined period of action.
- To give visibility of the involvement that high management and committees have in gender equality actions.

➤ **Intersectionality**

- To create awareness of existing protocols and actions through printed material.
- To establish secure channels of communication for the LGBTQ+ community.
- To understand and support persons undergoing a gender transition process.
- To use time in seminars and conferences to provide news and information in regards

this topic (create awareness).

➤ **Sexism and sexual harassment**

- To create awareness of existing protocols and actions through printed material.
- To establish mandatory induction courses addressing sexual harassment and the existing measures taken at the institute. This induction could be also addressed to other topics such as conflict resolution, diversity issues, among others.
- To use time in seminars and conferences to provide news and information in regards this topic.
- To establish secure channels of communication for gender/sexual related issues.
- To encourage participation of “ombudsperson” figure.

➤ **Transfer to Market/Innovation**

- To promote within the Institute the creation and participation of women in spin off companies.
- When publishing, patenting, etc., take into account the order of the authors, highlighting the participation of women.
- To develop a process of gradual integration of the gender perspective in the work procedures of each phase of the transfer process.
- To recommend and give advice of specific measures to spin-offs, specifying that they have to develop and execute equality plans or measures, encouraging those who stand out for their equality.

Summary of possible collaborative actions

The following collaborative actions have been identified:

- Recruitment: to include CERCA recruitment-gender bias video as a compulsory step to the Hiring Managers and people involved in the recruitment process. (Collaborative action).
- To foster an email/video campaign to create awareness on incorrect normalized behaviours and “micro machismo” (Collaborative action). Stakeholders that show interest to be a part of this action: PRBB (Academia and Universities) and CRG (Academia and Universities).
- To develop a method to keep track of the evolution of women in transfer to market results (collaborative action). Stakeholders that show interest to be a part of this action: PRBB (Academia and Universities) and CRG (Academia and Universities).

3.9 Executive Unit for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding in Romania (RFO)

Description of the R&I Hub

The RI&I Hub of UEFISCDI is formed by 5 actors from the academia, 11 stakeholders from the industry and professional sector, 1 ministry, 2 agencies from the public sector, and 4 civil society associations.

Type of stakeholder	Stakeholders
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Academia (5)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • University of Bucharest • SNSPA (National School of Political and Administrative Studies) • UPB (“Politechnica” University, Bucharest) • Department for biochemistry and bio resources - National Institute for R&D in Electrical Engineering (RPO) • Department of material sciences - National Institute for R&D in Electrical Engineering (RPO)
Industry & professionals (11)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One Night Gallery • STEP FWD • Trofic • Orange Fab Lab • The Long Run • Romanian Investor Relations Association • Impact Capital • The Institute • Alfa Transilvania • Romania Business Association • Digipixel
Ministries/Government (1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of National Education
Public sector (2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ADR-BI (Agency for Regional Development – Bucharest Ilfov region) • ANES (National Agency for Equal Opportunities between Woman and Men)
Civil society organizations (4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fundatia 9 (Foundation 9) • FEMINA project • Ana Aslan International Foundation • Association for Community Relations

Description of the workshops

The two workshops took place on the 16th March 2021 and lasted 2 hours each. In total, 25 people participated (20 women and 5 men). The participants of the first workshop were policy makers (national level), and representatives of higher education institutions, NGOs, business and industry, public sector bodies and discussed about human resources (gender sensitive protocols/policies for recruitment and hiring, work environments and working conditions), gender equality bodies, institutional communication, internal communication, and intersectionality. The participants of the second workshop were policy makers (regional level), and representatives of NGOs, business, and industry, RPOs, entrepreneurs, and business associations. They discussed about human resources (mentoring for women or the under-represented

gender in leadership position, career progression, sexual harassment), research funding and the innovation ecosystem.

The workshops were scheduled in the same day, due to previous engagements to the participants' agenda. The topics of the debates covered both internal and external relations. Because the internal relations covered 6 topics and the external 2 topics, it was decided to mix them so that all topics could be equally debated during discussions.

Regarding the organization of the workshops, both events had the same structure: they began with a short presentation of the CALIPER project and the stage of its implementation (elaboration of GEP for the project's partners). Then it moved to the goal of the meeting: which was to discuss scenarios and solutions that would help the process and provide additional information for implementing and development of institutional GEP. It has been explained to the external institutional partners that their contribution is very important in testing the proposed solutions in the scenarios and that their personal experiences and best practices are welcomed and necessary for the future actions. The presentation stated some internal facts and figures about UEFISCDI to help the participants became more familiar with the organization's structure and to set the framework of the discussions. In the end the goal of the workshop was one more declared (to test solutions, to conduct debates about the scenarios and to receive valuable input from best practices and other experiences). Following the presentation, the event started by asking all participants to introduce themselves and then the discussions on each topic started. The discussions were constructed as brainstorm sessions (of 15 minutes each) during which all participants contributed according to their expertise or experience. The discussions were moderated by one member of the WG for GEP and another member wrote the inputs of the debates on a shared whiteboard. In this manner all participants had access to the solutions/challenges/opportunities discussed. The events were conducted in Romanian.

The main results of the first workshop were:

- *Gender sensitive protocols/policies for recruitment and hiring* - The internal documents and regulations as well as the hiring procedures must be updated and must take into consideration gender sensitive aspects so that discrimination and stereotypes that might unconsciously be experienced by the recruitment experts could be removed.
- *Work environments and working conditions* - Several new suggestions regarding the balance between the professional and personal life were proposed. However, not all of them can be implemented because the legislation offers no framework or conditions for their implementation.
- *Gender Equality Body* - The elaboration of a GEP and the implementation of a GEP Body was positively received and although participants were not familiar with its role and purpose in an organisation, they expressed their intention to learn more about the subject.
- *Institutional communication - internal communication (use and training on gender sensitive language)* was a topic well received by the participants, many expressing the opinion that even if they were not aware of such regulations, they intend to search further information on the subject and to act accordingly.
- *Intersectionality* - Intersectionality was covered in the discussions of the previous topics and determined participants to conclude that all measures regarding gender equality must start with raising awareness and educate employees and employers alike; UEFISCDI are all biased (consciously or not) when evaluating persons around us and being and becoming aware of these stereotypes has a major role in removing discrimination.

The main results of the second workshop were:

- *-Mentoring for women or the under-represented gender in leadership position* – the topic received a lot of suggestions on how to conduct a mentoring program. The main input was that such a program should be accompanied by an inspirational program that would help women (or under-

represented gender) to gain personal confidence and raise aspirations among them.

- *Career progression* – the topic raised a lot of questions among the participants, the debates stressing the fact that even if gender must be considered, currently there is no legislation that would enable organizations to impose such quotas.
- *Sexual harassment* – being a sensitive topic, the discussions were slow at the beginning, but participants were encouraged to open and tackle the issue. The main result was a consensus on the idea of raising awareness about different types of harassment that might occur in different institutions. The participants also agreed on the importance of creating a safe environment for the employees to address such challenges.
- *Research funding* – the topic was debated in relation with career progression (imposing quotas / targets regarding gender) and raised the issue that the number of female researchers or evaluators is significantly smaller than the number of male researchers/evaluators in certain scientific areas. It was also correlated with the mentoring topic and emphasized the importance of providing role models and inspiration for women.
- *Innovation ecosystem* was addressed together with Intersectionality and Career progression. Most of the participants were familiar with the Innovation Café type of events and expressed no resistance when asked about setting gender targets for speakers and public. They also agreed that introducing topics addressing gender balance in STEM research would be beneficial for all participants to the events.

Shared challenges for gender equality

During the two workshops every stakeholder was invited to share his/her opinions regarding the solutions UEFISCDI proposed to tackle the identified issues. During the discussions, several challenges that could interfere with the solutions were identified:

➤ Cross-cutting challenges:

- UEFISCDI should pay attention to the real needs of women employees when developing the GEP actions and strategy. A deeper analysis should be made to identify them (interviews, focus-groups, questionnaires).
- Sometimes formalizing the existing **informal** modus operandi of each team (that are respecting the gender dimension) can result in worsening the situation (some stakeholders expressed their concern that if UEFISCDI tries to formalize too much and to standardize different informal approaches regarding the work flexibility, then it might lose **the flexibility itself**, as UEFISCDI must find common procedures that would be applicable to all teams and departments, regardless of the nature of their work).
- Many women in STEM are not aware of their own ceiling glass.
- Women are afraid that by taking empowering actions their relations with their men colleagues will be affected.
- Most of the men in STEM are not aware of any kind of discrimination that their women colleagues are exposed being to.

➤ Specific challenges:

➤ **Human resources**

- Gender sensitive protocols/policies for recruitment and hiring: An evaluation is needed after the hiring committee is trained regarding the gender sensitive protocols/policies for

recruitment and hiring. Tackling with the stereotypes should be a priority when developing the protocols.

- Work environments and working conditions: some of the actions proposed cannot be formalized due to the legal framework. UEFISCDI should pay attention when formalizing existing positive measures in place in order not to minimize their effect.
 - Mentoring for women or the under-represented gender in leadership position: If the percentage of women in leadership positions is already above 50% this kind of actions can be seen as discriminatory for men.
 - Career progression: proposing quotas for women in middle and high management position should be replaced with assuring gender balance in these positions.
- **Sexual harassment**
- For most of the participants the concept of sexual harassment was not clear enough.
 - Both men and women should be trained to identify this kind of abuses.
 - Anonymity is key when reporting sexual harassment.
- **Gender Equality Body**
- Prior to set the gender equality body and their roles and positions, the strategy should be already in place so that the members of the GEP body can be recruited based on their capabilities to serve the strategy.
- **Internal communication**
- Organizing trainings to improve gender sensitive language has its limits as the participants cannot easily access the information presented during the trainings.
- **Intersectionality**
- By dealing with intersectionality just as a transversal layer, the most important aspects can be easily overlooked.
- **Research funding**
- The resistance to change might be stronger than UEFISCDI initially considered.
- **Innovation ecosystem**
- No challenges regarding this topic were identified during discussions.

Portfolio of strategic opportunities

- Cross-cutting strategies:

During the discussions of the workshops several topics were correlated by the participants, therefore resulting some cross-cutting strategies that could be implemented in order to achieve several goals in the same time. Here are the main ideas for these strategies:

- ✓ Development of a gender sensitive kit that would be disseminated inside the organisation to all new employees upon hiring as part of the training /induction period. The kit will contain materials, documents, leaflets, presentations, and videos about:
 - The non-discrimination policies that UEFISCDI are committed to,
 - The internal communication regulations (with focus on gender sensitive language),

- Harassment (what is harassment, type of harassment, methods of reporting, etc)
- Intersectionality
- ✓ The organization of an internal communication and awareness campaign for all existing employees with the information stated above.
- ✓ If possible, all materials of the gender sensitive kit should be developed on media support (videos, presentations, etc) so that they can be easily used in other situations or events
- ✓ The development and implementation of evaluation methods that could be used for the gender sensitive kit and is subsequent actions to measure and evaluate the understanding degree of our colleagues (they could include for instance filling up questionnaires or taking tests that would evaluate personal biases and become aware of the personal stereotypes).
- Specific strategies:
 - **Human resources**
 - Gender sensitive protocols/policies for recruitment and hiring: specific trainings regarding gender discrimination and stereotypes identification for the hiring and evaluation committees prior to the evaluation of the candidates.
 - Work environments and working conditions: specific trainings for the employees returning to work after parental leave in order to help them regain professional competences; trainings on developing soft-skills and time management skills to increase work efficiency; an in-depth analysis of the employees needs related to the working environment.
 - Mentoring for women or the under-represented gender in leadership position: 1. Inspirational program to empower under-represented gender; 2. evaluation of leadership qualities and competences; 3. “Shadowing” program (participant is partnered with top management representative and shadows his/her routine for a specific period); 4. Selection of relevant candidates; 5. Development of personalized coaching & mentoring program for the selected participants.
 - Career progression: development of an internal educational program (with effects top-bottom) in which women are encouraged to take place and evaluate their leadership competence, their plan for the future career thus, changing mind sets and promoting women in top positions (committees or management). There is no legislative framework to impose quotas or targets for women in top positions.
 - **Sexual harassment:** clear definition of the concept and types of harassment must be announced in the internal organizational regulations as well as in the communication kit. Methods of reporting any types of harassment must be devised that would ensure the complainant safety and anonymity.
 - **Gender Equality Body:** the Gender Equality Body should be a mix between management and executive employees: the management should set and monitor the strategies of communicating and achieving gender equality targets while the executive branch should implement them. In this manner UEFISCDI does not lose focus of the subject.

*Some participants asked to be kept informed about our progress and to receive any related materials UEFISCDI could provide to set up their own GEP. Although most of them heard about this type of plan, no organisation invited to the event had one

already in place, thus making UEFISCDI a promoter of the initiative and an example of future good practices.

- **Institutional Communication:** specific training on this topic must be included in the gender sensitive kit and all employees must be made aware of it.
- **Intersectionality:** specific internal trainings to all employees about awareness and ethics of the topic; the concept must be included in the institutional culture and connected with all the other concepts.
- **Research funding:** an in-depth analysis of the reasons why women do not take part in research programs (research content); educational programs that would empower women and encourage them to join areas of research dominated mainly by men (analysis first).
- **Innovation ecosystem:** no specific strategy was identified for the innovation ecosystem, the solutions presented in the scenarios being very well received.

Summary of possible collaborative actions

During the workshops some opportunities for collaborative actions were identified:

- Firstly, Oana Baluta, lecturer at University of Bucharest (Faculty of Journalism and Communication Sciences) with great expertise in gender studies and a well-known activist for gender equality expressed her willingness to help UEFISCDI in developing the strategy for GEP. She considers the task of developing and implementing a GEP in the organization as an important step for assuring gender balance in public institutions. Further meetings will be organized when the strategy will be developed.
- Another opportunity from collaborative actions arose from the National Institute of R&D for Engineering (invited in the dialogues) when it has been suggested that further actions and meetings with different RPOs are needed to promote gender equality values, with focus on the recruitment procedures.
- Another collaborative action could take place between UPB (Romania's most important STEM University) and NGOs with focus on gender equality to organize workshops in which gender discrimination is being explained and participants are made aware of it, with the purpose of inspiring and empowering women willing to work in STEM.

3.10 Yasar University (RPO)

Description of the R&I Hub

The R&I Hub of Yasar University is formed by 3 universities, 12 stakeholders from the industry and professional sector, 3 municipalities, 1 agency from the public sector and 12 associations from the civil society.

Type of stakeholder	Stakeholders
Academia (3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ege University • İzmir Katip Çelebi University • Dokuz Eylül University

Industry & professionals (12)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Noti Training & Consulting • Yöntem Fleet Tracking and Vehicle Tracking Systems • Pınar Süt (Milk Products) • İzmir Commodity Exchange • ESİAD /Sun Textile Incorporated Company • Bağ Interactive Learning • Yaşar Holding Company • Pınar Et (Meat Products) • Özyeğin University • Kadir Has University • Sabancı University • Mimar Sinan University
Ministries/Government (3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • İzmir Metropolitan Municipality EU Project Office • Bornova Municipality • İzmir Metropolitan Municipality
Public sector (1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • İzmir Metropolitan City Council Women's Assembly
Civil society organizations (12)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung Turkey • Raoul Wallenberg Institute • Turuncu Association • Community Volunteers Foundation (TOG) • Pi Youth Association • Women's Human Rights New Solutions Association • Association for the Protection of Women's Rights • Aramızda Association • İnci Foundation • Yaşar Education and Culture Foundation • Farkındalık Yarat Association (FARYA) • Union of Turkish Engineers and Architects Chambers (TMMOB)

Description of the workshops

The two workshops were carried out on the 8th and 16th March 2021 and lasted 2 hours each. A total of 36 people participated (31 women and 5 men). The participants of the first workshop were stakeholders from the NGOs, businesses, government/public sector, private sector, and university and discussed about awareness raising, governance, work-life balance, research and research funding, institutional

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

communication, institutional collaborations for gender equality, gender-sensitive services. The participants of the second workshop were university representatives and discussed about human resources, governance, research, transfer to market, education, sexual Harassment, intersectionality, teaching process and relations with students, integration of gender in the research field.

The dialog meetings started with the presentation of the CALIPER project and the brief presentation of the results of the internal analysis of the YU. Afterward, the discussion and sharing of practices have started under the guidance of the moderator.

Shared challenges for gender equality

While some challenges were common to all the topics discussed and almost to all the stakeholder organization, (such as lack of awareness of gender equality issues); some challenges were specific to RPOs (such as lack of gender-sensitive teaching /curricula and lack of specific policy to attract more female students to STEM departments).

The challenges that were commonly shared by most of the stakeholders can be summarized as follows: One of the common challenges expressed by both RPOs and other types of stakeholder organizations was the lack of gender equality policy (or plan) in general. Also, participants expressed the lack of awareness regarding gender equality issues especially at the management level and underrepresentation of women in decision-making positions in general. The NGO representatives stressed the need for trainings for raising awareness on gender equality issues. Importance of maintaining work-life balance of female staff in business and academia was also emphasized. Representatives of RPOs also discussed the need for integration of gender into research and innovation through training and incentives. The possible ways to attract female students to STEM departments were also discussed by RPO representatives.

- **Cross-cutting challenges:** Lack of institutional policy on gender equality, lack of awareness regarding gender equality issues, underrepresentation of women in decision-making positions, glass-ceiling, lack of measures for work-life balance, lack of understanding of intersectionality issues.
- **Specific challenges:**
 - **Human resources:** Most of the participating organizations do not have a gender balance or gender equality policy in human resources area,
 - **Governance:** Women are underrepresented in high-level positions, most of the stakeholders (except some RPOs) does not have a gender equality plan or policy, lack of gender-disaggregated data collection
 - **Research/research funding:** Only some of the participating RPOs have gender equality plans, in most of the RPOs there is no policy or guidance on the integration of gender equality into the research/funding; gender is not integrated into the research or funding mechanism of the most of the RPOs
 - **Teaching:** lack of gender-sensitive teaching/ curricula, there are some existing courses or modules in RPOs in some departments, but there are no policy or guidelines to integrate gender into teaching
 - **Students and services to students:** No policy to attract more female students to STEM departments, lack of gender-sensitive student services in RPOs
 - **Communication:** Most of the stakeholder organizations does not aware of the gender-sensitive communication, lack of gender-sensitive institutional communication
 - **Intersectionality:** intersectionality issues are not considered, lack of awareness of the

intersectionality

- **Sexism and sexual harassment:** No established measures or structures to deal with sexism and sexual harassment

Portfolio of strategic opportunities

- **Cross-cutting strategies:**
 - Setting KPIs/ indicators for GEP actions and ensuring their follow-up.
 - Linking GEPS to global indicators/rankings such as SDGs.
 - Using personas and scenarios in the YU's internal GEP development workshops to facilitate dialogue and communication.
- **Specific strategies:**
 - **Human resources:**
 - Recruiting a full-time expert for gender equality position. This will ensure institutionalization and sustainability aside from project-based/ temporary positions.
 - **Governance:**
 - Adding gender dimensions in the key performance indicators of directors and managers to ensure that the GEP is implemented.
 - **Research:**
 - Project offices/TTO staff could follow grants/funding opportunities/calls for applications on gender issues (the specific calls can be identified in later stages).
 - **Teaching:**
 - Setting the goal of introducing at least one course on gender in each faculty
 - Reaching out to especially those faculties/departments which distance themselves from gender issues (e.g., engineering).
 - Supporting those departments by creating a skills and resources pool.
 - Adding texts and readings related with the gender equality into the compulsory courses such as Turkish Literature and History.
 - **Students and services to students**
 - Providing gender equality and sexism and sexual harassment training during the orientation.
 - **Communication**
 - Providing gender-sensitive communication training for the staff of the communication offices.
 - **Sexism and sexual harassment**
 - Appointing a special officer for sexism and sexual harassment issues.
 - Providing sexism and sexual harassment trainings during the orientation.

Summary of possible collaborative actions

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Regarding possible joint actions, some of the actions expressed by participants are the following:

- Academic contribution to the field through joint research with stakeholders especially other RPOs
- Cooperation with RPOs about gender sensitive teaching and curricula
- Cooperation and partnerships with stakeholders such as NGOs, RPOs, local authorities and companies through joint actions (such as awareness raising campaigns, training, research) and projects
- Providing trainings, workshops, mentorship, and scientific research support to stakeholders to raise awareness on gender equality and gender issues
- Cooperation with business sector on awareness raising activities and data analysis in terms of gender.
- Cooperating with public sector, e.g., directorates of education and high schools to attract more girls to STEM.
- Cooperation with business sector for female role models to attract more girls to STEM professions.
- Cooperation with municipalities and local governmental organization on incorporating gender dimension in local services provided joint awareness raising activities on gender equality, and promoting women's role in regional development and creating links with Women Friendly Cities. As a HEI, Yasar University is expected to provide technical support to municipalities for the development of local equality plans, and gender sensitive budgeting.

3.11 Salento University (RPO)

Description of the R&I Hub

The R&I Hub of Salento University is formed by 4 actors from the academia, 4 stakeholders from the industry and professional sector, 3 stakeholder from the government, 3 from the public sector and 1 civil society organization.

Type of stakeholder	Stakeholders
Academia (4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INFN – Sezione di Lecce (National Institute of Nuclear Physics – Lecce Department) • INDAM (National Institute of High Mathematics) • University of Bari • CNR (National Research Centre)
Industry & professionals (4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DHITECH Scarl • The Qube APS • Systea Spa • Innovaal Scarl

Ministries/Government (3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consigliera Nazionale di Parità (National Equality Adviser) • Department of Social Policies Municipality of Campi Salentina • Department for Equal Opportunities - Municipality of Lecce
Public sector (3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conferenza Nazionale Organi di Parità (National Conference of Equality Bodies) • Scientific High School Virgilio Redi • Equal Opportunities Committee of Professional Association of Lawyers of Lecce
Civil society organizations (1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Renata Fonte Anti-Violence Centre

Description of the workshops

The two workshops were carried out on the 9th March 2021 and lasted 2 hours each. A total of 18 people participated (16 women and 2 men). The participants of the first workshop were stakeholders from the government, the academia and the civil society and discussed about career support measures for women, identifying corrective measures to enable an even distribution between science and humanities degree courses, gender mainstreaming in teaching methodologies, gender mainstreaming in research, and the adoption of a gender dimension in the transfer of scientific results to the market. The participants of the second workshop were members of the academia and the government and discussed about career support measures for women. All the issues of interest of the CALIPER project and, thus, of the internal and external assessment actions, were presented to the external stakeholders with reference to the context of the University of Salento. But both for the convergence of interests of the partners on some issues in particular, and for organisational needs, the discussion focused mainly on some of them.

During the workshop the intermediate scenario description was reviewed, highlighting the main criticalities encountered but also the opportunities it presents. The presence of partners from the academic world also made it possible to assess the implications of the represented scenario from an expert and comparative perspective. It was not simple to identify the best strategies, but together with the stakeholders many best practices were identified that can be adopted and promoted to overcome the identified criticalities and trigger processes of change and risks to be avoided in their implementation.

Given the small number of participants in the two workshops, it was decided not to form subgroups, so that the ideas offered by each workshop could be shared immediately with all those present. Moreover, most of the participants were experts and/or very active in the field, thus giving some inspiring actions to be conducted together. It is worth mentioning that some of the stakeholders are active in participating and promoting technical working tables and permanent conferences set up within CRUI (Conference of Italian University Rectors) and MUR (Ministry of University and Research) and other have already been involved in school orientation activities, promoted by the University of Salento. They are keen to support us in several actions, like workshops, courses and specific meetings or dissemination activities to encourage and support girls and women in STEM careers.

Brainstorming tools were very useful to foster creativity and imagine diverse strategies. It is proposed to catalyse the adhesion of external stakeholders on common actions through further contacts with stakeholders, in order to take up their constructive proposals for collaboration on one or more of the identified actions, given their declared willingness to participate as external facilitators in the design, implementation and sustainability of GEPs.

Shared challenges for gender equality

- Cross-cutting challenges:
 - Enforcing more effectively the rules already present in our legal system, such as those defined in the 2006 equal opportunities code (shared with Equal Opportunities Committee of Professional Association of Lawyers of Lecce and with the President of National Conference of Equality Bodies)
 - To adopt measures that do not exclusively target women, but in more general terms, the less represented gender (shared with the President of National Conference of Equality Bodies and with the National Institute of High Mathematics)
- Specific challenges
 - **Human resources**
 - Identify corrective measures to counterbalance the effects of motherhood on the peak period of production in the research sector (between 28 and 35 years of age) and thus on the career of young female researchers (shared with the President of National Conference of Equality Bodies and with the National Institute of High Mathematics).
 - **Governance**
 - To review the parameters underpinning career assessments, which often reflect exclusively male-dominated criteria (shared with the National Equality Adviser).
 - **Research/research funding**
 - To promote the reintegration of young female researchers in the post-maternity period through measures that can support and encourage them to participate in conferences and present research projects (shared with the President of National Conference of Equality Bodies and with the National Institute of High Mathematics).
 - **Teaching**
 - to integrate gender dimensions in the courses of different departments
 - **Students and services to students**
 - To promote greater awareness of students' aptitudes in order to support them in making a choice as free as possible from cultural and personal conditioning (shared with the National Equality Advisor and the National Institute of High Mathematics).
 - **Communication**
 - This is a common challenge felt by all partners, for whom there is a need to promote initiatives to raise awareness on the use of gender-sensitive communication within their own spheres, as well as training and monitoring initiatives on the application of official protocols where they exist (as in the case of the guidelines adopted by the Ministry of University and Research with reference to administrative language).
 - **Transfer to market**

- To promote the adoption of a gender dimension in the transfer of scientific results to the market (shared with the National Equality Advisor).

Portfolio of strategic opportunities

In the introduction to the workshop, the topics on which the members of the GEP working group focused were proposed to the participants, due to their relevance and criticality in relation to the implementation of the GEP at the University of Salento. In particular, the difficulties that hinder the career of women and their low presence in top positions; the unbalanced gender distribution in STEM degree courses; the lack of formalisation of communication protocols and use of gender-sensitive language, but also the enhancement of gender issues in research and in the third mission.

Stakeholders noted a widespread awareness of the impact that events such as pregnancy and motherhood have on scientific production and therefore on the careers of women at university, and of the consequent need to identify measures which, in addition to allowing women to devote themselves to their care responsibilities - e.g. by suspending their research grants for a reasonable period of time - can have a corrective effect on career evaluation criteria, e.g. by introducing an extension of the evaluation period by a reasonable amount of time for each pregnancy. Equally important is the common challenge of wanting to influence the prevailing cultural attitudes, creating the conditions for girls to be able to assess the possible alternatives in their choice of studies and therefore of professions without conditioning and without preconceived limitations.

In support of these possible actions, mention was made of the good practices already in force at other Italian universities, and of the existence of legislation at national level which was appreciated at the time as being ahead of its time, but which in many respects has remained a dead letter, and therefore ignored.

- Cross-cutting strategies
 - To promote, together with the Equal Opportunities Committee of Professional Association of Lawyers of Lecce, an activity of dissemination of the contents of the Code for Equal Opportunities so that it does not remain a dead letter, but becomes an effective guide and reference framework for actions and choices in all the mentioned fields.
- Specific strategies
 - **Human resources**
 - It could be proposed to suspend the research grant during maternity leave, as other universities already do.
 - **Governance**
 - An extension of the university career evaluation period by 18 months for each pregnancy could be suggested.
 - **Research**
 - Funding could be considered for participation in conferences in the post-doctoral period.
 - Prizes could be awarded for gender-oriented research projects.
 - Mentoring and role models could be set up to support female researchers in presenting projects.
 - **Teaching**

- To give some lectures on GEP in the program of UniSalentoPLUS, an interdisciplinary didactic project, aimed at deepening through seminar meetings themes such as Gender Issues, Sustainable Development, Peace and Rights, Inequality and Racism.
- **Students and services to students**
 - Carrying out activities in schools aimed at promoting a gender culture.
 - Establishing scholarships for participation in specific degree courses (especially STEM) for the less represented gender.
 - Use the skills profile to provide a more objective guidance service, based on the real aptitudes of the students.
- **Communication**
 - To initiate actions for the gender-sensitive communication and language.
- **Sexism and sexual harassment**
 - To compare actions already in place in equality bodies of stakeholders workplaces and in NGOs which try to prevent violence against women.
- **Transfer to market**
 - Prizes could be awarded to research projects that develop gender-oriented products.

Summary of possible collaborative actions

All stakeholders have confirmed their willingness to support the project, collaborating in their specific fields (academia, governance, civil society). In order to discuss the modalities of collaboration and elaboration of common synergic actions, bilateral meetings with some of the stakeholders will be organised soon.

In particular National Conference of Equality Bodies of Italian Universities has proposed itself as leader to promote the exchange of good practices and the development of survey activities that can provide feedback in terms of context analysis to identify targeted actions, with the involvement also of CRUI (Conference of Italian University Rectors) and of the national network of CUGs (Committees for Equal Opportunities of Italian Universities).

Possible collaborative actions to be developed with the contribution of the R&I HUB are in particular:

- To tailor orientation activities for male and female students on the basis of the skills assessment methodology. In this action, Uniroma 1 can be a lead partner having already implemented the methodology of the skills assessment in its guidance office.
- To carry out continuous seminars of information and dissemination in high schools, presenting representative figures of both genders in different scientific-disciplinary areas, in collaboration with representatives of the productive world and/or civil society, telling their stories. On this issue UNILE has found great sensitivity on the part of local administrations, the representative partner of high schools and the National Conference of Equality Bodies.

Conclusion

The present deliverable 'D2.2 Reporting results of multi-stakeholder dialogues' is the basis for the design of the customized Gender Equality Plans of the CALIPER project. It provides the following elements for the development of the GEP:

- The analysis of the main gender equality problems/challenges and possible solutions for each partner of the CALIPER consortium.
- The examination of the resistances and opportunities for each problem within each topic (human resources, governance, research, teaching, students and services to students, knowledge transfer, communication, intersectionality, sexism and sexual harassment) and sub-topics.
- The identification of strategies to overcome the resistances, using the opportunities and the collaboration with external stakeholders.
- The established list of external stakeholders of each R&I Hub.
- The identification of possible actions to carry out collaboratively with external stakeholders.

CALIPER partners will be able to use this information and networks to design and develop their customized GEPs in the following tasks (T2.3). Thanks to this analysis, potential resistances have been anticipated and can be addressed in the GEP design to minimize them as much as possible and to guarantee the GEP is broadly accepted and sustained.

Moreover, possible solutions to gender equality problems and possible strategies to overcome resistances that are found in this deliverable can inspire not only the members of the consortium, but also any other higher education institution willing to promote institutional change for gender equality.

Annex

MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING

Between

“Partner”

And

XXX

1. Purpose

With the object of promoting gender equality in research and innovation, “Partner” and **xxx**, individually also “Party” and collectively the “Parties”, enter into the following Memorandum of Understanding (“MoU”), established in the frame of the Research and Innovation Hub (“R&I Hub”) set up within the CALIPER project, GA n. 873134. This MoU supports collaborative actions towards gender equality between the parties as well as the promotion of the project’s results.

2. Forms of Co-operation

The Parties agree on the benefit of collaborations within structural change processes towards gender equality, as well as on the importance of increasing the number of female researchers in STEM, improving their careers prospects and integrating a gender dimension in research. Within such fields as are mutually acceptable for the Parties, the following forms of co-operation, amongst others, may be pursued hereunder:

- Dialogues for the identification of common challenges related to gender inequalities
- Collaborative actions towards gender equality (including raising awareness activities, joint research activities, projects, etc.)
- Promotion/dissemination of the project’s results
- Actions for transferring the knowledge beyond academia
- Mobility projects for female STEM researchers
- Strategic plans for the project’s sustainability.

3. Specific Collaborative actions

Specific collaborative actions must be negotiated separately between the Parties and are in each specific case to be established in separate written agreements, stating the respective rights and obligations of the Parties. In case of any ambiguity or conflict of terms between the terms and conditions of this MoU and those of a separate agreement as mentioned above, the terms and conditions of such separate agreement shall prevail.

4 . Financial Arrangements

Both Parties understand that all financial arrangements between the Parties have to be further negotiated and mutually agreed, and will depend on the availability of funds. Both parties may seek financing of joint activities from internal and external sources available to them.

5 . General Coordinators

Each Party shall designate an office or a person to oversee and facilitate the implementation of any agreements arising out of this MoU. These offices/persons are:

For “Partner”:

.....

For **XX**:

XX

E-mail:

Tel:

E-mail:

Tel:

6 . Liability

Except for loss or damages caused through gross negligence or intent, the Parties shall have no liability to each other hereunder.

7 . Legal Relationship

This MoU shall be construed as a statement of purpose to promote a genuine and mutually beneficial collaboration between the Parties. Nothing in this MoU shall create any legal relationship between the Parties.

8 . Commencement, Renewal, Termination

This MoU will be effective from the date of the last signature hereto and will remain in force till the 31st of December 2023, which coincides with the end of the CALIPER project, with a possibility for renewal subject to the Parties’ written agreement. Either Party may terminate this MoU by giving six (6) months’ notice in writing to the other Party.

This MoU has been drawn up in two (2) original copies in the English language, each Party receiving one duly signed copy hereof .

Signed on behalf of “Partner”:

1.
Signed on behalf of **XX**:

Place:

Place

Date:

Date:

2.

3.
